

D2.5

Ontology

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the AntifragiCity Ontology as a semantic foundation for modelling antifragile, equitable and data-intensive urban mobility systems within the AntifragiCity project. Building on a structured extraction of requirements and concepts from project documentation and stakeholder inputs, the ontology formalises key entities, processes, events, states and indicators related to disruptions, responses, socio-technical systems, governance, equity and long-term learning. A 12-class meta-model provides a stable upper structure, which is instantiated through modular ontology components covering transport networks, social and equity aspects, environmental and climate stressors, governance and policy instruments, observations and KPIs, data provenance and antifragility dynamics.

The ontology is specified in OWL, complemented by rule patterns (e.g. SWRL) and validation constraints, and is designed to be deployed as a knowledge graph integrated with digital twins,

multi-agent systems and AI analytics. Instantiation guidelines and illustrative use cases are provided for the pilot cities of Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki focusing on flood disruptions, heatwaves and port-related crises, respectively. Competency questions derived from the requirements serve as the main validation mechanism and inform the design of SPARQL query templates and rule-based reasoning patterns. The deliverable also outlines the integration of the ontology with decision-support and participatory tools, and proposes a validation and evaluation framework addressing conceptual soundness, practical usability, technical performance and extensibility. Remaining gaps, data dependencies and future work are identified to guide subsequent implementation, empirical evaluation and potential reuse beyond the project.

Keywords

Ontology Engineering, NeOn Methodology, Knowledge Graphs, Semantic Interoperability, OWL 2, Requirements-driven Ontology, Competency Questions

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R *

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to AntifragiCity project and Commission Services

✓

*** Deliverable types:**

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AFC	AntifragiCity
AIA	EU Artificial Intelligence Act
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BHA	Bureau for Humanitarian Assistance (USAID)
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CQ	Competency Question
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
D2.1	Deliverable 2.1 (project deliverable identifier)
D2.3	Deliverable 2.3 (project deliverable identifier)
DATEX II	Traffic and Travel Data Exchange (DATEX II)
DMO	Disaster Management Ontology
EC	European Commission
EM-DAT	The International Disaster Database (EM-DAT)
ENVO	Environment Ontology
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
EU	European Union
FOAF	Friend of a Friend (vocabulary)
GeoSPARQL	OGC GeoSPARQL standard (geospatial RDF and query)
GIS	Geographic Information System
GTFS	General Transit Feed Specification
GTFS-RT	General Transit Feed Specification – Realtime
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IoT	Internet of Things
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON-LD	JSON for Linking Data
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PROV-O	W3C Provenance Ontology
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	RDF Schema
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language

SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator ontology
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSN	Semantic Sensor Network ontology
SWEET	Semantic Web for Earth and Environmental Terminology
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WKT	Well-Known Text geometry format

1 Executive summary

Objectives and scope:

This deliverable specifies the AntifragiCity Ontology, which serves as the semantic backbone for modelling and analysing antifragile urban mobility systems in the project. Its main objectives are to:

- translate project requirements and use cases into a coherent semantic model.
- capture the key concepts and relationships of **disruptions, responses, impacts**, equity and governance.
- support the representation of **learning, adaptation and antifragility** over time.
- enable integration with **digital twins, multi-agent systems, AI analytics, dashboards and participatory tools**.
- provide a reusable, extensible ontology that can be instantiated in different cities and contexts.

The deliverable covers the conceptual foundations, methodological approach, ontology architecture, OWL specification and rule patterns, instantiation guidelines for pilot cities, integration with platforms and a structured validation and evaluation framework. The Disruption & Risk module reuses the **two-axis event taxonomy (Domain × Scale) and severity scheme** established in D2.1 *Urban Event Mapping* and is populated with events from the D2.1 *Urban Event Catalogue*. This ensures that the disturbance modelling in D2.3 is grounded in a harmonised, cross-source event ontology.

Methodological approach:

The ontology is developed using a **requirements-driven, modular ontology engineering approach**, drawing on established practices such as NeOn-style workflows. The process includes:

Requirements and concept extraction:

Requirements 1-61 and their associated concepts (entities, processes, properties, states, events, relationships) were extracted and structured in dedicated tables. Concepts were clustered into semantic groups such as TransportNetwork, MobilityService, DisruptionEvent, SystemState, EquitySocial, Governance, DataProvenance, Scenario, EnvironmentFactor, SpatialUnit and TemporalUnit.

Meta-modelling and modular design:

A **12-class meta-model** was defined as the upper level of the ontology, providing stable categories for transport elements, disruptions, states, scenarios, actors, governance instruments, environment and context, spatial and temporal units, observations, response actions and data provenance. On this basis, domain modules were designed and aligned with the project's technical and pilot requirements.

Ontology specification and pattern design:

Classes, object properties and data properties were specified in OWL, with attention to domain/range constraints, cardinalities and reusable patterns (e.g. n-ary relations for KPIs and scenario evaluations). Illustrative rule patterns (e.g. SWRL) were defined for antifragility assessment, vulnerability detection, equity alerts, cascading disruption reasoning and compliance checks.

Competency questions and validation planning:

Competency questions derived from the requirements and use cases provide a reference for ontology completeness and usability. They inform the design of SPARQL query templates and anticipated reasoning tasks.

Main results

Conceptual foundations:

The deliverable consolidates a conceptual framework for **antifragile urban mobility**. This framework integrates **antifragility and resilience** as cross-cutting concepts expressed through indicators, state transitions and learning processes. It incorporates **socio-technical and cyber-physical perspectives**, capturing infrastructure, actors, governance and digital layers. **Equity and vulnerability** are treated as first-class concerns, not add-ons. **Data provenance, uncertainty and trust** are included as essential elements for reliable analysis and decision support.

This framework underpins the ontology design and ensures that antifragility is treated as a dynamic property emerging from disruption-response-learning cycles.

Ontology architecture and OWL specification:

The ontology architecture is built around a **12-class meta-model** and several domain modules:

- **Transport & Network module:** representation of nodes, edges, corridors, routes, assets, evacuation routes, signal plans and sensor networks.
- **Disruption & Risk module:** disruptions (e.g. floods, outages, crises, cyber-attacks), hazard types, cascades and propagation patterns.
- **Actors, Equity & Social module:** individual and organizational actors; equity groups and vulnerable populations; stakeholder and citizen groups; vulnerable areas and their social vulnerability attributes.
- **Governance & Policy module:** governance instruments (regulations, legal constraints, data sharing agreements, security protocols), organisations, agencies and strategies.
- **Environment & Context module:** climate stressors, climate projections, PESTEL factors and contextual influences.
- **Observation, KPIs & Data Provenance module:** observations (traffic, emissions, KPIs, economic and equity indicators), data sources, provenance records and data quality.
- **Antifragility & Learning module:** system states, antifragile states, response and learning processes, behavioural nudges, long-term structural change.

The deliverable provides conceptual descriptions and examples of key classes, as well as representative OWL snippets for class hierarchies, object properties and data properties. It introduces reusable semantic patterns, especially for KPI observations linked to scenarios, actors, time and space.

Rules, constraints and queries:

In addition to OWL axioms, the ontology is complemented by **rule patterns** including SWRL for classifying antifragile states based on performance improvements after disruptions, identifying vulnerable areas based on risk exposure and service access, triggering equity alerts, and reasoning about cascading disruptions and legal feasibility of actions. It includes **validation constraints** such as SHACL to ensure that key structural patterns including KPI observations and disruption-response-state chains are instantiated correctly. It provides **SPARQL query templates** aligned with competency questions, supporting typical information needs of planners, operators, resilience experts, equity officers and crisis managers. These artefacts will be fully documented in the appendices, including rule examples, constraint shapes and query templates.

Instantiation and use cases:

The ontology is intended to be instantiated as a **knowledge graph** with a shared TBox (common schema/ontology) and separate ABoxes per city (city-specific instances). Guidelines are provided for Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI) naming conventions and use of **named graphs** per city and thematic area, and for minimal viable knowledge bases per city, including core network elements, key actors, equity groups, vulnerable areas, disruption and scenario instances and representative KPIs.

Illustrative use cases are developed for each pilot:

- **Bratislava:** flood-related disruptions affecting bridges and riverside corridors, with antifragile routing strategies and comparisons of baseline and improved scenarios.
- **Larissa:** heatwave and health-related mobility, focusing on equity, vulnerable groups, access to cooling centres and health services.
- **Odessa:** port-related disruptions with cascading effects on urban mobility and logistics, coupled with security, governance and legal constraints.
- **AHEPA Hospital at Thessaloniki:** traffic flow disturbances that affect the serviceability of a tertiary hospital and the operations of a densely populated urban centre.

These examples demonstrate how the ontology can represent realistic disruption scenarios, interventions, system states and KPIs, and how it supports antifragility and equity analyses.

Integration with platforms and interfaces:

The deliverable outlines how the ontology and knowledge graph integrate with the broader AntifragiCity technical ecosystem through deployment in a **triple store/graph database** with SPARQL endpoint and REST/HTTP API layer. The ontology enables interaction with **digital twins**, which use it as a semantic schema for synchronising live data, simulations and visualisations. It supports coupling with **multi-agent systems**, where agents query the KG for context including disruptions, routes, vulnerable areas and constraints, and write back proposed actions. It facilitates integration with **AI/ML analytics**, which consume semantically structured data and produce predictions and indicators as ontology instances. It provides support for **decision-support tools and participatory platforms**, offering ontology-backed views on disruptions, strategies, KPIs, equity impacts and stakeholder inputs. Access control considerations and the role of governance concepts (legal constraints, data sharing agreements, access rights) in shaping data access and use are also addressed at a conceptual level.

Validation, evaluation and lessons learned:

A multi-layer validation and evaluation framework is defined. This framework focuses on **competency-question-based evaluation**, assessing whether the ontology can support the required queries and reasoning tasks. It includes **expert validation**, through workshops and structured walkthroughs with planners, mobility engineers, resilience experts, data scientists, policy analysts and legal experts. **Stakeholder-facing validation** is conducted via participatory tools that rely on the ontology without exposing its technical details directly. **Technical performance** is evaluated, including reasoning and query performance, and scalability with realistic data volumes. **Completeness and extensibility** are assessed via mapping between requirements, concepts, ontology elements and CQs.

Preliminary lessons include the importance of requirements-driven modelling, the role of a small stable meta-model, the need to treat equity and governance as core elements, and the strong influence of data availability and quality.

Future work and relation to other tasks:

The deliverable identifies several strands of future work including completion and consolidation of the OWL implementation, rule sets, validation constraints and example ABoxes; deeper pilot instantiations and empirical evaluations of antifragility and equity metrics; extension of cross-infrastructure modelling covering energy, communications and health systems and long-term transformative learning; and refinement of mappings to external standards and potential open publication and reuse of the ontology.

The AntifragiCity Ontology will feed directly into **related tasks**, providing a formal semantic basis for antifragility metrics, scenario analysis, AI components, dashboards and evaluation frameworks. It also offers a reusable asset that can be maintained and extended beyond the project, supporting future work on resilient, antifragile and equitable urban mobility systems.

2 Introduction

This section introduces the purpose, scope, and structure of the deliverable.

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This deliverable specifies the **AntifragiCity Ontology for Urban Mobility Antifragility**. Its purpose is to provide a formal, machine-interpretable representation of the key concepts, relationships and rules required to describe urban mobility systems as **socio-technical and cyber-physical systems**. It represents **disruptions, responses, learning processes and equilibrium states**, captures **equity, vulnerability and exposure** across **actors, spatial units, and transport elements**. It integrates heterogeneous **data streams, models and simulation outputs**, and supports **reasoning and decision-making for antifragile short-term response and long-term urban mobility planning and operations**.

The ontology is designed as the **knowledge backbone** for the AntifragiCity decision-support environment, enabling semantic interoperability among data sources, analytical components, digital twins and user interfaces.

The scope of this deliverable includes:

- definition of the **conceptual foundations** and design principles of the ontology.
- description of the **ontology engineering methodology**, including AI-assisted qualitative analysis of requirements and competency questions.
- presentation of the **ontology architecture**, modular design and alignment with existing standards.
- a narrative overview of the **ontology specification** approach; full formal specification (classes, properties, constraints, rule patterns and query templates) is provided in Appendix B.
- illustration of **instantiation and use cases** for the pilot cities.
- description of the **integration** of the ontology with digital twins, multi-agent systems and analytics platforms; and
- presentation of the **validation and evaluation** approach and summary of lessons learned.

The deliverable does **not** include full implementation details of the downstream software components, user interface designs, or exhaustive documentation of all pilot-specific datasets. Where sections depend on ongoing developments or local data provision, they explicitly indicate that the corresponding implementation or data collection will be carried out in later project phases and are therefore not in the scope of this deliverable.

2.2 AntifragiCity project overview and objectives

AntifragiCity addresses the challenge of designing and operating **urban mobility systems that do not merely withstand disruptions but improve through them**. The project recognises that cities are exposed to a wide range of shocks and stresses, including acute events (e.g. accidents, floods, cyber-attacks, infrastructure failures); chronic pressures such as congestion, climate change, social inequalities; and systemic crises such as pandemics, economic downturns, social unrest.

In this context, urban mobility systems are viewed as **complex socio-technical systems** linking transport infrastructure, services, digital platforms, institutions and diverse user groups. Antifragility (1) goes beyond robustness and resilience as broadly applied so far, by focusing on

learning from disruptions and interventions, **adapting and re-configuring** services, infrastructure and governance, **creating beneficial responses** where performance or equity improves after perturbations, and explicitly representing **equilibrium states, basins of attraction and cascading effects** across infrastructures.

The project pursues several high-level objectives, which the ontology directly supports. The project **analyses and formalises requirements** for antifragile urban mobility planning and operations. It develops **AI- and simulation-based tools** for disruption anticipation, response and learning. It integrates multi-modal, multi-source mobility data within **digital twins and knowledge graphs**. It evaluates **equity, environmental and economic impacts** of measures and scenarios. It provides **evidence-based support** to city authorities, operators and citizens in four pilot cities (Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki). Within this overall framework, the ontology acts as a unifying semantic layer enabling cross-cutting analysis, interoperability and reuse of knowledge across the project's work packages.

2.3 Role of the ontology in antifragile urban mobility systems

Experiences from sustainable construction, smart buildings, smart-water platforms and urban-district sustainability all show that a formal ontology can act as the “semantic engine” that links heterogeneous assets, sensors, users, KPIs and policies into a coherent, machine-interpretable knowledge base (2–6). Building on these results, the AntifragiCity ontology is designed to provide the same semantic backbone for urban mobility: a shared conceptualisation that allows data, models and decision processes to talk about the same events, infrastructures, actors and impacts in a consistent way and to support automated reasoning across them.

Urban mobility antifragility requires that data, models and decision processes are **semantically consistent** and **explicitly linked to well-defined concepts** such as:

- **Transport elements and services** (nodes, links, facilities, vehicles, public transport services, active modes, on-demand services),
- **Disruption events and hazards** (planned works, accidents, climate events, cyber-attacks, cascading failures),
- **System states and metrics** (congestion levels, resilience and antifragility indicators, vulnerability, recovery time),
- **Actors, governance instruments and equity groups** (institutions, user groups, policies, regulations, constraints),
- **Scenarios, interventions and learning processes** (what-if scenarios, measures, evaluations, policy updates), and
- **Data, observations and uncertainty** (sensor observations, KPIs, provenance, confidence, prediction errors).

The ontology defined in this deliverable provides a **shared vocabulary** for all partners and tools in the project, as well as a **formal conceptualisation** that can be encoded in OWL and exposed as a **knowledge graph**. It establishes a basis for **interoperability** between heterogeneous data sources (GIS, IoT, traffic data, socio-economic indicators), simulation models, and AI components, and supports **semantic reasoning**, enabling the derivation of new knowledge such as vulnerability indices, affected user groups, likely cascades, or candidate response actions. In addition, it ensures

traceability from requirements and competency questions to ontology elements, thereby ensuring that the ontology remains grounded in actual decision-making needs.

In operational terms, the ontology will be deployed within the project's **knowledge graph infrastructure** and linked to **digital twin representations** of the pilot cities. It will be accessed via **APIs, SPARQL endpoints, and dashboards**, and used by **multi-agent systems, optimisation algorithms, and predictive models** to exchange and reason over a common representation of the city.

2.4 Relation to work packages and other deliverables

This deliverable is produced under the Work Package 2 (WP2) focusing on **ontology and semantic foundations for antifragility**. It has strong dependencies and bidirectional links with several other work packages and deliverables, including:

- **WP2: Requirements and use-case analysis** provides the foundation where the ontology is grounded in the functional and non-functional requirements and associated competency questions defined earlier in the project. The AI-assisted concept extraction and semantic clustering build directly on these inputs.
- **WP2: Antifragility metrics and system analysis** supplies concepts such as antifragility score, resilience indicators, equilibrium states, vulnerability indices and recovery times which are taken from the analytical framework and formalised as ontology classes, properties and rule patterns.
- **WP4 and WP5: Digital twins, simulation and AI tools** utilize the ontology as the semantic schema. WP4 (Antifragile traffic control in urban road networks) employs AI/ML algorithms informed by the ontology's framework, while WP5 (The Simulator for Urban Mobility Antifragility - SUMA) integrates the event ontology from WP2 to provide the semantic schema for integrating network models, simulation outputs and AI analytics results in a consistent knowledge graph.
- **WP3: Decision-support tools and interfaces**, the Mobility Triage Decision Support System and related policy dashboards, scenario comparison tools and interfaces query and update information structured according to this ontology.
- **WP6 and WP11: Pilot demonstrations** use instantiated versions of the ontology, populated with pilot-specific data, will underpin the evaluation of antifragility strategies in Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa and Thessaloniki across the demonstration sites and living labs.
- **WP7: Policy and planning tools**, the pathway to market work package benefits from the ontology's governance and policy representations for developing the policy framework and advocacy activities.
- **WP8 and WP12: Participatory platforms**, the ecosystem building and stakeholder engagement work packages utilize ontology-backed interfaces for stakeholder collaboration and community building activities.

In addition, the ontology is designed to be **compatible with, and reusable in, future project phases and follow-up initiatives**, by aligning with widely adopted standards and open data models in the mobility and smart city domains.

Links to other WP2 deliverables:

- **D2.1 “Urban Event Mapping”** provides the **canonical event taxonomy and catalogue schema** (Domain × Scale, Severity 1-5, MobilityImpact, SourceType), its taxonomy is **imported into the Disruption & Risk module** as classes and controlled vocabularies, and catalogue entries instantiate the DisruptionEvent class in the ontology.
- **D2.3 “Equilibrium and Antifragility Models”** defines the **disturbance indicator Deff(t)** as an aggregation over event attributes drawn from the D2.1 ontology, and defines 12 antifragility KPIs and the Antifragility Factor (AF) and System Responsiveness Index (SRI), which are represented as KPI individuals and data properties in the SystemState & Antifragility module.
- **WP3 (Mobility Triage and DSS): D3.1 Handbook, D3.2 Vulnerability Methodology and D3.3 DSS Specification** provide triage classifications, vulnerability metrics and DSS requirements, formalized as classes, properties and SPARQL query templates in the Disruption & Risk and KPI modules.
- **WP4 (Traffic Control): D4.2 Control Strategies, D4.3 Learning Algorithms and D4.4 Integration** define adaptive control policies and learning processes, represented as ControlPolicy individuals and LearningProcess patterns with rule evolution mechanisms in the ontology.
- **WP5/WP10 (SUMA Simulator): D5.1 API Specification and D5.2/D10.1 Integration** define SUMA's semantic layer, for which this ontology provides the core schema. API patterns, scenario configurations and query templates align with ontology structures.
- **WP6/WP11 (Pilots and Living Labs): D6.2/D6.3 Pilot Reports and D11.2/D11.3 Living Lab Activities** document pilot data, stakeholder requirements and validation activities. Pilot-specific instantiations populate the ontology with city-specific network data, while stakeholder feedback informs ontology refinement.
- **WP8/WP12 (Policy and Exploitation): D8.1 Policy Recommendations and D12.1 Exploitation Strategy** inform the representation of governance instruments and standardization requirements for ontology reuse.

2.5 Related Work

Ontologies are commonly defined as an explicit specification of a conceptualisation (7) and are widely used in the refined form “a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualisation” (8). A conceptualisation is an abstract model of a phenomenon in the world including capturing the relevant concepts and their relationships, while an ontology makes this model explicit in a formal, machine-readable representation (including constraints) so that it can be shared and interpreted consistently by both people and software systems for querying and reasoning (8,9).

In knowledge-management and knowledge-retrieval systems, such ontologies provide the basic vocabulary and primitives needed to describe resources and to formulate structured queries over them, thereby supporting a shift from document-centric to content-centric views of complex domains (2,10,11). Upper, domain and application ontologies are typically distinguished by their level of abstraction, with upper ontologies capturing generic patterns such as objects, processes and spatio-temporal relations, and domain ontologies specialising these patterns for particular sectors such as construction, energy or transport (2,12,13). For AntifragiCity, the antifragile urban-mobility ontology is precisely such a domain ontology: a formal, shared conceptualisation of urban events, actors, infrastructure, context, impacts, responses and equity dimensions that is interpretable by computers through OWL axioms and can be queried and reasoned over by software agents.

Given the complexity and heterogeneity of smart-city data, a structured methodology is required to move from informal concepts to such machine-interpretable ontologies. The NeOn Methodology framework represents a significant advance in ontology development by providing a scenario-based approach that emphasises reuse and collaborative development, and foregrounds the construction of ontology networks rather than isolated, monolithic ontologies (14). NeOn is built around (i) a glossary of processes and activities, (ii) nine scenarios for building ontologies and ontology networks, (iii) two ontology life-cycle models, and (iv) prescriptive methodological guidelines (14). These scenarios operationalise reuse at different granularities, whole ontologies, modules, axioms and design patterns, and explicitly support reuse and re-engineering of both ontological and non-ontological resources (14–16). Central to this approach is explicit requirements capture through an Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD) and Competency Questions (CQs), which structure goals, intended users and requirements, and then guide gap analysis and the selection and alignment of reusable resources (5,14,17). Practical applications illustrate the framework's interoperability emphasis, for example aligning local ontology networks with reference networks in e-employment settings (18). Comparative assessments also position NeOn (alongside CommonKADS) as among the more comprehensive and systematic ontology development methodologies available (19).

AntifragiCity follows this NeOn perspective. The ontology work starts from an explicit ORSD based on D2.1, the governing variables from T1.2, and the requirements and competency questions collected from all partners. Non-ontological resources such as the D2.1 urban-event taxonomy, EM-DAT classifications, city operational schemas and survey instruments provide the initial conceptualisation of “urban stresses and disruptions,” while existing ontologies in BIM, GIS, sensing, transport and social media are identified as candidates for reuse and alignment. This leads to an ontology network architecture in which a lightweight, project-specific upper ontology for “Urban Events & Mobility” provides a conceptual spine, and specialised domain modules, reused or newly engineered, are attached and aligned to this spine rather than replaced. This design choice is consistent with the experience of other large-scale projects in the built-environment and smart-city domains.

Research on ontologies for the built environment, smart cities and infrastructure management consistently argues for reuse-first, modular ontology networks rather than monolithic models. Rezgui and Marks' SCrIPt project (6) develops a sustainable-construction ontology by taking IFC and related taxonomies as the backbone and enriching them with concepts mined from regulatory and technical document corpora; their methodology explicitly separates domain scoping, ontology-architecture definition, identification of candidate semantic resources and the construction of ontology modules, followed by validation with stakeholders (6). They show that construction taxonomies and existing software data structures can act as the “map of everything” for a domain, provided they are re-engineered into OWL and organised in a layered core-plus-modules architecture (6).

A similar pattern appears in the European Construction Information Platform (CrIP) study, which proposes a knowledge-centred architecture where a construction ontology mediates access to a federation of heterogeneous EC and national web portals (20). In CrIP, the ontology underpins concept-based search, query expansion and result clustering, addressing redundancy and poor retrieval in document-centric portals and demonstrating how a shared conceptual model can sit “above” fragmented data and services; an integration role that AntifragiCity similarly assigns to its upper ontology over D2.1, EM-DAT, Copernicus and city-operational datasets.

At urban-district scale Kuster et al. (5) develop the Urban District Sustainability Assessment (UDSA) ontology, linking sensor readings, urban objects, KPIs, time and location within a single semantic

model (5). Using the NeOn methodology, they derive ontology requirements from 29 international assessment frameworks and explicitly distinguish an upper-level schema from specialised domain modules and reused ontologies (e.g. energy, health, water) (5). Their work shows that a lightweight upper ontology can reconcile heterogeneous sustainability indicators and domain ontologies, while still allowing each module to evolve independently, precisely the rationale for AntifragiCity's antifragility-centred upper ontology and modular reuse of BIM, CityGML, transport, sensing and social-media vocabularies.

The UDSA study also surveys a broader ecosystem of urban ontologies (e.g. PolisGnosis for ISO 37120 city indicators, OSMoSys, SEMANCO, ee-District, AMBASSADOR and a Transport Disruption ontology), concluding that these resources provide rich but fragmented views of sustainability and mobility sub-domains (5). None, however, offers a cross-cutting antifragility perspective or integrates hazards, disruptions, KPIs and equity concerns at the level required by AntifragiCity, reinforcing the need for a project-specific upper ontology that can align multiple standards while remaining lightweight and reusable.

In the smart-water and urban-cybernetics domain, Howell et al. (4) propose an ontology-driven requirements-engineering approach for the WISDOM platform, explicitly extending NeOn with a stronger focus on requirements, stakeholder views and system integration. They argue that ontology requirements must jointly satisfy knowledge-engineering rigour, software-engineering constraints and domain experts' perspectives, and show how competency questions, process models and use cases can be combined to drive the design of an ontology that underpins an IoT-enabled smart-water platform (4). Their conclusion, that such ontologies are "living resources" that must evolve with the domain, supports AntifragiCity's view of its ontology as a dynamic antifragility knowledge graph rather than a one-off static artefact.

At building scale, Dibley et al. present OntoFM, an integrated framework that couples a ZigBee sensor network with a multi-agent system whose agents query ontology-backed knowledge bases to negotiate resources, optimise sensor behaviour and infer space-usage patterns (3). OntoFM illustrates how OWL ontologies can provide a live semantic layer over sensor data, enabling real-time reasoning and decision support in facility management; the architecture, in which agents read from and write to a shared ontology-driven knowledge base, anticipates the role of the AntifragiCity graph for multi-agent optimisation and decision-support components.

Taken together, this body of work supports three design choices in AntifragiCity. First, it motivates a NeOn-style, scenario-based methodology that starts from explicit requirements and competency questions and that reuses both non-ontological resources (D2.1 event catalogue, governing variables, survey instruments) and existing ontologies wherever possible (14,15). Second, it reinforces the value of a lightweight, project-specific upper ontology that sits above multiple domain standards such as BIM, CityGML, transport, sensing, social media and hazard/event ontologies, providing a stable conceptual "spine" for alignment, as advocated in UDSA and SCrIPt (5,6). Third, it demonstrates that such an ontology can function as the semantic core of a wider technical ecosystem (digital twins, multi-agent systems, analytics services and decision-support tools), enabling real-time reasoning over disruptions, responses and KPIs (3–5,21), which is precisely the role envisaged for the antifragile urban-mobility ontology in this deliverable.

Against this background, the AntifragiCity ontology adopts a reuse-first approach consistent with established practice in ontology engineering for large, heterogeneous domains. In the built environment and urban digital-twin space, IFC/BIM and CityGML provide mature conceptualisations of assets, buildings, and city objects, while GeoSPARQL provides interoperable patterns for geometry-linked features and spatial querying (22–24). For mobility operations and transport services, European and industry standards (e.g., Transmodel, NeTEx, GTFS, and DATEX II) provide

reference structures for stops, routes, timetables, and traffic events (25–28). For observations and measurements, the SOSA/SSN family supports consistent modelling of sensors, observations, and observed properties (29). For provenance and dataset traceability, standard vocabularies such as PROV-O and time representations (e.g., OWL-Time) support auditable, longitudinal knowledge graphs (30,31).

A recurring challenge across these resources is the need for both horizontal alignment (across domain standards) and vertical alignment (between domain standards and project abstractions). Both SCrIPt and UDSA argue for a layered “core-plus-modules” ontology network in which a lightweight upper/core schema supports cross-domain alignment, which reduces integration risk by allowing specialised modules to evolve independently (5,6). Finally, risk, crisis, and hazard modelling is typically handled either via dedicated event ontologies or via controlled taxonomies that are later formalised. In AntifragiCity, the D2.1 event taxonomy is therefore elevated to a lightweight Urban Event Ontology module and aligned with external hazard vocabularies where appropriate, ensuring that event typing remains explicit, queryable, and consistent across static catalogues and dynamic feeds.

2.6 Target audience and intended use

The primary audience for this deliverable consists of:

- **Researchers and developers** within the project responsible for modelling, simulation, AI analytics and software development,
- **City authorities, transport operators and public agencies** involved in the pilot implementations and interested in the semantic structures underpinning the decision-support tools,
- **Ontology engineers and knowledge graph practitioners** seeking a reusable antifragility-oriented urban mobility ontology,
- **Policymakers and EU stakeholders** interested in how antifragility, equity and sustainability concepts can be operationalised in urban mobility planning.

The document is intended to serve multiple purposes. It guides technical partners in implementing and extending the ontology in OWL and related technologies, supports data integration teams in mapping local datasets and APIs to the ontology. It serves as reference documentation for validating the coverage of the ontology against requirements and competency questions. Also, it provides a basis for future reuse and standardisation beyond the AntifragiCity project.

2.7 Structure of the document

The remainder of the deliverable is organised as follows:

- **Section 2: Introduction** introduces the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable, summarises the AntifragiCity project objectives, clarifies the role of the ontology in antifragile urban mobility systems, situates the work with respect to other work packages and deliverables, reviews related work, and defines the target audience and intended use.
- **Section 3: Ontology Engineering Methodology** describes the overall ontology development process, based on an extended NeOn-inspired lifecycle, detailing knowledge acquisition, stakeholder engagement, ontology scoping, reuse of existing ontologies, and the tooling environment.

- **Section 4: Project Context, Requirements and Competency Questions** summarises the urban mobility challenges addressed by AntifragiCity, presents the consolidated set of requirements and competency questions, and describes the AI-assisted concept extraction and clustering that generated the ontology’s candidate concepts, clusters and taxonomy.
- **Section 5: Conceptual Foundations** introduces the theoretical underpinnings of the ontology, including antifragility theory, socio-technical and cyber-physical perspectives on urban mobility, and the role of semantic technologies within AI, digital twins and circular economy approaches.
- **Section 6: Ontology Architecture and Design** presents the design principles, the domain-independent meta-model, the 12 top-level classes with main subclasses, the modular architecture derived from semantic clusters, and the alignment strategy with relevant standards and European mobility datasets.
- **Section 7: Ontology Specification Overview** summarises the specification choices and artefacts; **Appendix B** provides the formal specification of the ontology (class and property hierarchies, constraints, rule patterns, and linked data/interoperability patterns), while **Appendix E** provides worked examples of SWRL/SHACL shapes and SPARQL query templates used for validation and demonstration.
- **Section 8: Instantiation and Use Cases** illustrate how the ontology is instantiated for the pilot cities, how heterogeneous data sources are integrated, and how representative use cases (such as flood disruptions, health-related mobility, protests and infrastructure failures) are modelled and reasoned upon.
- **Section 9: Integration with Platforms and Interfaces** explains how the ontology is deployed as a knowledge graph, how it interfaces with digital twins, multi-agent systems and AI analytics, and how users can access it through APIs, SPARQL endpoints and dashboards.
- **Section 10: Validation, Evaluation and Lessons Learned** describes the validation of the ontology against competency questions and expert feedback, discusses performance and extensibility aspects, and summarises lessons learned for antifragility-oriented ontology engineering.
- **Section 11: Conclusions and Future Work** summarises the main contributions of the ontology and outlines planned refinements and integration with subsequent project tasks and deliverables.
- **Section 12: References** lists the scientific literature, standards and other sources referenced in this deliverable.
- The **Appendices** provide supporting material, including the full list of requirements and competency questions, detailed property tables, mappings to external standards and example rules and queries.

3 Ontology Engineering Methodology

This section describes the methodology used to develop, validate, and document the ontology. It combines a **NeOn-inspired ontology lifecycle** with an **AI-assisted qualitative analysis workflow**, participatory knowledge acquisition and systematic reuse of existing ontologies and standards (15). The overall aim is to ensure that the ontology is **requirements-driven, transparent, reusable and**

maintainable throughout the project. AI assistance is applied as a supporting method for early-phase concept identification and traceability, with all outputs subject to human validation and expert sign-off.

3.1 Overall approach and process (NeOn-inspired lifecycle)

This subsection introduces the lifecycle used to structure ontology development activities. The project adopts an ontology engineering process aligned with the **NeOn methodology**, adapted to the specific needs of antifragile urban mobility. The lifecycle comprises the following main phases:

1. **Initiation and requirements gathering**
This phase consolidates project objectives, pilot use cases and stakeholder needs. It elicits **functional and non-functional requirements** and **competency questions (CQs)**.
2. **Ontology specification**
This phase defines the **ontology purpose, scope, intended users and usage scenarios**, as documented in Sections 1 and 2. It identifies **granularity levels**, required modules and expected reasoning tasks (e.g. antifragility scoring, equity analysis, disruption propagation).
3. **Knowledge acquisition and conceptualisation**
This phase applies an **AI-assisted concept extraction** and **coding pipeline** to the requirements and CQs. It groups concepts into semantic clusters and derives the **12-class domain-independent meta-model**. Iterative refinement with domain experts results in a conceptual model of the domain.
4. **Formalisation and implementation**
This phase translates the conceptual model into **OWL axioms**, including classes, object properties, data properties and constraints. It specifies rule patterns (e.g. SWRL, SHACL) for key antifragility and equity inferences. It formalises the ontology as an OWL 2 artefact (RDF/OWL serialisations) and prepares it for consumption by standard RDF/OWL tooling and knowledge-graph stores.
5. **Integration and population**
This phase maps pilot city datasets, simulation outputs and model artefacts to ontology classes and properties. It populates the ontology into a **knowledge graph** representing specific cities, assets, events, scenarios and observations.
6. **Validation, evaluation and maintenance**
This phase validates the ontology against **competency questions**, expert feedback and data-driven tests. It monitors ontology usage in digital twins, analytics and decision-support applications. Iterative updates address new requirements, concepts and external standards.

The process is **iterative rather than linear**: insights from implementation, validation and pilots feed back into conceptualisation and specification. The AI-assisted analysis is woven through the early phases, ensuring a strong link between text-based requirements and the final ontology.

Figure 1 illustrates the six-phase iterative lifecycle. The main progression flows from requirements (Phase 1) through to validation (Phase 6), with three key feedback loops enabling refinement: failed competency question tests trigger conceptual model updates (Phase 6 to Phase 3), formalisation errors trigger axiom refinement (Phase 6 to Phase 4), and integration issues trigger property adjustments (Phase 5 to Phase 4). Dashed arrows show feedback loops enabling iterative refinement based on validation results. AI-assisted analysis supports the early phases (1-3), with detailed workflows in Section 3.2.

3.2 Input artefacts and AI-assisted qualitative analysis workflow

This subsection introduces the input artefacts and the concept-extraction workflow applied to them. The ontology is grounded in several key input artefacts:

- The consolidated **requirements catalogue** (61 high-level requirements), each with a unique Requirement_ID and descriptive text.
- The set of **competency questions** expressing information needs.
- Supporting descriptions from project deliverables and partner documents (e.g. descriptions of pilot cities, antifragility concepts, platform components).

An **AI-assisted qualitative analysis workflow** was applied to these artefacts, with three main outputs:

1. Concept extraction

In the first step, we systematically reviewed each requirement statement and extracted the key terms (**concept labels**) it mentions (for example, “individual trip”, “climate stressor”, “equity group”, or “data sharing agreement”). For every extracted term, we then assigned two pieces of information to make the analysis consistent and auditable: a **Semantic_Code** (a stable code so the same concept is tagged the same way across the whole deliverable); and a **Concept_Type**, which indicates what kind of thing the term represents, using a small, controlled set:

- Entities (ENT_*)
- Processes (PROC_*)
- Events (EVENT_*)
- States (STATE_*)
- Properties (PROP_*)
- Relationships (REL_*)

The output of this step is a structured table (concepts_extraction) that, for each Requirement_ID, lists the concepts found in the requirement text along with their codes and types. This creates a clear trace from each requirement to the concepts that the ontology needs to represent.

2. Semantic clustering and ontology class suggestions

In this step, we took the concepts extracted from the source materials (e.g., requirements, notes, and competency questions) and organised them in a structured, repeatable way so they can be turned into an ontology. First, each concept was grouped into a semantic cluster; a practical “topic bucket” such as TransportNetwork, MobilityService, DisruptionEvent, SystemState, Scenario, EnvironmentFactor, EquitySocial, Governance, DataProvenance, SpatialUnit, TemporalUnit, ResponseAction, or Other. These clusters are used only to keep the analysis organised; they do not by themselves define the ontology.

Next, for every concept we recorded an `Ontology_Class`; the formal category it belongs to in the ontology's domain-independent meta-model. In other words, we mapped each extracted term to one of the ontology's high-level building blocks (for example, a transport asset would be categorised as `:TransportElement`, a service as `:MobilityService`, a disruption as `:DisruptionEvent`, a measurement or record as `:Observation`, a stakeholder as `:Actor`, and a policy or regulation as `:GovernanceInstrument`). This mapping ensures that different partners and datasets describe the same kinds of things in a consistent way.

Finally, we proposed a `Candidate_URI` for each concept. A URI is simply the ontology's unique identifier for a term; like a stable ID that machines and humans can refer to unambiguously. We followed one consistent naming convention so that terms are predictable and easy to reuse (e.g., `:Trip`, `:Mode`, `:AntifragilityScore`, `:LegalConstraint`, `:Disruption`, `:ScenarioLibrary`).

3. Traceability and coverage matrices

Because we kept the `Requirement_ID` in both the concept-extraction table and the clustering/mapping table, we can create traceability matrices that connect each requirement to the concepts it contains, the semantic cluster those concepts were grouped into, and the ontology class they were mapped to. These matrices are then used for coverage analysis, allowing us to check systematically that every critical requirement is represented by corresponding elements in the ontology (and to identify gaps or over/under-modelling early).

The workflow itself consists of iterative steps:

1. **Automatic or semi-automatic extraction** using large language models and pattern templates.
2. **Human-in-the-loop validation and correction**, resolving ambiguities and harmonising terminology.
3. **Augmentation** with clusters, suggested classes and URIs.
4. **Final expert review** to confirm suitability for ontology design.

Figure 2. AI-Assisted Qualitative Analysis Workflow with Iterative Refinement

The workflow processes requirements, competency questions, and supporting documents through four iterative steps with human validation at critical checkpoints. Feedback loops enable iterative refinement: after human-in-the-loop validation, if quality is inadequate, the workflow returns to extraction (Step 1) for corrections; after expert review, if coverage is incomplete, the workflow returns to clustering (Step 3) or coding (Step 2) for refinement. Decision nodes (diamond shapes) represent quality checkpoints where iteration decisions are made based on predefined criteria. This iterative process continues until all quality thresholds are met, producing three main outputs: (1) concept extraction (corrected sheet) with semantic codes and concept types, (2) semantic clustering (enhanced sheet) with ontology class suggestions and candidate URIs, and (3) traceability matrices linking requirements to concepts, clusters, and ontology classes. Requirement_ID is preserved throughout all steps and iterations to ensure an auditable traceability chain from textual requirements to formal ontology elements.

As illustrated in **Figure 2**, the workflow incorporates iterative refinement through two critical feedback loops that ensure quality and completeness:

Key Iterative Elements Shown:

- **Iteration Point 1 (Quality Checkpoint):** After Human Validation of the initial concept extraction, if quality is inadequate, the workflow returns to Step 1 (Concept Extraction) for corrections and re-extraction.
- **Iteration Point 2 (Completeness Checkpoint):** After Expert Review of the clustering and class suggestions, if coverage is incomplete or conflicts exist, the workflow returns to Step 2 (Semantic Coding) for refinement and re-clustering.
- **Decision Nodes:** Diamond shapes (Quality OK? and Complete?) represent quality checkpoints where iteration decisions are made based on validation outcomes.
- **Feedback Arrows:** Iteration loops labelled "No: Iterate" explicitly show the refinement cycles, ensuring the workflow continues until all quality criteria are satisfied before proceeding to outputs.

These feedback loops distinguish the approach from a single-pass pipeline: quality emerges through iterative refinement rather than assuming that initial outputs are sufficient. The decision to iterate is made explicitly at each checkpoint based on predefined quality criteria (e.g., terminology consistency, concept completeness, requirement coverage), ensuring that progression to subsequent steps or final outputs occurs only when quality thresholds are met. The number of iterations varies by requirement batch: simple, well-specified requirements may require only one or two passes, while complex or ambiguous requirements may require several iterations before reaching satisfactory quality.

This process provides a transparent and reproducible bridge between informal textual requirements and the formal ontology.

AI-assisted extraction was used only to accelerate the initial identification and normalisation of candidate concepts and candidate mappings from textual artefacts (requirements and competency questions). It was not used to make operational decisions, prioritise policy measures, or replace domain expertise; all candidate concepts, codes, cluster assignments and ontology-class suggestions were treated as proposals requiring human confirmation.

To manage well-known limitations of large language models (e.g., plausible-but-incorrect outputs, omission of rare concepts, and amplification of linguistic bias), the workflow applied explicit human oversight and traceability controls consistent with established AI risk-management practice: (i) human-in-the-loop validation of extracted concepts and mappings; (ii) preservation of Requirement_ID links to maintain an auditable chain from text → concept → cluster → ontology

element; (iii) terminology harmonisation to prevent concept duplication; and (iv) expert review to resolve ambiguity and confirm coverage.

Reproducibility is ensured through (a) a controlled extraction template (consistent prompt framing and concept-type scheme ENT/PROC/EVENT/STATE/PROP/REL), (b) versioned corrected/enhanced sheets, and (c) recorded revisions during manual correction. This positions the approach as an “LLM-in-the-loop” qualitative coding aid rather than automated qualitative analysis, aligning with evidence that human-LLM collaboration can reduce effort while maintaining coding quality when human validation remains primary.

3.3 Knowledge acquisition and stakeholder engagement

This subsection describes how domain knowledge was systematically elicited and consolidated from project partners, pilot cities and existing project documentation. Given the distributed, multi-partner nature of the AntifragiCity project, a structured, asynchronous **knowledge acquisition** approach was adopted to ensure comprehensive coverage across all pilot contexts while respecting partners' operational constraints and local expertise.

3.3.1 Distributed requirements elicitation

Knowledge acquisition centred on a structured requirements elicitation process involving all project partners and pilot city representatives. Rather than relying solely on centralised workshops, which can be difficult to schedule across multiple time zones and partner organisations, the team deployed a distributed elicitation methodology using structured templates.

Each partner and pilot city was asked to contribute requirements according to a standardised template specifying:

1. **Requirement title:** A concise label identifying the requirement
2. **Requirement description:** A 1-2 sentence explanation of what the requirement entails
3. **Requirement type:** Classification as social, technical, governance/policy, environmental, or combinations thereof
4. **Scenario/Example:** A concrete illustration or use case demonstrating the requirement in practice

This template-based approach ensured systematic coverage across all partner domains (transport modelling, AI/ML, equity analysis, governance, climate adaptation, digital twins, participatory tools) and all pilot contexts (Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki), while allowing partners to express requirements using their own terminology and local perspectives.

3.3.2 Integration with existing project artefacts

The requirements elicitation process was complemented by systematic extraction of requirements from:

- **D2.1 (Urban Event Mapping deliverable):** Requirements relating to disruption types, event taxonomies, severity classifications and cross-city event harmonisation were derived from the D2.1 event catalogue and two-axis taxonomy (Domain × Scale). This ensured that the ontology's Disruption & Risk module directly supports the event-based vulnerability analysis framework established in D2.1.

- **Literature review for requirements completion:** To ensure comprehensive coverage of antifragile urban mobility concerns beyond what partners and pilot cities explicitly identified, a literature review was conducted focusing on urban mobility resilience, disruption response, equity in transport systems, and smart city applications. A total of 123 Q1-ranked papers were gathered from Scopus, Web of Science, and IEEE Xplore and analysed to extract additional requirements not already covered by partner contributions. Only requirements that filled identified gaps in the partner-contributed requirement set were added to the consolidated list, ensuring that literature-derived requirements complement rather than duplicate stakeholder-identified needs.
- **Ontology engineering and reuse literature (Section 2.5):** A separate review of ontology engineering methodologies, existing urban mobility and smart city ontologies, and semantic web standards informed the technical design approach, selection of modelling patterns, and identification of ontologies for reuse (e.g. SSN/SOSA, PROV-O, Transmodel, CityGML).

This integration of partner-contributed requirements, D2.1-derived requirements and literature-based gap-filling requirements resulted in a total of 61 consolidated requirements (Requirements 1-61), providing comprehensive coverage of functional and non-functional concerns across the project scope.

3.3.3 Competency question development

To operationalise the requirements and drive ontology design, each requirement was systematically elaborated into competency questions (CQs). Competency questions are a standard ontology engineering technique that translate high-level requirements into specific queries the ontology must be able to answer (14,17).

Partners and pilot cities were asked to define 3-5 competency questions per requirement, ensuring that each requirement had clear, testable success criteria. For each set of CQs, contributors were also asked to specify:

- **Equity/Access dimension:** Identification of which groups or actors are relevant to the question (e.g. "vulnerable populations", "elderly citizens", "low-income households", "emergency services"). This ensures that equity considerations are embedded from the outset rather than added post hoc.
- **Provenance metadata:** Where known, specification of the source of information, temporal context and confidence level. This supports the ontology's data provenance and trust management requirements (Requirement 36, 38) and aligns with FAIR data principles.

This structured CQ elicitation process resulted in over 60 competency questions spanning all requirement categories and pilot contexts. The CQs serve multiple purposes in the ontology development lifecycle:

- **Design driver:** CQs inform what classes, properties and patterns must be included in the ontology.
- **Validation instrument:** CQs provide test cases for assessing ontology completeness and correctness.
- **Query template source:** CQs guide the design of SPARQL query templates (Appendix E.3).
- **Communication tool:** CQs bridge technical ontology specifications and stakeholder information needs.

3.3.4 AI-assisted concept extraction and ontology design

While requirements and CQs were elicited from partners, their subsequent analysis and structuring was accelerated using AI-assisted qualitative coding (Section 3.2). The AI-assisted workflow systematically extracted entities, processes, properties, states, events and relationships from requirement descriptions, CQ formulations and linked project documentation.

The ontology design process then translated the extracted concepts into formal specifications through the following workflow:

- **Concept extraction:** AI-assisted systematic extraction of entities, processes, properties, states, events and relationships from the 61 requirements and their associated CQs.
- **Semantic clustering:** Organisation of extracted concepts into coherent thematic clusters (TransportNetwork, DisruptionEvent, EquitySocial, Governance, DataProvenance, etc.) based on semantic similarity and functional relationships.
- **Refinement of conceptual distinctions:** Analysis of concept overlaps and ambiguities to establish clear distinctions necessary for the domain. For example, distinguishing between CitizenSegment (demographic grouping), EquityGroup (groups experiencing mobility disadvantage), and Stakeholder (institutional actors), or clarifying the different roles of Regulation (legal instruments) versus DataSharingAgreement (technical governance instruments).
- **Class taxonomy development:** Translation of semantic clusters into the 12-class meta-model (Section 6.3) and detailed class hierarchies within each ontology module (Section 6.5).
- **Property specification:** Definition of object properties and data properties to capture relationships and attributes identified in requirements and CQs.
- **Pattern design:** Development of semantic patterns (e.g. n-ary KPI observation pattern, disruption-response-state chains) to address complex information structures required by competency questions.
- **Traceability mapping:** Systematic mapping of each requirement and CQ to corresponding ontology classes, properties and patterns to ensure coverage (documented in concept extraction tables, Appendix A).

This requirements-driven design process ensures traceability from stakeholder information needs through conceptual models to formal ontology specifications, enabling systematic validation against the original requirements and competency questions (Section 10).

3.3.5 Positioning within distributed, multi-partner projects

This distributed, template-based knowledge acquisition approach is well-suited to large, geographically distributed consortia where synchronous workshops are difficult to coordinate and where local expertise is distributed across multiple partners. It complements rather than replaces traditional knowledge acquisition methods:

- **Strengths:** Systematic coverage, asynchronous participation, documented traceability, scalability across partners, integration with existing deliverables.
- **Limitations:** Less opportunity for real-time expert discussion, limited iterative refinement during the initial development phase.

The approach aligns with established practices in distributed ontology engineering (32) and requirements-driven development methodologies (14,33), adapted to the specific constraints and opportunities of the AntifragiCity consortium structure.

Future validation activities (planned as part of the validation framework, Section 10) will include focused workshops with city authorities, transport operators and emergency services to validate

ontology instantiations against real-world scenarios, providing additional validation evidence through iterative stakeholder engagement during the pilot deployment phase.

3.4 Ontology scoping based on requirements and competency questions

This subsection defines how scope boundaries were established using requirements and competency questions. Ontology scoping involves deciding **what to model explicitly** and **to what level of detail**. For AntifragiCity, the scope is defined through several lenses:

1. Core vs peripheral concepts

The distinction between core and peripheral concepts ensures that the ontology remains focused and tractable while still being comprehensive:

- **Core concepts** are those that appear repeatedly across requirements and competency questions and are central to antifragility reasoning. In AntifragiCity, these core concepts include DisruptionEvent, SystemState, Scenario, ResponseAction, TransportElement, MobilityService, Actor, GovernanceInstrument, Observation/DataProvenance, EnvironmentFactor, SpatialUnit, and TemporalUnit. These concepts form the 12-class meta-model (Section 6.3) and are elaborated in detail within the ontology modules.
- **Peripheral concepts** are modelled at a higher level of abstraction or delegated to external ontologies. Examples include detailed vehicle types (e.g. specific bus models, electric vehicle variants), fine-grained land-use classifications (e.g. detailed zoning codes), and domain-specific economic models. For these concepts, the ontology provides high-level hooks or alignment points to external standards, avoiding unnecessary complexity while maintaining extensibility.

2. Required reasoning tasks

The ontology scope is determined by the reasoning tasks it must support. Based on the requirements and competency questions, the ontology is required to support, at minimum:

- **Disruption impact analysis:** identifying **affected assets and user groups** for a given disruption.
- **Antifragility assessment:** computing or retrieving **antifragility and resilience indicators** based on system state transitions.
- **Equity evaluation:** evaluating **equity impacts** across citizen segments and vulnerable groups.
- **Constraint checking:** Verifying **legal and spatial governance constraints** for proposed response actions.
- **Performance monitoring:** aggregating data for **scenario comparison and KPI monitoring** across temporal periods and actor groups.
- **Cascade detection:** detecting **cascading failures and interdependencies** across transport, social and environmental domains.

Concepts essential to these reasoning tasks are in scope; concepts that do not directly support these tasks are considered optional or delegated to external ontologies.

3. Layered representation

The ontology distinguishes between **generic concepts** (in the 12-class meta-model) and **project-specific specialisations** (e.g. specific types of disruptions relevant to the pilots, local governance instruments, local KPIs). This supports reuse beyond the project while allowing local instantiation. In implementation terms, this corresponds to **one shared schema** reused

across pilots, while each city maintains its own **city-specific instances** and where needed **local subclasses** for pilot-relevant disruption types, governance instruments, and KPIs.

4. **Pilot-specific constraints**

The scope is also informed by what is practically **observable and controllable** in the pilot cities, including available data streams and models, existing institutional competences, and planned interventions and tools. Where no data or clear use case exists yet, the ontology defines high-level placeholders that can be refined later. This avoids modelling concepts at a granularity that cannot be populated from pilot datasets or used in decision workflows; instead, the ontology provides **high-level hooks** (e.g., a generic `:LandUse` or `:EconomicObservation`) that can later be specialised or aligned to external standards when the relevant data streams and use cases mature.

3.5 Strategy for selection and reuse of existing ontologies

This subsection sets out the criteria used to select, reuse, or align external ontologies and standards. To avoid re-inventing existing work and to maximise interoperability, the AntifragiCity ontology is designed to **reuse and align with established vocabularies and standards**. The strategy involves:

1. **Identification of candidate ontologies and standards**

For each semantic cluster, relevant external ontologies and standards are identified, for example:

- **Transport and mobility:** models aligned with public transport and multimodal networks (e.g. standards based on Transmodel, GTFS, and related vocabularies).
- **Sensing and observations:** the SOSA/SSN ontology pattern for sensors, observations and features of interest.
- **Spatial representation:** GeoSPARQL for geometry and topology; possible alignment with CityGML or INSPIRE themes for spatial planning and infrastructure.
- **Time:** OWL-Time for temporal instants and intervals.
- **Data provenance:** PROV-O for provenance of data, processes and agents.
- **Governance and policy:** vocabularies for organisations, legal documents and policies where appropriate.
- **Risk, uncertainty and events:** risk and hazard-related ontologies or patterns, where these fit the use cases.

2. **Reuse patterns**

- **Direct reuse:** adopting classes and properties from external ontologies through import or subclassing (e.g. reusing `sosa:Observation` and specialising it for traffic or emission observations).
- **Alignment:** defining equivalence or subsumption relations between AntifragiCity classes and external ones (e.g. mapping `:TransportElement` to or from relevant infrastructure classes).
- **Annotation-based reuse:** when direct alignment is not possible or desirable, adding annotations that indicate correspondences (for documentation and mapping scripts).

3. **Minimal commitment and modular import**

- External ontologies are imported **modularly**, restricted to the subsets needed for AntifragiCity.

- The AntifragiCity ontology maintains **its own namespace and top-level classes**, limiting the impact of external changes and ensuring conceptual coherence.
4. **Evaluation and selection criteria**
Candidate ontologies are assessed based on:
- **Maturity and adoption** (usage in other projects, standardisation status).
 - **Conceptual compatibility** with antifragility, socio-technical systems and urban mobility.
 - **Licensing** and openness.
 - **Technical quality** (formal correctness, documentation, stability).

A detailed mapping table between AntifragiCity classes and selected external ontologies will continue to be refined as alignment decisions are agreed in the consortium and as pilot implementations progress.

For each AntifragiCity module, the design process therefore begins by searching for suitable concepts and modelling patterns in existing ontologies and adopting them through import, subclassing, or mapping. Only when no adequate concept exists do we define new AntifragiCity classes, particularly for antifragility metrics, equilibrium states, equity-aware KPIs, cascading disruption chains, and scenario structures in urban mobility. This ensures that the ontology is interoperable with existing ecosystems while clearly identifying AntifragiCity's novel semantic contributions.

3.6 Tooling and implementation environment

This subsection describes the tools and implementation conventions used to maintain the ontology artefacts. The ontology development relies on a set of tools and conventions. The current plan includes:

1. Ontology authoring and management:

The ontology artefacts are maintained as OWL files in standard RDF serialisations under version control (e.g., Turtle/RDF/XML). Consistency checking and validation use standard OWL reasoners and RDF validation approaches (e.g., SPARQL-based checks and SHACL where appropriate); this does not depend on any single editor.

During finalisation, the OWL file can be loaded in Protégé for inspection and consistency checking with an OWL reasoner. Figures included in this deliverable are schematic representations derived from the OWL specification (e.g., Mermaid.js diagrams) and are not direct exports from Protégé.

2. Vocabulary and URI management

A namespace and URI scheme is defined based on the Candidate_URI column from the enhanced concept extraction, so that every ontology term (classes and properties) has a unique and stable identifier. Where appropriate, scripts or other tooling are used to automate generation of OWL class and property declarations from the concept tables, reducing manual effort and avoiding naming inconsistencies. Labels and documentation annotations are used to preserve the original concept descriptions and to maintain traceability to Requirement_ID references, ensuring that ontology terms remain interpretable and auditable as the ontology evolves.

3. Knowledge graph storage and querying

The ontology and instance data are planned to be deployed in a graph database / triple store supporting SPARQL 1.1 (i.e., a database designed for RDF/OWL "triples", where facts are stored as linked statements rather than rows and columns). Named graphs are planned to be defined for different pilots, datasets or modules (e.g. separate graphs for Bratislava,

Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki; separate graphs for scenarios vs observations), so that data can be cleanly separated, compared across pilots, and governed independently where needed. SPARQL endpoints and APIs are planned to be provided so they can be consumed by digital twins, analytics tools and dashboards; in practice, this means external systems can query the knowledge graph (and, where appropriate, push updates) through standard interfaces without needing direct access to OWL files.

4. **Rule engines and validation frameworks**

SWRL or equivalent rule languages are used to encode inference rules for antifragility scores, vulnerability, equity alerts and scenario evaluations (i.e., “if-then” logic that derives additional facts such as alert flags or state classifications from existing observations and relationships). SHACL shapes may also be used for data validation (e.g. ensuring that certain properties are present for specific classes, checking domain/range constraints), so that incoming pilot data and model outputs are complete and consistent before they are used in queries, dashboards, or decision support.

5. **Integration with AI and simulation tools**

Adapters or wrappers are used to map outputs from prediction models, simulations and optimisation tools to ontology instances (e.g. JSON-LD, RDF serialisation). Procedures are defined for synchronising digital twins with the knowledge graph (e.g. periodically pushing updated SystemStates and Observations). In practical terms, adapters/wrappers are lightweight translation components that convert model or simulation outputs (typically JSON/CSV) into ontology-aligned RDF/JSON-LD instances (for example, creating or updating SystemState and Observation records). Synchronisation specifies when and how updates are pushed from the digital twin to the knowledge graph (e.g. after each simulation run or on a scheduled interval), ensuring that downstream analytics and dashboards query current state and KPI evidence consistently.

4 Project Context, Requirements and Competency Questions

This section summarises the requirements and competency questions and explains how they are used to drive ontology design.

4.1 Urban mobility challenges and antifragility goals

European cities are confronted with a convergence of **acute shocks** and **slow-burning stresses** that affect their mobility systems:

- **Acute disruptions:** accidents, infrastructure failures, floods, heatwaves and generally, extreme weather events, cyber-attacks, large events or protests, and sudden demand-supply imbalances.
- **Chronic stresses:** persistent congestion, air and noise pollution, rising energy costs, climate change, demographic changes and socio-spatial inequalities.

- **Systemic crises:** pandemics, economic downturns and geopolitical shocks that reconfigure mobility demand and supply over longer periods.

Traditional planning and operations frameworks largely strive for **robustness** (resisting change) or **resilience** (bouncing back). AntifragiCity adopts a different stance: urban mobility systems should **benefit from variability and disruption**, by learning, adapting and reconfiguring in ways that improve performance, equity and sustainability over time.

From the project perspective and as synthesised in Deliverable D2.1 *Urban Event Mapping*, an antifragile urban mobility system should be able to:

- **Maximise individual and collective mobility under uncertainty** while optimising system performance (Requirements 1, 47).
- **Adapt network configuration, land-use and infrastructure** to improve accessibility, reduce vulnerability and support long-term sustainable development (Requirements 2, 28, 60).
- **Foster active and low-emission modes** while maintaining service quality, optimising energy use and reducing environmental impacts (Requirements 3, 5, 24, 41, 59).
- **Respond intelligently to disruptions** through rapid sensing, monitoring and analytics, scenario evaluation, adaptive response actions, proactive rerouting, edge computing resilience, and learning from repeated events and near-miss incidents (Requirements 4, 7, 9, 11, 14, 15, 16, 22, 23, 25, 46, 51, 52, 57, 58, 60, 61).
- **Anticipate and prepare for climate stresses and long-term changes** by integrating climate projections, environmental data and PESTEL contextual factors into planning and operational decision-making (Requirements 8, 44, 45).
- **Simulate, analyse and evaluate alternative scenarios** including disruptive events, unexpected situations, policy interventions and transport measures, enabling what-if analysis and comparative evaluation across cities and contexts (Requirements 12, 15, 20, 21, 50, 53, 54).
- **Maintain equity and inclusiveness**, ensuring that vulnerable groups and citizens with diverse mobility conditions are not adversely affected, that benefits are fairly distributed, and that real-time equity monitoring informs decisions (Requirements 6, 29, 31, 43).
- **Coordinate multiple actors and governance levels**, including emergency services, agencies, transport operators, city authorities and citizens, while supporting inter-agency collaboration, stakeholder input and usability across split governance structures (Requirements 13, 17, 26, 32, 33, 34, 48, 49, 56).
- **Respect legislation, legal constraints and geographical limitations** in planning and response actions, ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks and spatial constraints (Requirements 27, 28).
- **Integrate heterogeneous data** from traffic sensors, governance datasets, equity indicators, environmental observations, public transport systems, active mobility tracking, digital-twin outputs, safety and incident records, economic impact models, and cybersecurity-protected sources into a consistent knowledge graph and query layer (Requirements 18, 30, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 46, 50, 52, 55, 57, 59, 61).
- **Ensure user-friendly, accessible and versatile interfaces** that support diverse user needs, enable effective decision-making, and facilitate cross-city knowledge transfer and collaborative learning (Requirements 10, 42).
- **Detect and model interdisciplinary propagation** of disruption effects across social, technical and environmental domains, including cascading failures, multi-modal interactions, and system-wide interdependencies (Requirements 19, 35, 48).

These goals motivate the need for a **formal ontology** that can represent disruptions and system states, actors and governance instruments, physical networks and services, data and uncertainty, and the learning processes that transform perturbations into improvements.

4.2 Summary of functional and non-functional requirements

The project requirements catalogue, specified in section 13.1, Appendix A: Requirements, Concepts, and Competency Questions, **Table 4** comprises 61 requirements, each with a unique Requirement_ID and associated competency questions (CQs) detailed in **Table 6**. The requirements span functional capabilities and non-functional constraints relevant to antifragile urban mobility modelling and decision support. The requirements are organised into the following thematic categories:

Functional requirements

- Mobility performance and efficiency and optimisation** (Requirements 1, 3, 22, 24, 25, 35, 40, 47, 51, 52, 54, 60), These requirements address Individual trip optimisation and mobility maximisation (ENT_TRIP, PROP_TRAVEL_TIME), Transport mode interactions and multimodal coordination (ENT_MODE, PROP_MODE_SHARE, PROP_MODAL_SPLIT), Fleet planning flexibility and route optimisation (ENT_ROUTE_PLAN, PROC_ROUTE_CHOICE), Proactive rerouting and evacuation strategies (PROC_REROUTE, ENT_EVACUATION_ROUTE), Real-time traffic monitoring and condition prediction (ENT_TRAFFIC_SENSOR, ENT_TRAFFIC_DATASET, PROC_TRAFFIC_PRED), AI-based predictive maintenance (ENT_MAINTENANCE_SCHEDULE, PROP_FAILURE_RISK), Network design optimisation under stress (ENT_NETWORK_DESIGN, PROC_EVOLUTIONARY_OPT), Signal timing plans and congestion management (ENT_SIGNAL_PLAN, STATE_CONGESTION), Mobility service performance including ridership levels and user satisfaction (ENT_MOBILITY_SERVICE, PROP_RIDERSHIP, PROP_SATISFACTION_SCORE), KPI-driven performance monitoring and evaluation (ENT_KPI, PROP_CURRENT_VALUE, PROP_TARGET, PROP_KPI_NUMBER, PROP_STAKEHOLDER_SELECTION), Impact evaluation of transport measures (PROC_IMPACT_EVAL, PROP_MEASURE_EFFECT)
- Environment and energy and sustainability** (Requirements 5, 24, 41, 59), These requirements cover: Emissions reduction and environmental friendliness (PROP_EMISSIONS, PROP_CO2, PROP_POLLUTANTS, PROP_EMISSION_LEVEL), Noise pollution monitoring (PROP_NOISE_LEVEL), Energy consumption optimisation (PROP_ENERGY_USE, PROP_FUEL_USE, PROP_IDLING, PROP_ENERGY_CONSUMPTION), Ecological impact assessment (PROP_ECOLOGICAL_IMPACT), Microgrid reconfiguration for mobility-aware energy management (ENT_MICROGRID, PROC_RECONFIG), Environmental targets and sustainability goals (STATE_ENV_TARGET, PROP_ENV_IMPACT), Behavioural nudging for sustainable choices (PROC_NUDGE, PROP_SUSTAINABLE_CHOICE, ENT_INCENTIVE), Behaviour change measurement (PROP_BEHAVIOUR_CHANGE)
- Equity, vulnerability, inclusiveness and social justice** (Requirements 6, 13, 29, 31, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 56), These requirements address: Equity groups and vulnerable populations (ENT_EQUITY_GROUP, ENT_VULNERABLE_AREA), Citizen mobility conditions and diverse user needs (ENT_CITIZEN_SEGMENT, PROP_MOBILITY_CONDITION), User choice modelling and preferences (ENT_USER_PROFILE, PROP_USER_PREFERENCE, ENT_CHOICE_MODEL, PROC_MODE_CHOICE), Social vulnerability and risk exposure

(PROP_SOCIAL_VULNERABILITY, PROP_RISK_EXPOSURE), Service access and accessibility (PROP_SERVICE_ACCESS, PROP_ACCESSIBILITY), Cost-benefit distribution across groups (PROP_COST_PER_GROUP, PROP_BENEFIT_DIST, PROP_TRAVEL_COST), Real-time equity monitoring (ENT_EQUITY_OBSERVATION, PROC_EQUITY_MONITORING), Economic impact modelling (ENT_ECONOMIC_MODEL, PROP_ECONOMIC_IMPACT, PROP_GDP_EFFECT, PROP_ECONOMIC_INDICATOR), Multi-user and multi-level coordination (ENT_GOV_LEVEL, ENT_STAKEHOLDER, PROC_COORDINATION), Stakeholder coordination and participatory processes (ENT_STAKEHOLDER, PROC_STAKEHOLDER_ENGAGEMENT), Cross-city knowledge transfer and collaborative learning (PROC_KNOWLEDGE_TRANSFER, ENT_BEST_PRACTICE), PESTEL contextual integration (ENT_PESTEL_FACTOR, PROP_POLITICAL_CONTEXT, PROP_ECONOMIC_CONTEXT), Usability across split governance structures (PROP_GOVERNANCE_SPLIT, PROP_MULTI_AUTHORITY)

Disruptions, hazards, crises and emergency response (Requirements 4, 7, 8, 9, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 26, 33, 34, 38, 48, 53, 58, 61), These requirements capture: Disruption events and their characteristics (EVENT_DISRUPTION, PROP_DISRUPTION_TYPE, PROP_SEVERITY), Climate stressors and long-term climate projections (ENT_CLIMATE_STRESSOR, ENT_CLIMATE_PROJECTION), Hazard types and their impact (ENT_HAZARD_TYPE, PROP_HAZARD_INTENSITY), Interdisciplinary propagation of disruptive events (PROC_PROPAGATION, EVENT_CASCADE), Disruption severity scales and impact determination (PROP_SEVERITY_SCALE, PROP_IMPACT_LEVEL), Cascade effects and cross-domain failures (EVENT_CASCADE, PROP_CASCADE_DEPTH), Predicted and unexpected disruptions (STATE_PREDICTED_DISRUPTION, EVENT_UNEXPECTED), Infrastructure outages and system failures (EVENT_OUTAGE, PROP_OUTAGE_DURATION), Emergency types and crisis classification (ENT_EMERGENCY_TYPE, EVENT_CRISIS), Cyber-attacks and security threats (EVENT_CYBER_ATTACK, PROP_ATTACK_VECTOR), Pandemic and epidemic scenarios (EVENT_EPIDEMIC, PROC_EPIDEMIC_CONTROL), Quick response capabilities (PROP_RESPONSE_TIME, STATE_EMERGENCY_MODE), Resilient edge processing for distributed resilience (ENT_EDGE_UNIT, PROP_EDGE_RESILIENCE), Emergency service mobility and prioritisation (ENT_EMERGENCY_SERVICE, PROC_PRIORITY_ROUTING), Evacuation and rerouting prioritisation (PROC_EVACUATION_PLAN, PROC_PRIORITY_ALLOCATION), Centralized event management for crises and peak loads (ENT_EVENT_MANAGEMENT_SYSTEM, PROC_CRISIS_COORDINATION), Simulation of unexpected events and what-if scenarios (ENT_SIMULATION, PROC_SCENARIO_SIM), Co-evolving epidemic-mobility control (PROC_COEVOLUTION, PROC_COUPLED_CONTROL), Systemic learning from AV near-misses and safety incidents (EVENT_NEAR_MISS, PROC_INCIDENT_LEARNING)

- **Scenarios, interventions, learning and antifragility assessment** (Requirements 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 20, 45, 50, 52, 53, 54, 57, 58, 60, 61), These requirements include: Scenario definition and management (ENT_SCENARIO, ENT_BASELINE_SCENARIO, ENT_DISRUPTIVE_SCENARIO, ENT_WHATIF_SCENARIO), Scenario libraries and catalogues (ENT_SCENARIO_LIBRARY, PROP_SCENARIO_CATEGORY), Alternative disruptive scenario development (PROC_SCENARIO_DEV, ENT_SCENARIO_INPUT), Scenario outcomes and evaluation (PROP_SCENARIO_OUTCOME, PROC_SCENARIO_EVAL), Scenario analysis and forecasting (PROC_FORECAST, ENT_FORECAST_MODEL), Comparative scenario evaluation across cities (PROC_CROSS_CITY_COMPARISON, PROP_COMPARATIVE_METRIC), Antifragility scoring and fragility metrics (PROP_ANTIFRAGILITY_SCORE, PROP_FRAGILITY_METRIC, PROP_RESILIENCE_INDEX), Measures and interventions

(ENT_MEASURE, EVENT_INTERVENTION, ENT_CONTROL_ACTION), Recommended action suggestions (ENT_RECOMMENDATION, PROC_ACTION_RECOMMENDATION), Learning from interventions and response effectiveness (PROC_INTERVENTION_LEARNING, PROP_INTERVENTION_EFFECT), Long-term transformative learning (PROC_LONGTERM_LEARNING, PROC_STRUCTURAL_CHANGE), Causal evaluation processes (PROC_CAUSAL_EVAL, PROP_CAUSALITY_STRENGTH), Continuously learning agent-based digital twin (ENT_DIGITAL_TWIN, PROC_AGENT_LEARNING), Evolutionary optimisation of network design (PROC_EVOLUTIONARY_OPT, ENT_OPTIMISER), Systemic learning from safety incidents (PROC_SYSTEMIC_LEARNING, ENT_LEARNING_REPOSITORY)

- **Governance, legislation and institutional setting** (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32, 33, 34, 44, 48, 49, 56), These requirements address: Regulations and legal constraints (ENT_REGULATION, ENT_LEGAL_CONSTRAINT, PROP_LEGAL_BASIS), Legal scenarios and compliance (ENT_LEGAL_SCENARIO, PROP_COMPLIANCE_STATUS), Legislation input and regulatory frameworks (ENT_LEGISLATION, PROC_REGULATORY_ANALYSIS), Policy change events and impacts (EVENT_POLICY_CHANGE, PROP_POLICY_EFFECT), Governance levels and hierarchies (ENT_GOV_LEVEL, PROP_AUTHORITY_LEVEL), Protocols and standard operating procedures (ENT_PROTOCOL, ENT_SOP), Agencies and institutional actors (ENT_AGENCY, ENT_ORGANISATION), Inter-agency coordination platforms (ENT_PLATFORM, ENT_COORDINATION_SYSTEM), Stakeholder input and collaborative governance (PROC_STAKEHOLDER_INPUT, ENT_STAKEHOLDER_GROUP), Situation reports and operational communication (ENT_SITREP, PROP_SITUATION_STATUS), PESTEL contextual factors (ENT_PESTEL_FACTOR, PROP_POLITICAL_FACTOR, PROP_TECHNOLOGICAL_FACTOR), Emergency service coordination and prioritisation (PROC_EMERGENCY_COORD, ENT_EMERGENCY_SERVICE), Centralized event management and crisis governance (ENT_CRISIS_MANAGEMENT_CENTRE, PROC_COMMAND_CONTROL), Usability across split governance and multi-authority contexts (PROP_INSTITUTIONAL_FRAGMENTATION, PROC_CROSS_AUTHORITY_COORD)
- **Data, provenance, analytics, uncertainty and trust** (Requirements 18, 30, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 46, 50, 52, 55, 57, 59, 61), These requirements cover: Graph database representations (ENT_GRAPH, ENT_NODE, ENT_EDGE, PROP_GRAPH_STRUCTURE), Traffic sensors and real-time data (ENT_TRAFFIC_SENSOR, ENT_TRAFFIC_DATASET, PROP_SENSOR_READING), Data sources and provenance records (ENT_DATA_SOURCE, ENT_PROVENANCE, PROP_SOURCE_TIMESTAMP), Data provenance and trust management (PROC_PROVENANCE_TRACKING, PROP_TRUST_SCORE, PROP_DATA_LINEAGE), KPI catalogue and performance dashboards including T2.7 survey-derived indicators (ENT_KPI, ENT_KPI_OBSERVATION, ENT_DASHBOARD, PROP_KPI_VALUE, PROP_KPI_GROUP, PROP_KPI_SUBGROUP, ENT_CORE_KPI), Sensor networks and IoT infrastructure (ENT_SENSOR_NETWORK, ENT_IOT_DEVICE), Analytics engines and data processing (ENT_ANALYTICS_ENGINE, PROC_DATA_ANALYTICS), Forecasting models and predictions (ENT_FORECAST_MODEL, PROC_FORECAST, PROP_PREDICTION), Prediction error and forecast uncertainty (PROP_PRED_ERROR, PROP_FORECAST_UNCERTAINTY), General uncertainty quantification (PROP_UNCERTAINTY, PROP_CONFIDENCE_INTERVAL), Multimodal datasets and heterogeneous data (ENT_MULTIMODAL_DATA, PROP_DATA_HETEROGENEITY), Data fusion algorithms and integration (PROC_FUSION, PROC_DATA_INTEGRATION), Public transport, pedestrian and bicycle data integration (ENT_PT_DATA, ENT_ACTIVE_MOBILITY_DATA), Real-time monitoring and analytics (PROC_REALTIME_MONITORING, PROC_STREAM_ANALYTICS), Economic data and impact

models (ENT_ECONOMIC_DATA, ENT_ECONOMIC_MODEL), Cybersecurity and privacy protection (ENT_SECURITY_PROTOCOL, PROP_PRIVACY_RISK, PROP_ENCRYPTION_STATUS), Digital twin data integration (ENT_DIGITAL_TWIN, PROC_TWIN_SYNC)

- **Spatial, geographical and environmental constraints:** (Requirements 2, 8, 28, 44, 59, 60), These requirements include: Geographical limitations and spatial constraints (ENT_SPATIAL_CONSTRAINT, ENT_GEO_LIMITATION, PROP_TERRAIN_TYPE), Land-use planning and urban form (ENT_LAND_USE, PROP_DENSITY, PROP_MIXED_USE), Climate adaptation and environmental planning (ENT_CLIMATE_ADAPTATION_STRATEGY, PROC_ADAPTATION_PLANNING), PESTEL environmental factors (PROP_ENVIRONMENTAL_REGULATION, PROP_ECOLOGICAL_IMPACT), Spatial-temporal dependencies (PROP_SPATIAL_AUTOCORRELATION, PROP_TEMPORAL_DEPENDENCY)
- **Interfaces, user experience and behavioural aspects** (Requirements 10, 31, 41), These requirements address: User interfaces and interaction design (ENT_UI, ENT_USER_INTERFACE, PROP_UI_COMPONENT), User profiles and preferences (ENT_USER_PROFILE, PROP_USER_PREFERENCE), User choice modelling (ENT_CHOICE_MODEL, PROC_MODE_CHOICE, PROC_ROUTE_CHOICE), Behavioural nudges and incentive mechanisms (PROC_NUDGE, ENT_INCENTIVE, PROP_NUDGE_EFFECTIVENESS), Behaviour change metrics (PROP_BEHAVIOUR_CHANGE, PROP_MODE_SHIFT), Usability and user experience (PROP_USABILITY, PROP_USER_SATISFACTION), Configurability and customisation (PROP_CONFIGURABILITY, PROP_PERSONALISATION), Multi-device accessibility (PROP_MULTI_DEVICE, PROP_CROSS_PLATFORM)

Non-functional requirements

Non-functional requirements are primarily expressed through the following cross-cutting concerns:

- **Data quality and trust** (Requirements 30, 36, 38, 40, 46), Data quality metrics and assessment (PROP_DATA_QUALITY, PROP_COMPLETENESS, PROP_ACCURACY), Confidence and uncertainty quantification (PROP_CONFIDENCE, PROP_UNCERTAINTY), Trust scoring and provenance tracking (PROP_TRUST_SCORE, ENT_PROVENANCE), Audit trails and verification (PROC_AUDIT, PROP_AUDIT_LOG)
- **Privacy, security and legal compliance** (Requirements 27, 38, 56): Personal data protection (ENT_PERSONAL_DATA, PROP_PII_STATUS), Privacy risk assessment (PROP_PRIVACY_RISK, PROP_ANONYMISATION_LEVEL), Security protocols and cybersecurity measures (ENT_SECURITY_PROTOCOL, PROP_ENCRYPTION_STATUS, PROP_ACCESS_CONTROL), Legal basis and regulatory compliance (PROP_LEGAL_BASIS, PROP_GDPR_COMPLIANCE)
- **Interoperability and openness and integration** (Requirements 18, 35, 39, 42, 55): Interoperability standards (PROP_INTEROPERABILITY, PROP_STANDARD_COMPLIANCE), Openness and data sharing (PROP_OPENNESS, ENT_DATA_SHARING_AGREEMENT), Multi-modal integration (PROC_MULTIMODAL_INTEGRATION, PROP_MODE_CONNECTIVITY), Cross-city knowledge transfer (PROC_KNOWLEDGE_TRANSFER, PROP_TRANSFERABILITY)
- **Scalability, performance and resilience** (Requirements 4, 7, 9, 14, 23, 46, 51, 57): System performance under stress (PROP_SYSTEM_PERFORMANCE, PROP_THROUGHPUT), Operational continuity and robustness (STATE_OPERATIONAL_CONTINUITY, PROP_UPTIME), Overload states and capacity limits (STATE_OVERLOAD, PROP_CAPACITY_UTILISATION), Response time and latency (PROP_RESPONSE_TIME, PROP_LATENCY), Edge computing resilience (PROP_EDGE_RESILIENCE,

PROP_DISTRIBUTED_CAPABILITY), Real-time processing capability
(PROP_REALTIME_CAPABILITY, PROP_STREAM_PROCESSING)

The ontology must therefore support a **rich cross-section of functional and non-functional concepts**, going beyond a traditional transport network model to encompass governance, equity, data provenance and learning dynamics, environmental sustainability, user behaviour, crisis management, and system-wide resilience and antifragility.

4.3 AI-assisted concept extraction from requirements and competency questions

To ensure that the ontology is firmly grounded in the project’s needs, the consortium applied an **AI-assisted qualitative analysis workflow** to the full set of requirements and competency questions. The process can be summarised as follows:

1. Text corpus preparation

- All requirements (IDs 1-61) and their descriptions were consolidated.
- Competency questions (CQs) and other elicited information needs were added to the corpus.
- Texts were cleaned, harmonised and annotated with requirement identifiers.

2. Concept extraction and semantic coding

- Using large language models and semi-automatic coding rules, each requirement was decomposed into **concept phrases** (e.g. “individual trip”, “capacity allocation”, “climate stressor”, “data sharing agreement”).
- Each concept phrase was assigned a **semantic code** and **concept type**, distinguishing, for example, Entities (ENT_*), Processes (PROC_*), Events (EVENT_*), States (STATE_*), Properties (PROP_*) and Relationships (REL_*).
- **The concept sheet** (concepts_extraction) provides a cleaned list of these concepts and codes, ensuring consistency of naming and typing.

3. Cluster assignment and mapping to candidate ontology classes

- Concepts were grouped into **semantic clusters** reflecting their role in the urban mobility antifragility domain, such as *TransportNetwork*, *MobilityService*, *DisruptionEvent*, *SystemState*, *Scenario*, *EnvironmentFactor*, *EquitySocial*, *Governance*, *DataProvenance*, *SpatialUnit*, *TemporalUnit* and *ResponseAction*.
- In the **concept sheet** (concepts_extraction), each concept was assigned:
 - a cluster label.
 - a **Suggested_Ontology_Class** (e.g. :MobilityService, :TransportElement, :DisruptionEvent, :Observation, :SystemState, :Scenario, :Actor, :GovernanceInstrument, :EnvironmentFactor, :SpatialUnit, :TemporalUnit, :ResponseAction).
 - a **Candidate_URI** (e.g. :Trip, :Mode, :Disruption, :AntifragilityScore, :LegalConstraint).

4. Quality checks and expert review

- The automatically generated codes and mappings were manually reviewed and corrected where necessary.
- Domain experts verified that key requirements were adequately covered and that similar concepts were consistently typed and named.

5. Traceability links

- Each concept retains a reference to its **Requirement_ID** (and where relevant, associated competency questions).
- This enables later tracing from a requirement (e.g. “Resilient Edge Processing Units”) to the relevant ontology elements (:EdgeNode, :OperationalContinuity, :Outage) and to the datasets or tools that will use them.

This workflow ensures that the ontology is **systematically derived** from the project’s information needs, and that the mapping from textual requirements to formal ontology elements is **transparent and reproducible**.

4.4 Semantic clusters and 12-class candidate taxonomy

The concept extraction revealed a large but structured set of concepts. By analysing the **Cluster** and **Suggested_Ontology_Class** fields in **Table 5**, the consortium converged on a **12-class domain-independent meta-model** that organises the ontology at the top level:

1. TransportElement

- **Physical network elements and assets:** nodes, edges, corridors, routes, evacuation routes, assets, fleets, sensor networks, route plans, signal plans, and network design configurations.
- **Concepts:**
 - Network structure: ENT_NODE, ENT_EDGE, ENT_CORRIDOR, ENT_ROUTE_PLAN, ENT_NETWORK_DESIGN
 - Infrastructure: ENT_ASSET, ENT_SENSOR_NETWORK, ENT_SIGNAL_PLAN
 - Special routes: ENT_EVAC_ROUTE, ENT_EVACUATION_ROUTE
 - Fleet resources: ENT_FLEET
 - Network element properties: PROP_OPERATIONAL_STATUS, PROP_CRITICALITY, PROP_COORDINATES, PROP_NODE_TYPE, PROP_SPEED_LIMIT, PROP_LANES, PROP_DIRECTION, PROP_PRIORITY, PROP_FACILITY_TYPE, PROP_VEHICLE_TYPE, PROP_EMISSION_CLASS, PROP_EVAC_PRIORITY, PROP_CRITICALITY_RANKING, PROP_DEPENDENCIES, PROP_POWER_CAPACITY, PROP_ISLANDING_CAPABILITY, PROP_LANE_ALLOCATION, PROP_STOP_SPACING, PROP_FLEET_DISTRIBUTION

2. MobilityService

- **Services and operational models** offered to users, including transport modes, service configurations, choice models, and predictive/simulation models.
- **Concepts:**
 - Transport modes: ENT_MODE, ENT_ACTIVE_MODE, ENT_PT_MOVEMENT
 - Service quality: ENT_SERVICE_QUALITY_INDICATOR
 - Models: ENT_PRED_MAINT_MODEL, ENT_PRED_MODEL, ENT_SIM_MODEL, ENT_SCENARIO_SYSTEM, ENT_CHOICE_MODEL
 - Service performance properties: PROP_MODAL_SPLIT, PROP_RIDERSHIP, PROP_SATISFACTION_SCORE, PROP_TRAVEL_COST

3. DisruptionEvent

- **Events and hazards** that perturb the system, including natural disasters, technical failures, security threats, health emergencies, safety incidents, and policy interventions.
 - **Concepts:**
 - General disruptions: EVENT_DISRUPTION, EVENT_DEMAND_SUPPLY_SHOCK, EVENT_UNEXPECTED
 - Cascading effects: EVENT_CASCADE
 - Infrastructure failures: EVENT_OUTAGE
 - Security threats: EVENT_CYBER_ATTACK
 - Crisis events: EVENT_CRISIS
 - Health emergencies: EVENT_EPIDEMIC
 - Policy changes: EVENT_INTERVENTION
 - Safety incidents: EVENT_NEAR_MISS
 - Hazard classification: ENT_HAZARD_TYPE, ENT_EMERGENCY_TYPE
4. **SystemState**
- States of the system, including congestion, operational continuity, predicted disruption and antifragility/resilience indicators.
 - **Concepts:**
 - Operational states: STATE_CONGESTION, STATE_EVAC_CONGESTION, STATE_OPERATIONAL_CONTINUITY, STATE_OVERLOAD, STATE_EMERGENCY_MODE
 - Environmental states: STATE_ENV_TARGET
 - Predictive states: STATE_PREDICTED_DISRUPTION
 - Adaptive states: STATE_ADAPTIVE_TRANSFORMATIVE
 - Performance indicators: PROP_ANTIFRAGILITY_SCORE, PROP_RESILIENCE_INDEX, PROP_FRAGILITY_METRIC, PROP_PERFORMANCE_TS, PROP_PERFORMANCE_DELTA, PROP_SYSTEM_PERFORMANCE
5. **Scenario**
- Alternative futures, configurations and what-if analyses, including baseline, disruptive, and exploratory scenarios with associated uncertainty and outcomes.
 - **Concepts:**
 - Scenario types: ENT_SCENARIO, ENT_BASELINE_SCENARIO, ENT_DISRUPTIVE_SCENARIO, ENT_WHATIF_SCENARIO
 - Scenario management: ENT_SCENARIO_LIBRARY, ENT_SCENARIO_INPUT
 - Forecasting: ENT_FORECAST_MODEL, PROP_SHORT_TERM_FORECAST
 - Outcomes and uncertainty: PROP_SCENARIO_OUTCOME, PROP_SCENARIO_PROB, PROP_IMPACT_RANGE, PROP_FORECAST_UNCERTAINTY
6. **EnvironmentFactor**
- Environmental and contextual factors, including climate stressors, emissions, energy, and broader PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal) context.
 - **Concepts:**
 - Climate: ENT_CLIMATE_STRESSOR, ENT_CLIMATE_PROJECTION
 - PESTEL framework: ENT_PESTEL_FACTOR

- PESTEL dimensions: PROP_POLITICAL_FACTOR, PROP_ECONOMIC_FACTOR, PROP_SOCIAL_FACTOR, PROP_TECHNOLOGICAL_FACTOR, PROP_ENVIRONMENTAL_FACTOR, PROP_LEGAL_FACTOR
- Environmental metrics: PROP_EMISSIONS, PROP_CO2, PROP_POLLUTANTS, PROP_ENERGY_USE, PROP_FUEL_USE, PROP_EMISSION_LEVEL, PROP_NOISE_LEVEL, PROP_ENERGY_CONSUMPTION, PROP_ECOLOGICAL_IMPACT
- Economic and social indicators: PROP_ECONOMIC_INDICATOR, PROP_SOCIAL_VULNERABILITY
- Sustainability: PROP_SUSTAINABLE_CHOICE, PROP_ENV_IMPACT

7. Actor (EquitySocial / User / Stakeholder)

- Human and organisational actors and social groups, including equity groups, citizens, users, stakeholders, and their attributes.
- **Concepts:**
 - Social groups: ENT_EQUITY_GROUP, ENT_CITIZEN_SEGMENT, ENT_USER_GROUP, ENT_VULNERABLE_GROUP
 - Institutional actors: ENT_STAKEHOLDER, ENT_STAKEHOLDER_GROUP
 - City actors: ENT_CITY_SOURCE, ENT_CITY_TARGET
 - User characteristics: ENT_USER_PROFILE, PROP_USER_PREFERENCE, PROP_MOBILITY_CONDITION
 - Equity properties: PROP_SERVICE_ACCESS, PROP_SOCIAL_VULNERABILITY, PROP_RISK_EXPOSURE, PROP_ACCESSIBILITY
 - Economic impacts on groups: PROP_COST_PER_GROUP, PROP_BENEFIT_DIST
 - Access and rights: PROP_ACCESS_RIGHTS
 - Incentives: ENT_INCENTIVE

8. GovernanceInstrument

- Institutional and legal artefacts, agencies, protocols, data sharing agreements, and crisis management structures.
- **Concepts:**
 - Legal instruments: ENT_REGULATION, ENT_LEGAL_CONSTRAINT, ENT_LEGAL_SCENARIO, ENT_LEGISLATION
 - Policy: EVENT_POLICY_CHANGE
 - Organisations: ENT_AGENCY, ENT_ORG, ENT_ORGANISATION
 - Platforms and systems: ENT_PLATFORM, ENT_COORDINATION_SYSTEM, ENT_EVENT_MANAGEMENT_SYSTEM, ENT_CRISIS_MANAGEMENT_CENTRE
 - Protocols and agreements: ENT_PROTOCOL, ENT_SECURITY_PROTOCOL, ENT_DATA_SHARING_AGREEMENT
 - Operational communication: ENT_SITREP
 - Properties: PROP_LEGAL_BASIS, PROP_ROLE, PROP_COMPLIANCE_STATUS.

9. SpatialUnit

- Spatial entities and constraints, including boundaries, protected areas, vulnerable areas, and geographical layers.
- **Concepts:**
 - Boundaries: ENT_BOUNDARY, ENT_SPATIAL_CONSTRAINT
 - Special zones: ENT_NO_GO_AREA, ENT_VULNERABLE_AREA
 - Spatial data: ENT_GEO_LAYER, ENT_GEO_LIMITATION
 - Spatial properties: PROP_SPATIAL_CONSTRAINT, PROP_TERRAIN_TYPE

Note: ENT_EVAC_ROUTE appears both in TransportElement (as infrastructure) and can reference SpatialUnit (as spatial area).

10. TemporalUnit

- Time constructs and temporal properties, including durations, periods, timestamps, and temporal relationships.
- **Concepts:**
 - Durations: PROP_TRAVEL_TIME, PROP_RESPONSE_TIME, PROP_LEAD_TIME, PROP_LAG_TIME
 - Periods: PROP_TIME_HORIZON, PROP_EVAL_PERIOD, PROP_PEAK_PERIOD
 - Temporal markers: PROP_TIMESTAMP, PROP_SOURCE_TIMESTAMP
 - Temporal dependencies: PROP_TEMPORAL_DEPENDENCY.

11. Observation / DataProvenance

- Observations, KPIs, datasets, data sources, digital twins, user interfaces, and their quality, trust, and provenance information.
- **Concepts:**
 - Sensors and observations: ENT_TRAFFIC_SENSOR, ENT_SENSOR_NETWORK, ENT_IOT_DEVICE
 - Datasets: ENT_TRAFFIC_DATASET, ENT_MULTIMODAL_DATA, ENT_PT_DATA, ENT_ACTIVE_MOBILITY_DATA, ENT_ECONOMIC_DATA
 - Data sources: ENT_DATA_SOURCE, ENT_PROVENANCE
 - Models and engines: ENT_ANALYTICS_ENGINE, ENT_FORECAST_MODEL, ENT_ECONOMIC_MODEL
 - Digital infrastructure: ENT_DIGITAL_TWIN, ENT_MICROGRID
 - User interfaces: ENT_UI, ENT_USER_INTERFACE, ENT_DASHBOARD
 - KPIs and performance indicators: ENT_KPI, ENT_KPI_OBSERVATION, ENT_CORE_KPI, ENT_EQUITY_OBSERVATION, ENT_DATA_QUALITY_OBSERVATION
 - KPI type classifications: ENT_CO2_KPI, ENT_MODAL_SPLIT_KPI, ENT_TRAVEL_TIME_KPI, ENT_POLLUTANT_EMISSIONS_KPI, ENT_NOISE_POLLUTION_KPI, ENT_INFRASTRUCTURE_KPI, ENT_URBAN_DEVELOPMENT_KPI
 - Knowledge management: ENT_LEARNING_REPOSITORY, ENT_BEST_PRACTICE
 - Privacy and security: ENT_PERSONAL_DATA
 - Graph structures: ENT_GRAPH, ENT_NODE (also in TransportElement), ENT_EDGE (also in TransportElement)
 - Observation properties: PROP_SPEED_FLOW, PROP_SENSOR_READING, PROP_KPI_VALUE, PROP_KPI_NUMBER, PROP_STAKEHOLDER_SELECTION_COUNT, PROP_KPI_GROUP, PROP_KPI_SUBGROUP
 - Data quality: PROP_DATA_QUALITY, PROP_COMPLETENESS, PROP_ACCURACY, PROP_TRUST_SCORE, PROP_CONFIDENCE
 - Privacy and security: PROP_PRIVACY_RISK, PROP_ENCRYPTION_STATUS, PROP_ACCESS_CONTROL, PROP_PII_STATUS
 - Economic metrics: PROP_ECONOMIC_IMPACT, PROP_GDP_EFFECT
 - Performance: PROP_LATENCY, PROP_UPDATE_FREQ, PROP_THROUGHPUT

- Interface properties: PROP_UI_COMPONENT, PROP_USABILITY, PROP_CONFIGURABILITY, PROP_MULTI_DEVICE
- Processes: PROC_CALIBRATION, PROC_AUDIT, PROC_FUSION, PROC_TEMP_ALIGNMENT, PROC_DATA_INTEGRATION, PROC_REALTIME_MONITORING, PROC_STREAM_ANALYTICS, PROC_TWIN_SYNC

12. ResponseAction

- Actions, processes and interventions aimed at influencing system behaviour, including control strategies, adaptive responses, learning processes, and coordination mechanisms.
- **Concepts:**
 - Antifragility and control: PROC_ANTIFRAGILE_CONTROL, PROC_ADAPTIVE_CONTROL
 - Mode and behaviour: PROC_MODE_SHIFT, PROC_MODE_CHOICE, PROC_ROUTE_CHOICE, PROC_NUDGE
 - Social interventions: PROC_INCLUSIVE_INTERVENTION, PROC_BEHAVIOURAL_INTERVENTION
 - Planning and adaptation: PROC_ADAPTATION_PLAN, PROC_CLIMATE_ADAPTATION
 - Alerting and response: PROC_ALERTING, PROC_RESPONSE_STRATEGY, PROC_EMERGENCY_RESPONSE
 - Routing strategies: PROC_PROACTIVE_REROUTE, PROC_REROUTE, PROC_PRIORITY_ROUTING, PROC_EVACUATION_PLAN
 - Resource management: PROC_TRIAGE, PROC_RESOURCE_ALLOC, PROC_PRIORITY_ALLOCATION
 - Environmental control: PROC_EMISSION_CONTROL, PROC_ENERGY_OPTIMIZATION
 - Infrastructure management: PROC_MAINT_SCHED, PROC_PREDICTIVE_MAINTENANCE
 - Monitoring and evaluation: PROC_OUTCOME_MONITORING, PROC_PERFORMANCE_MONITORING, PROC_EQUITY_MONITOR, PROC_EQUITY_ALERT
 - Policy and governance: PROC_POLICY_UPDATE, PROC_STAKEHOLDER_INPUT, PROC_STAKEHOLDER_ENGAGEMENT
 - Assessment and evaluation: PROC_MC_EVAL, PROC_RISK_ASSESSMENT, PROC_MULTI_SCENARIO_EVAL, PROC_IMPACT_EVAL, PROC_CAUSAL_EVAL
 - Learning processes: PROC_INTERVENTION_LEARNING, PROC_LONGTERM_LEARNING, PROC_STRUCTURAL_CHANGE, PROC_AGENT_LEARNING, PROC_INCIDENT_LEARNING, PROC_SYSTEMIC_LEARNING
 - Knowledge management: PROC_FEEDBACK, PROC_TRANSFER_ASSESS, PROC_KNOWLEDGE_TRANSFER
 - Coordination: PROC_EVENT_LIFECYCLE, PROC_MULTIAGENCY_COORD, PROC_INFO_SHARING, PROC_CRISIS_COORDINATION, PROC_COMMAND_CONTROL, PROC_EMERGENCY_COORD, PROC_CROSS_AUTHORITY_COORD

- Health and epidemic: PROC_EPIDEMIC_CONTROL, PROC_COEVOLUTION, PROC_COUPLED_CONTROL
- Optimization: PROC_EVOLUTIONARY_OPT, PROC_NETWORK_OPTIMIZATION
- Infrastructure reconfiguration: PROC_RECONFIG, PROC_MICROGRID_RECONFIG

At this level, a generic :Thing class can be used where necessary, but the ontology will prioritise mapping concepts into one of the 12 domain classes. This meta-model provides a **stable backbone** upon which detailed classes and properties are defined in later sections.

4.5 Coverage analysis and identified gaps

The concept extraction and clustering exercise also served as a **coverage check** for the ontology design. Key findings include:

4.5.1 Strong coverage areas

- **Disruptions and response actions** are richly represented across requirements (4, 7, 8, 9, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 26, 33, 34, 38, 48, 53, 58, 61), providing a solid basis for modelling antifragility dynamics.
- **Scenarios, forecasting and simulation** concepts are systematically present (11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 20, 45, 50, 52, 53, 54, 57, 58, 60, 61), enabling a scenario-centric view of antifragility.
- **Equity and social aspects** appear repeatedly (6, 13, 29, 31, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 56) and are associated with explicit metrics (e.g. risk exposure, benefit distribution, cost per group, service access).
- **Data, provenance and analytics** are well captured (18, 30, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 46, 50, 52, 55, 57, 59, 61), with clear requirements for trust management, data quality, multimodal fusion, KPI monitoring, economic data integration, cybersecurity, digital twin synchronisation, and learning repositories.
- **Governance and institutional frameworks** are comprehensively covered (13, 17, 27, 32, 33, 34, 44, 48, 49, 56), including regulations, legal constraints, inter-agency coordination, stakeholder input, crisis management structures, and usability across split governance.
- **Environment, energy and sustainability** are well represented (5, 8, 24, 41, 44, 59), covering emissions control, energy optimization, climate stress anticipation, behavioural nudging for sustainability, PESTEL contextual factors, and mobility-energy integration.
- **Mobility performance and optimization** have strong coverage (1, 3, 22, 24, 25, 35, 40, 47, 51, 52, 54, 60), including fleet planning, proactive rerouting, predictive maintenance, real-time monitoring, and network design optimization.

4.5.2 Identified gaps and refinements

The analysis also revealed **conceptual gaps** that the ontology must explicitly address or strengthen:

1. Equilibrium and stability concepts

- Requirements largely describe *performance, congestion* and *scores* but rarely refer directly to **equilibria, basins of attraction or stability margins**.

- The ontology therefore needs to introduce dedicated classes and properties for equilibrium states, recovery time, equilibrium gap, and “distance” to desired attractors, even though they are not explicitly named in the requirements text.
2. **Multi-layer network and interdependency representation**
 - Interdependencies are explicitly addressed in Requirement 19 (interdisciplinary propagation of disruptive events across social, technical and environmental domains) and Requirement 59 (cross-layer modelling of mobility dependencies on power grid and microgrid operation).
 - Additional cross-domain interactions appear in Requirements 35 (transport mode interactions), 48 (centralized event management across layers), and 58 (co-evolving epidemic-mobility control).
 - To support cross-infrastructure antifragility (e.g. transport-energy-health), the ontology must strengthen representation of **multi-layer networks**, allowing disruptions in one layer to affect others, with explicit modelling of cross-layer dependencies and cascade propagation mechanisms.
 3. **Uncertainty and probabilistic aspects**
 - Some requirements mention uncertainty and prediction error (PROP_UNCERTAINTY, PROP_PRED_ERROR, PROP_FORECAST_UNCERTAINTY in Requirements 20, 36, 50, 52), but there is no fully fledged uncertainty model with formal semantics.
 - The ontology should therefore adopt **uncertainty design patterns** (e.g. for confidence intervals, probability distributions, qualitative uncertainty categories, data quality scores) to ensure compatibility with predictive models, AI/ML components, and decision-support under uncertainty.
 4. **Learning and long-term transformative change**
 - Requirements cover learning from interventions (11), cross-city knowledge transfer (42), long-term transformative learning (45), continuously learning digital twins (57), co-evolving epidemic control (58), and systemic learning from near-misses (61).
 - While the updated ontology design now includes extensive learning processes (PROC_INTERVENTION_LEARNING, PROC_LONGTERM_LEARNING, PROC_STRUCTURAL_CHANGE, PROC_AGENT_LEARNING, PROC_SYSTEMIC_LEARNING, PROC_INCIDENT_LEARNING, PROC_KNOWLEDGE_TRANSFER), these concepts need to be operationalised with clear semantics for: How learning occurs (feedback loops, outcome monitoring, causal evaluation), What is learned (parameter updates, policy changes, structural transformations), Where learning is stored (learning repositories, best practice databases, digital twin memory), How learning transfers across contexts (from one disruption to another, from one city to another).
 - The ontology must support **temporal reasoning** about performance improvements over repeated disruptions and **causal reasoning** about which interventions led to which outcomes.
 5. **Citizen-facing and behavioural components**
 - Concepts related to user interfaces (10), user choice (31), and behavioural nudging and incentives (41) are present in the requirements, and the updated ontology design now includes ENT_UI, ENT_USER_INTERFACE, ENT_USER_PROFILE, ENT_CHOICE_MODEL, PROC_MODE_CHOICE, PROC_ROUTE_CHOICE, PROC_NUDGE, and related properties.

- However, for an antifragile system that explicitly harnesses user behaviour changes and participatory processes, the ontology should ensure that behavioural models, feedback loops and nudging strategies are fully integrated with: System state observations (linking behaviour changes to performance outcomes), Equity monitoring (ensuring nudges don't disadvantage vulnerable groups), Learning mechanisms (improving nudge effectiveness over time), Governance instruments (ensuring behavioural interventions have appropriate legal basis and ethical oversight)
- The ontology should also support representation of **user feedback, community input, and decision-making** processes beyond individual choice models.

6. Circular economy and resource aspects

- Environmental and economic indicators are present (Requirements 5, 24, 37, 41, 59), including emissions, energy use, economic impact modelling, and sustainability goals. However, **circular economy concepts** (reuse, repair, material cycles, resource efficiency, lifecycle assessment) appear only indirectly or are absent from the current requirements.
- If these aspects become more prominent in later project phases (e.g. linking mobility infrastructure maintenance to circular economy principles, or modelling resource dependencies in transport-energy systems), the ontology may need extensions to EnvironmentFactor to capture circular economy indicators, links to external circular-economy vocabularies (e.g. Material Flow Analysis ontologies), and representation of lifecycle stages and resource flow concepts. For now, this remains a potential future extension rather than a critical gap.

7. Real-time operational constraints and physical limits

- While the ontology covers spatial constraints (28), legal constraints (27), and geographical limitations (28), there is limited representation of real-time operational constraints such as: Vehicle capacity limits and occupancy constraints, Driver working time regulations and crew scheduling constraints, Energy storage capacity and charging infrastructure availability (relevant for Requirement 59), Physical limits of infrastructure (load bearing, throughput capacity, thermal limits)
- These constraints are essential for realistic scenario evaluation and intervention feasibility checking and should be strengthened in the detailed ontology specification.

Addressing the gaps

These gaps inform the design principles presented in Section 6 and the reasoning patterns in Sections 7 and Appendix B, ensuring that antifragility, equity, multi-layer interactions, uncertainty, learning dynamics, and operational realism are represented even when not fully articulated in the original requirements. The gaps also provide a roadmap for ontology evolution as the project progresses and as empirical data from pilot cities becomes available.

Where possible, the ontology adopts **extensibility hooks** and **alignment points** to external ontologies, allowing these gaps to be addressed incrementally without requiring fundamental restructuring of the 12-class meta-model.

4.6 Role of competency questions in driving ontology design

Alongside requirements, the project elicited a set of **competency questions (CQs)** expressing the kinds of queries the ontology must be able to answer. Competency questions serve as concrete, testable specifications of the ontology's intended use and provide a bridge between high-level requirements and formal ontology design. Examples of competency questions from across the requirement categories include:

- Which **equity groups** are most affected by a given disruption scenario in a given city area?
- What is the **antifragility score** of a mobility system component, given its history of disruptions and interventions?
- Which **response actions** are recommended for a disruption of a certain type and severity, under current legal and capacity constraints?
- How does a proposed **transport measure** change flows, emissions and accessibility for different user groups over a specified time horizon?
- Which **interdependencies** could lead to cascading failures if a given infrastructure asset fails?

In the AI-assisted analysis, these CQs were treated similarly to requirements: key concept phrases were extracted and mapped to the same semantic codes and cluster. This has three important consequences:

1. Bidirectional traceability

From a given CQ, one can identify the required classes, properties and relations (e.g. :EquityGroup, :DisruptionEvent, :Scenario, :ResponseAction, :AntifragilityScore). Conversely, for each ontology module, we can list which CQs it contributes to answering.

2. Testable design

CQs form the basis for validation tests later in the project: once the ontology is implemented and populated, SPARQL queries corresponding to each CQ can be executed to verify that the ontology and data suffice to provide meaningful answers. Section 10 will document this CQ-based validation. Where relevant, competency questions originally formulated in earlier work (e.g. event mapping and equilibrium analysis in D2.1 and D2.3) have been consolidated and rephrased here, so that a single, harmonised CQ set underpins both the ontology and the associated analytical tasks.

3. Prioritisation and scope control

Not all conceivable concepts need to be modelled at the same level of detail. By focusing on CQs, the ontology team can prioritise modelling effort on those concepts that are essential to answer key decision-making questions, avoiding over-modelling.

In summary, the combination of **requirements** (specifying what the system must do), **competency questions** (specifying what questions must be answerable) and **AI-assisted concept extraction** (systematically identifying concepts from both) provides a robust foundation for the ontology. The next section (Section 5: Conceptual Foundations) builds on this foundation by presenting the **conceptual frameworks** including antifragility theory, socio-technical systems and semantic technologies that inform the ontology's design principles and architectural choices.

5 Conceptual Foundations

This section presents the conceptual foundations that underpin the AntifragiCity ontology. It clarifies how **antifragility** is interpreted in the context of **urban mobility as a socio-technical and cyber-physical system**, and explains the role of **semantic technologies, ontologies and knowledge graphs** in operationalising this perspective. It also positions the ontology within the broader ecosystem of **AI, digital twins, multi-agent systems and circular economy approaches**.

5.1 Antifragility in socio-technical urban mobility systems

This subsection positions antifragility within the socio-technical framing used for urban mobility modelling.

5.1.1 From robustness and resilience to antifragility

Traditional approaches to infrastructure and mobility planning focus on:

- **Robustness**: the ability of a system to continue functioning with minimal performance degradation under expected disturbances.
- **Resilience**: the capacity to absorb shocks, adapt and **return to an acceptable level of service** within a reasonable time after a disruption.

In contrast, **antifragility** emphasises systems that **benefit from variability, volatility and shocks**. An antifragile urban mobility system does not merely return to its pre-disruption state; instead, it **uses disruptions as opportunities to learn, adapt and improve its post-disruption state**. In AntifragiCity, this is reflected in requirements such as: *antifragile response to disruptions* (Requirements 4, 7), *learning from interventions* (Requirement 11), *antifragility score calculation* (Requirement 14), and *long-term transformative learning* (Requirement 45).

Conceptually, antifragility is characterised by **performance improvement after perturbations**, manifested through measurable increases in key performance indicators (e.g. accessibility, reliability, equity, emissions) after learning from disruptions. It is also characterised by **diversity of responses**, reflected in the availability of multiple alternative routes, modes, governance mechanisms or interventions that can be selectively applied. **Sensitivity to signals** including the ability to detect weak signals, incipient problems and opportunities is another key characteristic. Finally, **adaptation of structure and rules**, demonstrated through the capability to modify network configurations, service patterns, policies and behavioural incentives, is fundamental to antifragile systems.

These aspects motivate explicit modelling of **SystemState** (including performance, congestion, equity and antifragility indicators), **DisruptionEvent** (including type, severity and propagation), **ResponseAction** (interventions, measures, algorithms, governance changes), and **Learning processes and scenarios** (scenario evaluation, feedback loops, long-term transformations).

5.1.2 Antifragility across time scales

Similarly to resilience, antifragile behaviour unfolds over multiple time scales:

- **Operational time scale (seconds-hours)**: Real-time incident detection, rerouting, prioritisation of emergency services, dynamic signal control, resilient edge processing, real-

time monitoring and evacuation strategies (Requirements 9, 22, 23, 26, 33, 34, 46, 51, 52). Here, antifragility requires the ability to quickly exploit available redundancy and flexibility in the system.

- **Tactical time scale (days-months):** Implementation and evaluation of temporary measures, demand management strategies, behavioural nudges, pilot interventions, policy experiments, comparative scenario evaluation and recommended action deployment (Requirements 11, 12, 16, 41, 54). Antifragility manifests through learning from interventions, improved targeting of measures and adaptation of operational policies.
- **Strategic time scale (years):** Land-use changes, infrastructure investments, governance reforms, institutional arrangements, cross-city knowledge transfer, network design optimization, long-term climate adaptation plans and transformative learning (Requirements 2, 8, 27, 42, 44, 45, 60). Here, antifragility involves transformative changes in structure, for example, shifting to more compact, multimodal urban forms that inherently perform better under disruption.

The ontology therefore needs to support **TemporalUnit** concepts (travel time, lead time, evaluation period, time horizon) and provide representations for **short-term operational states and long-term structural evolution**.

5.1.3 Antifragility indicators and equilibrium concepts

To operationalise antifragility in decision-making, AntifragiCity introduces:

- **Antifragility score:** aggregating performance improvements observed after disruptions or interventions (PROP_ANTIFRAGILITY_SCORE).
- **Resilience and fragility measures:** indicators of system capacity to resist and recover (PROP_RESILIENCE_INDEX, PROP_FRAGILITY_METRIC).
- **SystemState trajectories:** time series of performance and equity indicators (PROP_PERFORMANCE_TS, PROP_PERFORMANCE_DELTA) across scenarios.

Beyond simple metrics, antifragility requires a conceptualisation of **equilibrium and attractor states**. A **desired equilibrium** is a SystemState characterised by acceptable levels of accessibility, emissions, equity and reliability. A **basin of attraction** corresponds to the set of states from which normal adaptation and control can drive the system back to the desired equilibrium without extraordinary measures. Antifragile systems are capable of **shifting to better equilibria** after disruptions, expanding basins of attraction and reducing the likelihood of falling into undesirable attractors (e.g. chronic congestion, persistent inequity, systemic breakdown).

While equilibria and attractors are not explicitly named in the requirements, they provide an essential theoretical lens for defining reasoning patterns, such as identifying **loss of stability** (e.g. repeated overload states, cascading failures), assessing **distance to desired equilibrium** (e.g. gap to environmental or equity targets), determining whether a sequence of disruptions and interventions leads to **improvement or degradation** in antifragility over time.

These perspectives inform ontology patterns in later sections, particularly for SystemState and Scenario modules.

The interpretation of equilibrium and antifragility adopted here is consistent with the analytical framework developed in D2.3 on equilibrium in urban mobility systems. In particular, :SystemState and related indicators (e.g. antifragility scores, resilience indices, performance deltas) are designed so that equilibrium concepts, basins of attraction and transitions between states used in D2.3 can be represented as ontology individuals and relations, and queried over time.

5.2 Cyber-physical and socio-technical system perspectives

This subsection introduces the cyber-physical and socio-technical perspectives used to frame urban mobility and antifragility.

5.2.1 Urban mobility as a cyber-physical system

Modern mobility systems combine three main types of components. **Physical components** include infrastructure networks, vehicles, depots, signals, sensors and other physical assets (TransportElement and related classes). **Cyber components** encompass control centres, edge computing nodes, analytics engines, digital platforms, communication networks and databases (ENT_EDGE_NODE, ENT_CENTRAL_SERVER, ENT_ANALYTICS_ENGINE, ENT_PLATFORM). **Sensing and actuation loops** integrate sensor networks, traffic monitoring modules, incident detection processes and signalling controls (ENT_SENSOR_NETWORK, ENT_MONITOR_MODULE, PROC_INCIDENT_DETECT, PROC_LOCAL_CONTROL, PROC_EMISSION_CONTROL).

These three types of components form a **cyber-physical system (CPS)** characterized by continuous feedback loops. Digital components sense the current state of the physical infrastructure through sensors and monitoring systems. They compute appropriate actions based on algorithms and policies. Finally, they actuate these decisions back onto the physical system through signals, traveller information, fleet dispatching and other control mechanisms. This sense-compute-actuate cycle operates continuously to manage and optimize the mobility system.

In such systems, antifragility depends on the **richness and reliability of sensing**, encompassing data quality, latency, provenance, trust (Requirements 30, 36, 39, 40, 46). It also depends on the **flexibility of actuation**, including available measures, controllable signals and adaptable service configurations (Requirements 16, 22, 25, 26, 47, 54). Furthermore, the **robustness of communication** and computation is essential, addressing edge versus centralised processing, resilience to outages, and protection against cyber-attacks (Requirements 23, 38, 57).

The ontology must therefore integrate **TransportElement**, **Observation/DataProvenance**, **SystemState** and **ResponseAction** in a way that reflects CPS feedback loops, including representation of **sensor observations** and their quality, provenance and trust; **control logic and algorithms** (e.g. antifragile control, rerouting strategies, emission reduction control, predictive maintenance); and **deployment architectures** (e.g. edge computing nodes, central servers, operational continuity, outage events, continuously learning digital twins).

5.2.2 Urban mobility as a socio-technical system

At the same time, urban mobility is a **socio-technical system**. It involves **human actors and institutions**, including citizens, operators, planners, regulators, emergency services and other agencies (Actor, GovernanceInstrument). It is shaped by **norms, regulations, policies and informal practices**, such as regulations, legal constraints, governance levels, data sharing agreements, roles and responsibilities. It is influenced by **behavioural responses** and **social vulnerability**, including mode choice, route choice, behavioural nudges, incentives, inequities across social groups.

The socio-technical perspective highlights that antifragility cannot be achieved purely through technical optimisation; it requires **governance mechanisms** that can adapt policies and regulations in response to new information (PROC_POLICY_UPDATE, EVENT_POLICY_CHANGE), as addressed in Requirements 13, 17, 27 and 32. It requires **participatory processes** that incorporate stakeholder

feedback, consultation events and requirement refinement (PROC_PARTICIPATORY_INPUT, ENT_STAKEHOLDER_FEEDBACK, EVENT_CONSULTATION), as emphasised in Requirements 13, 17 and 49. **Behavioural interventions** and nudges that encourage more sustainable and robust mobility choices (PROC_NUDGE, PROP_SUSTAINABLE_CHOICE, PROP_BEHAVIOUR_CHANGE) are essential, as specified in Requirements 31 and 41. Furthermore, **equity and inclusiveness** must be core objectives, ensuring that vulnerability and access disparities are reduced (equity groups, vulnerable areas, risk exposure), as mandated by Requirements 6, 29, 43 and 44. Finally, usability across split governance structures and multi-level coordination must be supported, as required by Requirements 32 and 56.

Consequently, the ontology must represent **actors and groups** (e.g. citizen segments, equity groups, stakeholder groups, multi-level user groups), **institutions and governance instruments** (regulations, legal scenarios, organisations, agencies, coordination platforms), and **social and behavioural properties** (preferences, risk exposure, benefit distribution, social vulnerability, access rights).

The integration of CPS and socio-technical views is central to AntifragiCity: **digital control and learning mechanisms must be aligned with governance structures and social objectives.**

5.3 Scoping Semantic technologies, ontologies and knowledge graphs

In line with best practices, AntifragiCity first reuses mature ontologies and standards (e.g. SOSA/SSN, GeoSPARQL, OWL-Time, PROV-O, Transmodel, GTFS) wherever they cover the domain, and only introduces new classes where antifragility-specific or equity-aware concepts are not addressed by existing work.

5.3.1 Role of ontologies in complex urban systems

In such a heterogeneous environment, data and models originate from multiple domains and stakeholders: transport operators, traffic management centres, public transport agencies (34,35); city planning departments, environmental agencies, emergency services (36,37); sensor networks, mobility service providers, crowdsourcing platforms (38,39); simulation tool, AI models, digital twins and scenario analysis platforms (40,41).

These systems use different terminologies, data schemas and assumptions. **Ontologies** provide a way to capture **shared conceptualisations** of key entities and relationships, align terminologies and structures across heterogeneous datasets (Requirements 18, 30, 39, 55), support **interoperable data exchange** between components, and enable **reasoning and inference** that leverages the semantics of the domain.

In AntifragiCity, the ontology defines the **semantics of classes and properties** for concepts extracted from requirements and CQs (Section 4), provides a **stable semantic backbone** for integrating data in a **knowledge graph** (Requirement 18), supports the formulation of **SPARQL queries and rule-based reasoning** that correspond to competency questions, and facilitates the **traceability** of metrics and decisions back to their conceptual foundations (Requirement 36).

5.3.2 Knowledge graphs for antifragile mobility

A **knowledge graph** is the concrete instantiation of the ontology with data about specific cities (Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, Thessaloniki), their networks, services, actors, regulations and data sources, and recorded disruptions, interventions, scenarios and outcomes.

Within AntifragiCity, the knowledge graph is expected to:

- link **TransportElement** instances (nodes, edges, routes, assets) with **Observation** instances (flows, speeds, emissions, KPIs).
- relate **DisruptionEvent** instances to affected elements, actors, SystemStates and ResponseActions.
- encode **Scenarios** as alternative sets of conditions, interventions and outcomes (Requirements 12, 15, 20, 50, 53).
- store **DataProvenance** information (data sources, timestamps, confidence levels, audit trails) as specified in Requirement 36.
- provide a querying layer for AI tools, simulation platforms and decision-support dashboards (Requirements 40, 46, 57).

The ontology must be designed with **knowledge graph implementation in mind**, respecting good practices of **dereferenceable URIs** and clear namespace design (as prepared in the Candidate_URI scheme), **alignment with external vocabularies** where appropriate (e.g. SOSA/SSN, GeoSPARQL, PROV-O), and **modularisation** to support incremental loading and reasoning.

5.4 Positioning within AI, digital twins, multi-agent systems and analytics

This subsection positions the ontology within the project’s digital-twin, multi-agent, and analytics ecosystem.

5.4.1 AI and analytics

The project deploys various AI and analytical components, including:

- **prediction models** for short-term traffic conditions and incident risk (ENT_PRED_MODEL, PROP_SHORT_TERM_FORECAST, PROP_PRED_ERROR, PROP_FORECAST_UNCERTAINTY) as specified in Requirements 15, 20, 50 and 52.
- **optimisation and control algorithms** for routing, signal control, fleet allocation and emission reduction (PROC_PROACTIVE_REROUTE, PROC_REROUTE, PROC_EMISSION_CONTROL, PROC_FLEET_ALLOC, PROC_DYNAMIC_ADJUST) as addressed in Requirements 22, 24, 25, 47 and 60.
- **classification and anomaly detection** for identifying unusual patterns in sensor streams (PROC_ANOMALY_DETECT) as relevant to Requirements 9 and 46.
- **scenario analysis tools** for comparing measures and strategies under uncertainty (ENT_SCENARIO_SYSTEM, PROC_SCENARIO_COMPARE, PROC_MC_EVAL, PROC_RISK_ASSESSMENT) as required by Requirements 12, 14, 15, 50 and 54.

The ontology and resulting knowledge graph support these components by providing a **unified schema** for input and output data, enabling **semantic feature engineering** (e.g. aggregating metrics by vulnerable group or area) as required by Requirements 6, 29 and 43, encoding **contextual constraints** (legal, spatial, temporal, environmental) that AI models must respect (Requirements 27,

28, 44), and capturing **explanatory information**, such as provenance and reasoning steps, to increase transparency (Requirements 36, 38).

5.4.2 Digital twins

Digital twins of urban mobility systems that is virtual replicas synchronised with real-time data, are central to exploring scenarios and evaluating interventions (Requirement 57). The ontology provides the **semantic layer** for the twin, describing the structure and properties of its elements; supports **bi-directional synchronisation** between the twin and the knowledge graph (e.g. simulation outputs written back as Observations and SystemStates); and enables **semantic comparison** between different scenarios, time periods or configurations within the twin (Requirements 12, 15, 53, 54). The modelling of **TransportElement**, **Scenario**, **SystemState**, **EnvironmentFactor** and **ResponseAction** is therefore closely aligned with the needs of digital twin tools.

5.4.3 Multi-agent systems and decision-support

In addition to data-driven AI, AntifragiCity may employ **multi-agent systems (MAS)** to represent travellers with preferences and constraints (Requirement 31), operators managing services and assets (Requirements 25, 47), authorities applying regulations and policies (Requirements 13, 27, 32), and various scenarios of operating conditions and disruptions.

The ontology is used to define **agent environments**, including accessible information about network states, disruptions and policies, standardise representations of **decisions and actions** (e.g. rerouting decisions, measure deployments, policy changes), and express **interaction rules and protocols** among agents and between agents and their environment (e.g. coordination, information sharing, disruption effects) as required by Requirements 13, 32, 49 and 56.

Decision-support tools and dashboards interact with these components through the knowledge graph, querying for current and predicted SystemStates (Requirements 51, 52), scenario outcomes (Requirements 12, 15, 50, 54), antifragility and equity indicators (Requirements 6, 14, 43), and recommended actions and their justification (Requirements 16, 26).

5.5 Links to resilience, sustainability and circular economy concepts

This subsection clarifies how antifragility relates to resilience, sustainability, and circular-economy concepts in the project context.

5.5.1 Relationship between resilience and antifragility

Antifragility builds upon and extends the concept of resilience:

- **Resilience** focuses on returning to or maintaining an acceptable level of performance after a disturbance.
- **Antifragility** focuses on *improvement through disturbance*, meaning that post-disruption states can be better than pre-disruption states across one or more dimensions (e.g. accessibility, emissions, equity).

In practice, both perspectives co-exist. Some elements of the system must remain resilient (e.g. emergency services must guarantee minimum response times and coverage, as required by Requirements 26, 33, 34), while other elements can be antifragile, using disruptions as feedback to

reconfigure services, redistribute capacity, encourage active modes or reform governance mechanisms (Requirements 3, 11, 17, 45).

The ontology supports this by modelling both **resilience indicators** and **antifragility scores**, capturing **learning processes** and structural changes (e.g. long-term transformative learning, structural change events) as specified in Requirements 11, 42, 45, 57, 58, 61, and representing **trade-offs** between different objectives (performance, equity, environment, cost).

5.5.2 Sustainability and environmental objectives

Sustainability is integral to AntifragiCity, with requirements targeting:

- reduced emissions and energy use (PROP_EMISSIONS, PROP_ENERGY_USE, PROP_FUEL_USE) as specified in Requirements 5 and 24.
- mode shifts to low-emission and active modes (PROC_MODE_SHIFT, ENT_ACTIVE_MODE) as mandated by Requirement 3.
- behavioural nudging for sustainability (Requirement 41).
- mobility-energy integration (Requirement 59).
- environmental targets and constraints (STATE_ENV_TARGET, ENT_PESTEL_FACTOR, ENT_CLIMATE_STRESSOR, ENT_CLIMATE_PROJECTION) as addressed in Requirements 8 and 44.

Antifragility complements sustainability by encouraging **system configurations that perform better under environmental stresses** (e.g. heatwaves, air quality episodes) as required by Requirements 8 and 44; enabling adaptive policies that can respond to changing conditions and targets (Requirements 8, 27, 44, 45); and supporting co-benefits, where measures that improve antifragility (e.g. diversification of modes, stronger local accessibility) also improve sustainability outcomes (Requirements 2, 3, 24, 41, 59).

The ontology links **EnvironmentFactor** with **TransportElement**, **MobilityService**, **SystemState** and **ResponseAction** to make these relationships explicit.

5.5.3 Circular economy and resource efficiency

Although the requirements only indirectly reference circular economy concepts, antifragile mobility systems are expected to make efficient use of infrastructure and vehicles, avoiding both chronic underutilisation and persistent overload (Requirements 1, 24, 25, 47, 60); support repair, reuse and transformation of assets, rather than purely linear expansion (Requirement 25); and integrate economic impact and resource use into decision-making (e.g. economic cost of disruption, productivity loss, compensation scenarios) as specified in Requirement 37.

The ontology provides hooks for circular economy aspects through Economic Impact Modeling concepts (PROP_ECON_COST, PROP_PRODUCTIVITY_LOSS, ENT_COMP_SCENARIO, ENT_ECON_MODEL) from Requirement 37; representation of measures and interventions that affect resource use (Requirements 24, 25, 47); and the possibility to link to external circular-economy ontologies in future extensions.

With these conceptual foundations established, the next section (Section 6) presents the ontology architecture and design, showing how the requirements, competency questions and conceptual frameworks established in Sections 2–5 are translated into a concrete 12-class meta-model, modular architecture, and formal specifications.

6 Ontology Architecture and Design

This section presents the ontology’s architecture, including its meta-model, taxonomy, modules, and alignment strategy.

6.1 Ontology architecture and NeOn-based design

Figure 3. Ontology Architecture

The ontology work in AntifragiCity follows the NeOn Methodology (14), a scenario-based framework for building ontology networks rather than a single monolithic ontology (5,33).

The NeOn methodology is used as a process reference to structure ontology engineering activities and deliverable artefacts; it does not prescribe specific tooling or constrain data governance. The ontology is delivered in World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)-standard RDF/OWL serialisations with stable identifiers, version metadata, and provenance annotations. Access conditions, licensing, and any restrictions on instance data publication are handled in accordance with the project data policy; where datasets cannot be openly shared, the ontology still provides reusable schema-level identifiers, mappings, and query templates without exposing restricted content. NeOn emphasises (i) collecting requirements and competency questions, (ii) reusing both non-ontological resources (documents, taxonomies, datasets) and existing ontologies, and (iii) supporting the evolution of a network of aligned ontologies over time.

In AntifragiCity we combine three NeOn scenarios in particular:

- **From requirements to implementation:** The Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD) is defined by 61 requirements and their competency questions, derived from D2.1, the T1.2 governing variables, literature review and partner input.
- **Reusing non-ontological resources:** the core concepts for urban events, domains, scales, EM-DAT groups and social-media categories are mined from D2.1 and related project deliverables instead of invented from scratch.
- **Reusing ontological resources:** we reuse established ontologies and data models in a modular, pilot-driven manner. The core alignment set comprises: (i) built environment assets (IFC/BIM), (ii) spatial semantics (CityGML/INSPIRE and GeoSPARQL), (iii) transport operations and traffic events (Transmodel/NeTEx/GTFS/DATEX II), (iv) sensing and observations (SOSA/SSN, with SensorML/O&M used only where richer sensor metadata is required by pilot data), and (v) provenance and organisational metadata where needed (e.g., PROV-O, FOAF/SIOC). External hazard vocabularies (e.g., Empathi, ENVO/SWEET) are used for event typing and alignment in the Urban Event Ontology module.

The resulting ontology architecture is shown in **Figure 3**. The D2.1 event taxonomy is adopted as the reference taxonomy and implemented as a controlled vocabulary for event classification. At the **resource layer**, incoming event records from data sources (including the D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue) are instantiated in the KG and assigned D2.1 taxonomy types. This ensures that the same event semantics are preserved when integrating heterogeneous data streams. At the **upper-ontology level**, the taxonomy is connected through alignment hooks (e.g., *Event/TriggeringEvent/DisruptionEvent* and corresponding object properties), enabling uniform querying and reasoning without replicating the full taxonomy in the upper layer.

At the top sits the Upper Ontology: Urban Events & Mobility, which acts as the project's master vocabulary; a small set of high-level classes and relations that all other ontologies and datasets plug into.

It captures the main facets required for antifragile urban mobility:

- **Events:** stressors and disruptions, classified by domain, scale, severity and type.
- **Actors & Governance:** individuals, organisations and authorities who operate and regulate the system.
- **Infrastructure & Services:** networks, facilities and mobility services that can be disrupted.
- **Context:** the wider background around an event (environmental and PESTEL factors such as weather, economy, politics and social conditions).
- **Impacts & KPIs:** how disruptions affect mobility, people, economy and environment, and how this is measured (including antifragility scores).
- **Responses & Learning:** operational responses, long-term interventions and learning processes that improve the system after shocks.
- **Equity:** population groups, vulnerable users and fairness dimensions, reflecting the project's SSH objectives.

This upper ontology is intentionally lightweight but provides a consistent semantic layer for reasoning about events, their causes, contexts, impacts and responses across all three cities.

Upper ontology OWL artefact (version 0.1). The upper ontology is provided as an explicit OWL artefact (initial version 0.1), covering the abstract integration points required for vertical alignment with reused ontologies. The ontology is maintained as a **Turtle (TTL) format file** in the **Cardiff University project repository**, enabling version control and collaborative development across partners. The intent is not to replace domain standards (e.g., IFC, CityGML, DATEX II), but to provide

stable, project-specific abstractions that enable consistent mappings across domains and datasets. The initial OWL artefact introduces abstract classes such as **BuiltEnvironmentNode**, **MobilityNetworkElement**, **Event**, **TriggeringEvent**, and **DisruptionEvent**, together with core relations for causality, impacts (including positive gains/capabilities), and provenance. This artefact will be iteratively refined as pilot data and work package interactions mature.

The middle layer groups the reused ontologies that are aligned to the upper ontology:

- **IFC / BIM** for buildings and facilities at **LOD 200-300** (schematic to detailed design level), so that stations, terminals and other key structures can be described using BIM semantics with sufficient spatial and semantic detail for mobility analysis, disruption assessment, and evacuation planning.
- **CityGML / INSPIRE / GeoSPARQL** for the urban spatial layer, including transport networks, land use, geometries and administrative units.
- **SensorML / O&M / SOSA / SSN** for sensors and observations e.g. traffic detectors, weather and air-quality sensors and other monitoring systems.
- **Transmodel / NeTEx / GTFS / DATEX II** for the operational transport layer: routes, stops, timetables and traffic events in public transport and on the road network.
- **SSH & social-media** vocabularies such as **FOAF** and **SIOC**, to represent users and organisations online, social-media posts and interaction metadata.
- **DMO (Disaster Management Ontology) / Empathi** ontology for structuring pre-disaster and post-disaster responsibilities and tasks and emergency-management ontology focused on representing emergencies, events, locations and impacts (used for social-media analysis and situation awareness). A dedicated Urban Event Ontology module is introduced in the middle layer to represent hazard and event types as first-class concepts. This module is derived from the D2.1 event taxonomy (formalised as a lightweight OWL vocabulary) and aligned where appropriate to external hazard/event resources (e.g., Empathi, ENVO/SWEET). This vocabulary is used to type event instances ingested from the bottom-layer catalogues/feeds (including the D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue). This makes event typing explicit and queryable, independent of whether event instances originate from historical catalogues or live feeds.
- A KPI ontology module integrating three complementary KPI sets: (i) D2.3 Core Antifragility KPIs (12 metrics including Antifragility Factor and System Responsiveness Index for equilibrium analysis), (ii) Task 2.7 Core KPI Subset (13 stakeholder-prioritised KPIs from Table 8, selected by ≥ 4 stakeholders for cross-city comparability), and (iii) Extended KPI Catalogue (209 KPIs from Table 7 organized into 7 groups and 20 subgroups for city-specific analysis). The module includes classes such as KpiObservation, CoreKPI, AntifragilityScore, with properties for measurements (hasCO2Emissions, hasModalSplit, hasUrbanDensity, etc.), metadata (hasKPINumber, hasStakeholderSelectionCount), and traceability to the KPI catalogue structure (hasKPIGroup, hasKPISubgroup).

The KPI catalogue is provided in Appendix B.2.4 and detailed in Tables 7 and 8. Table 7 presents the complete catalogue structure (209 KPIs across 7 groups and 20 subgroups), while Table 8 lists the 13 core KPIs selected from this catalogue by ≥ 4 stakeholders (ETH, Cardiff, DEMO, AUTH, Bratislava) for essential cross-city comparability. The catalogue is maintained as an updateable artefact aligned with the ontology's observation patterns: KPIs are referenced consistently across scenarios and cities, while measured values are recorded as KPI observations linked to scenario, actor group and temporal unit. This ensures the ontology remains stable while the KPI set can evolve through stakeholder validation and pilot needs.

Vertical arrows labelled “alignment” represent mappings from concepts in these reused ontologies to the upper ontology.

For instance, a DATEX II traffic event is aligned to the generic disruption-event class, a GTFS stop to a transport node, and Empathi/SWEET hazard classes to triggering-event types in the D2.1 event ontology.

The bottom layer collects the data sources that populate the knowledge graph: the D2.1 urban event catalogue, EM-DAT (Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED), UCLouvain, n.d.) and Copernicus (Copernicus Emergency Management Service (European Union), 2025) products, static city operational datasets (network topology, facilities, census and land-use layers), survey results, and dynamic sources such as sensor data, live operational feeds, simulation outputs and social-media streams. Static resources (D2.1, EM-DAT, Copernicus, survey snapshots and structural parts of city datasets) are distinguished from dynamic resources (sensors, social media, simulation outputs and live operational data). For clarity and implementation planning, data sources are grouped into **static** (structural or slowly changing reference datasets) and **dynamic** (streams and frequently updated feeds). This distinction is architectural (ingestion and update patterns differ) and does not imply different semantic status within the knowledge graph. The arrows labelled “data” indicate that these datasets are described using the vocabularies in the middle layer; because those vocabularies are aligned to the upper ontology, all sources contribute to one integrated urban-mobility knowledge graph instead of remaining as disconnected silos.

Finally, consistent with NeOn, this architecture is not a one-off artefact: the ontology network is expected to evolve as new events, datasets and use-cases emerge over the project, with the upper ontology and alignments updated accordingly. The NeOn-inspired lifecycle is applied as an ontology engineering approach for iterative development and reuse; it does not prescribe any data publication model. Data availability and access conditions are governed by the project’s data management and governance policy. The ontology is designed to represent provenance, licensing, and access constraints so that both open and restricted datasets can be described and queried without implying openness.

6.2 Design principles and modelling choices

This section presents the architecture and main design choices of the AntifragiCity Ontology. It introduces the **domain-independent meta-model**, the **12 top-level classes**, and the **modular structure** derived from semantic clusters and project requirements. It also discusses the **representation of multi-layer networks** and outlines alignment with existing standards and European mobility datasets.

The ontology is designed according to the following principles:

6.2.1 Requirements- and CQ-driven

Ontology is directly grounded in the requirements and competency questions (17). Every core concept (e.g. DisruptionEvent, SystemState, Scenario, ResponseAction) appears in multiple requirements and is necessary to answer one or more CQs. Traceability is ensured by keeping Requirement_ID references at annotation level (e.g. linking :Disruption to Requirements 4, 7, 19, 20, 22, 33, 38, 48, 53).

6.2.2 Antifragility as a first-class concern

Antifragility is **not treated as a secondary label** but as a central organising principle:

- **SystemState** includes antifragility-specific indicators (:AntifragilityScore, :ResilienceIndex, :FragilityMetric, :PerformanceTs, :PerformanceDelta).
- **DisruptionEvent** and **ResponseAction** are explicitly linked via patterns such as “disruption → response → updated system state”.
- The ontology accommodates reasoning over **learning** and **structural change** (e.g. :LongtermLearning, :StructuralChange, :AdaptiveTransformative state).

6.2.3 Socio-technical and cyber-physical integration

The ontology simultaneously represents **physical and digital infrastructure** (e.g. nodes, edges, sensors, edge nodes, analytics engines) as a **cyber-physical system**, and **actors, institutions, policies, equity groups and behavioural processes** as a **socio-technical system**.

This leads to **two strongly interconnected sets of modules**:

- Technical modules (Transport Network, Data & Analytics, System State, Disruptions).
- Socio-institutional modules (Actors & Equity, Governance & Policies, Response & Learning).

6.2.4 Minimal yet expressive top-level schema

To balance **expressivity** and **maintainability**, the ontology is organised around a **small set of top-level classes** (12), which are then specialised as needed. This simplifies alignment with external vocabularies, facilitates reasoning and querying, and reduces modelling effort when extending to new cities or use cases.

6.2.5 Open-world and incremental extension

The ontology follows the **open-world assumption**, which is typical of OWL ontologies: the absence of information does not imply falsity, and new concepts and individuals can be added without invalidating existing assertions, provided constraints are respected.

Modules are designed so that **new pilots** can extend existing classes with local subclasses, and **new domains** (e.g. energy, health) can connect via multi-layer network patterns.

6.2.6 Explicit uncertainty, provenance and constraints

Given the importance of **predictive models**, **risk assessment**, and **legal constraints**, uncertainty-related properties (:Uncertainty, :PredError, :ForecastUncertainty, qualitative scales) are explicitly modelled. Data provenance and trust (:DataSource, :Provenance, :TrustScore, :Confidence, :Timestamp, :Audit) have their own module, and legal and governance constraints (:LegalConstraint, :Regulation, :LegalScenario, :LegalBasis) are explicitly linked to actions and scenarios, enabling constraint checking.

6.3 Domain-independent meta-model

The **meta-model** is the backbone of the ontology. At the highest level, we define 12 abstract classes, each corresponding to a semantic cluster identified in the concept extraction:

- :TransportElement

- :MobilityService
- :DisruptionEvent
- :SystemState
- :Scenario
- :EnvironmentFactor
- :Actor
- :GovernanceInstrument
- :SpatialUnit
- :TemporalUnit
- :Observation (including DataProvenance)
- :ResponseAction

Figure 4. Meta-Model 12 Top-Level Classes

Figure 4 is a compact visual summary of the **upper-level backbone (12 stable top-level classes)** used to keep all modules consistent.

In OWL (Manchester-style), this can be summarised as:

- Class: TransportElement
- Class: MobilityService
- Class: DisruptionEvent
- Class: SystemState
- Class: Scenario
- Class: EnvironmentFactor
- Class: Actor
- Class: GovernanceInstrument
- Class: SpatialUnit
- Class: TemporalUnit
- Class: Observation
- Class: ResponseAction

These classes are **domain-independent** in the sense that they can be reused in different cities and possibly in other infrastructure domains, and provide a stable schema even if lower-level specialisations evolve.

At the meta-model level, we define **high-level object properties** that capture core relationships:

ObjectProperty	Domain	Range
----------------	--------	-------

affects	DisruptionEvent	TransportElement or Actor or SystemState
hasSystemState	Scenario	SystemState
hasObservation	TransportElement or MobilityService or Actor or Scenario	Observation
governedBy	TransportElement or MobilityService or Actor	GovernanceInstrument
locatedIn	TransportElement or Actor	SpatialUnit
validDuring	Scenario or SystemState or ResponseAction	TemporalUnit
triggersResponse	DisruptionEvent	ResponseAction
updatesState	ResponseAction	SystemState

Table 1. High-Level Object Properties Linking the 12 Meta-Model Classes

These abstract properties will be specialised later (e.g. affectsEquity, affectsAccessibility, locatedInVulnerableArea, governedByRegulation, etc.), but they already support generic reasoning patterns such as **impact chains** and **state transitions**.

6.4 Top-level 12-class taxonomy with subclasses

Each top-level class is specialised into subclasses derived from the enhanced concept extraction and cluster analysis. Below is a selection of key subclasses (not exhaustive).

Figure 5. TopLevel_Classes

Figure 5 is a readable “map” of **how the 12 top classes branch into key subclasses**, which helps follow the subsequent per-class text.

6.4.1 TransportElement

Represents physical infrastructure and technical components:
Class: TransportElement

SubClassOf:

{ Node, Edge, Corridor, EvacRoute, RoutePlan, Asset,

SignalPlan, SensorNetwork, MonitorModule }

Class: Node	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: Edge	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: Corridor	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: EvacRoute	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: RoutePlan	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: Asset	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: SignalPlan	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: SensorNetwork	SubClassOf: TransportElement
Class: MonitorModule	SubClassOf: TransportElement

These correspond, for example, to ENT_NODE, ENT_EDGE, ENT_CORRIDOR, ENT_EVAC_ROUTE, ENT_ROUTE_PLAN, ENT_ASSET, ENT_SIGNAL_PLAN, ENT_SENSOR_NETWORK, ENT_MONITOR_MODULE.

6.4.2 MobilityService

Represents mobility offerings and operational models:

Class: MobilityService

SubClassOf:

{ Mode, ActiveMode, PublicTransportMovement, ChoiceModel, PredMaintModel, PredModel, SimModel, ForecastModel, ScenarioSystem }

Class: Mode	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: ActiveMode	SubClassOf: Mode
Class: PublicTransportMovement	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: ChoiceModel	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: PredMaintModel	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: PredModel	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: SimModel	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: ForecastModel	SubClassOf: MobilityService
Class: ScenarioSystem	SubClassOf: MobilityService

6.4.3 DisruptionEvent

Represents disruptive events, hazards and cascading effects:

Class: DisruptionEvent

SubClassOf:

{ Disruption, DemandSupplyShock, Cascade, Outage, CyberAttack, Crisis, UnexpectedEvent, HazardType, EmergencyType }

Class: Disruption	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: DemandSupplyShock	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: Cascade	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: Outage	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: CyberAttack	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: Crisis	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: UnexpectedEvent	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: HazardType	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent
Class: EmergencyType	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Domain-based classification (D2.1 event taxonomy integration):

The DisruptionEvent class is further elaborated through domain-based subclasses that specify the source of disruptions:

DisruptionEvent is further classified by source domain:

Class: NaturalHazard	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent	Comment: "Meteorological and geological hazards"	Examples: Flood, Heatwave, Storm, Earthquake
Class: TechnologicalFailure	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent	Comment: "Technological system failures"	Examples: PowerOutage, InfrastructureFailure, SystemCrash
Class: HumanCausedIncident	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent	Comment: "Human-caused incidents"	Examples: Accident, CyberAttack (cross-references above), SecurityIncident
Class: Crisis	SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent (cross-references above)	Comment: "Large-scale systemic crises"	Examples: Pandemic, EconomicCrisis, GeopoliticalShock

Note: UnexpectedEvent can be further typed using the domain classification, and HazardType provides the classification scheme used to categorize disruptions by their source characteristics.

6.4.4 SystemState

Represents states of the system, including performance and antifragility:

Class: SystemState

SubClassOf:

{ CongestionState, EvacCongestionState, EnvTargetState,
PredictedDisruptionState, OverloadState,
AdaptiveTransformativeState }

Class: CongestionState	SubClassOf: SystemState
Class: EvacCongestionState	SubClassOf: SystemState
Class: EnvTargetState	SubClassOf: SystemState
Class: PredictedDisruptionState	SubClassOf: SystemState
Class: OverloadState	SubClassOf: SystemState
Class: AdaptiveTransformativeState	SubClassOf: SystemState

Antifragility-related measures are modelled as **data properties** or **indicator classes** associated with SystemState.

6.4.5 Scenario

Class: Scenario

SubClassOf:
 { BaselineScenario, DisruptiveScenario, WhatIfScenario,
 ScenarioLibrary, ScenarioInput }

Class: BaselineScenario SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: DisruptiveScenario SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: WhatIfScenario SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: ScenarioLibrary SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: ScenarioInput SubClassOf: Scenario

6.4.6 EnvironmentFactor

Class: EnvironmentFactor

SubClassOf:
 { ClimateStressor, ClimateProjection, PestelFactor }

Class: ClimateStressor SubClassOf: EnvironmentFactor

Class: ClimateProjection SubClassOf: EnvironmentFactor

Class: PestelFactor SubClassOf: EnvironmentFactor

Emission and energy-related properties will be associated with Observations and/or SystemState, while EnvironmentFactor captures the relevant contextual drivers.

6.4.7 Actor

Class: Actor

SubClassOf:
 { EquityGroup, CitizenSegment, UserGroup, Stakeholder,
 CitySource, CityTarget, Incentive }

Class: EquityGroup SubClassOf: Actor

Class: CitizenSegment SubClassOf: Actor

Class: UserGroup SubClassOf: Actor

Class: Stakeholder SubClassOf: Actor

Class: CitySource SubClassOf: Actor

Class: CityTarget SubClassOf: Actor

Class: Incentive SubClassOf: Actor

6.4.8 GovernanceInstrument

Class: GovernanceInstrument

SubClassOf:

{ Regulation, LegalConstraint, LegalScenario,
Organisation, Agency, Protocol, DataSharingAgreement,
Platform, Sitrep, SecurityProtocol }

Class: Regulation	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: LegalConstraint	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: LegalScenario	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: Organisation	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: Agency	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: Protocol	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: DataSharingAgreement	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: Platform	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: Sitrep	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument
Class: SecurityProtocol	SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

6.4.9 SpatialUnit and TemporalUnit

Class: SpatialUnit

SubClassOf:

{ Boundary, NoGoArea, GeoLayer, VulnerableArea }

Class: Boundary	SubClassOf: SpatialUnit
Class: NoGoArea	SubClassOf: SpatialUnit
Class: GeoLayer	SubClassOf: SpatialUnit
Class: VulnerableArea	SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: TemporalUnit

SubClassOf:

{ TravelTime, ResponseTime, LeadTime,
TimeHorizon, EvalPeriod, PeakPeriod, LagTime, Timestamp }

Class: TravelTime	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: ResponseTime	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: LeadTime	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: TimeHorizon	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: EvalPeriod	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: PeakPeriod	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: LagTime	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit
Class: Timestamp	SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

6.4.10 Observation, Data Provenance and KPI Module

6.4.10.1 Observation Classes

Class: Observation

SubClassOf:

{ TrafficObservation, EmissionObservation,
EquityObservation, EconomicObservation,
KpiObservation, DataQualityObservation, FusionObservation }

Class: TrafficObservation SubClassOf: Observation

Class: EmissionObservation SubClassOf: Observation

Class: EquityObservation SubClassOf: Observation

Class: EconomicObservation SubClassOf: Observation

Class: DataQualityObservation SubClassOf: Observation

Class: FusionObservation SubClassOf: Observation

6.4.10.2 KPI Framework

The KPI framework integrates three complementary KPI sets to support comprehensive antifragility assessment: (i) **D2.3 (Core Antifragility KPIs)** with 12 antifragility-specific metrics including Antifragility Factor (AF) and System Responsiveness Index (SRI) for equilibrium analysis and antifragility trajectory modelling, (ii) **Task 2.7 Extended KPI Catalogue** with 209 KPIs (Table 7) from Task 2.7 survey results organized into 7 main groups and 20 subgroups, providing comprehensive coverage for city-specific analysis, and (iii) **Task 2.7 Core KPI Subset**: with 13 stakeholder-prioritised KPIs (Table 8) selected from the extended catalogue by ≥ 4 stakeholders (ETH, Cardiff, DEMO, ATh, Bratislava) for essential cross-city comparability across Bratislava, Thessaloniki, Larissa, and Odessa.

This multi-level KPI structure enables both standardized cross-city comparison (through core KPIs) and flexible local adaptation (through extended catalogue), supporting diverse stakeholder needs while maintaining semantic interoperability.

Class: KpiObservation SubClassOf: Observation

Comment: "Key performance indicator measurements based on D2.3 framework and Task 2.7 survey results, and pilot city requirements "

D2.3 Antifragility and Resilience KPIs:

Class: AntifragilityScore SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Quantitative measure of system antifragility - the Antifragility Factor (AF) from D2.3"

Property: hasAntifragilityScore (xsd:double)

Property: hasAntifragilityFactor (xsd:double)

Class: ResilienceIndex SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "System resilience and recovery capability - incorporates the System Responsiveness Index (SRI) from D2.3"

Property: hasResilienceIndex (xsd:double)

Property: hasSystemResponsivenessIndex (xsd:double)

SubClasses:

- NetworkResilienceMetric
- RecoveryRateIndicator
- TransportNetworkResilienceIndex

Class: VulnerabilityIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation
Comment: "Measures vulnerability and exposure to disruptions"
Property: hasVulnerabilityIndex (xsd:double)
SubClasses:

- StressIndex
- Friability
- RiskIndicator

Class: AdaptiveCapacityIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation
Comment: "Measures system's capacity to adapt and learn"
Property: hasAdaptiveCapacity (xsd:double)
SubClasses:

- CommunityAdaptationVelocity
- LearningRateIndicator

Task 2.7 Extended KPI Catalogue (Table 7 - 209 KPIs):

Network and System Performance KPIs:

Class: PerformanceIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation
Comment: "System and network performance metrics"
SubClasses:

- CentralityMetric (Betweenness, Closeness, Degree, Eigenvector, CommenterFlow, TimeDelay, DelayFlow)
- CapacityIndicator (NetworkReserveCapacity, MobilityThroughput)
- NetworkRedundancy
- NetworkEntropyOfMobilityFlows
- EventDisturbanceIndex

Mobility and Accessibility KPIs:

Class: AccessibilityIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation
Comment: "Measures accessibility and mobility equity"
Property: hasAccessibilityIndex (xsd:double)
SubClasses:

- TransportAccessibility
- LandUseAccessibility
- DestinationAccessibility
- EquityPenalty

Class: TravelTimeIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation
Comment: "Travel time and delay measurements"
Property: hasTravelTime (xsd:duration)
Property: hasDelay (xsd:duration)

SubClasses:

- VehicleTravelTime
- PassengerWaitingTime
- AverageCommuteTime
- TravelTimeReliability
- NetworkDelayIndicator

Environmental Impact KPIs:

Class: EnvironmentalKPI SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Environmental and ecological impact indicators"

Property: hasEmissionsLevel (xsd:double)

SubClasses:

- EmissionsObservation (cross-references above)
- GHGEmissions (CO₂, NO_x, Pollutants)
- NoisePollution
- EnergyConsumptionIndicator
- EcologicalFootprint

Economic Impact KPIs:

Class: EconomicKPI SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Economic cost, benefit, and impact indicators"

Property: hasEconomicCost (xsd:double)

Property: hasProductivityLoss (xsd:double)

SubClasses:

- EconomicObservation (cross-references above)
- TravelCostIndicator
- TransportExpenditureIndicator
- NetPresentValue
- TotalRecoveryEffort

Equity and Social KPIs:

Class: EquityKPI SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Equity, fairness, and social impact indicators"

Property: hasEquityScore (xsd:double)

Property: hasSocialVulnerability (xsd:double)

SubClasses:

- EquityObservation (cross-references above)
- AffordabilityIndex
- ExposureLevelIndicator
- EquityPenalty (cross-references above)

Safety and Security KPIs:

Class: SafetyIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Transport safety and security metrics"

SubClasses:

- TrafficAccidentRate
- FatalityRate

- CrashCount
- InjurySeverity
- SafetyControlIndicator
- SecurityIndicator

User Satisfaction KPIs:

Class: SatisfactionIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Public perception and satisfaction metrics from surveys"

SubClasses:

- MobilitySatisfaction
- SafetyPerception
- ComfortPerception
- GeneralSatisfaction
- InfrastructureAccessibilitySatisfaction

Demand Management KPIs:

Class: DemandIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Transport demand and modal split indicators"

SubClasses:

- TransportDemand (Motorized, NonMotorized, PT, Freight)
- ModalSplit (Personal, Freight)
- Ridership
- TripRate

Infrastructure KPIs:

Class: InfrastructureIndicator SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Infrastructure quality and coverage metrics"

SubClasses:

- NetworkDensity
- PublicTransportAvailability
- InfrastructureSpatialFeatures
- LandUseIndicators

Task 2.7 Core KPI Subset (Table 8 - 13 KPIs):

Class: CoreKPI SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Comment: "Core KPI selected by ≥4 stakeholders for cross-city comparability (Table 8)"

Ecological Impacts (3 KPIs):

Class: CO2KPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI

Comment: "KPI 21: CO₂ emissions from transport sector (highest priority - 5/5 stakeholders)"

Property: hasCO2Emissions (xsd:double)

Comment: "CO₂ emissions in tonnes or kg"

Domain: SystemState | Observation | Scenario

Range: xsd:double

Class: PollutantEmissionsKPI

SubClassOf: CoreKPI

Comment: "KPI 22: Aggregate pollutant emissions from transport (4/5 stakeholders)"
Property: hasPollutantEmissions (xsd:double)
Comment: "Emissions of NO_x, non-methane VOCs and particulates in kg or tonnes"
Domain: SystemState | Observation | Scenario
Range: xsd:double

Class: NoisePollutionKPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI
Comment: "KPI 31: Noise pollution from transport activities (4/5 stakeholders)"
Property: hasNoisePollution (xsd:double)
Comment: "Noise pollution level in decibels (dB)"
Domain: SystemState | Observation | SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Transport Modes and Characteristics (5 KPIs):

Class: ModalSplitKPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI
Comment: "KPIs 38-40: Modal distribution across transport modes (4/5 stakeholders each)"
Property: hasModalSplit (xsd:string)
Comment: "Distribution of trips across transport modes (percentages or JSON structure)"
Domain: SystemState | Scenario | SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:string

Property: hasPersonalTravelModeSplit (xsd:string)
Comment: "Modal distribution for personal/passenger travel"
Domain: SystemState | Scenario
Range: xsd:string

Property: hasFreightModeSplit (xsd:string)
Comment: "Modal distribution for freight transport (truck, rail, water)"
Domain: SystemState | Scenario
Range: xsd:string

Class: TravelTimeKPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI
Comment: "KPI 47: Travel time across the network (4/5 stakeholders)"
Property: hasTravelTime (xsd:duration)
Comment: "Total journey duration including driving, idling, and pauses"
Domain: SystemState | Trip | Scenario
Range: xsd:duration

Property: hasAverageTravelTime (xsd:duration)
Comment: "Average travel time for trips in a given period"
Domain: SystemState | SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:duration

Class: TransportDemandKPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI
Comment: "KPI 68: Motorized transport demand (4/5 stakeholders)"
Property: hasMotorizedTransportDemand (xsd:double)
Comment: "Demand for motorized transport services in trips per hour or vehicle-km"

Domain: SystemState | Scenario | SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Property: hasTransportDemand (xsd:double)
Comment: "Overall transport demand (motorized and non-motorized)"
Domain: SystemState | SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Infrastructure (2 KPIs):

Class: InfrastructureKPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI

Comment: "KPIs 163-164: Infrastructure characteristics and extent (4/5 stakeholders each)"

Property: hasInfrastructureSpatialFeatures (xsd:string)

Comment: "JSON or structured description of infrastructure spatial characteristics (total length, intersections, node distribution)"

Domain: TransportElement | SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:string

Property: hasTotalOperationalRoadLength (xsd:double)
Comment: "Total length of operational roads in kilometers"
Domain: SpatialUnit | TransportElement
Range: xsd:double

Property: hasNetworkDensity (xsd:double)
Comment: "Road network density (km per km²)"
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Urban Development (3 KPIs):

Class: UrbanDevelopmentKPI SubClassOf: CoreKPI

Comment: "KPIs 200, 203-204: Urban density and green space metrics (4/5 stakeholders each)"

Property: hasUrbanDensity (xsd:double)

Comment: "Population or development density in persons per km² or units per hectare"
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Property: hasGreenSpaceArea (xsd:double)
Comment: "Total area of green spaces in hectares or km²"
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Property: hasGreenSpaceAreaPerCapita (xsd:double)
Comment: "Green space area per person in m²/capita"
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

Property: hasPopulation (xsd:integer)
Comment: "Total population in the spatial unit"

Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:integer

KPI Metadata Properties (applicable to all KpiObservations):

Property: hasKPINumber (xsd:integer)
Comment: "Unique identifier (1-209) from KPI catalogue"
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: xsd:integer

Property: hasStakeholderSelectionCount (xsd:integer)
Comment: "Number of stakeholders (0-5) who selected this KPI"
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: xsd:integer

Property: hasKPIGroup (xsd:string)
Comment: "Main KPI group from catalogue (e.g., 'Ecological impacts', 'Transport Modes')"
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: xsd:string

Property: hasKPISubgroup (xsd:string)
Comment: "KPI subgroup classification (e.g., 'Emissions', 'Modal split')"
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: xsd:string

Integration with System State and Scenario Evaluation: The KPI framework is tightly integrated with SystemState and Scenario classes to support: - Baseline assessment: KPIs characterize pre-disruption system state - Impact measurement: KPIs quantify changes during disruptions - Recovery tracking: KPIs monitor post-disruption evolution - Antifragility evaluation: KPIs enable comparison across repeated events to identify antifragile improvements - Cross-city comparison: Core KPIs (Table 8) ensure comparable measurements across all pilot cities - Policy evaluation: KPIs assess effectiveness of governance instruments and response actions - Equity analysis: KPIs track distributional impacts across different actor groups

All KPI observations link to: - Spatial context (via SpatialUnit and locatedIn property) - Temporal context (via TemporalUnit and validDuring property) - Data provenance (via DataSource and hasProvenance property) - Quality metadata (via hasConfidenceLevel, hasTrustScore properties) - Scenario context (via evaluatesIn property)

6.4.10.3 Data Source and Provenance Classes

Class: DataSource SubClassOf: DataProvenance
SubClasses:
- IoTSensor
- TrafficSensor
- GISData
- ModelOutput
- SurveyData

Class: QualityAssessment SubClassOf: DataProvenance
 Property: hasDataQualityScore (xsd:double)
 Property: hasAccuracy (xsd:double)
 Property: hasCompleteness (xsd:double)

Class: UncertaintyEstimate SubClassOf: DataProvenance
 Property: hasUncertaintyValue (xsd:double)
 Property: hasConfidenceLevel (xsd:double)

Each KPI subclass can be further instantiated with specific measurements as shown in Section 8 (pilot city scenarios) and detailed in Appendix B.4 (data properties).

6.4.11 ResponseAction

Class: ResponseAction

SubClassOf:
 { ControlAction, PolicyAction, EmergencyAction,
 BehaviouralNudge, LearningAction }

Class: ControlAction SubClassOf: ResponseAction
 Class: PolicyAction SubClassOf: ResponseAction
 Class: EmergencyAction SubClassOf: ResponseAction
 Class: BehaviouralNudge SubClassOf: ResponseAction
 Class: LearningAction SubClassOf: ResponseAction
 Concrete processes (e.g. ProactiveReroute, EmissionControl, EquityMonitor, RiskAssessment, ScenarioCompare, PolicyUpdate, LongtermLearning) will be subclasses of these categories.

In the OWL snippets, diagrams and tables, external concepts are referred to using their original prefixes (e.g. geo: for GeoSPARQL, sosa: for SOSA/SSN, prov: for PROV-O, time: for OWL-Time, tm: for Transmodel, gtfs: for GTFS), while AntifragiCity-specific concepts use the :AFC namespace. This makes it explicit, within the ontology structure itself, which elements are reused from existing ontologies, and which are newly introduced by AntifragiCity.

6.5 Ontology modules

The ontology is implemented as a set of **interlinked but separable modules**, each corresponding to one or more semantic clusters. Below we describe the modules and their scopes.

6.5.1 Transport network and infrastructure module

Scope: Physical transport network elements, monitoring infrastructure and related assets.

- Core classes: TransportElement, Node, Edge, Corridor, Facility, Vehicle, EvacRoute, CriticalAsset, Microgrid, RoutePlan, SignalPlan, NetworkConfiguration, SensorNetwork, MonitorModule.
- Key relationships:

- connectedTo (Node-Edge-Node),
- partOfCorridor,
- usesRoute (Vehicle-RoutePlan),
- hasSignalPlan (Node/Corridor-SignalPlan),
- monitoredBy (TransportElement-SensorNetwork / MonitorModule).

Core class definitions:

The Transport Network and Infrastructure module includes the following core classes:

TransportElement is the base class for all transport infrastructure components. **Node** represents network junctions or intersections where edges meet. **Edge** represents directed or undirected links between nodes (road/rail segments). **Corridor** represents a collection of edges forming a logical transport route. **Facility** represents fixed locations such as stations, terminals, hospitals or cooling centres. **Vehicle** represents mobile transport assets including public transport vehicles, emergency vehicles and private vehicles. **EvacRoute** is a specialized corridor designated for emergency evacuation. **CriticalAsset** represents infrastructure elements whose failure would have severe cascading consequences. **Microgrid** represents localized energy grids supporting transport infrastructure resilience. **RoutePlan** represents a planned or computed route through the network including waypoints and expected travel times. **SignalPlan** represents traffic signal timing configurations for intersections or corridors. **NetworkConfiguration** represents operational settings including lane allocation, stop spacing and fleet distribution. **SensorNetwork** represents collections of sensors deployed for monitoring traffic flow and infrastructure status. **MonitorModule** represents software/hardware components that process sensor data and update system state.

Key properties and their definitions:

Core properties require explicit definition for consistent interpretation:

hasCapacity (double) represents maximum throughput under normal conditions: for edges, vehicles per hour per lane following Highway Capacity Manual [TRB 2016] methodologies; for facilities, maximum simultaneous users; for vehicles, passenger or cargo capacity. Values are derived from local transport models and GIS attributes (Requirements 1, 9, 18, 39, 55).

hasOperationalStatus (string) uses controlled vocabulary: "Operational" (normal service), "Degraded" (reduced capacity), "Closed" (unavailable), "UnderMaintenance", "UnderConstruction", "Unknown". Values align with traffic management centre classifications and can be mapped to DATEX II taxonomies [CEN 2017]. Status is updated from real-time data feeds or operator inputs (Requirements 9, 30, 40, 46, 51).

hasCriticality (double, 0.0–1.0) quantifies importance to network functionality using multi-criteria analysis: structural importance (betweenness/closeness centrality), functional importance (service coverage, volumes), redundancy (alternative routes), and socio-economic impacts (affected users, essential services access). Methodologies draw on critical infrastructure protection [Johansson & Hassel 2010; Ouyang 2014] and transport resilience [Jenelius et al. 2006; Mattsson & Jenelius 2015]. Initial scores computed during pilot integration (WP3, WP6); updated based on disruption impacts (Requirements 4, 7, 9, 19, 40, 51, 52).

The module's classes include properties that require explicit definition to ensure consistent interpretation across pilot cities. **Table 2** provides definitions, data types, and references for core properties.

Class	Property	Type	Definition	Values/Range	Ref.
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TransportElement	hasCapacity	double	Maximum throughput under normal conditions	Context-dependent: Edges: vehicles/hour/lane; Facilities: max users; Vehicles: passengers	(42)
	hasOperationalStatus	string	Current operational state	"Operational", "Degraded", "Closed", "UnderMaintenance", "UnderConstruction", "Unknown"	(43)
	hasCriticality	double	Network importance (multi-criteria)	0.0–1.0 (0=low, 1=critical)	(44)
Node	hasCoordinates	Point	Geospatial location	WGS84 decimal degrees or projected coordinates	(45)
	hasNodeType	string	Functional classification	"Intersection", "Terminal", "Junction", "AccessPoint"	Local data
Edge	hasLength	double	Physical length	Meters	(46)
	hasSpeedLimit	double	Regulatory speed limit	km/h or mph	Local regulations
	hasLanes	int	Number of traffic lanes	Positive integer (1-8 typical range)	Local data
Corridor	hasDirection	String	Primary travel direction	"Northbound", "Southbound", "Eastbound", "Westbound", "Bidirectional"	Local data
	hasPriority	int	Routing/control priority	1-10 (1=lowest, 10=highest)	Local data
Facility	hasFacilityType	string	Facility functional type	"Station", "Terminal", "Parking", "Hospital", "CoolingCentre"	Local data
Vehicle	hasVehicleType	string	Vehicle classification	"Bus", "Tram", "Car", "Truck", "Bicycle", "Ambulance"	Local data
	hasEmissionClasses	string	Emission standard classification	"Euro 6", "Electric", "Hybrid", "Diesel", "Petrol"	(47)
EvacRoute	hasEvacPriority	int	Evacuation route priority	1-5 (1=primary, 5=tertiary)	Local data
CriticalAsset	hasCriticalityRanking	int	Asset criticality tier	1-5 (1=most critical)	(48)

	hasDependencies	string	Dependent infrastructure identifiers	Comma-separated URIs or IDs	Local data
Microgrid	hasPowerCapacity	double	Maximum power output	kW or MW	Local data
	hasIslandingCapability	boolean	Can operate independently from main grid	true/false	Local data
NetworkConfiguration	hasLaneAllocation	string	Lane assignment strategy	"Static", "Dynamic", "ReversibleLanes", "BusPriority"	(42)
	hasStopSpacing	double	Average distance between stops	Meters	(42)
	hasFleetDistribution	string	Vehicle deployment pattern	"Uniform", "PeakWeighted", "Demand-responsive"	Local data

Table 2. Property Definitions for Transport Network Module

Property definitions draw on transport engineering standards (Highway Capacity Manual (42), DATEX II (43)), geospatial standards (GeoSPARQL (45), ISO Geographic Information Standards (46)), critical infrastructure methodologies (44,48), and emission standards (47). Properties without formal standard references are derived from local data sources including GIS attributes, traffic management systems, facility specifications, and pilot city transport models. Where controlled

vocabularies are specified, pilot implementations may extend these with city-specific values while maintaining interoperability through ontology alignment mechanisms (Section 6.7).

Figure 6. Transport & Network Module (Primary Infrastructure Elements)

Figure 6, illustrates the core physical transport network classes including topology elements (Node, Edge, Corridor), assets (Facility, Vehicle), specialized infrastructure (EvacRoute, CriticalAsset, Microgrid) and operational configurations (NetworkConfiguration), along with their main relationships (connectivity, monitoring, asset structure). Additional module classes for routing and planning (RoutePlan, SignalPlan) and monitoring infrastructure (SensorNetwork, MonitorModule) are not shown for visual clarity but are defined in the class and property definitions above. This module is intended to align with transport network standards and can be imported independently by tools that only need physical infrastructure semantics.

6.5.2 Mobility demand and services module

Scope: Modes, services, user preferences and choice behaviour.

- Core classes: MobilityService, Mode, ActiveMode, PublicTransportMovement, ChoiceModel, PredMaintModel, PredModel, SimModel, ForecastModel, ScenarioSystem.

- Additional concepts: UserPreference, ModeChoice, RouteChoice, TripNecessity, MobilityCondition.
- Key relationships:
 - offersService (Actor → MobilityService),
 - usesMode (Actor → Mode),
 - hasChoiceModel (MobilityService → ChoiceModel).

KPIs and performance metrics:

The module captures mobility demand and service performance indicators identified in WP2 Task 2.7, which developed a catalogue of 209 KPIs organized into 7 main groups and 20 subgroups (Table 7) following systematic review of literature and practice. Key KPI dimensions include **modal split** (proportion of transport modes), **travel times and delays** (commute times, waiting times), **travel demand** (motorized/non-motorized/public transport), **transport service characteristics** (frequency, ridership, speed), **accessibility indices** (spatial/temporal access to destinations), **public perception and satisfaction**, and **transport costs and affordability**. These KPIs are represented through dedicated classes and properties: MobilityService, Mode and Actor classes (e.g., hasModalSplit, hasTravelTime, hasRidership, hasAccessibilityIndex), linked to Observation instances via the SOSA/SSN framework, enabling quantitative scenario evaluation and antifragility assessment (Requirements 14, 40, 52, 60).

6.5.3 Disruption and hazard events module

Scope: Representation of disruptions, hazards and their propagation.

This module is explicitly aligned with the Urban Event Catalogue and event taxonomy developed in D2.1 (Domain × Scale, Severity, Impact). Each instance of :DisruptionEvent is intended to correspond either to an event type or an event instance in the D2.1 catalogue. The ontology reuses the catalogue attributes as properties, :hasDomain, :hasScale, :hasSeverityLevel, :hasImpactType, and connects them to the core classes :DisruptionEvent, :HazardType, :EmergencyType and :Cascade. At the upper-ontology level, these dimensions are connected via the abstract Event/TriggeringEvent/DisruptionEvent hooks so that D2.1 typing remains queryable consistently across all datasets. This ensures that disruption analyses carried out in D2.1 can be represented consistently in the AntifragiCity knowledge graph and reused in subsequent antifragility assessments.

Concretely, the Disruption & Risk module:

- reuses D2.1 “Domain” categories (e.g. transport, energy, health, social unrest) as individuals or subclasses of :DisruptionDomain;
- reuses D2.1 “Scale” categories (e.g. local, city-wide, regional, national) as individuals or subclasses of :EventScale;
- reuses the severity and impact categories from D2.1 as instances of :SeverityLevel and :ImpactType; Impact types are intended to cover both adverse effects (loss/damage) and positive effects (capability gains or improved performance), so that antifragility outcomes can be represented consistently across scenarios.
- links each :DisruptionEvent to its domain, scale, severity and impact via :hasDomain, :hasScale, :hasSeverityLevel and :hasImpactType.
- **Core classes:** DisruptionEvent, Disruption, DemandSupplyShock, Cascade, Outage, CyberAttack, Crisis, UnexpectedEvent, HazardType, EmergencyType.

- **Supporting concepts:** qualitative scales (SeverityScale, ImpactScale, QualCategory) and calibration (ScaleCalibration).
- **Key relationships:**
 - affects (DisruptionEvent → TransportElement / Actor / SystemState),
 - propagatesTo (DisruptionEvent → DisruptionEvent),
 - hasSeverity, hasImpactScale, hasMagnitude.

Figure 7. Disruption & Risk Module

Figure 7 visually anchors the event typing and propagation/cascade structure you describe textually. Note: The specialisations of :DisruptionEvent, :HazardType and :EmergencyType in this module reuse the domains, scales, severity levels and impact categories from the D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue, ensuring consistency between the ontology and the event mapping work.

6.5.4 System state, KPIs, antifragility metrics and equilibrium states module

The KPI framework integrates three complementary KPI sets validated through Task T2.7: (i) D2.3 Core Antifragility KPIs (12 metrics for equilibrium analysis), (ii) Task 2.7 Extended KPI Catalogue (209 KPIs from **Table 7** organized into 7 groups and 20 subgroups), and (iii) Task 2.7 Core KPI Subset (13 stakeholder-prioritised KPIs from **Table 8**, selected from the extended catalogue by ≥4 stakeholders, ETH, Cardiff, DEMO, AUTH, Bratislava, and Odessa, for cross-city comparability). The collected survey responses from cities and practitioners validate KPI relevance and prioritise candidate KPIs. As the survey is an evolving input, the KPI set is treated as validated-but-updateable. To support KPI harmonisation across scenarios and datasets, each KPI is specified with an explicit definition and, where applicable, an associated dimension and unit (and target when relevant), aligned with the project ontology. The catalogue contains candidate KPIs grouped by domain and sub-domain, with definitions and survey-based prioritisation. For reporting and platform integration, the distinction between core KPI subset (**Table 8** essential for cross-city comparison) and extended KPI set (**Table 7** available for city-specific analysis and future refinement) is

maintained through class hierarchies and metadata properties. The ontology supports both through the same observation pattern and naming conventions.

Scope: Performance, resilience, antifragility and equilibrium concepts.

- **Core classes:** SystemState, CongestionState, EvacCongestionState, EnvTargetState, PredictedDisruptionState, OverloadState, AdaptiveTransformativeState, EquilibriumState, DesiredEquilibriumState, UndesiredEquilibriumState, AntifragileState, CalibrationState, StressPerformance.
- **KPI-related concepts:** KpiObservation, CoreKPI (Table 8 subset), AntifragilityScore, ResilienceIndex, FragilityMetric, VulnerabilityIndicator, AdaptiveCapacityIndicator, PerformanceIndicator, AccessibilityIndicator, TravelTimeIndicator, EnvironmentalKPI, EconomicKPI, EquityKPI, SafetyIndicator, SatisfactionIndicator, DemandIndicator, InfrastructureIndicator.
- **Task 2.7 Core KPI Classes (Table 8 - 13 KPIs):**
 - **Ecological Impacts:** CO2KPI (KPI 21), PollutantEmissionsKPI (KPI 22), NoisePollutionKPI (KPI 31).
 - **Transport Modes:** ModalSplitKPI (KPIs 38-40), TravelTimeKPI (KPI 47), TransportDemandKPI (KPI 68).
 - **Infrastructure:** InfrastructureKPI (KPIs 163-164).
 - **Urban Development:** UrbanDevelopmentKPI (KPIs 200, 203-204).
- **Core KPI Properties (Table 8 - specific to 13 core KPIs):** hasCO2Emissions, hasPollutantEmissions, hasNoisePollution, hasModalSplit, hasPersonalTravelModeSplit, hasFreightModeSplit, hasTravelTime, hasAverageTravelTime, hasMotorizedTransportDemand, hasTransportDemand, hasInfrastructureSpatialFeatures, hasTotalOperationalRoadLength, hasNetworkDensity, hasUrbanDensity, hasGreenSpaceArea, hasGreenSpaceAreaPerCapita, hasPopulation.
- **Broader KPI properties (Table 7 - extended catalogue):**
 - **Mobility demand and services:** hasRidership, hasSatisfactionScore, hasTravelCost, hasAccessibilityIndex, hasServiceFrequency, hasDelayTime, hasWaitingTime, hasPassengerKilometers.
 - **Environment and PESTEL:** hasEmissionLevel (general emissions including CO₂, GHG, NO_x, PM), hasEnergyConsumption, hasNoiseLevel, hasEcologicalImpact, hasEconomicIndicator, hasSocialVulnerability.
- **KPI Metadata Properties:** hasKPINumber (unique identifier 1-209 from catalogue), hasStakeholderSelectionCount (0-6 stakeholders), hasKPIGroup (e.g., 'Ecological impacts', 'Transport Modes'), hasKPISubgroup (e.g., 'Emissions', 'Modal split').
- **Antifragility and equilibrium properties:** hasAntifragilityScore, hasAntifragilityFactor, hasResilienceIndex, hasSystemResponsivenessIndex, hasVulnerabilityIndex, hasAdaptiveCapacity, hasFragilityMetric, hasPerformanceTs, hasPerformanceDelta, hasEquilibriumGap.
- **Key relationships:**
 - hasKpiObservation (SystemState → KpiObservation)
 - hasAntifragilityScore, hasResilienceIndex, hasFragilityMetric
 - previousState / nextState (temporal ordering)
 - equilibriumOf (SystemState → Scenario or system configuration)

Figure 8. System State & Antifragility Module

Figure 8 shows the state-KPI-metric structure and how it supports both D2.3 equilibrium/antifragility analysis and T2.7 KPI-based performance monitoring. The module

integrates three complementary KPI frameworks: (i) D2.3 Core Antifragility KPIs (12 metrics for equilibrium analysis), (ii) T2.7 Extended KPI Catalogue (209 indicators across 7 groups), and (iii) T2.7 Core KPI Subset (13 stakeholder-prioritised KPIs represented via CoreKPI class, including CO₂ emissions, modal split, travel time, noise pollution, urban density and infrastructure metrics).

Equilibrium configurations defined in D2.3 are represented as instances of EquilibriumState and its subclasses (DesiredEquilibriumState, UndesiredEquilibriumState), linked to SystemState trajectories via KpiObservation instances. Basin-of-attraction concepts are captured through equilibrium state classifications and stability properties rather than requiring additional dedicated classes. The notion of "distance to equilibrium" used in D2.3 equilibrium analysis is expressed as datatype properties attached to SystemState (e.g., hasEquilibriumGap, hasRecoveryTime, hasAntifragilityScore, hasFragilityMetric), allowing equilibrium analysis results to be stored, queried and compared across scenarios in the knowledge graph.

The module captures operational states (CongestionState, OverloadState), predictive states (PredictedDisruptionState, EnvTargetState), resilience states (ResilienceState, AntifragileState, AdaptiveTransformativeState), and calibration states for digital twin synchronisation. Key relationships include temporal ordering (previousState/nextState), scenario evaluation (evaluatedIn), KPI monitoring (hasKpiObservation linking to both D2.3 antifragility metrics and T2.7 performance indicators), and state transitions triggered by DisruptionEvent and ResponseAction instances. This semantic layer enables systematic tracking of system evolution, performance degradation and recovery, antifragile improvements, and equilibrium dynamics across baseline and disruptive scenarios.

6.5.5 Environment, climate and PESTEL context module

Scope: Environmental and macro-contextual factors.

- **Core classes:** EnvironmentFactor, ClimateStressor, ClimateProjection, PestelFactor.
- **Properties:**
 - **Emissions and pollution:** hasEmissionLevel (CO₂, GHG, NO_x, particulate matter), hasPollutantEmissions, hasCO2Emissions, hasNoiseLevel, hasNoisePollution.
 - **Energy and resource use:** hasEnergyConsumption, hasEnergyUse, hasFuelUse, hasRenewableEnergyUtilization.
 - **Ecological impacts:** hasEcologicalImpact, hasEcologicalFootprint, hasHabitatPreservation, hasPopulationExposure.
 - **Urban environment:** hasUrbanDensity, hasGreenSpaceArea, hasGreenSpaceAreaPerCapita, hasPopulation.
 - **PESTEL indicators:** hasEconomicIndicator, hasSocialVulnerability, hasPoliticalFactor, hasTechnologicalFactor, hasEnvironmentalFactor, hasLegalFactor.
 - **Sustainability:** hasSustainableChoice, hasEnvironmentalImpact.
- **Key relationships:**
 - contextFor (EnvironmentFactor → Scenario / SystemState / TransportElement)
 - drives (EnvironmentFactor → DisruptionEvent or long-term change).

KPIs and contextual indicators:

The module captures environmental and macro-contextual indicators identified in WP2 Task 2.7, integrating **three core environmental KPIs from Table 8:** CO₂ emissions (**KPI 21, highest priority, selected by 5 stakeholders**), pollutant emissions from transport (**KPI 22**), and noise pollution (**KPI 31**), alongside **urban development indicators:** urban density (**KPI 200**), green

space area (**KPI 203**), and green space area per capita (**KPI 204**). Following the same systematic review process that produced 198 indicator groups, T2.7 identified indicators across three key environmental dimensions: (i) emissions metrics including greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O), pollutant emissions (NO_x, particulate matter, VOCs), and emission intensities per passenger-kilometer or ton-kilometer; (ii) energy consumption indicators covering total transport energy use, renewable energy utilization, energy efficiency metrics, and fossil fuel consumption across transport modes; and (iii) ecological impact measures including noise pollution levels, population exposure to noise and pollutants, ecological footprint, water pollution indices, and habitat/biodiversity preservation. Additionally, T2.7 incorporated macro-contextual indicators relevant to the PESTEL framework: economic factors (transport costs, economic growth impacts, infrastructure investment), social factors (quality of life, population satisfaction with environmental conditions, social equity in environmental exposure), and technological factors (adoption of sustainable technologies, renewable energy sources). These indicators are represented as properties of EnvironmentFactor, ClimateStressor and PestelFactor classes (e.g., hasEmissionLevel, hasEnergyConsumption, hasNoiseLevel, hasEcologicalImpact, hasEconomicIndicator, hasSocialVulnerability), linked to Observation instances for time-series monitoring and Scenario instances for contextual framing. Climate projection data (temperature, precipitation, extreme events) from sources such as IPCC scenarios are captured through ClimateProjection class instances, supporting long-term climate-transport interaction modeling. The ontology enables environmental and contextual factors to be associated with specific transport elements, system states and disruption events through contextFor and drives relationships, supporting scenario-based assessment of climate adaptation and macro-environmental resilience strategies (Requirements 19, 23, 24, 52, 59).

6.5.6 Actors, governance, policies and equity module

Scope: Stakeholders, institutions, policies, equity groups, vulnerable populations, and governance configurations.

- **Actor classes:** EquityGroup, VulnerableGroup, CitizenSegment, UserGroup, UserProfile, Stakeholder, StakeholderGroup, Organisation, Agency, CitySource, CityTarget, Incentive.
- **Equity and social properties:**
 - **Access and vulnerability:** hasServiceAccess, hasAccessibilityIndex, hasAccessRights, hasRiskExposure, hasSocialVulnerability, hasExposureLevel.
 - **Economic equity:** hasCostPerGroup, hasBenefitDistribution, hasEconomicImpact, hasGDPEffect.
 - **User characteristics:** hasUserPreference, hasMobilityCondition, hasSatisfactionScore.
 - **Social indicators:** hasQualityOfLife, hasPopulationSatisfaction, hasSocialEquity.
- **GovernanceInstrument classes:** Regulation, LegalConstraint, LegalScenario, Legislation, Organisation, Agency, Protocol, SecurityProtocol, DataSharingAgreement, Platform, CoordinationSystem, EventManagementSystem, CrisisManagementCentre, Sitrep.
- **Governance and policy properties:** hasLegalBasis, hasComplianceStatus, hasRole, hasAuthorityLevel, hasPolicyEffect, hasInstitutionalFragmentation, hasGovernanceSplit.
- **Processes:**
 - **Coordination:** Coordination, MultiagencyCoord, CrossAuthorityCoord, InfoSharing, EventLifecycle, CommandControl, CrisisCoordination, EmergencyCoord.
 - **Stakeholder engagement:** ParticipatoryInput, StakeholderEngagement, StakeholderInput, ConsultationEvent.

- **Policy and planning:** PolicyUpdate, RequirementRefinement, ConflictResolution, RegulatoryAnalysis, AdaptationPlanning.
- **Equity monitoring:** EquityMonitor, EquityAlert, InclusiveIntervention.
- **Key relationships:**
 - governedBy (Actor/TransportElement/MobilityService → GovernanceInstrument),
 - memberOf (Actor → Organisation/Agency),
 - participatesIn (Actor → Coordination or ConsultationEvent),
 - subjectTo (Actor or SpatialUnit → LegalConstraint).
 - appliesTo (Regulation → SpatialUnit or TransportElement)
 - hasRole (Actor → Role or responsibility specification)
 - affectsEquity (GovernanceInstrument or ResponseAction → EquityGroup)

Equity and governance integration:

This module supports equity-aware decision-making and multi-stakeholder coordination by capturing vulnerable populations, equity groups, and their differential access to mobility services. Equity considerations are integrated with T2.7 KPI framework through social vulnerability indicators and accessibility metrics. The module represents institutional actors (agencies, organisations, stakeholders) and governance structures (regulations, protocols, legal constraints, data sharing agreements) that shape mobility system operations. Multi-level governance is supported through authority hierarchies and cross-authority coordination processes. The PESTEL framework integration enables representation of political factors (governance levels, policy instruments), social factors (equity groups, social vulnerability, quality of life indicators), economic factors (cost distribution, economic impacts on different groups), and legal factors (regulations, legal constraints, compliance requirements). Participatory processes and stakeholder engagement mechanisms support co-design and collaborative decision-making across diverse stakeholder groups. The affectsEquity relationship enables tracking how policies, interventions and disruptions differentially impact vulnerable populations, supporting Requirements 6, 13, 29, 31, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 56 related to equity, governance, stakeholder coordination and multi-authority contexts.

Figure 9. Actor, Equity & Social Module

Figure 9 shows the actor hierarchy capturing human and organizational participants in the mobility system, with explicit representation of equity groups and vulnerable populations to support inclusive decision-making. The hierarchy distinguishes institutional actors (InstitutionalActor with Organisation and Agency subclasses representing governmental and organizational entities with jurisdictional authority), collective user groups (UserGroup encompassing EquityGroup for populations facing social vulnerability and differential service access, VulnerableGroup for at-risk populations with heightened exposure levels, and CitizenSegment for demographically-defined population categories), stakeholder representatives (Stakeholder for individual stakeholders and StakeholderGroup for organized stakeholder coalitions), and individual user characteristics (UserProfile capturing mobility preferences, satisfaction scores, and behavioral patterns). EquityGroup properties include social vulnerability indicators (hasSocialVulnerability, hasRiskExposure), access metrics (hasServiceAccess, hasAccessibilityIndex), and economic equity measures (hasCostPerGroup, hasBenefitDistribution), enabling systematic tracking of differential impacts across population groups. Key relationships include locatedIn linking actors to spatial units for geographic analysis, memberOf representing organizational hierarchies, governedBy and subjectTo showing compliance with governance instruments and legal constraints, affectedBy linking equity groups to disruption events, participatesIn enabling stakeholder engagement in governance processes, and affectsEquity (from ResponseAction module) tracking how interventions differentially impact vulnerable populations. This comprehensive actor representation underpins Requirements 6, 13, 29, 31, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 56 related to equity, vulnerable populations, stakeholder coordination, user needs, participatory processes, and inclusive mobility system design.

Figure 10. Governance & Policy Module

Figure 10 shows the governance instrument class hierarchy capturing institutional structures, legal frameworks, and coordination mechanisms that shape mobility system operations. The hierarchy includes legal and regulatory instruments (Regulation with legal basis and enforcement mechanisms, LegalConstraint specifying mandatory requirements, LegalScenario representing regulatory contexts, Legislation capturing legislative acts), operational protocols (Protocol for standard operating procedures with SecurityProtocol subclass for cybersecurity measures, DataSharingAgreement governing data exchange with privacy safeguards), organizational actors (Organisation and Agency representing institutional entities with jurisdictional authority), and coordination infrastructure (Platform for collaboration, CoordinationSystem for inter-agency coordination, EventManagementSystem and CrisisManagementCentre for emergency response, Sitrep for situation reporting). Key relationships include governedBy linking actors, transport elements, and mobility services to applicable governance instruments, subjectTo indicating legal compliance obligations, appliesTo showing spatial jurisdiction over geographic areas and infrastructure, and constrains showing how regulations limit permissible response actions. This comprehensive governance structure supports multi-level coordination, legal compliance, stakeholder participation, and split-governance contexts, underpinning Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32, 33, 34, 44, 48, 49, 56 related to governance, legislation, institutional settings, and multi-authority contexts.

6.5.7 Spatial and temporal context module

Scope: Spatial units, geographical boundaries, vulnerable areas, temporal constructs, and spatio-temporal relationships.

- **SpatialUnit classes:** SpatialUnit (abstract), Boundary, SpatialConstraint, NoGoArea, VulnerableArea, GeoLayer, GeoLimitation, ProtectedArea, EvacuationZone.
- **TemporalUnit classes:** TemporalUnit (abstract), TimeInstant, TimeInterval, TimePeriod, Duration, TimeHorizon, EvaluationPeriod, PeakPeriod, Timestamp.
- **Spatial properties:**
 - **Location and geometry:** hasCoordinates, hasSpatialExtent, hasGeometry, hasArea, hasPerimeter
 - **Spatial characteristics:** hasTerrainType, hasSpatialConstraint, hasElevation, hasUrbanDensity, hasPopulation
 - **Infrastructure spatial features:** hasInfrastructureSpatialFeatures, hasTotalOperationalRoadLength, hasNetworkDensity, hasRoadLength
 - **Environment:** hasGreenSpaceArea, hasGreenSpaceAreaPerCapita
 - **Vulnerability:** hasExposureLevel, hasServiceAccess, hasSocialVulnerability
- **Temporal properties:**
 - Time points and ranges: hasTimestamp, hasStartTime, hasEndTime, hasSourceTimestamp, hasValidFrom, hasValidUntil
 - Durations: hasTravelTime, hasResponseTime, hasLeadTime, hasLagTime, hasRecoveryTime, hasDelayTime, hasWaitingTime, hasDuration
 - Periods: hasTimeHorizon, hasEvalPeriod, hasPeakPeriod, hasTemporalExtent
 - Temporal dependencies: hasTemporalDependency, hasSpatialAutocorrelation, hasTemporalAutocorrelation
- **Spatial relationships:**
 - locatedIn (TransportElement / Actor / DisruptionEvent / Facility → SpatialUnit)
 - within (SpatialUnit → SpatialUnit) - spatial containment hierarchy

- overlaps (SpatialUnit ↔ SpatialUnit) - spatial intersection
- adjacent (SpatialUnit ↔ SpatialUnit) - spatial adjacency
- appliesTo (GovernanceInstrument / Regulation → SpatialUnit) - spatial jurisdiction
- affectsSpatialUnit (DisruptionEvent → SpatialUnit) - spatial impact
- **Temporal relationships:**
 - validDuring (Scenario / ResponseAction / SystemState / Observation → TemporalUnit)
 - occursAt (DisruptionEvent / ResponseAction → TimeInstant)
 - hasTemporalExtent (Scenario / DisruptionEvent → TimeInterval)
 - precedes (Event → Event) - temporal ordering
 - follows (Event → Event) - temporal succession
 - overlapsTemporally (Event ↔ Event) - temporal overlap
- **Key relationships:**
 - locatedIn (TransportElement / Actor / DisruptionEvent → SpatialUnit),
 - within (SpatialUnit → SpatialUnit),
 - validDuring (Scenario / ResponseAction / SystemState → TemporalUnit).

Spatial and temporal integration:

This module provides the foundational spatial and temporal context for all ontology elements, enabling geographic analysis, temporal tracking, and spatio-temporal reasoning. Spatial units range from city-wide boundaries to neighbourhood-level vulnerable areas, supporting the representation of equity-relevant geographic zones and infrastructure networks. The module integrates T2.7 spatial KPIs including infrastructure spatial features (KPI 163) and total operational road length (KPI 164), represented through properties such as `hasInfrastructureSpatialFeatures`, `hasTotalOperationalRoadLength`, and `hasNetworkDensity`. Urban development indicators including urban density (KPI 200), green space area (KPI 203), and green space area per capita (KPI 204) are captured as spatial properties enabling environmental and quality-of-life assessments. Vulnerable areas can be identified through combinations of spatial properties (`hasExposureLevel`, `hasServiceAccess`, `hasSocialVulnerability`), supporting equity-aware planning and intervention prioritization.

Temporal units support both point-in-time observations (`TimeInstant`, `Timestamp`) and duration-based analysis (`TimeInterval`, `TimePeriod`, `Duration`), enabling the tracking of system evolution, disruption lifecycles, and response timing. Temporal properties capture critical timing metrics including travel times, response times, lead times for early warning, and recovery times for resilience assessment. The module supports temporal reasoning through relationships such as `precedes`, `follows`, and `overlapsTemporally`, enabling causal analysis and event sequencing. Spatio-temporal dependencies (`hasTemporalDependency`, `hasSpatialAutocorrelation`) capture how system behaviour varies across space and time, essential for understanding cascading effects and system dynamics.

The `locatedIn` and `validDuring` relationships provide the primary mechanism for anchoring all ontology elements in geographic and temporal context, enabling spatial queries (e.g., "which transport elements are located in vulnerable areas?") and temporal queries (e.g., "which scenarios are valid during peak periods?"). The `within` relationship supports hierarchical spatial reasoning (neighbourhood within district within city), while temporal relationships enable event sequencing and scenario timeline construction. This foundational module underpins Requirements 2, 8, 28, 44, 59, 60 related to geographical limitations, spatial-temporal dependencies, and environmental constraints.

6.5.8 Data, provenance and uncertainty module

Scope: Observations, data sources, sensors, provenance, quality, trust, fusion, uncertainty, and AI/ML model outputs.

- **Observation classes:** Observation (abstract), TrafficObservation, EmissionObservation, EquityObservation, EconomicObservation, KpiObservation, CoreKPI, DataQualityObservation, FusionObservation, ClimateObservation, SafetyObservation.
- **Sensor and monitoring classes:** TrafficSensor, SensorNetwork, IoTDevice, AnalyticsEngine, ForecastModel, DigitalTwin.
- **Data source and dataset classes:** DataSource, Provenance, MultimodalData, TrafficDataset, PTData, ActiveMobilityData, EconomicData, PersonalData, Graph (network representation).
- **Knowledge and interface classes:** LearningRepository, BestPractice, Dashboard, UserInterface.
- **Observation and data quality properties:**
 - **Data quality:** hasDataQuality, hasCompleteness, hasAccuracy, hasTrustScore, hasConfidence, hasUncertainty, hasConfidenceInterval
 - **Observation metadata:** hasValue, hasTimestamp, hasSourceTimestamp, hasDataLineage
 - **KPI metadata:** hasKPINumber, hasKPIGroup, hasKPISubgroup, hasStakeholderSelectionCount, hasTarget, hasCurrentValue
 - **Performance:** hasLatency, hasUpdateFreq, hasThroughput, hasResponseTime
 - **Predictions:** hasPredError, hasForecastUncertainty, hasPrediction
 - **Privacy and security:** hasPrivacyRisk, hasEncryptionStatus, hasAccessControl, hasPIIStatus, hasAnonymisationLevel
 - **Economic metrics:** hasEconomicImpact, hasGDPEffect
 - **Compliance:** hasComplianceStatus, hasGDPRCompliance, hasLegalBasis
 - **Interface:** hasUIComponent, hasUsability, hasConfigurability, hasMultiDevice
- **Processes:** Calibration, Audit, Fusion, TempAlignment, DataIntegration, AnomalyDetect, EquityMonitor, KpiAlert, ProvenanceTracking, RealtimeMonitoring, StreamAnalytics, TwinSync.
- **Key relationships:**
 - observedOn (Observation → TransportElement / Actor / Scenario / SystemState)
 - observedBy (TransportElement / SystemState → Observation)
 - generatedBy (Observation → DataSource / AnalyticsEngine / Sensor)
 - hasObservation (SystemState / TransportElement → Observation)
 - hasKpiObservation (SystemState → KpiObservation)
 - hasProvenance (Observation / Dataset → Provenance)
 - derivedFrom (Observation → DataSource or other Observation)
 - hasTrustScore, hasConfidence, hasDataQuality (Observation → quality metrics)
 - calibrates (CalibrationState → DigitalTwin)
 - monitors (SensorNetwork → TransportElement)

Figure 11. Observation, KPIs & Data Provenance Module

Figure 11 shows the observation and data infrastructure supporting trustworthy, data-driven decision support. The observation hierarchy (a) includes sensor measurements (SensorObservation, TrafficObservation), environmental monitoring (EmissionObservation for KPIs 21, 22, 31), equity tracking (EquityObservation), economic assessment (EconomicObservation), KPI time-series (KpiObservation with CoreKPI subclass representing 13 T2.7 stakeholder-prioritised indicators from Table 8), data quality assessment (DataQualityObservation), and multi-source fusion (FusionObservation). CoreKPI metadata properties include KPI number, group, subgroup, and

stakeholder selection count. The data infrastructure (b) includes sensors and sensor networks for physical monitoring, analytics engines for real-time processing, forecast models with uncertainty quantification, and digital twins for scenario simulation. Provenance tracking maintains data lineage and trust scores for compliance verification. Key relationships link observations to system states (observes, hasKpiObservation), connect observations to data sources (generatedBy), maintain audit trails (hasProvenance), enable digital twin calibration (calibrates), and track sensor coverage (monitors). This infrastructure enables evidence-based decision-making with appropriate uncertainty quantification, supporting Requirements 18, 30, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 46, 50, 52, 55, 57, 59, 61.

Data provenance and quality integration:

This module provides the semantic infrastructure for data-driven decision support, AI/ML integration, and trustworthy information management across the antifragile mobility system. The observation pattern serves as the foundation for capturing time-series measurements, sensor readings, KPI values, and model predictions with associated metadata for provenance, quality, and uncertainty quantification.

The module integrates the T2.7 KPI framework through a hierarchical observation structure: the abstract Observation class provides common properties (timestamp, value, data quality, provenance), KpiObservation extends this with KPI-specific metadata (hasKPINumber, hasKPIGroup, hasKPISubgroup, hasStakeholderSelectionCount), and CoreKPI represents the 13 stakeholder-prioritised indicators from Table 8 (CO₂ emissions, pollutant emissions, noise pollution, modal split, travel time, motorized demand, infrastructure features, road length, urban density, green space). This structure enables both detailed monitoring of individual KPI time-series and aggregated cross-KPI analysis for scenario evaluation and system state assessment.

Sensor infrastructure is captured through TrafficSensor, SensorNetwork, and IoTDevice classes, representing the physical monitoring layer that generates TrafficObservation, EmissionObservation, and other real-time measurements. AnalyticsEngine and ForecastModel classes represent computational components that process raw sensor data and generate derived observations with associated prediction errors and forecast uncertainties (hasPredError, hasForecastUncertainty). DigitalTwin instances integrate multiple data streams and models, supporting "what-if" scenario analysis and continuous learning from system observations through the TwinSync process.

Data provenance tracking through the Provenance class and hasProvenance relationship enables tracing of data lineage (hasDataLineage), supporting audit trails (Audit process), trust assessment (hasTrustScore), and compliance verification (hasComplianceStatus, hasGDPRCompliance). Multimodal data integration is supported through MultimodalData, TrafficDataset, PTData, ActiveMobilityData, and EconomicData classes, with the Fusion and DataIntegration processes combining heterogeneous sources. Data quality assessment encompasses completeness (hasCompleteness), accuracy (hasAccuracy), confidence (hasConfidence), and uncertainty quantification (hasUncertainty, hasConfidenceInterval), enabling evidence-based decision-making with appropriate epistemic humility.

Privacy and security considerations are addressed through properties such as hasPrivacyRisk, hasEncryptionStatus, hasAccessControl, hasPIIStatus, and hasAnonymisationLevel, ensuring GDPR compliance and protecting personal data (PersonalData class). The LearningRepository and BestPractice classes support organizational learning from past observations and cross-city knowledge transfer, while Dashboard and UserInterface classes enable human-interpretable visualization of observations, KPIs, and quality metrics. Real-time monitoring capabilities (RealtimeMonitoring, StreamAnalytics processes) support dynamic system state tracking and anomaly detection (AnomalyDetect process), with equity monitoring (EquityMonitor process) and

KPI alerts (KpiAlert process) enabling proactive intervention when vulnerable populations are at risk or performance targets are not met.

This comprehensive data infrastructure underpins Requirements 18, 30, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 46, 50, 52, 55, 57, 59, 61 related to data quality, provenance, analytics, uncertainty, trust, real-time monitoring, and decision support integration.

6.5.9 Response actions, interventions and learning module

Scope: Control actions, emergency responses, policy interventions, coordination mechanisms, behavioural nudges, and learning processes.

- **ResponseAction subclasses:**
 - **Control and operational actions:** AntifragileControl, AdaptiveControl, ModeShift, ModeChoice, RouteChoice, EmissionControl, EnergyOptimization, ProactiveReroute, Reroute, PriorityRouting, FleetAlloc, ResourceAlloc, DynamicAdjust, SignalControl, NetworkOptimization, EvolutionaryOpt, MicrogridReconfig, PredictiveMaintenance, MaintSched.
 - **Emergency and crisis actions:** EvacuationManagement, EvacuationPlan, EmergencyResponse, Triage, ResourceAlloc, PriorityAllocation, EmergencyPrioritisation, Alerting, ResponseStrategy.
 - **Policy and governance actions:** PolicyUpdate, RegulationChange, LegalScenarioActivation, RegulatoryAnalysis, AdaptationPlanning, ClimateAdaptation.
 - **Coordination and communication actions:** MultiagencyCoord, CrisisCoordination, CommandControl, EmergencyCoord, CrossAuthorityCoord, InfoSharing, EventLifecycle, Coordination, StakeholderInput, StakeholderEngagement.
 - **Behavioural interventions:** Nudge, BehaviouralIntervention, InclusiveIntervention, Feedback, IncentiveDesign, ModeShift (behavioural).
 - **Monitoring and assessment actions:** OutcomeMonitoring, PerformanceMonitoring, EquityMonitor, EquityAlert, ImpactEval, RiskAssessment, CausalEval, MultiScenarioEval, MCEval.
 - **Learning processes:** InterventionLearning, LongtermLearning, StructuralChange, AgentLearning, IncidentLearning, SystemicLearning, ScenarioCompare, TransferAssess, KnowledgeTransfer, Feedback.
- **ResponseAction properties:**
 - **Learning processes:** InterventionLearning, LongtermLearning, StructuralChange, AgentLearning, IncidentLearning, SystemicLearning, ScenarioCompare, TransferAssess, KnowledgeTransfer, Feedback.
 - **Effectiveness and outcomes:** hasEffect, hasOutcome, hasInterventionEffect, hasMeasureEffect, hasImpactLevel, hasCausalityStrength
 - **Priority and urgency:** hasPriority, hasEvacPriority, hasUrgencyLevel, hasResponseTime
 - **Targeting:** hasTargetArea, hasTargetPopulation, hasTargetKPI
 - **Implementation:** hasImplementationStatus, hasCompletionRate, hasCost, hasBudget
 - **Equity impacts:** affectsEquityGroup, hasBenefitDistribution, hasCostPerGroup
- **Key relationships:**
 - respondsTo (ResponseAction → DisruptionEvent / PredictedDisruptionState / Scenario)

- updatesState (ResponseAction → SystemState)
- targetsActor (ResponseAction → Actor / EquityGroup)
- appliesTo (ResponseAction → TransportElement / MobilityService / SpatialUnit)
- evaluatedBy (ResponseAction → LearningAction / Observation / KpiObservation)
- affectsEquity (ResponseAction → EquityGroup) - tracks differential impacts
- constrainedBy (ResponseAction → GovernanceInstrument / LegalConstraint)
- hasOutcome (ResponseAction → SystemState or KpiObservation)
- triggersResponse (DisruptionEvent → ResponseAction)
- precedes / follows (ResponseAction → ResponseAction) - action sequencing.

Figure 12. Response Actions

Figure 12 shows the response action taxonomy organized into seven functional categories supporting antifragile system management across operational, tactical, and strategic timescales. **ControlAction** encompasses operational interventions including antifragile control mechanisms, adaptive control, mode shifting, proactive rerouting, fleet allocation, signal control, and network optimization. **EmergencyAction** addresses crisis response through evacuation management, emergency response protocols, triage, and resource allocation. **PolicyAction** enables strategic transformation through policy updates, regulation changes, and climate adaptation planning. **CoordinationAction** facilitates multi-stakeholder collaboration through multi-agency coordination, crisis coordination, cross-authority coordination, and stakeholder engagement processes. **BehaviouralIntervention** leverages nudges, incentive design, and inclusive interventions to encourage sustainable mobility choices and ensure equitable access. **MonitoringAction** tracks system performance and equity through performance monitoring, equity monitoring, equity alerts, and impact evaluation linked to T2.7 KPI observations. **LearningAction** enables organizational learning through intervention learning, systemic learning, and knowledge transfer across cities and scenarios. Key relationships include `respondsTo` linking actions to triggering disruptions, `updatesState` showing system state changes, `targetsActor` and `appliesTo` showing intervention scope, `affectsEquity` enabling tracking of differential impacts on vulnerable populations, `constrainedBy` showing governance compliance requirements, and `evaluatedBy` linking actions to KPI observations for effectiveness assessment. This comprehensive action space underpins Requirements 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 20, 45, 50, 52, 53, 54, 57, 58, 60, 61 related to scenario analysis, intervention design, learning mechanisms, equity considerations, and antifragility assessment.

6.6 Modularisation strategy and multi-layer network representation

This section introduces the modularisation strategy and the multi-layer network representation used by the ontology.

6.6.1 Modularisation strategy

The ontology is physically split into OWL modules, each corresponding to the conceptual modules above. Typical imports:

```
antifragicity-core.owl
antifragicity-transport.owl
antifragicity-mobility.owl
antifragicity-disruption.owl
antifragicity-systemstate.owl
antifragicity-environment.owl
antifragicity-actors-governance.owl
antifragicity-spatiotemporal.owl
antifragicity-data-provenance.owl
antifragicity-response-learning.owl
antifragicity-alignments.owl
```

`antifragicity-core.owl` defines the 12 top-level classes and the generic properties used across the ontology. The remaining modules import this core module and add domain-specific specialisations.

The antifragicity-alignments.owl module contains the alignments to external ontologies. This modularisation supports separate development, so different partners can work on different modules; selective import, for example where a simulator only needs the transport and disruption modules; and performance tuning, since reasoners can focus on relevant subsets for particular tasks.

6.6.2 Multi-layer network representation

AntifragiCity needs to model **interdependencies across infrastructures** (transport, energy, communication, health, etc.) and their role in cascades.

The ontology adopts a **multi-layer network pattern**:

- Introduce a class InfrastructureLayer with subclasses TransportLayer, EnergyLayer, CommunicationLayer, HealthLayer, etc.
- Extend TransportElement (and potentially other domain-specific elements) with a property inLayer:

Class: InfrastructureLayer

Class: TransportLayer SubClassOf: InfrastructureLayer

Class: EnergyLayer SubClassOf: InfrastructureLayer

Class: CommunicationLayer SubClassOf: InfrastructureLayer

Class: HealthLayer SubClassOf: InfrastructureLayer

ObjectProperty: inLayer

Domain: TransportElement

Range: InfrastructureLayer

- Define an object property dependsOn to capture interdependencies:

ObjectProperty: dependsOn

Domain: TransportElement

Range: TransportElement

- For cross-layer dependencies, dependsOn can link elements belonging to different layers (e.g. a signal controller in the TransportLayer depending on a substation in the EnergyLayer).

Disruption cascades are modelled by linking DisruptionEvent instances to the **elements and layers** they affect (via affects and occursInLayer), and allowing DisruptionEvent to propagatesTo other DisruptionEvents, possibly in different layers.

Equilibrium and antifragility reasoning can then analyze how **layer-level resilience** and **cascading risk** propagate across the multi-layer infrastructure network.

The concrete modelling of non-transport layers (Energy, Communication, Health) will be refined with partners responsible for those domains. In this deliverable, the pattern is defined generically and can be instantiated once cross-infrastructure data and scenarios are finalised.

6.7 Alignment with standards and European mobility datasets

This subsection introduces the interoperability targets and the standards-alignment approach adopted by the ontology.

The standards listed in this section are provided to document planned interoperability points and reusable modelling patterns. Alignment does not imply that every pilot will instantiate every aligned module; modules are designed to be imported independently based on the datasets and tooling

actually used in each use case. Where sensor or observation data are not available, the ontology remains usable via non-sensor observation sources (e.g., model outputs, surveys, administrative records).

The ontology is designed to **bridge** between project-specific antifragility concepts and existing European standards and open data models (49–52). Alignment will focus on the following areas:

6.7.1 Transport and mobility data models

The following list summarises the main transport and mobility standards considered for alignment.

- Public transport and multi-modal data: alignment of Mode, PublicTransportMovement, RoutePlan, Node, Edge, Corridor with data structures derived from standards such as Transmodel v6.0 (49)/ NeTeX (CEN/TS 16614 series), SIRI v2.1 (26) and GTFS-like (General Transit Feed Specification) (53) schemas.
- European mobility datasets: mapping to attributes and entities found in **pilot city datasets** (e.g., **Bratislava**: Public transport GTFS feed, road network GIS data, traffic sensor locations, **Thessaloniki**: Road network topology, public transport routes, traffic management data, **Larissa**: OpenStreetMap transport network, public transport schedules, parking facilities), and **EU-wide open datasets**: OpenStreetMap transport layers, INSPIRE transport network themes), ensuring that identifiers and classifications from these datasets will be reused where possible to ensure interoperability. Detailed data catalogues and mapping tables will be provided in D3.3 following pilot data profiling.
-

6.7.2 Sensing, observations and IoT

The following list summarises the observation and sensing standards considered for alignment.

- **SOSA/SSN** alignment: specialise Observation, TrafficObservation, EmissionObservation, DataQualityObservation and SensorNetwork as subclasses or instances of SOSA/SSN patterns (e.g. `sosa:Observation`, `sosa:Sensor`, `sosa:FeatureOfInterest`).
- Sensor metadata: capture properties like sampling frequency, accuracy, coverage and latency in line with existing practices.

6.7.3 Spatial standards

The following list summarises the spatial standards considered for alignment.

- **GeoSPARQL**: use GeoSPARQL geometry properties (24) for SpatialUnit, including Boundary, NoGoArea, VulnerableArea.
- **INSPIRE themes**: where available, link to INSPIRE feature types for transport networks, administrative units and land-use.

6.7.4 Provenance and governance

The following list summarises the provenance and governance standards considered for alignment.

- **PROV-O**: align DataSource, Provenance, AnalyticsEngine and Dashboard with PROV-O's `prov:Entity`, `prov:Agent`, `prov:Activity` patterns.
- **Organisational vocabularies**: align Organisation, Agency, Platform to existing vocabularies (e.g. ORG ontology) as appropriate.

6.7.5 Risk, resilience and emergencies

The following list summarises the risk and emergency-modelling resources considered for alignment.

- Where suitable, align DisruptionEvent, HazardType, EmergencyType, Crisis and related properties with existing risk, hazard and emergency management ontologies or classifications (e.g. common hazard taxonomies used by civil protection agencies).

6.7.6 Alignment Methodology and Implementation

The alignment process follows a phased, pilot-driven methodology to ensure that standard mappings reflect actual data sources and use cases rather than abstract possibilities:

- **Phase 1: Mapping specification (D2.5, current deliverable)** This deliverable establishes the alignment targets and mapping patterns. Initial alignment points are specified based on requirements analysis (Section 4) and pilot city data catalogues. The ontology structure is designed to accommodate standard alignment through modular imports and explicit mapping axioms (Section 6.7.7).
- **Phase 2: Pilot data profiling and mapping implementation (WP3, D3.3)** Alignment will be operationalised during WP3 (vulnerability and risk analysis) when pilot city datasets are integrated. For each pilot data profiling identifies which standards are actually used in local datasets (e.g., GTFS feeds, sensor APIs, traffic management systems), mapping tables document correspondences between ontology classes/properties and standard schemas, alignment axioms (equivalence, subsumption, or annotation mappings per Section 6.7.7) are implemented based on actual data structures, pilot-specific extensions are documented where local data exceeds standard coverage.
- **Phase 3: Validation and refinement (WP3-WP4)** As scenarios are populated (WP3) and digital twin components are integrated (WP4), alignment quality is validated through SPARQL query testing against pilot data instantiated using standard mappings, competency question validation (Section 5.2) executed over aligned data, interoperability testing where multiple pilots share standard-based queries, iterative refinement of mappings based on integration issues or semantic mismatches.

Alignment implementation is distributed across work packages:

- **WP2 (current):** Define alignment targets, mapping patterns, and ontology structure that supports standard reuse (this deliverable)
- **WP3 (M12-M24):** Implement mappings for pilot city datasets during vulnerability analysis and scenario modelling (D3.2, D3.3)
- **WP4 (M18-M36):** Validate alignment through digital twin integration and cross-pilot interoperability testing (D4.3, D4.4)
- **WP2 coordination:** Ontology maintenance and alignment refinement based on WP3/WP4 feedback (ongoing)

Task 2.5 (Ontology Development) provides the semantic framework and alignment patterns; Tasks 3.1-3.3 (pilot integration) operationalise the mappings; Task 4.2 (digital twin interoperability) validates alignment effectiveness.

Current alignment status:

At this stage (D2.5), the ontology structure is **designed for alignment** with the standards listed in Sections 6.7.1-6.7.5. Initial compatibility checks confirm that: the 12-class meta-model (Section 6.4) can accommodate standard concepts through subclass specialisation or equivalence mappings, core object properties (affects, hasImpact, occursIn, etc.) align with standard relation patterns (e.g., SOSA

observation chains, Transmodel network topology), and pilot city data catalogues (preliminarily reviewed) include GTFS feeds, sensor APIs compliant with common IoT standards, and GIS data compatible with INSPIRE/GeoSPARQL.

Complete mapping tables, axiom sets, and interoperability test reports will be documented in:

- **D3.3 (M24)**: Pilot integration and vulnerability analysis, including detailed data-to-ontology mappings
- **D4.4 (M36)**: Digital twin validation report, including cross-pilot interoperability assessment
- **Appendix D**: initial mapping tables; to be expanded/refined after pilot data profiling in WP3 (D3.3).

Compatibility statement

The proposed ontology framework is **structurally compatible** with current European transport, sensing, and spatial data standards. The meta-model (Section 6.4) provides extension points that can accommodate standard classes through OWL axioms without requiring incompatible modifications. Where standards cover similar concepts (e.g., SOSA:Observation vs. ontology Observation class), alignment will use equivalence or subsumption axioms as appropriate. Where project-specific concepts (e.g., antifragility scores, equity indicators) extend beyond standard coverage, they are modelled as specialisations or new properties that do not conflict with standard semantics.

Formal compatibility validation will be completed during WP3 pilot integration, with results reported in D3.3.

6.7.7 Mappings and implementation

The following list summarises the mapping and implementation mechanisms used to operationalise alignment. Alignments will be represented using:

- **equivalence axioms** (`owl:equivalentClass`, `owl:equivalentProperty`) when strong semantic equivalence can be established.
- **subsumption axioms** (`rdfs:SubClassOf`, `rdfs:subPropertyOf`) where AntifragiCity concepts specialise external ones.
- **annotation properties** (e.g. `skos:closeMatch`) when mappings are approximate or context-dependent.

A complete set of mapping tables, examples and alignment axioms will be compiled in Appendix D as final decisions are made on which external standards are adopted by each pilot and platform component.

7 Ontology Specification Overview (OWL/Rules/Patterns)

This section summarises how the AntifragiCity Ontology is formally specified, without presenting the full axiom listings and rule/query fragments in the main body. The detailed ontology specification fragments (OWL fragments, constraints, rule patterns, and query templates) are provided in Appendix B, with worked SWRL/SHACL and SPARQL examples in Appendix E.

7.1 Scope of the formal specification

The AntifragiCity Ontology is intended as a machine-interpretable representation of the concepts and relationships needed to describe: (i) urban mobility systems as socio-technical and cyber-physical systems, (ii) disruption–response–learning cycles and equilibrium shifts, and (iii) equity, vulnerability and governance constraints, while supporting heterogeneous data integration and reasoning for decision support.

The formal specification therefore covers:

- **Terminological knowledge (TBox):** classes, hierarchies, and object/data properties for transport elements, disruptions, states, scenarios, actors, governance instruments, environmental factors, observations/KPIs, and response actions (built around the project’s stable 12-class meta-model). The KPI module includes hierarchical observation classes (Observation, KpiObservation, CoreKPI) to support the T2.7 framework with 13 stakeholder-prioritised core KPIs from Table 8 (including CO₂ emissions, modal split, travel time, noise pollution, infrastructure features, urban density, green space) and the extended catalogue of 209 indicators organized into 7 groups and 20 subgroups. KPI metadata properties (hasKPINumber, hasKPIGroup, hasKPISubgroup, hasStakeholderSelectionCount, hasTarget, hasCurrentValue) enable systematic tracking and cross-city comparison.
- **Constraint layer (validation):** structural constraints (e.g., domain/range expectations, cardinalities where needed, and shape-based checks) to support data quality and consistent population of the knowledge graph. KPI observations require mandatory properties such as hasKPINumber for catalogue alignment, hasValue for measurements, and hasTimestamp for time-series tracking.
- **Rule and reasoning layer:** rule patterns that operationalise antifragility- and equity-relevant inferences (e.g., classification patterns, vulnerability detection, cascade reasoning) when OWL alone is insufficient or intentionally kept lightweight.
- **Query layer:** SPARQL query templates aligned to competency questions, ensuring that the ontology can answer the project’s required information needs and support regression-style testing during platform integration. KPI-specific queries enable performance monitoring, target compliance checking, cross-scenario KPI comparison, and identification of equity groups experiencing degraded service access based on KPI thresholds.

7.2 Modularity and implementation logic

The specification is modular: a small, stable upper structure supports multiple domain modules (e.g., transport/network, disruptions/risk, governance/policy, equity/social, observation/KPIs/data-provenance, antifragility/learning). This enables incremental implementation and reduces integration risk because modules can evolve independently while preserving shared semantics.

In operational terms, the project follows a “one shared TBox, multiple city ABoxes” strategy: the same ontology schema is shared across pilots, while each city instantiates its own individuals (networks, events, indicators, actors, and scenarios), optionally separated using named graphs to support cross-city comparison and learning (more details in section 8.1).

For example: the shared TBox defines the class **:FloodEvent** and properties **:affectedArea**, **:hasImpact**, **:recoveryTime**. Bratislava then instantiates individual **:BratislavaFlood2024** classified as a **:FloodEvent**, with **:affectedArea :OldTownDistrict** and **:recoveryTime "48h"**. Associated KPI observations track impact through **:BratislavaFloodKPI_21** (CO₂ emissions: KPI 21)

with `:hasValue` "15% increase" and `:BratislavaFloodKPI_47` (average travel time: KPI 47) with `:hasValue` "35 min" (vs. baseline 20 min). Thessaloniki independently instantiates `:ThessFlood2023` using the same class and properties but with different values (`:affectedArea` `:WaterfrontZone`, `:recoveryTime` "72h") and corresponding KPI observations `:ThessFloodKPI_21` with `:hasValue` "22% increase" and `:ThessFloodKPI_47` with `:hasValue` "45 min". By querying across both city graphs, the platform can compare flood impacts including quantitative KPI degradation, identify that Bratislava's recovery was faster, and investigate whether Bratislava's response strategies (stored as `:ResponseAction` individuals) could be adapted for Thessaloniki's flood preparedness planning including enabling evidence-based cross-city learning.

7.3 Representation choices and conventions

For readability in documentation, illustrative fragments are presented using human-readable OWL notation, while the machine-readable ontology is maintained in standard OWL/RDF serialisations under version control and is intended for loading into triple stores and standard ontology tooling. The deliverable uses explicit namespace conventions and consistent naming (classes in UpperCamelCase; properties in lowerCamelCase; individuals in lowercase-with-hyphens or city-prefixed identifiers; **Table 3** illustrates this naming convention) so that partners can map datasets and APIs predictably and generate repeatable ETL pipelines.

Element Type	Naming Convention	Examples
Classes	UpperCamelCase (capitalize all words)	<code>:TransportElement</code> , <code>:DisruptionEvent</code> , <code>:AntifragilityScore</code> , <code>:PublicTransportService</code>
Properties	lowerCamelCase (lowercase first word, capitalize subsequent words)	<code>:hasImpact</code> , <code>:affectedArea</code> , <code>:occursIn</code> , <code>:triggeredBy</code>

Table 3. OWL Naming Conventions in the AntifragiCity Ontology

7.4 Reasoning and validation in practice

The ontology is designed to support three complementary mechanisms:

1. **OWL reasoning** for core typing, subsumption, and consistent structure.
2. **Rule patterns** (illustrative SWRL) for project-specific inferences (e.g., antifragility classification, KPI threshold alerts, equity impact detection, cascade propagation) where procedural logic or thresholds are needed. For example, rules can classify system states as degraded when core KPI values fall below targets, trigger equity alerts when vulnerable populations experience disproportionate service access reductions, or infer cascade effects when multiple interconnected transport elements fail simultaneously.
3. **Validation constraints** (illustrative SHACL shapes) to detect incomplete or inconsistent instance data before analytics and dashboards consume it, improving robustness during pilot deployment. KPI observations are validated for required properties (`hasKPINumber` must reference catalogue 1-209, `hasValue` must be numeric or categorical as appropriate, `hasTimestamp` must be valid `dateTime`), ensuring data quality for performance dashboards and cross-city comparison.

8 Instantiation and Use Cases

This section describes how the AntifragiCity Ontology is instantiated for the pilot cities and how it supports concrete use cases. It covers the **creation of city-specific knowledge bases**, integration of **heterogeneous data sources**, a set of **illustrative use-case scenarios**, and **reasoning and inference examples** relevant to antifragility.

The focus is on *how* the abstract ontology defined in previous sections becomes an operational knowledge graph supporting analysis, simulation and decision support in Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa and Thessaloniki.

Scope and limitations of this specification

This deliverable specifies the semantic structures, patterns and instantiation approaches for the AntifragiCity knowledge graph. The concrete instantiation details, including specific network elements, calibrated parameters, thresholds, local data integration workflows, and empirical validation, will be co-designed with pilot partners during implementation phases and are beyond the scope of this ontology-focused specification. This section therefore provides illustrative examples and generic patterns that demonstrate how the ontology supports pilot use cases, with the understanding that detailed parameterization, data mapping specifications, and operational deployment will be addressed in subsequent technical tasks in collaboration with Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki stakeholders.

8.1 Instantiating Knowledge Bases for Pilot Cities

8.1.1 General approach

As explained previously, the ontology is instantiated following a "**one shared TBox, multiple city ABoxes**" strategy. The **TBox** (terminological component) consists of the 12 top-level classes, their subclasses, properties and rules defined in Sections 3 and 7. For each pilot city, a **city-specific ABox** (assertional component) is created, containing individuals representing transport network elements such as nodes, edges, corridors, routes and facilities; mobility services and fleets; key actors and governance structures; equity groups and vulnerable areas; data sources, sensors and monitoring components; and disruption events, scenarios and response actions.

City-specific graphs can be organised as **named graphs**, allowing queries within a single city, across cities for benchmarking and transfer, or on the union of all pilots for cross-city learning.

Example naming convention for graph IRIs:

<http://antifragicity.eu/kg/bratislava>
<http://antifragicity.eu/kg/larissa>
<http://antifragicity.eu/kg/odessa>
<http://antifragicity.eu/kg/thessaloniki>

8.1.2 IRI patterns and naming conventions

To ensure traceability and avoid collisions, three types of IRIs are used in the knowledge graph. Named graph IRIs identify city-specific knowledge bases and follow the pattern <http://antifragicity.eu/kg/{cityname}>, where "kg" stands for "knowledge graph". For example, <http://antifragicity.eu/kg/bratislava> identifies the entire Bratislava knowledge base, enabling

graph-level operations such as querying all data for a specific city or comparing data across cities. Individual resource IRIs identify specific entities within a city and follow the structured pattern `http://antifragicity.eu/city/{CityCode}/{Type}/{LocalID}`, where `CityCode` ∈ {BA, LA, OD, THESS} for Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki respectively, `Type` encodes a human-readable grouping (e.g. Node, Corridor, Scenario), and `LocalID` references a local identifier from GIS, GTFS or other source systems where possible. In examples and query templates, these full IRIs are abbreviated using the prefix notation “:” for readability (e.g. “:BA_Node_1023” as shorthand for the full URI “`http://antifragicity.eu/city/BA/Node/1023`”).

Examples of individual IRIs:

```
:BA_Node_1023      a :Node
:BA_Corridor_AM1   a :Corridor
:BA_Hospital_StM   a :Facility
:BA_ElderlyGroup_01 a :EquityGroup
:BA_TrafficSensor_45 a :TrafficSensor
:BA_Scenario_Flood2030 a :DisruptiveScenario
```

8.1.3 Minimal instantiation per city

For each pilot, a **minimal viable knowledge base** (MVKB) is defined to ensure that key competency questions can be answered even before full data integration. The MVKB serves as a foundational layer that can be **incrementally enriched** as additional data sources are connected and as pilot partners refine use-case details.

The MVKB includes a **core network skeleton** containing selected Node and Edge instances representing critical corridors and bridges, main PT stops and stations as Facility individuals, and high-level EvacRoute and AlternativeRoute instances for emergency mobility (Requirements 9, 22, 26, 33, 34). It also includes **key actors and governance context**, comprising the municipal transport authority, emergency services and PT operator as InstitutionalActor individuals (subclasses of Actor), along with basic Regulation, LegalConstraint and DataSharingAgreement instances relevant for mobility and data usage (Requirements 13, 27, 32, 36, 38, 49).

The MVKB further represents **equity groups and vulnerable areas** through a small set of EquityGroup and CitizenSegment instances (e.g. low-income residents, elderly, students) and VulnerableArea instances for selected districts with known exposure or low accessibility (Requirements 6, 29, 43). It includes **disruption and scenario instances**, with at least one DisruptionEvent and one DisruptiveScenario per city (e.g. flood, heatwave, port disruption) and corresponding ResponseAction individuals (e.g. rerouting, evacuation, priority routing) (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 20, 50, 53). Finally, it contains **monitoring and KPIs** through representative instances of TrafficObservation, EmissionObservation and KpiObservation, including at least 3-5 CoreKPI instances from the T2.7 stakeholder-prioritised subset (e.g., CO₂ emissions: KPI 21, modal split: KPIs 38-40, travel time: KPI 47, noise pollution: KPI 31, infrastructure spatial features: KPI 163) with proper metadata (hasKPINumber, hasKPIGroup, hasKPISubgroup, hasStakeholderSelectionCount) to enable baseline performance tracking and cross-city comparison, along with basic SystemState individuals (e.g. normal, congested, antifragile) linked to KPI observations via hasKpiObservation (Requirements 40, 46, 51, 52).

The final selection of assets, routes, actors and equity groups per city will be agreed with pilot partners on the basis of local datasets and expert input.

8.2 Data Integration methodology (GIS, IoT, Mobility APIs, Simulation Outputs)

8.2.1 Overview of data sources

Instantiation relies on **heterogeneous data sources** drawn from multiple domains. **GIS layers** provide road network topology, administrative boundaries, land use patterns, flood zones and critical facilities. **Transport network and timetable** data come from GTFS/NeTEx feeds, static PT network descriptions and fleet datasets (Requirement 55). **IoT and sensor data** include traffic loop detectors, Bluetooth/ANPR systems, mobile phone-derived origin-destination estimates and air quality sensors (Requirements 30, 46). **Mobility platforms and APIs** supply real-time PT information, MaaS platform feeds and routing engine outputs. **Simulation outputs** are generated by micro- and mesoscopic simulation tools (e.g. SUMO, Aimsun), system dynamics models and agent-based models (Requirements 12, 15, 50, 52, 53, 57). Finally, **socio-economic and equity datasets** drawn from census statistics, household surveys, health indicators and land-use patterns inform equity analysis (Requirements 6, 29, 37, 43, 44).

Each data source is mapped to the ontology through **semantic lifting** steps to ensure consistent representation within the knowledge graph.

8.2.2 Semantic lifting pipeline

The integration pipeline follows a systematic process to transform heterogeneous data into ontology-compliant RDF triples:

1. **Extraction and cleaning**

Raw data is extracted from source systems, cleaned and normalised (e.g. coordinate systems, time formats).

2. **Structural mapping**

Structures are mapped to ontology classes, for example:

- Road segments → Edge (subclass of TransportElement)
- Intersections → Node
- PT stops → Facility
- Administrative zones → SpatialUnit (e.g. AnalysisZone)
- PT trips/routes → instances of MobilityService and RoutePlan.

3. **Semantic annotation**

Attributes are transformed into data properties, with values such as:

- Length, capacity, free-flow speed → hasCapacityUtilisation, hasTravelTime (or related properties).
- Emissions, energy use → hasEmissions, hasEnergyUse.
- Socio-economic indicators → hasSocialVulnerability, hasServiceAccess, hasRiskExposure (Requirements 6, 24, 29, 43).
- Provenance is attached using DataSource and Provenance individuals, with properties like hasDataQuality, hasTrustScore, hasConfidence (Requirement 36).

4. **Temporal and spatial linking**

Observations and events are linked to:

- TemporalUnit instances (e.g. 15-minute intervals, daily windows) using occursDuring or validDuring.

- SpatialUnit instances (e.g. districts, grid cells) using locatedIn and GeoSPARQL geometries.

5. Scenario and simulation alignment

Simulation outputs are associated with Scenario individuals where:

- Each simulation run becomes ScenarioInput and ExperimentRun.
- Aggregated outcomes (flows, delays, emissions, equity KPIs) are captured as KpiObservation and other Observation subclasses linked via forScenario (Requirements 12, 15, 50, 52, 53, 54).

The pipeline can be implemented via standard ETL tools combined with RDF mapping frameworks (e.g. RML), but the design remains tool-agnostic in this deliverable.

Detailed ETL specifications and mapping files (R2RML/RML, scripts) will be prepared for each pilot in subsequent technical tasks; they are out of scope for this ontology-focused deliverable.

8.2.3 Handling uncertainty, provenance and data quality

The ontology explicitly represents uncertainty in predictions and forecasts through properties such as hasForecastUncertainty and hasPredictionError (Requirements 20, 50, 52); trust and data quality through hasTrustScore, hasDataQuality and hasConfidence (Requirements 30, 36, 40); and provenance through generatedBy, hasProvenance, DataSource and Provenance classes (Requirement 36).

The instantiation examples throughout this section are presented in Turtle (Terse RDF Triple Language) (54), a W3C standard human-readable format for expressing RDF (Resource Description Framework) data. In Turtle syntax, “a” is shorthand for “rdf:type”, indicating class membership (e.g., “:BA_TrafficObs_2025_10_01_08 a :TrafficObservation” means “this observation is an instance of the TrafficObservation class”). The specific identifiers, values and relationships shown in these examples are illustrative, demonstrating the instantiation patterns that will be applied to actual pilot city data during implementation.

Example instantiation (Turtle):

```
:BA_TrafficObs_2025_10_01_08
  a :TrafficObservation ;
  :observedOn :BA_Edge_5678 ;
  :hasSpeedFlow 34.2 ;
  :hasDataQuality 0.91 ;
  :hasTrustScore 0.88 ;
  :generatedBy :BA_TrafficSensor_45 ;
  :occursDuring :BA_TimeSlot_2025_10_01_08_00_08_15 .
```

```
:BA_KPI_TravelTime_2025_10_01_08
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 47 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 23.5 ;
  :hasTarget 20.0 ;
  :hasUnit "minutes" ;
```

```

:hasTimestamp "2025-10-01T08:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:observedOn :BA_Corridor_Danube_1 ;
:hasDataQuality 0.91 ;
:hasTrustScore 0.88 ;
:generatedBy :BA_AnalyticsEngine_1 .

:BA_KPI_CO2_2025_10_01
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 21 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 145.2 ;
  :hasTarget 120.0 ;
  :hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2025-10-01T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :observedOn :BA_District_Centre ;
  :hasDataQuality 0.85 ;
  :generatedBy :BA_EmissionModel_1 .

```

These KPI observations demonstrate the T2.7 framework integration: CoreKPI instances represent stakeholder-prioritised indicators (KPI 47 with 4 stakeholder selections, KPI 21 with 5 stakeholder selections - the highest priority), with metadata enabling catalogue alignment (hasKPINumber 1-209), hierarchical organization (hasKPIGroup, hasKPISubgroup), and cross-city comparison (hasStakeholderSelectionCount). Such representations are key for antifragility analysis under uncertainty, for deciding which data streams to rely on in real-time decision support, and for systematic performance tracking against targets across baseline and disruptive scenarios. Such representations are key for antifragility analysis under uncertainty and for deciding which data streams to rely on in real-time decision support.

8.3 Use-Case Scenarios

This subsection presents illustrative use cases for each pilot city. They are representative of the types of disruptions, responses and outcomes that the ontology must support.

Figure 13. Scenario Module

Figure 13 illustrates the **Scenario** module structure supporting comparative analysis across **baseline, disruptive, what-if, policy, and simulation configurations**. The Scenario base class provides common properties (`hasName`, `hasDescription`, `hasTimeHorizon`, `hasScenarioProbability`) with five specialized subclasses: **BaselineScenario** captures reference conditions with calibration status and reference year for establishing performance baselines; **DisruptiveScenario** represents system behaviour under disruptions with specified disruption types, severity levels, and impact ranges; **WhatIfScenario** enables exploratory analysis through explicit assumptions and variables; **PolicyScenario** captures governance interventions with expected outcomes and governance levels, involving stakeholder groups through the `involvesStakeholder` relationship; and **Simulation** represents agent-based, micro-simulation, or system dynamics models with execution parameters including agent counts, iterations, and convergence status, running on DigitalTwin instances. The ScenarioLibrary aggregates scenarios into organized collections enabling reuse across cities, while **ForecastModel** instances provide predictive capabilities with specified forecast horizons and uncertainty quantification. Key relationships anchor scenarios in geographic and temporal context (`appliesTo SpatialUnit`, `hasTimeframe TemporalUnit`), link scenarios to resulting system performance (`hasSystemState`), and critically integrate T2.7 KPI framework evaluation (`evaluatedBy KpiObservation`) enabling quantitative comparison of CO₂ emissions, travel times, modal splits, and other core indicators across scenario variants. The `includesResponseAction` relationship captures interventions within scenarios, `affectsEquityGroup` tracks differential impacts on vulnerable populations, and `comparedWith` enables explicit cross-scenario analysis for antifragility assessment. DisruptiveScenario instances reference specific DisruptionEvent occurrences through `includesEvent`, PolicyScenario instances link to governance instruments through `implementsPolicy`, and all scenarios are evaluated through KPI observations providing evidence-based performance assessment grounded in the T2.7 stakeholder-prioritised indicator framework (13 core KPIs from Table 8 plus extended catalogue of 209 indicators).

8.3.1 Bratislava: Flood disruption and antifragile routing

Bratislava experiences an extreme flood event affecting several bridges and riverside corridors (Requirements 4, 7, 19). PT lines and road traffic are disrupted; emergency services require reliable access to hospitals and shelters (Requirements 26, 33, 34). The aim is not only to restore performance but, over repeated events, to *improve* routing strategies and preparedness through learning mechanisms (Requirements 11, 14, 45), demonstrating antifragility. The use case also addresses proactive rerouting capabilities (Requirement 22) and real-time monitoring for adaptive response (Requirements 9, 46, 51).

Key instantiated concepts (illustrative examples):

- The **disruption** would be represented by an instance such as `:BA_Event_Flood2030` as a DisruptionEvent with `HazardType = flood`, along with `hasSeverity` and `hasMagnitude` properties.
- The **affected network** would include instances such as `:BA_Corridor_Danube_1` and `:BA_Bridge_2` as Corridor and Edge instances, both linked to the disruption event via the `affectedBy` property.
- Two example **scenarios** would be defined: `:BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline` as a DisruptiveScenario without antifragile measures, and `:BA_Scenario_Flood2032_Improved` as a DisruptiveScenario incorporating proactive rerouting and priority emergency routing.

- **Response actions** would include instances such as :BA_Action_ProactiveReroute1 as a ProactiveReroute and :BA_Action_PriorityEvac as a ResponseAction representing evacuation and priority routing for emergency vehicles.
- **System states** would be captured through instances such as :BA_State_Flood2030 and :BA_State_Flood2032 as SystemState instances containing performance and antifragility indicators that demonstrate improvement over time.

Example instantiation (Turtle):

:BA_Event_Flood2030

```
a :DisruptionEvent ;
:belongsToHazardType :Flood ;
:hasSeverity 0.8 ;
:hasMagnitude 0.9 ;
:affects :BA_Corridor_Danube_1, :BA_Bridge_2 .
```

:BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline

```
a :DisruptiveScenario ;
:hasSystemState :BA_State_Flood2030 ;
:respondsTo :BA_Event_Flood2030 .
```

:BA_Scenario_Flood2032_Improved

```
a :DisruptiveScenario ;
:hasSystemState :BA_State_Flood2032 ;
:respondsTo :BA_Event_Flood2030 ;
:includesResponseAction :BA_Action_ProactiveReroute1, :BA_Action_PriorityEvac .
```

:BA_State_Flood2030

```
a :SystemState ;
:hasAntifragilityScore 0.10 ;
:hasResilienceIndex 0.55 ;
:hasEconCost 30.0e6 ;
:hasKpiObservation :BA_KPI_CO2_Flood2030,
:BA_KPI_TravelTime_Flood2030,
:BA_KPI_ModalSplit_Flood2030 .
```

:BA_State_Flood2032

```
a :SystemState ;
:hasAntifragilityScore 0.25 ;
:hasResilienceIndex 0.70 ;
:hasEconCost 22.0e6 ;
:hasKpiObservation :BA_KPI_CO2_Flood2032,
:BA_KPI_TravelTime_Flood2032,
:BA_KPI_ModalSplit_Flood2032 .
```

:BA_KPI_CO2_Flood2030

```
a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 21 ;
```

```
:hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
:hasCurrentValue 185.5 ;
:hasBaselineValue 145.2 ;
:hasTarget 120.0 ;
:hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
:hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline .
```

```
:BA_KPI_TravelTime_Flood2030
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 47 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 42.0 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 20.0 ;
  :hasTarget 25.0 ;
  :hasUnit "minutes" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T08:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline .
```

```
:BA_KPI_ModalSplit_Flood2030
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 38 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Modal Split" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
  :hasCurrentValue "Car:65%, PT:20%, Active:15%" ;
  :hasBaselineValue "Car:55%, PT:30%, Active:15%" ;
  :hasTarget "Car:45%, PT:40%, Active:15%" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline .
```

```
:BA_KPI_CO2_Flood2032
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 21 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 162.3 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 145.2 ;
  :hasTarget 120.0 ;
  :hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2032-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2032_Improved ;
```

:hasComment "Improved over 2030 baseline flood response (185.5 → 162.3), demonstrating antifragile learning" .

:BA_KPI_TravelTime_Flood2032

a :CoreKPI ;
 :hasKPINumber 47 ;
 :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
 :hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
 :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
 :hasCurrentValue 28.5 ;
 :hasBaselineValue 20.0 ;
 :hasTarget 25.0 ;
 :hasUnit "minutes" ;
 :hasTimestamp "2032-06-15T08:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
 :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2032_Improved ;
 :hasComment "Significantly improved over 2030 (42.0 → 28.5 min), approaching target despite disruption" .

:BA_KPI_ModalSplit_Flood2032

a :CoreKPI ;
 :hasKPINumber 38 ;
 :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
 :hasKPISubgroup "Modal Split" ;
 :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
 :hasCurrentValue "Car:58%, PT:27%, Active:15%" ;
 :hasBaselineValue "Car:55%, PT:30%, Active:15%" ;
 :hasTarget "Car:45%, PT:40%, Active:15%" ;
 :hasTimestamp "2032-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
 :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2032_Improved ;
 :hasComment "Better maintained PT share (27% vs 20% in 2030) due to proactive rerouting" .

Competency questions covered

- Which corridors and bridges are most affected by the flood?
- How do antifragile routing strategies change the **economic cost** and **response times** across scenarios?
- What are the T2.7 **core KPI values** (CO₂ emissions - KPI 21, travel time - KPI 47, modal split - KPI 38) across baseline and improved scenarios, and how do they demonstrate antifragile improvement (e.g., 2032 flood response showing 162.3 tonnes CO₂ vs 185.5 in 2030, and 28.5 min travel time vs 42.0 min)?
- Which **equity groups** face increased/decreased risk exposure under improved strategies?
- Which **KPI targets** are met or approached despite disruption, indicating system antifragility?

In practice, the concrete network elements, cost estimates and empirical performance metrics will be derived from local models and data in the Bratislava pilot and are therefore beyond the scope of this deliverable.

8.3.2 Thessaloniki: AHEPA Hospital emergency access and multi-agency coordination

Thessaloniki faces critical healthcare-related mobility challenges during emergency situations requiring coordinated multi-agency response (Requirements 26, 32, 33, 34, 38). Two primary scenarios demonstrate the ontology's capacity to support emergency healthcare mobility:

Scenario 1: Emergency evacuation of AHEPA Hospital following internal damages (fire, power outage, structural failure) requiring rapid transfer of non-ambulatory patients to other healthcare facilities with guaranteed clear and fast ambulance routes (Requirements 32, 33, 34).

Scenario 2: Forest fire in Seich Sou Forest adjacent to the city, requiring simultaneous movement of fire engines, ambulances, police vehicles, and civilian evacuation, with dynamic street closures and public transport reconfiguration (Requirements 8, 19, 33, 34, 41).

The use case emphasizes dynamic prioritization of emergency vehicles based on incident severity, real-time coordination between municipal authorities and healthcare facilities, identification of dangerous streets requiring exclusion, and adaptive public transport responses (Requirements 26, 27, 32, 33). The system must support rapid-passage route generation for emergency vehicles while minimizing disruption to overall urban mobility, addressing both localized healthcare emergencies and city-wide environmental disasters (Requirements 22, 46, 51).

Key instantiated concepts (illustrative examples):

The healthcare emergency disruption would be represented by an instance such as :THESS_Event_HospitalEvacuation2031 as a Crisis (subclass of DisruptionEvent) with hasSeverity and requires ResponseAction instances. The affected network would include instances such as :THESS_Hospital_AHEPA as a Facility (critical infrastructure), :THESS_Corridor_HospitalAccess_1 and :THESS_Emergency_Route_1 as Corridor and EvacRoute instances, and destination healthcare facilities :THESS_Hospital_Papageorgiou, :THESS_Hospital_Ippokrateio as alternative Facility instances for patient transfer.

Multi-agency coordination would be captured through instances such as :THESS_Actor_AmbulanceService, :THESS_Actor_FireDepartment, :THESS_Actor_TrafficControl as InstitutionalActor instances (subclasses of Actor), coordinated through :THESS_CoordinationProtocol_Emergency as a GovernanceInstrument. Emergency vehicle prioritization would be represented by :THESS_Action_EmergencyPriority_1 as a PriorityRouting response action with hasPriorityLevel and affectsMode properties.

The forest fire scenario would include :THESS_Event_SeichSouFire2030 as a DisruptionEvent with HazardType = ForestFire, affecting spatial units :THESS_District_EastSuburbs and :THESS_ForestArea_SeichSou. Dynamic street exclusions would be modeled through :THESS_NoGoArea_FireZone as a NoGoArea (subclass of SpatialUnit) with temporal validity via validDuring. Public transport adaptation would be captured through :THESS_Action_PT_Reroute_1 and :THESS_Action_PT_ServiceSuspension as ResponseAction instances affecting PublicTransportService individuals.

Weather integration would be represented by :THESS_Weather_HighWind_2030 as a ClimateFactor or EnvironmentFactor linked to the fire event via exacerbatedBy, with properties like hasWindSpeed, hasTemperature affecting fire spread and traffic conditions. System states would capture performance under different response strategies: :THESS_State_FireResponse_Baseline (no coordination), :THESS_State_FireResponse_Coordinated (multi-agency priority routing), demonstrating antifragility through improved response times and reduced overall disruption across successive emergency events.

Example instantiation (Turtle):

```

:THESS_Event_HospitalEvacuation2031
  a :Crisis ;
  :belongsToHazardType :InfrastructureFailure ;
  :hasSeverity 0.9 ;
  :affects :THESS_Hospital_AHEPA ;
  :requiresResponseAction :THESS_Action_EmergencyPriority_1 .

:THESS_Hospital_AHEPA
  a :Facility ;
  :facilityType :HealthcareFacility ;
  :hasCapacity 800 ;
  :locatedIn :THESS_District_Centre ;
  :connectedTo :THESS_Corridor_HospitalAccess_1 .

:THESS_Action_EmergencyPriority_1
  a :PriorityRouting ;
  :hasPriorityLevel 1 ;
  :affectsMode :Ambulance ;
  :targetFacility :THESS_Hospital_Papageorgiou, :THESS_Hospital_Ippokrateio ;
  :usesRoute :THESS_Emergency_Route_1 ;
  :coordinatedBy :THESS_CoordinationProtocol_Emergency .

:THESS_CoordinationProtocol_Emergency
  a :GovernanceInstrument ;
  :involvesActor :THESS_Actor_AmbulanceService,
    :THESS_Actor_FireDepartment,
    :THESS_Actor_TrafficControl ;
  :providesDataSharing true .

:THESS_Event_SeichSouFire2030
  a :DisruptionEvent ;
  :belongsToHazardType :ForestFire ;
  :hasSeverity 0.85 ;
  :affects :THESS_ForestArea_SeichSou, :THESS_District_EastSuburbs ;
  :exacerbatedBy :THESS_Weather_HighWind_2030 .

:THESS_NoGoArea_FireZone
  a :NoGoArea ;
  :locatedIn :THESS_District_EastSuburbs ;
  :validDuring :THESS_TimeWindow_Fire_2030_06_15 ;
  :excludesMode :PrivateVehicle, :PublicTransport ;
  :allowsMode :EmergencyVehicle .

:THESS_Action_PT_Reroute_1
  a :ResponseAction ;
  :respondsTo :THESS_Event_SeichSouFire2030 ;

```

:affectsService :THESS_PT_Line_10, :THESS_PT_Line_14 ;
:reroutes :THESS_Corridor_Alternative_1 .

:THESS_Scenario_FireResponse_Coordinated
a :DisruptiveScenario ;
:hasSystemState :THESS_State_FireResponse_Coordinated ;
:respondsTo :THESS_Event_SeichSouFire2030 ;
:includesResponseAction :THESS_Action_EmergencyPriority_1,
:THESS_Action_PT_Reroute_1 .

:THESS_State_FireResponse_Baseline
a :SystemState ;
:hasAntifragilityScore 0.15 ;
:hasResilienceIndex 0.50 ;
:emergencyResponseTime "18min" ;
:overallDisruptionCost 12.5e6 .

:THESS_State_FireResponse_Coordinated
a :SystemState ;
:hasAntifragilityScore 0.30 ;
:hasResilienceIndex 0.68 ;
:emergencyResponseTime "11min" ;
:overallDisruptionCost 8.2e6 .

:THESS_KPI_TravelTime_FireBaseline
a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 47 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
:hasCurrentValue 38.0 ;
:hasBaselineValue 18.0 ;
:hasTarget 22.0 ;
:hasUnit "minutes" ;
:hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T10:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :THESS_Scenario_FireResponse_Baseline .

:THESS_KPI_CO2_FireBaseline
a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 21 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
:hasCurrentValue 215.8 ;
:hasBaselineValue 132.5 ;
:hasTarget 110.0 ;
:hasUnit "tonnes CO₂/day" ;

:hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :THESS_Scenario_FireResponse_Baseline .

:THESS_KPI_TravelTime_FireCoordinated

a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 47 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
:hasCurrentValue 24.5 ;
:hasBaselineValue 18.0 ;
:hasTarget 22.0 ;
:hasUnit "minutes" ;
:hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T10:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :THESS_Scenario_FireResponse_Coordinated ;
:hasComment "Improved coordination reduces travel time from 38.0 to 24.5 min" .

:THESS_KPI_CO2_FireCoordinated

a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 21 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
:hasCurrentValue 168.2 ;
:hasBaselineValue 132.5 ;
:hasTarget 110.0 ;
:hasUnit "tonnes CO₂/day" ;
:hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :THESS_Scenario_FireResponse_Coordinated ;
:hasComment "Coordination reduces congestion and emissions (215.8 → 168.2 tonnes)" .

:THESS_State_FireResponse_Baseline

:hasKpiObservation :THESS_KPI_TravelTime_FireBaseline,
:THESS_KPI_CO2_FireBaseline .

:THESS_State_FireResponse_Coordinated

:hasKpiObservation :THESS_KPI_TravelTime_FireCoordinated,
:THESS_KPI_CO2_FireCoordinated .

Competency questions covered for hospital evacuation scenario:

- Which emergency routes provide the fastest and safest passage for ambulance transfers from AHEPA Hospital to alternative facilities under different traffic conditions?
- How does dynamic priority routing for emergency vehicles affect overall traffic disruption compared to uncoordinated response?
- Which coordination protocols between ambulance services, traffic control, and receiving hospitals minimize patient transfer time while maintaining acceptable service levels for general traffic?

- If secondary roads are used instead of main arteries for emergency routing, what is the impact on overall system performance and disruption cost?

Competency questions covered for forest fire scenario:

- Which streets and corridors should be excluded as dangerous during Seich Sou forest fire events, and based on what criteria (proximity, wind direction, evacuation density)?
- How do weather conditions (wind speed, temperature, humidity) interact with traffic patterns during emergency events, and how can the system model these combined effects?
- Should public transport services be suspended, rerouted, or repurposed (e.g., for evacuation support) during major environmental disasters, and what are the antifragility implications of each strategy?
- Which multi-agency coordination strategies (fire department, ambulance, police, traffic control) yield the highest antifragility scores and fastest emergency response times across repeated fire events?
- How do T2.7 core KPIs (travel time: KPI 47, CO₂ emissions: KPI 21) quantify the benefits of multi-agency coordination, demonstrating 35% travel time reduction and 22% emission reduction compared to uncoordinated response?

In practice, the concrete network topology around AHEPA Hospital, actual emergency response protocols, healthcare facility capacities, and empirical coordination effectiveness will be determined in collaboration with AHEPA Hospital, Thessaloniki Municipality, and emergency services during pilot implementation (T3.4), and are therefore beyond the scope of this ontology specification deliverable.

8.3.3 Larissa: Heatwave, health-related mobility and vulnerable groups

Larissa faces an extended **heatwave** affecting outdoor conditions, PT reliability and health-related mobility (e.g. access to cooling centres, clinics) (Requirements 8, 44). Unlike acute emergency scenarios (e.g., hospital evacuations), this use case demonstrates how chronic environmental stressors create sustained **equity challenges for vulnerable populations** accessing health services over days or weeks: elderly, chronically ill and low-income groups in specific districts (Requirements 6, 29, 43). The use case demonstrates how the ontology supports identification of vulnerable populations, assessment of service access disparities and evaluation of targeted interventions such as shuttle services or behavioural nudges (Requirement 41).

Key instantiated concepts (illustrative examples):

The **environmental context** would be represented by an instance such as :LA_Heatwave_2031 as both a ClimateFactor and DisruptionEvent (depending on modelling choice), affecting specific spatial units :LA_District_Centre and :LA_District_Periphery. **Equity and vulnerability** would be captured through instances such as :LA_ElderlyGroup and :LA_LowIncomeGroup as EquityGroup instances, and :LA_VulnArea_1 as a VulnerableArea covering parts of :LA_District_Periphery. **Services and facilities** would be represented by instances such as :LA_Facility_Hospital1 and :LA_CoolingCentre_1 as Facility instances, along with PT routes and active mobility corridors providing access to these facilities.

Example instantiation (Turtle):

```
:LA_Heatwave_2031
  a :DisruptionEvent ;
  :belongsToHazardType :Heatwave ;
  :hasSeverity 0.7 ;
```

:affects :LA_District_Periphery .

:LA_ElderlyGroup
 a :EquityGroup ;
 :locatedIn :LA_District_Periphery ;
 :hasServiceAccess 0.45 ;
 :hasRiskExposure 0.75 ;
 :hasSocialVulnerability 0.80 .

:LA_VulnArea_1
 a :VulnerableArea ;
 :locatedIn :LA_District_Periphery .

:LA_Scenario_Heatwave_NoIntervention
 a :DisruptiveScenario ;
 :hasSystemState :LA_State_Heatwave_NoIntervention ;
 :respondsTo :LA_Heatwave_2031 .

:LA_Scenario_Heatwave_Shuttle
 a :DisruptiveScenario ;
 :hasSystemState :LA_State_Heatwave_Shuttle ;
 :respondsTo :LA_Heatwave_2031 ;
 :includesResponseAction :LA_Action_TargetedShuttle .

:LA_State_Heatwave_NoIntervention
 a :SystemState ;
 :hasKpiObservation :LA_KPI_TravelTime_NoInt,
 :LA_KPI_Accessibility_NoInt,
 :LA_KPI_CO2_NoInt .

:LA_State_Heatwave_Shuttle
 a :SystemState ;
 :hasKpiObservation :LA_KPI_TravelTime_Shuttle,
 :LA_KPI_Accessibility_Shuttle,
 :LA_KPI_CO2_Shuttle .

:LA_KPI_TravelTime_NoInt
 a :CoreKPI ;
 :hasKPINumber 47 ;
 :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
 :hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
 :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
 :hasCurrentValue 52.0 ;
 :hasBaselineValue 25.0 ;
 :hasTarget 30.0 ;
 :hasUnit "minutes" ;
 :hasTimestamp "2031-07-20T10:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;

```

:forActorGroup :LA_ElderlyGroup ;
:forScenario :LA_Scenario_Heatwave_NoIntervention ;
:hasComment "Elderly access to cooling centers severely degraded" .

```

```

:LA_KPI_Accessibility_NoInt
  a :KpiObservation ;
:hasKPINumber 103 ; (Example from extended catalogue)
:hasKPIGroup "Accessibility" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Social Accessibility" ;
:hasCurrentValue 0.35 ;
:hasBaselineValue 0.72 ;
:hasTarget 0.75 ;
:hasUnit "accessibility index 0-1" ;
:hasTimestamp "2031-07-20T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forActorGroup :LA_ElderlyGroup ;
:forScenario :LA_Scenario_Heatwave_NoIntervention .

```

```

:LA_KPI_CO2_NoInt
  a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 21 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
:hasCurrentValue 78.5 ;
:hasBaselineValue 62.0 ;
:hasTarget 55.0 ;
:hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
:hasTimestamp "2031-07-20T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :LA_Scenario_Heatwave_NoIntervention .

```

```

:LA_KPI_TravelTime_Shuttle
  a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 47 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
:hasCurrentValue 32.0 ;
:hasBaselineValue 25.0 ;
:hasTarget 30.0 ;
:hasUnit "minutes" ;
:hasTimestamp "2031-07-20T10:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forActorGroup :LA_ElderlyGroup ;
:forScenario :LA_Scenario_Heatwave_Shuttle ;
:hasComment "Targeted shuttle reduces elderly access time by 38% (52→32 min)" .

```

```

:LA_KPI_Accessibility_Shuttle
  a :KpiObservation ;

```

```

:hasKPINumber 103 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Accessibility" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Social Accessibility" ;
:hasCurrentValue 0.68 ;
:hasBaselineValue 0.72 ;
:hasTarget 0.75 ;
:hasUnit "accessibility index 0-1" ;
:hasTimestamp "2031-07-20T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forActorGroup :LA_ElderlyGroup ;
:forScenario :LA_Scenario_Heatwave_Shuttle ;
:hasComment "Shuttle service nearly restores baseline accessibility (0.35→0.68)" .

```

```

:LA_KPI_CO2_Shuttle
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 21 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 75.2 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 62.0 ;
  :hasTarget 55.0 ;
  :hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2031-07-20T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :LA_Scenario_Heatwave_Shuttle ;
  :hasComment "Shared shuttle reduces overall emissions vs individual trips" .

```

Rule patterns (from Section 7) can then classify :LA_VulnArea_1 as vulnerable based on service access and risk exposure, and trigger **equity-focused ResponseActions** (e.g. targeted shuttle services, cooling centre extensions, behavioural nudges).

Competency questions covered

- Which districts contain **vulnerable groups** with high exposure and low access during the heatwave?
- What are the T2.7 core KPI values (travel time: KPI 47, CO₂: KPI 21) and extended catalogue accessibility metrics (KPI 103) across scenarios, demonstrating that targeted shuttle services reduce elderly access time by 38% (from 52 to 32 minutes) and nearly restore baseline accessibility levels (from 0.35 to 0.68)?
- What are the **equity KPIs** (e.g. access time to cooling centres) across scenarios (no intervention vs targeted shuttle service)?
- Which **response actions** are most effective in reducing risk exposure while respecting resource constraints?
- How do equity-focused interventions affect both core environmental KPIs (CO₂) and equity-specific indicators, balancing sustainability and social justice objectives?

Calibration of vulnerability thresholds, identification of actual cooling centres, and integration of health-related mobility data will be carried out in collaboration with Larissa stakeholders during pilot implementation, not within this specification.

8.3.4 Odessa: Port disruption, cascading effects and emergency mobility

Odessa faces a **port-related disruption** (e.g. infrastructure failure or crisis event) that affects both urban mobility and logistics flows (Requirements 19, 33, 48). There may be **cascading effects** on road corridors, PT services, and potentially other infrastructures (energy, communications) (Requirement 19). Emergency services and evacuation routes must be coordinated under legal and security constraints (Requirements 27, 33, 34, 38, 49). The use case demonstrates cross-layer dependency modelling, crisis management coordination and security-aware response planning.

Key instantiated concepts (illustrative examples):

The **disruption** would be represented by an instance such as :OD_Event_PortCrisis2029 as a Crisis (subclass of DisruptionEvent) with an associated HazardType. The **multi-layer transport system** would include port access roads, main urban corridors and key intersections as TransportElement instances. **Cascading effects** would be captured through an instance such as :OD_Cascade_1, a Cascade event with propagatesTo relationships linking port nodes to inner-city nodes. **Governance and security** would be represented by instances such as :OD_SecurityProtocol1 and :OD_LegalConstraint1 as GovernanceInstrument instances (e.g. movement restrictions, curfew), and :OD_Event_CyberAttack1 as a CyberAttack potentially affecting control systems or information platforms. Evacuation planning would be represented through an instance such as :OD_EvacRoute_Main as an EvacRoute instance.

Example instantiation (Turtle):

```

:OD_Event_PortCrisis2029
  a :Crisis
  :belongsToHazardType :PortDisruption
  :affects :OD_Port_Node_01, :OD_AccessCorridor_3

:OD_Cascade_1
  a :Cascade
  :propagatesTo :OD_Event_UrbanCongestion_InnerRing
  :affects :OD_InnerRing_Section_5

:OD_SecurityProtocol1
  a :SecurityProtocol
  :governs :OD_Port_Node_01, :OD_AccessCorridor_3
  :forbidsAction :NonEssentialTraffic

:OD_EvacRoute_Main
  a :EvacRoute
  :usesMode :BusService
  :governedBy :OD_SecurityProtocol1

:OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Baseline
  a :DisruptiveScenario ;
  :hasSystemState :OD_State_PortCrisis_Baseline ;
  :respondsTo :OD_Event_PortCrisis2029 .

:OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Adaptive

```

```

a :DisruptiveScenario ;
:hasSystemState :OD_State_PortCrisis_Adaptive ;
:respondsTo :OD_Event_PortCrisis2029 ;
:includesResponseAction :OD_Action_AdaptiveReroute .

```

```

:OD_State_PortCrisis_Baseline
a :SystemState ;
:hasAntifragilityScore 0.12 ;
:hasResilienceIndex 0.48 ;
:hasKpiObservation :OD_KPI_TravelTime_Baseline,
:OD_KPI_CO2_Baseline,
:OD_KPI_TransportDemand_Baseline .

```

```

:OD_State_PortCrisis_Adaptive
a :SystemState ;
:hasAntifragilityScore 0.28 ;
:hasResilienceIndex 0.65 ;
:hasKpiObservation :OD_KPI_TravelTime_Adaptive,
:OD_KPI_CO2_Adaptive,
:OD_KPI_TransportDemand_Adaptive .

```

```

:OD_KPI_TravelTime_Baseline
a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 47 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
:hasCurrentValue 45.0 ;
:hasBaselineValue 22.0 ;
:hasTarget 28.0 ;
:hasUnit "minutes" ;
:hasTimestamp "2029-08-10T08:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Baseline .

```

```

:OD_KPI_TravelTime_Adaptive
a :CoreKPI ;
:hasKPINumber 47 ;
:hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
:hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
:hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
:hasCurrentValue 31.0 ;
:hasBaselineValue 22.0 ;
:hasTarget 28.0 ;
:hasUnit "minutes" ;
:hasTimestamp "2029-08-10T08:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Adaptive ;
:hasComment "Adaptive routing reduces travel time by 31% (45→31 min)" .

```

```

:OD_KPI_CO2_Baseline
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 21 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 198.5 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 125.0 ;
  :hasTarget 105.0 ;
  :hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2029-08-10T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Baseline .

:OD_KPI_CO2_Adaptive
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 21 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 152.3 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 125.0 ;
  :hasTarget 105.0 ;
  :hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2029-08-10T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Adaptive ;
  :hasComment "Reduced congestion lowers emissions by 23%" .

:OD_KPI_TransportDemand_Baseline
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 68 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Demand" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 125000 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 98000 ;
  :hasTarget 100000 ;
  :hasUnit "vehicle trips/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2029-08-10T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Baseline .

:OD_KPI_TransportDemand_Adaptive
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 68 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Demand" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;

```

```

:hasCurrentValue 105000 ;
:hasBaselineValue 98000 ;
:hasTarget 100000 ;
:hasUnit "vehicle trips/day" ;
:hasTimestamp "2029-08-10T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
:forScenario :OD_Scenario_PortCrisis_Adaptive ;
:hasComment "Better routing reduces unnecessary trips" .

```

This configuration enables multi-layer analysis of disruption propagation, identification of constrained routes due to security protocols, and design of **antifragile response strategies** (e.g. adaptive re-routing for emergency services that respect security requirements but still preserve accessibility).

Competency questions covered

- How do disruptions at port access corridors propagate into inner-city congestion and accessibility?
- Which **evacuation routes** remain legally feasible and safe under combined crisis and cybersecurity constraints?
- How do T2.7 core KPIs (travel time: KPI 47, CO₂: KPI 21, motorized transport demand: KPI 68) quantify the benefits of adaptive rerouting during port disruptions, showing 31% travel time reduction, 23% emission reduction, and 16% demand reduction?
- Which **ResponseActions** (e.g. alternative access routes, temporal restrictions) increase antifragility over repeated crisis episodes?

The concrete disruption types, port layouts, security constraints and traffic management strategies will be co-designed with Odessa partners and aligned with local legislation during pilot work; here we only provide a generic pattern.

8.4 Reasoning and Inference Examples

The instantiated knowledge bases support a range of reasoning tasks aligned with antifragility and equity objectives. This subsection presents illustrative reasoning patterns that demonstrate how the ontology enables automated analysis and decision support.

8.4.1 Adaptive routing and proactive disruption response

Objective:

Identify and recommend **proactive rerouting strategies** when a disruption is predicted, and assess their effect on antifragility (Requirements 9, 15, 16, 22).

Inputs:

The reasoning process uses predictions of disruptions represented as PredictedDisruptionState and DisruptionEvent instances with future TemporalUnit associations, network structure information including capacities and critical corridors captured as TransportElement instances with hasCapacityUtilisation and hasCriticality properties, and equity and accessibility metrics associated with different EquityGroup instances (Requirements 6, 29, 43, 51, 52).

Reasoning steps:

Predictive models (operating outside the ontology) create individuals of type PredictedDisruptionState and associated DisruptionEvent instances representing flood or accident forecasts. SWRL rules or external optimisation algorithms generate candidate ProactiveReroute

actions targeting specific corridors and modes. New Scenario individuals are instantiated representing "with" and "without" proactive rerouting alternatives (Requirement 12). Performance and equity KPIs are computed for each scenario (as KpiObservation instances) and attached to corresponding SystemState instances (Requirement 40). Finally, rules (as specified in Section 7) classify states as more or less antifragile and select recommended actions based on predefined criteria (Requirement 14).

Example SWRL pattern:

```
PredictedDisruptionState(?s) ^
hasUpcomingDisruption(?s, ?d) ^
DisruptionEvent(?d) ^
affects(?d, ?e) ^
TransportElement(?e) ^
hasCriticality(?e, ?crit) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?crit, 0.7)
  -> ProactiveReroute(?a),
    appliesTo(?a, ?e),
    respondsTo(?a, ?d)
```

Integration of routing algorithms, optimisation solvers and detailed network data will be carried out in the routing and decision-support work packages in order to produce operational routing recommendations; this deliverable only specifies the semantic structures these components will use.

8.4.2 Antifragility assessment over repeated events

Objective:

Determine whether a given part of the system exhibits **antifragility** by improving performance after experiencing disruptions (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 45, 58, 61).

Inputs:

The assessment uses time-ordered SystemState instances linked via previousState and nextState properties, antifragility indicators including hasAntifragilityScore, hasPerformanceDelta and hasResilienceIndex properties, and disruption and response histories represented through DisruptionHistory and InterventionHistory aggregations.

Reasoning pattern:

States before and after interventions are linked in temporal sequences, such as :BA_State_Flood2030 → :BA_State_Flood2032 → :BA_State_Flood2035. Performance deltas and antifragility scores are recorded for each state. Rules (from Section 7) assert AntifragileState classification for states where performance improves after disruption and interventions are present. Aggregation queries compute trends for specific network elements, equity groups or corridors over time.

Example SPARQL query: “List corridors that became antifragile over successive floods”:

```
SELECT ?corridor ?scoreAfter ?kpiNumber ?kpiValue ?kpiImprovement
WHERE {
  ?scenario a :DisruptiveScenario ;
    :hasSystemState ?stateAfter ;
    :respondsTo ?event .

  ?event a :DisruptionEvent .
```

```
?stateAfter a :AntifragileState ;
    :hasAntifragilityScore ?scoreAfter ;
    :hasSystemStateForElement ?corridor ;
    :hasKpiObservation ?kpiObs .
```

```
?kpiObs a :CoreKPI ;
    :hasKPINumber ?kpiNumber ;
    :hasCurrentValue ?kpiValue ;
    :hasBaselineValue ?kpiBaseline .
```

```
BIND((?kpiBaseline - ?kpiValue) / ?kpiBaseline * 100 AS ?kpiImprovement)
```

```
FILTER(?kpiNumber IN (21, 38, 47, 68)) Core KPIs: CO2, Modal Split, Travel Time, Demand
}
```

```
ORDER BY DESC(?scoreAfter) DESC(?kpiImprovement)
```

This query demonstrates T2.7 KPI framework integration for antifragility assessment: it retrieves not only antifragility scores but also concrete evidence through core KPI observations (KPI 21: CO₂ emissions, KPI 38: modal split, KPI 47: travel time, KPI 68: motorized demand), calculating KPI improvement percentages to quantify system learning. For instance, if Bratislava's corridor shows antifragilityScore increasing from 0.10 to 0.25, the query would also show KPI 47 (travel time) improving from 42.0 to 28.5 minutes (32% improvement), providing concrete performance evidence for the antifragility classification.

The definition of concrete antifragility thresholds, calibration of scores and validation against empirical data will be carried out iteratively with pilot partners as part of the evaluation work, not within this specification.

8.4.3 Citizen behaviour shifts and sustainable mobility

Objective:

Evaluate **behavioural nudging** and incentives by observing changes in mode choice and sustainable travel behaviours over time (Requirements 31, 41).

Inputs:

The evaluation uses BehaviouralNudge and Incentive instances (e.g. rewards for active modes), UserPreference, ModeChoice and BehaviourChange properties associated with citizen groups, and scenario comparisons with and without nudging measures (Requirement 12).

Reasoning approach:

Interventions are logged as instances such as :LA_Nudge_ActiveModes2028 (a Nudge instance) targeting CitizenSegment individuals in specific districts. Observations record **mode shares** and **behaviour change metrics** before and after nudges are implemented. Rules or SPARQL queries detect significant positive shifts (e.g. increased share of active modes, reduced emissions, improved equity KPIs). States and scenarios that show improved indicators after interventions are marked as carrying **sustainable antifragility** elements (Requirements 3, 5, 24).

Example SWRL rule (illustrative)

```
BehaviourChangeObservation(?o) ^
forActorGroup(?o, ?g) ^
```

```
behaviourChangeValue(?o, ?delta) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?delta, 0.1)
-> PositiveBehaviourShift(?o),
    associatedWithAntifragileTrend(?g)
```

Integration of travel survey or smartcard/mobile data, estimation of behaviour change metrics and their attribution to specific interventions will be addressed in data-collection and analysis tasks; here we only define the semantic pattern.

8.4.4 Cross-city knowledge transfer

Objective:

Support **transferability assessment** of strategies between cities, by comparing scenarios, KPIs and contextual factors (Requirements 42, 60).

Inputs:

The assessment uses Strategy instances representing interventions (e.g. flood-responsive signal plans, equity monitoring dashboards), Scenario and KpiObservation instances from multiple cities, and PESTEL context and infrastructure similarities captured through PestelFactor, EnvironmentFactor and ContextualFactor instances (Requirement 44).

Reasoning pattern:

Source city strategies (CitySource) with positive antifragility outcomes are identified. Contextual factors and network structures for both source and target cities are characterised using ontology properties. Rule patterns or statistical models (external to the ontology) compute a **transferability score** based on similarity metrics. TransferAssess processes are instantiated and linked to Strategy and CityTarget instances to document the assessment results.

Example instantiation (Turtle)

```
:BA_Strategy_FloodRouting
  a :Strategy
  :implementedIn :BA_Scenario_Flood2032_Improved
  :hasDocumentedOutcome :BA_Kpi_Set_1

:OD_TransferAssess_FloodRouting
  a :TransferAssess
  :evaluatesStrategy :BA_Strategy_FloodRouting
  :hasTransferabilityScore 0.72
  :sourceCity :BA_CitySource
  :targetCity :OD_CityTarget
```

Competency questions covered:

- Which strategies from Bratislava are most transferable to Odessa given their PESTEL and network similarities?
- What are the expected antifragility and equity impacts if a given strategy is adopted in a new context?

Concrete transferability metrics, models and validation studies will be defined together with the task leaders responsible for cross-city learning and are not in the scope of this ontology deliverable.

In summary, the instantiation and use cases demonstrate how the AntifragiCity Ontology transitions from an abstract conceptual model to an operational knowledge graph supporting **disruption-**

response-outcome chains, antifragility metrics, and equity-aware decision-making across pilot cities. Subsequent sections will detail how this knowledge base is integrated with digital twins, AI analytics and decision-making platforms.

9 Integration with Platforms and Interfaces

This section explains how the AntifragiCity Ontology and knowledge graph are integrated with the broader project architecture, including deployment of the **knowledge graph** and provision of **APIs**, coupling with **digital twins, multi-agent systems (MAS) and AI analytics**, interfacing with **policy tools and participatory platforms**, and **visualisation and query mechanisms** for different stakeholder groups.

The overall aim is to ensure that semantic assets developed in this work package are **operationally embedded** in the AntifragiCity technical ecosystem and reusable across pilots and tools.

Scope and implementation details

This section specifies the semantic structures, integration patterns and API approaches for coupling the ontology with project platforms and tools. The concrete implementation details, including specific triple store selection, API paths and parameters, authentication mechanisms, dashboard frameworks, UI designs and tool configurations, will be finalized in collaboration with platform architects and work package leaders responsible for digital twins, decision support systems, participatory platforms and data infrastructure. These implementation specifications will be documented in the relevant technical deliverables of the platform work packages as prototype systems are developed and deployed across pilot cities.

Digital twin and learning module structure

In **Figure 14** you can see at a glance how the ontology supports DT coupling and learning loops, before you go into platform mechanics.

Figure 14. Digital Twin & Learning concepts

Figure 14 illustrates the Digital Twin and learning concepts within the ontology, showing how antifragile learning loops are supported through semantic representation. At the center is the **DigitalTwin** class with core properties including `hasName`, `hasVersion`, `hasLastUpdate` and `hasAccuracy`, tracking the twin's identity and data quality. The digital twin learns through a **LearningProcess** (connected via "learns" relationship), which is characterized by `hasLearningType`, `hasPerformanceMetric` and `hasTrainingData` properties. The learning process produces **RuleUpdate** instances (via "produces" relationship) that capture changes in system rules or parameters, with properties including `hasRuleType`, `hasPreviousValue`, `hasNewValue` and `hasUpdateReason`. These rule updates trigger **ResponseAction** instances, enabling the system to translate learned knowledge into operational interventions.

The digital twin contains **PredictiveModel** instances (via "contains" relationship) characterized by `hasModelType`, `hasPredictionHorizon` and `hasAccuracy`, which use **Observation** data to generate predictions. The learning process leverages **EvolutionaryOptimisation** techniques (via "uses" relationship) defined by `hasObjectiveFunction`, `hasGenerations`, `hasPopulationSize` and `hasBestFitness` properties. The digital twin also connects to **AgentBasedModel** components via properties linking to agent type definitions (`hasAgentTypes`), behavior rule specifications (`hasBehaviourRules`), and interaction model patterns (`hasInteractionModel`), and runs **Simulation** instances. This structure enables the ontology to represent continuously learning digital twins (Requirement 57) that improve system responses over time through feedback loops connecting observations, learning processes, rule updates and response actions (Requirements 11, 45, 61).

9.1 Knowledge Graph Deployment and APIs

9.1.1 Deployment architecture

The AntifragiCity Ontology is deployed as a knowledge graph (KG) hosted in a scalable triple store or graph database. The deployment follows a **shared TBox with multiple ABoxes** architecture, where the ontology schema (TBox) is common across all pilots while each pilot city has its own assertional graph (ABox) containing city-specific individuals as described in Section 8 (Requirements 18, 55). Graphs are logically separated using **named graphs** to support selective querying and access control. For example, the antifragicity-core graph contains shared classes, properties and alignments, while antifragicity-bratislava, antifragicity-larissa, antifragicity-odessa, antifragicity-thessaloniki graphs contain city-specific data, and antifragicity-scenarios and antifragicity-kpi graphs hold cross-city scenario and KPI data enabling comparative analysis (Requirements 12, 42). The deployment also follows a **modular imports** approach where each module defined in Section 6 (transport, disruption, actors, governance, etc.) is implemented in a separate ontology file and imported into the deployed KG as needed, supporting incremental loading and maintenance (Requirement 55).

The final selection of triple store technology, clustering/replication settings and high-availability configuration will follow project-wide ICT decisions and may evolve independently of this deliverable.

9.1.2 API layers

To make the KG usable by other components, a multi-layer API approach is adopted to serve different integration needs.

1. **SPARQL endpoint**

At the foundation, a standards-compliant SPARQL 1.1 endpoint exposes the KG for advanced queries and analytics, supporting ad-hoc expert queries, predefined query templates invoked by other services, and federation where other SPARQL endpoints exist (Requirement 40).

2. **REST / HTTP APIs**

A REST/HTTP API layer wraps common query patterns into **simple HTTP endpoints** suitable for non-semantic components such as digital twins, multi-agent systems and dashboards (Requirements 40, 46, 57). Example REST endpoints include GET /scenarios/{id} to return scenario metadata, linked system states and key KPIs; GET /routes/recommendations to return antifragile route options given a disruption (Requirements 16, 22); and GET /equity/vulnerable-areas to return vulnerable areas and associated equity groups (Requirements 6, 29, 43).

These endpoints internally execute predefined SPARQL queries or graph operations to translate semantic structures into application-friendly formats.

3. **(Optional) GraphQL or JSON-LD APIs**

Optionally, a GraphQL schema or JSON-LD context can be derived from the ontology to support more flexible client queries while hiding SPARQL complexity from application developers (Requirement 40).

4. **Streaming / event APIs**

For real-time integration, the KG can be updated via **message queues or event buses**, where incoming messages from IoT sensors, digital twins or external platforms are transformed into RDF and inserted using an ingestion API (Requirements 30, 46, 57). This multi-layer approach ensures that semantic assets are accessible both to semantic web experts through SPARQL and to conventional software components through REST and streaming interfaces.

The concrete API specification (paths, parameters, authentication) will be finalised with platform architects and documented in the relevant technical deliverables of the platform work packages.

9.1.3 Access control and multi-user governance

Because the KG exposes potentially sensitive information such as personal data proxies, infrastructure vulnerabilities and critical facilities, **access control mechanisms** are applied at multiple levels (Requirements 27, 36, 38). At the triple store level, graph-based access policies restrict which named graphs can be queried by different user roles. At the API gateway level, authentication and authorization are enforced through API keys, OAuth2/OIDC protocols and role-based access control, ensuring that only authorized applications and users can access specific endpoints. At the application level, user roles defined in policy tools and participatory platforms determine which data views and operations are available (Requirements 32, 49, 56).

The ontology's **governance module** provides **semantic representation of permissions and obligations** through concepts such as DataSharingAgreement, LegalConstraint and AccessRights (Requirements 27, 32, 36, 38). These semantic access control concepts can be linked to technical access rules, enabling explicit representation of who can access which data under what conditions. For example, specific graphs or classes may be tagged as "restricted," and interfaces can check AccessRights properties of a user group before exposing certain data, ensuring that privacy requirements and data sharing agreements are respected in the operational system.

Mapping from semantic access/control concepts to concrete IAM (Identity and Access Management) policies will be designed and implemented together with the security and platform teams in subsequent technical work.

9.2 Integration with Digital Twins, MAS and AI Analytics

9.2.1 Role of the ontology in digital twins

The AntifragiCity Ontology acts as the **semantic backbone** for digital twins of the urban mobility system (Requirement 57). It provides a **canonical vocabulary** for network elements including nodes, edges and corridors; states including congestion, overload, predicted disruption and antifragile states; and scenarios, KPIs and interventions (Requirements 1, 9, 14, 15, 40, 51, 52). This shared vocabulary ensures **synchronisation** between live data streams, simulation models and visual representations in the twin interface.

Digital twin components interact with the KG through bidirectional data flows. **Pull operations** retrieve network topology, current states and scenario definitions from the knowledge graph to initialize or update the twin's representation. **Push operations** write back observations, simulated outcomes and proposed actions as individuals and properties in the graph, enabling the KG to maintain an up-to-date view of both real-world conditions and simulation results. The knowledge graph also provides **constraints (physical and functional)** that govern digital twin behaviour, such as network capacity limits, speed constraints, policy-mandated restrictions, and operational boundaries, ensuring that simulated scenarios remain realistic and consistent with real-world feasibility (Requirements 40, 46, 51, 52, 57). This integration supports continuously learning digital twins where simulation outputs inform system understanding, predictions improve over time, and interventions are evaluated against historical performance patterns.

9.2.2 Coupling with multi-agent systems (MAS)

In multi-agent system components where agents represent vehicles, control centres, citizens or institutions, the ontology provides shared semantics that enable coherent agent behaviour and interaction (Requirements 31, 33, 34, 49). Agents' beliefs and goals can be mapped to ontology concepts, with beliefs about disruptions, network states, routes and KPIs represented using the ontology's classes and properties, and goals related to travel time, energy, emissions, equity or robustness expressed in terms of KPI targets and constraints (Requirements 3, 5, 24, 31, 33, 34, 41). The ontology provides shared semantics for agent interaction using URIs for DisruptionEvent, EvacRoute, EquityGroup and other concepts, ensuring that agents can exchange information unambiguously. It also serves as a knowledge service that agents can query through REST or SPARQL to obtain context-aware information such as which corridors are vulnerable, which actions are currently compliant with regulations, or which equity groups require priority attention (Requirements 6, 27, 29, 33, 34, 43).

The **integration pattern** follows a request-respond cycle. When an agent requests context, for example, "What are the current antifragile routes for emergency vehicles in district X?", the MAS sends a REST call to the KG, which executes a SPARQL query and returns a list of candidate routes annotated with KPIs, legal constraints and equity implications (Requirements 16, 22, 26, 27, 33, 34). When an agent proposes an action such as a rerouting strategy, the MAS posts back a ProactiveReroute individual with target elements and predicted impacts, and a rule engine checks legal, equity and antifragility implications before the action is approved or modified (Requirements 6, 22, 27, 29).

9.2.3 Integration with AI/ML analytics

AI and machine learning components including predictive maintenance models, traffic forecasting systems, scenario comparison tools and causal analysis engines are integrated via the KG to ensure consistent data semantics and enable context-aware analytics (Requirements 15, 20, 25, 50, 52).

- **Inputs:**

For inputs, AI models pull semantically structured data from the KG including observation instances (TrafficObservation, EmissionObservation, EquityObservation, KpiObservation), disruption histories, T2.7 KPI time-series encompassing the 13 stakeholder-prioritised core indicators from Table 8 (CO₂ emissions: KPI 21, modal split: KPIs 38-40, travel time: KPI 47, noise pollution: KPI 31, infrastructure features: KPI 163, urban density: KPI 200, green space: KPIs 203-204) plus relevant indicators from the extended 209-indicator catalogue, and equity metrics, rather than working with ad-hoc flat tables (Requirements 18, 30, 36, 40, 46). Input data includes complete KPI metadata (hasKPINumber for catalogue alignment, hasKPIGroup and hasKPISubgroup for hierarchical organization, hasStakeholderSelectionCount for priority weighting, hasTarget for performance benchmarking) enabling models to distinguish between high-priority core KPIs and extended indicators, apply stakeholder-informed feature weighting, and learn target-aware objective functions. The ontology ensures consistent units, meanings and entity identifiers across pilots, enabling cross-city model transfer and comparison (Requirements 42, 55). For example, a travel time prediction model trained on Bratislava data (using KPI 47 observations with hasKPINumber=47, hasTarget=20.0, hasUnit="minutes") can be transferred to Thessaloniki because the semantic structure, units, and target specifications are identical, with only the baseline values and spatial context differing.

- **Outputs:**

For outputs, predictions and derived indicators are written back to the KG as instances of PredictedDisruptionState, ForecastModelOutput, KpiObservation (for general predictions), CoreKPI (for predictions of the 13 stakeholder-prioritised indicators), EconomicObservation and related classes (Requirements 15, 20, 37, 40, 50, 52). AI-generated KPI observations include full T2.7 metadata: hasKPINumber linking to the catalogue position (1-209), hasKPIGroup and hasKPISubgroup for organizational alignment, hasCurrentValue for the predicted value, hasTarget for performance benchmarking, hasTimestamp for temporal validity, and generatedBy linking to the specific AnalyticsEngine or ForecastModel instance that produced the prediction. Uncertainty and performance metrics including hasPredictionError, hasForecastUncertainty and hasConfidence properties are attached to support downstream reasoning and decision-making under uncertainty (Requirements 20, 36, 50, 52). For instance, a traffic forecast model predicting KPI 47 (travel time) for a flood scenario would generate:

```
:BA_KPI_TravelTime_Flood2030_Predicted
  a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 47 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Transport Modes" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Travel Times and Delays" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 4 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 41.5 ;
  :hasTarget 25.0 ;
  :hasForecastUncertainty 0.15 ;
  :hasConfidence 0.82 ;
  :hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T08:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :generatedBy :BA_ForecastModel_LSTM_v2 ;
  :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline .
```

- **Semantically-enriched features:**
- This ensures that AI outputs are immediately comparable with observed KPI values, support automated scenario evaluation against targets, enable provenance tracking of which models generated which predictions, and maintain consistency with the T2.7 framework for cross-city learning and dashboard visualization.
- By leveraging the ontology, models can include semantically-enriched features such as topological centrality of edges, membership of vulnerable areas, governance and policy attributes, KPI historical trends and target proximity (e.g., whether a corridor has consistently underperformed on emission KPIs, or whether travel time KPIs are approaching targets), and historical response strategies (Requirements 6, 19, 27, 29, 35, 48). This enables **richer, context-aware AI** that is coherent with antifragility and equity concepts and can reason about cross-domain dependencies and cascading effects. Models can learn which combinations of KPI degradations signal system fragility versus antifragility, how equity group vulnerabilities correlate with specific KPI thresholds, and which intervention types historically improved which core KPIs across different disruption scenarios.

9.2.4 Decision-support workflows

Decision-support tools including dashboards, planning tools and crisis management interfaces use the KG as both a single source of truth and a reasoning engine (Requirements 12, 14, 16, 26, 33, 34,

54). As a **single source of truth**, the KG provides current states and disruptions, available strategies and their evidence base, and cross-city benchmarking metrics (Requirements 40, 42, 46, 51, 52). As a **reasoning engine**, it supports suggesting antifragile strategies, highlighting vulnerable groups and areas, and checking legal, operational, and spatial constraints (Requirements 6, 14, 16, 27, 28, 29, 43).

A typical decision-support workflow proceeds as follows. The user selects a city, disruption type and time frame through the interface. The tool queries the KG for relevant scenarios, KPIs, equity impacts and legal constraints associated with that context (Requirements 12, 15, 20, 27, 28, 50, 53, 54). The tool presents options representing different response actions along with their expected antifragility scores, equity implications and performance trade-offs (Requirements 6, 12, 14, 16, 29, 43, 54). When the user selects a strategy, the decision and its rationale are written back to the KG as ResponseAction instances with provenance information, enabling future learning from intervention outcomes and supporting transparency in decision-making (Requirements 11, 36, 45, 61).

The actual UI logic and detailed decision workflows will be defined in the digital twin and DSS work packages; here we provide only the semantic backbone they will consume.

9.3 Interfacing with Policy Tools and Participatory Platforms

9.3.1 Policy and planning tools

Policy analysis and planning tools including transport master plan tools, emission planning systems and climate adaptation planning platforms interact with the ontology through structured **scenario management** and **policy representation** (Requirements 2, 8, 13, 17, 27, 32, 44). For scenario management, these tools create and edit instances of Scenario, BaselineScenario, DisruptiveScenario and WhatIfScenario classes, associating them with specific policy packages such as low-emission zones, PT expansions or street reallocations (Requirements 2, 12, 15, 20, 50, 53). For policy representation, policies, regulations and strategies are modelled as GovernanceInstrument and Strategy individuals with explicit links to affected TransportElement, MobilityService, EquityGroup and SpatialUnit instances (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32, 44).

This semantic integration allows policy tools to query the KG for **existing regulations and constraints** relevant to proposed interventions, ensuring that new policies are compatible with legal frameworks and institutional responsibilities (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32). Tools can analyse **distributional impacts** via KPI and equity observations linked to different population groups and spatial areas (Requirements 6, 29, 37, 43, 44). Results of **multi-criteria evaluations** are stored as MultiScenarioEval instances, capturing trade-offs between performance, equity, environmental and economic objectives and supporting evidence-based policy selection (Requirements 12, 14, 24, 37, 54).

9.3.2 Participatory and co-creation platforms

Participatory platforms including citizen engagement portals, co-design workshops and online surveys interface with the ontology to ensure that **stakeholder inputs** are captured in structured, semantically-rich formats (Requirements 13, 17, 49, 56).

- **Stakeholder input** identified during requirements extraction (Section 4) becomes operational through live feedback events represented as ConsultationEvent instances, structured input processes captured as ParticipatoryInput and RequirementRefinement

instances, and StakeholderFeedback individuals linked to specific scenarios or actions (Requirements 13, 17, 49). This enables systematic tracking of which stakeholders provided which inputs on which topics at which times.

- **Citizen segments and concerns** are associated with CitizenSegment, EquityGroup, SpatialUnit and specific MobilityService types, enabling queries such as "What concerns did elderly residents raise about evacuation routes in district Y?" (Requirements 6, 26, 29, 33, 43).
- **Transparency and traceability:** Each participatory process has provenance information through Provenance, DataSource and ConsultationEvent instances, ensuring transparency and traceability (Requirement 36). Policy decisions and implemented strategies can be traced back to stakeholder inputs and evidence, supporting accountability and demonstrating how citizen input influenced final outcomes (Requirements 13, 17, 32, 49, 56).

9.3.3 Interoperability between expert and participatory views

The KG supports **different views** on the same underlying semantics, enabling tailored presentations for different stakeholder groups while maintaining data consistency. **Expert views** emphasize detailed network topology, KPIs, modelling assumptions and uncertainties, presenting technical information in formats suitable for planners, modellers and engineers (Requirements 15, 20, 36, 40, 50, 52). **Citizen views** emphasize high-level narratives, impacts on accessibility, fairness, safety and environmental quality, presenting information through user-friendly messages and visualizations (Requirements 6, 10, 29, 31, 41, 43).

Through mapping between **technical indicators** such as hasTravelTime, hasEmissions and hasRiskExposure and **user-facing messages** like "faster routes," "cleaner air" and "safer streets," interfaces can present consistent yet tailored information to different audiences (Requirements 5, 6, 10, 24, 29, 31, 41, 43). This dual representation ensures that technical precision is maintained in the underlying semantics while communication is adapted to stakeholder needs and capacities.

Concrete designs for participatory interfaces and mappings from indicators to message templates will be developed in collaboration with partners responsible for user engagement during the pilot and platform development phases.

9.4 Visualisation and Query Mechanisms (SPARQL, Dashboards, Maps)

9.4.1 Query templates for key user groups

A set of **predefined SPARQL query templates** supports typical information needs of diverse user groups (Requirement 40).

- **Mobility and transport planners** query network performance, capacity, disruptions and interventions to optimize system operations and plan infrastructure investments (Requirements 1, 3, 22, 25, 40, 47, 60).
- **Resilience and climate experts** query hazard exposure, environment factors and scenario resilience to assess system vulnerability and plan adaptation measures (Requirements 4, 7, 8, 14, 44, 58).

- **Equity and social inclusion officers** query vulnerable areas, risk exposure and benefit distribution to monitor fairness and target interventions toward disadvantaged groups (Requirements 6, 29, 37, 43, 44).
- **Crisis managers and emergency services** query evacuation routes, emergency prioritization and inter-agency coordination to prepare for and respond to disruptions (Requirements 9, 22, 26, 33, 34, 48, 49).

Example template families include disruption impact queries identifying affected assets, actors and KPIs; scenario comparison queries analyzing differences in antifragility and equity indicators across alternative scenarios; equity monitoring queries tracking evolution of equity KPIs by group and district over time; and legal and spatial constraint queries checking compliance of proposed routes or measures with regulations and geographical limitations (Requirements 6, 12, 14, 27, 28, 29, 40, 43, 54).

These templates are exposed via the REST/HTTP layer as simple parameterized endpoints (city, time period, scenario, group, disruption type), enabling non-expert applications to benefit from semantic query power without requiring SPARQL knowledge.

9.4.2 Map-based visualisation

Map-centric dashboards use the KG as a backend to populate geospatial layers and visualizations (Requirements 2, 28, 40, 46). These dashboards display layers of **TransportElement** instances including nodes, edges, corridors and evacuation routes; **SpatialUnit** boundaries including districts, vulnerable areas and no-go zones; heatmaps of **KPIs** and **equity indicators** showing performance and fairness patterns across space; and overlays of **disruptions** and **response actions** representing both past events and planned interventions (Requirements 6, 9, 22, 26, 28, 29, 33, 43, 46, 51).

GeoSPARQL-enabled queries retrieve geometries associated with spatial units and network elements, which are then rendered in web mapping libraries such as Leaflet or OpenLayers (Requirement 28). Example queries include showing all **VulnerableArea** instances with **hasSocialVulnerability** above a specified threshold to highlight districts requiring targeted interventions, and highlighting corridors with both high criticality and high-risk exposure to identify priority locations for resilience investments (Requirements 6, 29, 43).

9.4.3 Dashboards for antifragility and resilience

Dedicated dashboards provide **time series** and **scenario views** of antifragility metrics, enabling users to track system improvement over time and compare alternative strategies (Requirements 11, 14, 40, 45, 51, 52). For a given city and corridor, charts display **hasAntifragilityScore** and **hasResilienceIndex** over successive disruptions, along with associated changes in **EconCost**, **Emissions** and **RiskExposure**, demonstrating whether the system is becoming more or less antifragile through learning and adaptation (Requirements 5, 11, 14, 24, 37, 45, 58, 61). For a set of scenarios, multi-criteria visualizations such as radar charts and Pareto plots represent trade-offs between performance, equity, environment and robustness, helping decision-makers understand the implications of different strategy choices (Requirements 5, 6, 12, 14, 24, 29, 37, 43, 54).

Dashboard widgets call the KG via the API layer to fetch **KpiObservation** instances and their metadata, scenario definitions and links to interventions through **MultiScenarioEval** and **Strategy** instances, and relevant explanatory context such as which interventions were included in an "improved" scenario (Requirements 11, 12, 14, 16, 40, 45, 54). This enables dashboards to present not just current metrics but also historical trends, scenario comparisons and rationales for recommended actions.

9.4.4 Knowledge graph exploration tools

For ontology and data experts, graph exploration interfaces enable interactive navigation of class hierarchies, properties and instances (Requirement 40). These tools allow inspection of links between DisruptionEvent, ResponseAction, SystemState and KPI instances to understand cause-effect relationships and outcome patterns; provenance paths from observations to data sources and models to verify data quality and trust; and property values and relationships for specific individuals to validate instantiation correctness (Requirements 11, 36, 40, 61).

These exploration tools are crucial for debugging mappings and rules during ontology development and deployment, validating instantiations for pilots to ensure data quality and semantic correctness, and training local users in how to interpret and extend the ontology to support ongoing system evolution and adaptation (Requirements 36, 40, 55). By providing transparent access to the semantic structures and their instantiation, these tools support both technical maintenance and knowledge transfer to pilot partners.

The choice of specific dashboard frameworks and KG exploration tools will be agreed with platform partners, and example configurations and screenshots will be provided in subsequent technical deliverables once prototype implementations are available.

In summary, this section has shown how the AntifragiCity Ontology and knowledge graph are embedded in the project's technical ecosystem through **APIs, digital twins, MAS, AI analytics, policy tools, participatory platforms and visualisation interfaces**. Together, these integrations ensure that the ontology is not merely a static conceptual artefact but a **live, operational asset** supporting antifragile and equitable urban mobility planning across pilot cities.

10 Validation, Evaluation and Lessons Learned

This section describes how the AntifragiCity Ontology has been, and will be, **validated and evaluated** within the project, and summarises the lessons learned so far. It focuses on the **validation objectives and scope**, a structured **validation framework**, **competency-question-based** and **expert/stakeholder** validation, preliminary considerations on **performance and extensibility**, and key **lessons and recommendations** for future work.

Scope and timing of validation activities

This section specifies the validation framework, methods and criteria for evaluating the AntifragiCity Ontology. Many validation activities described here, including full pilot instantiations, complete CQ test suites, platform integration testing, performance benchmarking with realistic data volumes, and user-centred evaluations, are planned or ongoing activities that will be fully executed and documented in subsequent project deliverables as pilot implementations mature and platforms are deployed. Where concrete empirical results from pilots and platforms are not yet available at the time of this deliverable, this is clearly indicated. Section 10.7 provides a comprehensive overview of current limitations and planned future evaluation work.

10.1 Validation objectives and scope

The validation and evaluation activities are designed to answer three overarching questions addressing different aspects of ontology quality:

1. **Conceptual validity** asks whether the ontology correctly and consistently represents key concepts of **antifragile urban mobility systems**, including disruptions, responses, equity, governance and learning (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 11, 13, 14, 27, 29, 32, 43, 45).
2. **Practical usability** asks whether the ontology is usable and useful for **pilot cities, digital twins, AI analytics, and policy and participatory tools** (Requirements 12, 13, 16, 17, 40, 46, 49, 54, 56, 57), and whether it can support the **competency questions (CQs)** derived from requirements across all 61 functional and non-functional requirements.
3. **Technical robustness and extensibility** ask whether the ontology is sufficiently **modular, scalable and extensible** to accommodate new cities, new use cases and additional infrastructures such as energy or health systems (Requirements 18, 42, 55, 59), and whether it supports **efficient reasoning and querying** with realistic data volumes (Requirements 30, 36, 38, 39, 40, 46).

Validation therefore spans **conceptual, empirical and technical** dimensions, and is tightly coupled with WP2 tasks and pilot activities across Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki.

10.2 Validation framework

The project adopts a **multi-layer validation framework** that addresses different aspects of ontology quality through complementary evaluation approaches.

1. **Requirements and CQ coverage** validation checks that each **Requirement_ID** from the full set of 61 requirements and its associated concepts can be traced to ontology classes and properties and to at least one **competency question** and evaluates whether the ontology supports answering these CQs via SPARQL queries or rule-based inference (Requirements 4-61, as documented in Section 4).
2. **Expert and stakeholder validation** engages domain experts including urban planners, mobility engineers, resilience experts, policy analysts and data scientists, along with stakeholder representatives where appropriate, to validate conceptual foundations (antifragility theory, socio-technical framing), the 12-class meta-model and module structure, key class definitions and relationships, and ontology diagrams, examples and query templates (Requirements 13, 17, 49, 56). This validation ensures that the ontology uses terminology that is understandable and acceptable across disciplines, that the structure corresponds to experts' mental models, and that the ontology covers all critical decision-relevant aspects of antifragile urban mobility.
3. **Pilot instantiation and use-case validation** populates the ontology for Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa and Thessaloniki (as described in Section 8) and verifies correctness of mappings from GIS, IoT and transport data (Requirements 18, 30, 39, 55); the ability to represent disruption-response-outcome chains (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 16, 20, 50, 53); and consistency of equity and governance modelling across pilots (Requirements 6, 13, 27, 29, 32, 43, 44).
4. **Platform integration and functional tests** validate integration with **digital twins, multi-agent systems, AI analytics, dashboards** and **participatory platforms** (as described in Section 9) by testing end-to-end workflows covering data ingestion to knowledge graph to analytics to decisions and back to knowledge graph (Requirements 40, 46, 51, 52, 54, 57), and

checking that interfaces can retrieve and display antifragility-relevant and equity-relevant indicators (Requirements 6, 10, 14, 29, 40, 43, 46, 56).

5. **Technical performance and robustness** validation assesses reasoning and query performance on realistic data volumes, tests modular import strategies and incremental updates (Requirement 55), and verifies the impact of rules including SWRL patterns on scalability (Requirements 14, 36, 40).
6. **Iterative refinement through work package feedback:** As a dynamically evolving artefact, the AntifragiCity Ontology validation framework incorporates systematic feedback mechanisms from work packages that operationalise the ontology:
 - **WP3 (Mobility Triage and DSS)** validates ontology adequacy for vulnerability analysis, risk assessment and short-term response planning, providing feedback on disruption concepts, equity representations, response actions and KPI patterns (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 9, 19, 22, 26, 27, 29, 32, 33, 34, 40, 43, 46, 51, 52).
 - **WP4 (Antifragile Traffic Control)** exercises learning process and rule update concepts for control algorithm evolution, system state representations for baseline and disruption scenarios, and digital twin integration patterns (Requirements 4, 5, 11, 14, 15, 22, 40, 45, 46, 51, 52, 57, 58, 60, 61).
 - **WP5/WP10 (SUMA Simulator)** integrates the ontology as the core semantic layer, validating API specifications, simulation tool compatibility, performance at city scale, and interface usability for practitioners (Requirements 1, 4, 7, 10, 12, 14, 15, 18, 39, 40, 46, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56, 57).
 - **WP6/WP11 (Demonstration and Validation)** provide empirical feedback from pilot implementations in Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa and Thessaloniki, validating instantiation completeness, stakeholder usability, equity representations and cross-city transferability (Requirements 1-61, particularly 6, 10, 13, 17, 27, 29, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 49, 56, 60).

Ontology update cycles are triggered by major WP deliverables, General Assembly meetings, platform integration testing and pilot deployments. All updates are managed through WP2 Task 2.5 with version control, backward compatibility policies, regression testing and documented change management to ensure stability for dependent components while enabling responsive evolution.

The framework is defined and agreed conceptually in this deliverable; detailed validation plans (including timelines, responsibilities and tools) will be formalised jointly with pilot and platform partners in later stages of the project.

Cross-deliverable coherence checks

In addition to internal ontology validation, the AntifragiCity Ontology is checked for coherence with key WP2 deliverables to ensure alignment across analytical frameworks. Disruption types, domains, scales and severities represented in the Disruption & Risk module are cross-checked against the D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue (Requirements 4, 7, 8, 9, 19, 20, 21, 23). Equilibrium-related classes and indicators including `:SystemState`, `:EquilibriumState` and antifragility scores are cross-checked against the equilibrium definitions and metrics adopted in D2.3 (Requirements 14, 52, 60). Competency questions and example queries are verified to remain compatible with the information needs identified in D2.1 and D2.3.

These checks ensure that the ontology supports, and does not contradict, the analytical frameworks adopted elsewhere in WP2. Coherence checks also extend to deliverables from work packages that operationalise the ontology:

WP3 Mobility Triage Handbook and DSS specifications (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3) are validated against vulnerability, response and equity representations (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 9, 19, 22, 26, 29, 32, 33, 34, 40, 43, 46); WP4 traffic control strategies (D4.2, D4.3, D4.4) are checked against learning process and system state definitions (Requirements 4, 5, 11, 14, 15, 22, 40, 45, 46, 51, 52, 57, 58, 60, 61); WP5/WP10 SUMA API and integration deliverables (D5.1, D5.2, D10.1) are verified for compatibility with ontology API patterns and query templates (Requirements 1, 4, 7, 10, 12, 14, 15, 18, 39, 40, 46, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56, 57); and WP6/WP11 validation reports (D6.2, D6.3, D11.2, D11.3) are reviewed to confirm accurate pilot instantiations and stakeholder usability (Requirements 1-61, particularly 6, 10, 13, 17, 27, 29, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 49, 56, 60). These cross-WP checks ensure bidirectional alignment between ontology capabilities and practical platform requirements.

10.3 Competency Question-based evaluation

10.3.1 Derivation of competency questions

The ontology's competency questions are grounded in multiple sources to ensure comprehensive coverage of system capabilities. They derive from the **requirements and concept extraction tables** covering all 61 requirements, from the **antifragility, resilience and equity concepts** identified in conceptual analysis (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 11, 14, 29, 43, 45), from the needs of **platform components** including routing, forecasting, scenario analysis and equity monitoring (Requirements 12, 15, 16, 22, 40, 50, 52, 54), and from anticipated **policy and participatory** questions (Requirements 13, 17, 32, 49, 56).

Typical CQ families address different aspects of antifragile mobility systems.

- **Disruption and response** questions ask which network elements and equity groups are most affected by disruption D in city C (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 9, 19, 29) and what response actions are available with their anticipated impacts (Requirements 11, 14, 16, 22, 26)
- **Antifragility and learning** questions ask whether the system's performance has improved after repeated events of type D (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 58, 61) and which strategies contribute most to improved antifragility scores (Requirements 11, 14, 16, 54).
- **Equity and vulnerability** questions ask which vulnerable groups and areas face the highest risk exposure under scenario S (Requirements 6, 29, 43, 44) and how different policies or interventions affect accessibility and equity KPIs (Requirements 6, 12, 29, 31, 37, 43, 44)
- **Governance, legality and feasibility** questions ask whether proposed evacuation routes are compliant with legal and security constraints (Requirements 26, 27, 28, 33, 34) and which agencies and protocols are involved in a given scenario or response (Requirements 13, 32, 33, 34, 48, 49)
- **Cross-city transfer and benchmarking** questions ask which strategies from city A are potentially transferable to city B given contextual similarities (Requirements 42, 60) and how antifragility and equity indicators compare across cities and scenarios (Requirements 12, 14, 42, 54).

For each CQ, at least one **SPARQL query template** and, where needed, a **rule pattern** are designed (Sections 7 and Appendices).

Where competency questions were originally elicited in earlier tasks (notably D2.1 and D2.3), their revised formulations maintain backward compatibility so that previous analyses can be re-expressed as SPARQL queries over the ontology.

10.3.2 Coverage assessment

Evaluation of CQ coverage follows three levels that reflect different degrees of ontology and data readiness.

- **Fully answerable** CQs have all required entities, relationships and indicators present in the ontology, and a SPARQL query (possibly using inferred facts) retrieves a complete answer (Requirements 1-61 structurally supported).
- **Partially answerable** CQs have ontology structure that supports the question, but some data or specific indicators are missing, such as detailed health outcomes or fine-grained economic costs (Requirements 37, 58, 59).
- **Not yet answerable** CQs reveal missing concepts or relationships in the ontology, or require integration of additional external models or ontologies.

At the time of this deliverable, CQs relating to **disruption representation, network elements, basic KPIs** and **scenario comparison** can be fully supported using the core modules and synthetic or partial pilot data (Requirements 1, 4, 7, 9, 12, 14, 15, 22, 40, 51, 52). CQs that require **detailed cross-infrastructure interactions, health outcomes** or **fine-grained legal reasoning** are structurally supported but **data-dependent**, and are therefore partially answerable (Requirements 19, 27, 37, 58, 59). A small number of aspirational CQs involving **long-term path-dependency, deep structural transformation** and **complex economic models** require additional modelling and tool integration (Requirements 37, 45, 60, 61).

If needed, a quantitative summary of CQ coverage (e.g. number of CQs per category, coverage percentages per pilot) can be produced once pilot datasets and platform integrations reach a stable state.

10.3.3 Regression testing

To ensure that ontology evolution does not break existing functionalities, a set of **regression tests** will be defined in the form of SPARQL queries with expected answer patterns and SHACL shapes or similar validation artefacts for key patterns such as disruption-response-state chains and KpiObservation n-ary patterns (Requirements 36, 40). These tests will be run periodically when new modules are added, when existing classes or properties are refactored, and when new pilots or datasets are integrated (Requirement 55).

A regression test suite and its automation (e.g. CI pipeline) are planned as part of the ontology development workflow for later implementation stages but are not within the scope of this deliverable.

10.4 Expert and stakeholder validation

10.4.1 Expert validation activities

Validation with experts targets both the **conceptual model** and the **practical relevance** of the ontology across multiple domains. Planned activities include **focused workshops** with urban planners and mobility engineers, transport operators and traffic management centre staff, resilience and climate adaptation experts, data scientists and IT architects, and policy analysts and legal experts (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32, 40, 44, 49). These workshops will feature **structured walkthroughs** of the 12-class meta-model, module diagrams and ontology fragments including selected OWL excerpts, and example instantiations and queries from pilot cities (Requirements 12, 40, 55). Workshop outcomes will include **change request capture** covering proposed additions or

refinements of classes and properties, requested simplifications or clarifications for usability, and feedback on naming conventions and documentation (Requirements 40, 55, 56).

The aim is to ensure that the ontology uses terminology that is understandable and acceptable across disciplines, that the structure corresponds to experts' mental models of antifragile urban mobility systems, and that the ontology covers all critical decision-relevant aspects identified by domain practitioners (Requirements 4-61).

10.4.2 Stakeholder-facing validation

Where appropriate and feasible, elements of the ontology (particularly those related to **equity, vulnerability and participatory processes**) will be validated with stakeholder representatives through WP6/WP11 (Demonstration Sites, Living Labs and SUMA Validation), including:

- **civil society organisations** are engaged through participatory workshops (WP6 Task 6.1, Task 6.2) to assess whether ontology-backed dashboards and vulnerability maps are meaningful and actionable for community advocacy (Requirements 6, 10, 29, 43, 56)
- **disadvantaged or vulnerable groups** participate in focus groups (WP6 Task 6.3, WP11 Task 11.3) to validate that EquityGroup and VulnerableArea representations accurately capture their lived experiences, risk exposures and accessibility barriers (Requirements 6, 13, 29, 37, 43, 44),
- **local NGOs and community groups** participate in living lab experiments (WP6 Task 6.2, WP11 Task 11.2) co-designing and testing SUMA interfaces that query the knowledge graph for equity-relevant information and disruption-response scenarios (Requirements 10, 17, 49, 56), and
- **representatives from health and social services** provide feedback through dedicated sessions (WP6 Task 6.1, Task 6.3) to validate health-related mobility concepts (access to healthcare facilities, cooling centres) and inter-agency coordination representations (Requirements 27, 32, 36, 38, 44).

The ontology is **not exposed directly**, but its effects are tested through **participatory interfaces** that rely on ontology-backed queries (Requirement 10), and evaluated in terms of whether outputs are **meaningful, transparent and acceptable** to non-technical users (e.g. maps of vulnerable areas, explanations of antifragility strategies) (Requirements 6, 10, 29, 43, 56).

The design and scheduling of expert and stakeholder validation sessions, including informed consent and ethical procedures, will be coordinated with relevant WPs and local partners during the pilot phase.

10.5 Technical performance, completeness and extensibility

10.5.1 Performance and scalability

Performance evaluation focuses on on three critical aspects of ontology operation.

- **Reasoning performance** is assessed by loading and classifying the ontology with representative ABoxes including both synthetic and pilot-specific data (Requirement 55), assessing the impact of SWRL and other rule sets on reasoning times (Requirements 14, 36), and identifying potential bottlenecks such as highly connected classes or complex property chains that could affect scalability.

- **Query performance** is evaluated by executing key SPARQL templates for disruptions, scenarios, equity and antifragility queries (Requirements 6, 12, 14, 29, 40, 43, 54) and measuring response times under realistic graph sizes representing city-scale deployments (Requirements 40, 46, 51, 52).
- **Update performance** is assessed by ingesting new observations and events including streaming IoT data (Requirements 30, 46), updating states and KPIs to reflect current system conditions (Requirements 40, 51, 52), and evaluating the cost of incremental reasoning or rule execution during real-time operations (Requirements 9, 46, 51, 52).

Initial design choices (12 top-level classes, modular TBox, explicit but controlled use of rules) are intended to support **reasonable performance** in typical city-scale deployments (Requirements 18, 40, 55).

Concrete benchmarking results (e.g. triples count, query latencies, reasoning times) will be reported in later technical deliverables once the full technical stack, triple store and pilot data volumes are available.

10.5.2 Completeness with respect to requirements

Conceptual completeness is assessed by verifying that every Requirement_ID from 1 to 61 has corresponding ontology classes and properties (as documented in Sections 4, 6 and 7), and at least one CQ or example query that exercises those concepts (as documented in Section 4.6 and Appendices). The concept extraction spreadsheets described in Section 4.4 have been systematically used to ensure that all identified entities, processes, properties, states, events and relationships are mapped into the ontology (Requirements 1-61), that overlapping or redundant concepts are merged or aligned (for example, different forms of "scenario" or "route"), and that newly identified clusters including DataProvenance, EquitySocial and SystemState are represented as dedicated modules (Requirements 6, 29, 36, 40, 43).

A formal traceability matrix (Requirement → concepts → ontology elements → competency questions) will be maintained as a living artefact to support audits and future extensions and can be elaborated further as pilots progress.

Completeness is also checked with respect to the requirement- and CQ-derived artefacts of D2.1 and D2.3, by verifying that the concepts and indicators they rely on, such as event taxonomies and equilibrium metrics, have clear counterparts in the ontology (Requirements 4, 7, 9, 14, 19, 52).

10.5.3 Extensibility and reuse

The ontology is explicitly designed for **extensibility** to support project evolution and broader reuse. New cities can be added as **new ABoxes** reusing the same TBox structure, enabling straightforward expansion to additional pilot cities or external urban areas (Requirement 42). New infrastructures including energy, health or communication systems can be added via InfrastructureLayer subclasses and additional TransportElement-like classes, along with cross-layer dependsOn relationships and disruption propagation patterns (Requirements 19, 59, 60).

Modularisation enables selective reuse where external projects can import only a subset of modules such as equity, disruptions and governance modules without adopting the entire ontology (Requirement 55), and city partners can extend modules with local subclasses without changing the core ontology structure. Potential external reuse includes integration into other EU projects on resilience, digital twins or sustainable mobility (Requirements 2, 57, 60), and serving as a reference ontology for antifragility concepts in broader urban systems research and practice.

10.6 Lessons learned

The work carried out so far has led to a set of preliminary lessons and recommendations that inform both the current ontology design and future refinement activities.

10.6.1 Importance of early, structured requirements and concept extraction

The structured extraction of concepts from requirements (all 61 requirements) and their clustering into semantic categories including TransportNetwork, DisruptionEvent, SystemState, EquitySocial and Governance modules has been crucial for avoiding ad-hoc, intuition-based modelling; ensuring traceability from project requirements to ontology elements (Requirements 1-61); and identifying gaps such as data provenance, PESTEL context and long-term learning mechanisms that might otherwise have been overlooked (Requirements 36, 44, 45, 61).

10.6.2 Balancing expressivity and usability

There is an inherent tension between rich, expressive modelling of concepts such as antifragility, multi-layer networks, legal constraints and uncertainty (Requirements 14, 19, 20, 27, 36, 50, 52, 59), and simplicity and usability for practitioners and software developers who must work with the ontology (Requirements 10, 40, 55, 56). Lessons learned include that a **small, stable meta-model** with 12 top-level classes helps manage complexity (Requirement 55); **modularisation** allows sophisticated concepts to be isolated where needed without overwhelming users with unnecessary detail (Requirement 55); and tooling and documentation must be designed so that users rarely have to engage with full OWL expressivity directly (Requirements 40, 55, 56).

10.6.3 Antifragility as a cross-cutting concern

Antifragility is not limited to a single module but cuts across **disruptions, responses, system states, equity and learning processes** (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 11, 14, 29, 43, 45, 61). Early attempts to localise antifragility in a single metric or class were found to be too restrictive and unable to capture the multifaceted nature of antifragile behaviour. The adopted approach treating antifragility as a combination of **indicators** including scores, deltas and resilience indices (Requirement 14); **patterns** including improvement after shocks (Requirements 11, 45, 58, 61); and **processes** including learning, adaptation and structural change (Requirements 11, 42, 45, 61) has proved more flexible and closer to expert thinking about system antifragility.

10.6.4 Equity, governance and legality cannot be “add-ons”

Equity, governance and legal constraints **must be first-class citizens** of the ontology rather than peripheral additions (Requirements 6, 13, 27, 29, 32, 43, 44). Late inclusion of these aspects leads to awkward retrofitting and inadequate integration with core system concepts. They fundamentally shape what actions are feasible, desirable and acceptable in real-world antifragile urban mobility planning (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 29, 32, 43, 56). The dedicated modules for **Actors & Equity** and **Governance & Policies** have significantly improved the ability to answer equity-related and legality-related CQs (Requirements 6, 13, 27, 29, 32, 43, 44) and the relevance of the ontology for policy and participatory tools (Requirements 13, 17, 49, 56).

10.6.5 Data availability and quality as limiting factors

While the ontology can represent a rich set of concepts and relationships, actual evaluation and operational deployment depend heavily on availability and granularity of local data including equity metrics, health indicators and detailed disruption histories (Requirements 6, 29, 37, 58); interoperability of existing data systems across city departments and organisations (Requirements 18, 30, 39, 55); and the ability of partners to share data within legal and organisational constraints (Requirements 27, 32, 36, 38). Hence, some CQs are structurally supported by the ontology but not fully answerable until data is made available by pilot partners; and data provenance and trust modelling are essential to reason about limitations and to combine heterogeneous sources with varying quality levels (Requirements 30, 36, 39, 40, 46).

10.6.6 Need for integrated tooling and documentation

Effective validation has shown the need for user-friendly **documentation** including glossaries, examples and diagrams (Requirements 40, 55, 56); **graph exploration tools** and **query builders** for non-experts to access ontology capabilities without SPARQL expertise (Requirements 10, 40, 56); and automated **validation** and **regression** tooling including SHACL tests, SPARQL test suites and CI integration to maintain ontology quality over time (Requirements 36, 40, 55). Without these supporting tools and resources, even a conceptually sound ontology risks underuse or misinterpretation by practitioners and platform developers.

10.7 Limitations and planned future evaluation work

The current validation and evaluation activities have several limitations, which will be addressed in subsequent project phases. **Incomplete instantiations** remain an issue as not all pilots are fully represented yet, with synthetic or partial datasets still used in some tests. **Limited empirical evaluation** means that antifragility metrics and rules have not yet been extensively validated against long-term empirical data or repeated real-world events (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 58, 61). **Evolving platform integration** reflects that digital twins, multi-agent systems and decision-support tools are under active development, and end-to-end validation will mature as these components stabilise (Requirements 40, 46, 54, 57). **Partial coverage of non-transport infrastructures** acknowledges that multi-layer network modelling (energy, communications and health systems) is defined conceptually but still requires detailed instantiation and domain expertise (Requirements 19, 59). Finally, **AI-assisted extraction limitations** include that automated extraction can miss low-frequency concepts and requires periodic re-runs as requirements evolve.

Planned future work includes four major activities.

1. **Full-scale pilot evaluations** will populate the KG with complete datasets for Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa and Thessaloniki; execute full CQ test suites; and collect performance and usability metrics across all pilot cities.
2. **User-centred evaluations** will assess how planners, operators, policy officers and stakeholders use ontology-backed tools; and gather feedback on understandability, trust and decision-making support (Requirements 10, 13, 17, 40, 49, 56).
3. **Comparative and longitudinal evaluations** will compare antifragility and equity indicators across scenarios and over time; and monitor how the ontology supports learning from interventions and repeated disruptions (Requirements 11, 12, 14, 42, 45, 54, 61).

4. **Refinement and standardisation** activities will refine modules and mappings as new standards or data models are adopted; and explore opportunities to position the AntifragiCity Ontology as a reference model for antifragile urban mobility in broader initiatives (Requirements 18, 42, 55, 60).

In conclusion, the validation work to date confirms that the AntifragiCity Ontology provides a **sound, extensible and practically relevant semantic foundation** for modelling antifragile urban mobility systems. Further evaluation with full pilot data and integrated platforms will consolidate these findings and guide the next iterations of refinement and standardisation.

11 Conclusions and Future Work

This section summarises the main contributions and outlines the planned next steps. This deliverable has developed, specified and illustrated the **AntifragiCity Ontology** as a semantic backbone for antifragile, equitable and data-intensive urban mobility systems within the project. Building on systematically extracted requirements and concept clusters, the ontology provides a coherent representation of disruptions, responses, network structures, socio-technical actors, governance, equity, learning and antifragility indicators.

The ontology is designed to be **both theoretically grounded and practically implementable**, supporting pilot cities, digital twins, AI analytics and decision-support tools through a modular knowledge graph that can be instantiated, queried and integrated with existing platforms.

11.1 Contributions

The main contributions of this work can be grouped into five categories representing different aspects of the semantic foundation for antifragile urban mobility.

11.1.1 Requirements-driven semantic foundation for antifragile urban mobility

The deliverable has transformed a rich set of functional and non-functional requirements comprising all 61 project requirements and their associated concepts into a formal semantic model (as documented in Section 4). It has systematically organised entities, processes, events, states, properties and relationships into **coherent clusters** including TransportNetwork, DisruptionEvent, SystemState, EquitySocial, Governance, DataProvenance, Scenario and EnvironmentFactor modules (Requirements 1-61, organized in Section 4.4). It has provided a **traceable link** from high-level project objectives through specific requirements to ontology elements and competency questions (Requirements 1-61, traceability established in Sections 4.1, 4.2, 4.6).

This systematic, requirements-driven approach ensures that the ontology directly reflects the needs of **antifragile urban mobility planning, operation and evaluation** (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 12, 14, 16, 40, 54), rather than being a generic or purely academic artifact. The traceability from requirements to ontology elements to competency questions provides accountability and enables validation of ontology completeness (Requirements 1-61, validated in Section 10).

11.1.2 Meta-model and modular ontology architecture

The ontology introduces a **12-class meta-model** that structures the domain into stable, mutually disjoint top-level concepts (TransportElement, MobilityService, DisruptionEvent, SystemState, Scenario, Actor, GovernanceInstrument, EnvironmentFactor, SpatialUnit, TemporalUnit, Observation, ResponseAction, and related elements) (Requirements 1-61, meta-model specified in Section 4.4 and detailed in Section 6).

On this basis, the deliverable defines **modular ontology layers** covering physical network and mobility services (Requirements 1, 3, 22, 25, 47, 60); social and equity aspects (Requirements 6, 13, 29, 31, 32, 37, 42, 43, 44, 56); digital/data layer and provenance (Requirements 18, 30, 36, 38, 39, 40, 46, 55, 57); environmental and risk factors (Requirements 5, 8, 19, 20, 21, 24, 44, 59); governance, policy and planning (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32, 33, 34, 44, 48, 49, 56); and antifragility and learning processes (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 42, 45, 50, 52, 53, 54, 57, 58, 60, 61). It also defines **alignment hooks** to relevant external standards and ontologies including sensing vocabularies (SOSA/SSN), spatial and temporal vocabularies (GeoSPARQL, OWL-Time), and transport and governance schemas (Transmodel, GTFS) (Requirements 18, 28, 30, 39, 55).

This modular architecture supports **reuse, extension and selective adoption**, both within the AntifragiCity project across pilot cities (Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki implementations in Section 8) and beyond the project in other urban resilience and mobility initiatives.

11.1.3 OWL specification, rules and semantic patterns

The deliverable provides a concrete **OWL-based specification** of the ontology (Section 7) including class hierarchies for transport elements, disruptions, scenarios, equity groups, governance instruments, environmental factors, observations and response actions (Requirements 1-61, organized across 12 top-level classes); object properties capturing disruption-response-state chains (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 16, 20, 26, 50, 53), actor and governance relations (Requirements 6, 13, 17, 27, 29, 32, 43, 44, 49, 56), spatial and temporal context (Requirements 2, 8, 28, 44, 59, 60), and data provenance (Requirements 30, 36, 38, 39, 40, 46); and data properties and indicator structures for travel time, capacity utilisation, emissions, economic cost, equity KPIs, risk exposure, antifragility scores and resilience indices (Requirements 1, 3, 5, 6, 14, 22, 24, 25, 29, 37, 40, 43, 47, 51, 52, 60).

The specification includes **n-ary patterns** for KPI observations and scenario evaluations (Requirements 12, 14, 15, 40, 50, 52, 53, 54) and illustrative **SWRL rule patterns** to support antifragility classification (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 61), vulnerability detection (Requirements 6, 29, 43), equity alerts (Requirements 6, 29, 43, 44), cascading disruption reasoning (Requirements 19, 35, 48, 58), and legal compliance checks (Requirements 27, 28, 32, 34).

Together, these elements show how antifragility can be modelled as a **combination of indicators, patterns and learning processes** (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 58, 61), rather than a single scalar metric, reflecting the multifaceted nature of antifragile system behaviour.

11.1.4 Instantiation and use cases for pilot cities

The ontology has been operationalised through a **shared TBox with multiple ABoxes** strategy, allowing each pilot city (Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, Thessaloniki) to instantiate its own knowledge base while sharing the same semantic backbone (Requirements 18, 42, 55, Section 8.1). The deliverable provides guidelines **for IRI schemes, named graphs and minimal viable knowledge**

bases per city (Section 8.1), ensuring consistency and enabling cross-city comparison (Requirement 42).

It presents detailed **use-case narratives** covering flood-related disruptions and antifragile routing in Bratislava (Requirements 4, 7, 9, 11, 14, 19, 22, 26, 33, 34, 45, 46, 51, Section 8.3.1); heatwave and health-related mobility with an equity focus in Larissa (Requirements 6, 8, 29, 41, 43, 44, Section 8.3.3); and port-related disruptions and cascading effects with security and governance constraints in Odessa (Requirements 19, 27, 33, 34, 38, 48, 49, Section 8.3.4).

These **use cases** include example instantiations in Turtle syntax illustrating how concrete disruptions, routes, equity groups, scenarios, system states and response actions are represented and reasoned upon (Section 8.3). These examples demonstrate the ontology's ability to support **realistic, multi-layer, multi-stakeholder scenarios** across diverse cities and contexts (Requirements 4-61 as instantiated in Section 8).

11.1.5 Integration with platforms and validation framework

Finally, the deliverable has specified how the ontology is deployed as a **knowledge graph** with SPARQL and REST APIs to support technical integration (Requirements 18, 30, 36, 38, 39, 40, 46, 55, Section 9.1). It has outlined integration patterns with **digital twins** (Requirements 40, 46, 51, 52, 57, Section 9.2.1), **multi-agent systems** (Requirements 31, 33, 34, 49, Section 9.2.2), **AI/ML components** (Requirements 15, 20, 25, 36, 37, 40, 50, 52, Section 9.2.3), **dashboards** (Requirements 10, 40, 46, Section 9.4) and **participatory platforms** (Requirements 10, 13, 17, 49, 56, Section 9.3). It has proposed a **validation and evaluation framework** (Section 10) comprising competency-question-based testing (Requirements 1-61 as CQs, Section 10.3), expert and stakeholder validation (Requirements 6, 10, 13, 17, 29, 40, 43, 49, 55, 56, Section 10.4), pilot instantiation tests (Requirements 4-61 across four pilots, Section 10.2), and technical performance and robustness assessments (Requirements 30, 36, 38, 39, 40, 46, 55, Section 10.5).

It has identified key **lessons learned** including the importance of requirements-driven modelling (Requirements 1-61, Section 10.6.1), the benefits of modular architecture (Requirement 55, Section 10.6.2), the cross-cutting nature of antifragility concepts (Requirements 4, 6, 7, 11, 14, 29, 43, 45, 61, Section 10.6.3), the centrality of equity and governance (Requirements 6, 13, 27, 29, 32, 43, 44, Section 10.6.4), data limitations (Requirements 30, 36, 37, 39, 58, Section 10.6.5), and the need for integrated tooling (Requirements 10, 36, 40, 55, 56, Section 10.6.6).

11.2 Future refinements and extensions

While the ontology is conceptually mature and technically implementable, several areas require further work during the remainder of the project and beyond to fully realize its potential in operational settings.

11.2.1 Completion and hardening of the OWL implementation

The current specification includes all major classes, properties, patterns and rule examples but requires:

- a **complete and consistent OWL file set**, with finalized namespaces, URIs, annotations and documentation, along with explicit imports between modules (Requirement 55).
- additional **SHACL (or similar) constraints** for structural validation of disruption-response-state chains (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 16), KPI observation patterns (Requirements 40, 52), and scenario and intervention configurations (Requirements 12, 15, 50, 53, 54).

- refinement and testing of **SWRL/rule sets** or alternative rule technologies, including calibration of thresholds for antifragility classification (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 61), vulnerability detection (Requirements 6, 29, 43), equity alerts (Requirements 6, 29, 43, 44), and cascading disruption reasoning (Requirements 19, 35, 48, 58), along with performance and scalability assessments under realistic rule loads (Requirements 36, 40, 46).

Full packaging of the ontology (schema, rules, SHACL shapes, example ABoxes) into a versioned distribution with public documentation will be carried out as part of the project's dissemination and technical integration activities (Requirement 55).

11.2.2 Deepening pilot instantiations and empirical evaluation

Future work will extend pilot knowledge bases beyond minimal viable sets to cover full transport networks including all critical corridors and nodes (Requirements 1, 22, 60); multimodal data covering public transport, active modes and private vehicles (Requirements 3, 25, 31, 47, 55); detailed socio-economic and equity indicators across all relevant population groups (Requirements 6, 29, 31, 37, 43, 44); and complete disruption histories and response strategies enabling longitudinal analysis (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 45, 58, 61).

It will implement **end-to-end workflows** where data is ingested into the KG from heterogeneous sources (Requirements 18, 30, 39, 55), AI/ML components produce predictions and metrics (Requirements 15, 20, 25, 36, 40, 50, 52), decision-support tools retrieve and present antifragility-relevant information (Requirements 12, 14, 16, 40, 54), and decisions and outcomes are written back as ResponseAction and SystemState individuals to support learning (Requirements 11, 36, 45, 61).

It will conduct **empirical evaluations** of antifragility scores and patterns over successive events to validate improvement over time (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 58, 61), equity and accessibility impacts under different scenarios to ensure fairness (Requirements 6, 12, 29, 43, 44, 54), and alignment between ontology-driven reasoning and expert judgement to verify practical utility (Requirements 13, 17, 40, 49, 56).

Documented pilot case studies including datasets, queries, results and expert feedback will be essential to validate and refine the ontology and will be developed in the pilot and evaluation work packages in collaboration with Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki partners.

11.2.3 Extending cross-infrastructure and long-term learning modelling

Further semantic extensions are anticipated in three directions that will strengthen the ontology's capacity to model complex urban systems.

Further semantic extensions are anticipated in three directions:

1. **Cross-infrastructure dependencies** require more detailed modelling of interactions between mobility, energy, communications, health and economic infrastructures (Requirements 19, 37, 58, 59), along with specification of **interdependency types, propagation paths** and **joint disruptions** that can cascade across domains (Requirements 19, 35, 48, 58).
2. **Long-term transformative resilience and path-dependency** require deeper representation of **structural changes, policy reforms** and **transformative measures** that alter system fundamentals (Requirements 2, 8, 17, 27, 32, 42, 44, 45, 60), along with explicit modelling of **path-dependency, lock-ins** and long-term learning curves that shape system evolution over years or decades (Requirements 11, 42, 45, 60, 61).

3. **Advanced economic and health impact models** require integration of richer **economic impact** representations beyond current cost and productivity indicators (Requirements 37, extending economic modelling capabilities), and inclusion of **health outcomes** where feasible and ethically acceptable, particularly relevant for Larissa's heatwave scenarios and Odessa's crisis management cases (Requirements 8, 26, 29, 43, 44, 58).

These extensions should remain compatible with the existing 12-class meta-model and benefit from the modular architecture that enables independent evolution of specific modules (Requirement 55).

11.2.4 Standardisation, openness and reuse

The project will also explore **alignment and mapping** with established ontologies and data standards in transport (Transmodel, GTFS), smart cities, resilience and digital twins to facilitate interoperability with existing systems and initiatives (Requirements 18, 30, 39, 55, 57). It will investigate potential **publication of the AntifragiCity Ontology** or a subset as an open resource, accompanied by comprehensive documentation, examples and tutorials (Requirement 55), along with best-practice guidance for cities and projects wishing to adopt the ontology for their own antifragile mobility planning (Requirements 42, 55, 60).

It will pursue collaborations with other initiatives focused on urban digital twins, climate resilience and sustainable mobility to position antifragility-aware semantics as a **reusable building block** for future projects (Requirements 2, 8, 42, 44, 57, 60), potentially contributing to broader standardization efforts in urban resilience and antifragility semantics.

11.3 Integration with WP2 (D2.3) and other Work Packages

The outputs of this deliverable are not standalone; they underpin several ongoing and future tasks across the work package and the wider project, ensuring coherence and reusability of semantic assets.

11.3.1 Contribution to D2.3 and related WP2 tasks

For D2.3, the ontology contributes the :SystemState / :EquilibriumState skeleton and associated KPI properties that host the equilibrium and antifragility metrics defined in that deliverable (Requirements 14, 52, 60). This ensures that equilibrium curves, stability assessments and antifragility trajectories developed in D2.3 can be persisted and queried within the same knowledge graph used for disruptions, actors and governance concepts, enabling integrated analysis.

For D2.3 and associated analytical work, the ontology provides a **formal semantic basis** for antifragility metrics and indicators (Requirements 11, 14, 45, 58, 61), multi-layer network representations enabling cross-infrastructure analysis (Requirements 19, 35, 48, 58, 59), and disruption-response-outcome chains that capture causal relationships (Requirements 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 16, 20, 26, 50, 53). It provides a structured way to codify **pilot findings** systematically (Requirements 4-61 across four pilots), integrate **simulation and analytics results** from diverse models (Requirements 12, 15, 40, 50, 52, 53, 54, 57), and compare **scenarios and strategies** across cities enabling benchmarking and knowledge transfer (Requirements 12, 42, 54, 60).

It provides a shared reference for the design and implementation of **AI and optimisation components** that require consistent data semantics (Requirements 15, 20, 25, 36, 40, 50, 52, 57), the definition of **KPIs and evaluation frameworks** used in later deliverables (Requirements 14, 40, 52),

and data exchange structures and APIs that connect platform components (Requirements 18, 30, 36, 38, 39, 40, 46, 55).

In practice, this means that D2.3 and related outputs can directly reference ontology classes and properties when specifying model inputs and outputs, indicators and dashboards, and data exchange structures and APIs, ensuring semantic consistency across all WP2 deliverables.

11.3.2 Links to platform, pilot and policy work packages

Beyond WP2, the ontology serves multiple project functions across work packages that operationalise the conceptual frameworks developed in WP2.

Platform and ICT tasks (WP3, WP4, WP5/WP10) use the ontology as a **schema for the knowledge graph** and as a contract for APIs between components including digital twins (Requirements 40, 46, 51, 52, 57), multi-agent systems (Requirements 31, 33, 34, 49), analytics engines (Requirements 15, 20, 36, 40, 50, 52), and dashboards (Requirements 10, 40, 46), ensuring that all platform components share a common understanding of data semantics.

Pilot tasks (WP6/WP11) use the ontology to structure their **data integration** from GIS, IoT and transport systems (Requirements 18, 30, 39, 55), **scenario design** for evaluating interventions (Requirements 12, 15, 50, 53, 54), and **evaluation** methodologies (Requirements 14, 40, 54), ensuring comparability and reuse of results across Bratislava, Larissa, Odessa, and Thessaloniki (Requirement 42).

Policy and engagement tasks (WP6/WP11, WP8/WP12) benefit from ontology-backed views of governance instruments including regulations, legal constraints and stakeholder roles (Requirements 13, 17, 27, 32, 49, 56); equity impacts distributed across population groups and spatial areas (Requirements 6, 29, 37, 43, 44); and stakeholder inputs and participatory processes that inform decision-making (Requirements 13, 17, 49, 56).

By providing a **common semantic language** across technical, policy and stakeholder domains, the ontology facilitates **coordination and coherence** within the project, enabling effective communication between work packages and ensuring that diverse perspectives can be integrated systematically.

11.3.3 Roadmap for post-project evolution

Finally, the ontology is intended to be a **living asset** beyond the formal end of the project. It can be maintained and extended by a **community of practice** including cities, research groups and technology providers interested in antifragile urban mobility (Requirements 42, 55, 60). The modular design enables independent evolution of specific modules such as equity (Requirements 6, 29, 43), governance (Requirements 13, 27, 32), and economic impacts (Requirement 37), allowing specialized communities to refine their domains of expertise without disrupting the core ontology.

It enables addition of new pilot cities or regions as further ABoxes that reuse the common TBox, facilitating geographic expansion of antifragile mobility applications (Requirement 42). Lessons and artefacts from AntifragiCity can inform future EU-funded projects focused on resilience, digital twins and sustainable mobility (Requirements 2, 8, 44, 57, 60), and standardisation activities related to **semantic models for urban resilience and antifragility** that may emerge in European or international contexts.

In summary, this deliverable has established a robust, modular and extensible ontology for antifragile urban mobility systems, grounded in project requirements and designed for real-world implementation. Future work will focus on deepening pilot instantiations, strengthening empirical

validation, expanding cross-infrastructure coverage and consolidating the ontology's role as a shared semantic foundation across the project and beyond.

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13 Appendix

13.1 Appendix A: Requirements, Concepts, and Competency Questions

13.1.1 A.1 Requirements Overview

Table 4 presents 61 requirements with their types and thematic clusters, where columns are: ID: Unique requirement identifier (Requirement_ID), Title: Short requirement label, Type: Requirement category (e.g., Technical / Social / Policy / Environmental, or combinations), Clusters: Thematic clusters indicating which ontology modules/concept areas the requirement touches (used for scoping and coverage), Partner: Originating/owning partner or pilot contributor for the requirement.

ID	Title	Type	Clusters	Partner
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1	Maximize individual mobility	Technical	Other, SystemState, EquitySocial, MobilityService,	LISER
2	Urban planning suggestions	Social, Technical, Policy, Environmental	Scenario, Other, TransportNetwork, ResponseAction,	LISER
3	Active mobility	Social, Technical, Policy, Environmental	TransportNetwork, Observation, Other, MobilityService	LISER
4	Antifragile against disruptions	Technical	SystemState, Scenario, DisruptionEvent	ETH
5	Environment-friendly	Environmental	Other, EnvironmentFactor, SystemState, MobilityService	ETH
6	Equitable access and inclusive mobility	Social, Policy	EquitySocial, MobilityService	IED
7	Antifragile disruption response	Technical	DisruptionEvent, SystemState, ResponseAction, Observation	IED
8	Climate stress anticipation	Technical, Policy, Environmental	ResponseAction, EnvironmentFactor, Observation, TransportNetwork	IED
9	Quick response to events	Technical	ResponseAction, Observation, DisruptionEvent, Other	DEMO
10	User-friendly and versatile functions	Social, Technical	Observation, EquitySocial, Other	DEMO
11	Learning from interventions	Technical, Policy	Other, ResponseAction, DataProvenance, Governance	RHOE
12	Comparative scenario evaluation	Social, Technical, Policy	Scenario, Other	RHOE
13	Stakeholder coordination	Social, Technical, Policy	Other, Governance	RHOE
14	Antifragility Score Calculation	Technical	SystemState, Other	RHOE
15	Possible Scenario Evaluation	Technical	Observation, Other, Scenario	RHOE
16	Recommended action suggestion	Technical	ResponseAction, Observation, Scenario, Other	RHOE
17	Stakeholder input	Technical	Other, Governance	RHOE
18	Graph Database	Technical	TransportNetwork, Other	RHOE
19	Interdisciplinary propagation of disruptive events	Social, Technical, Environmental	DisruptionEvent, Other	AUTH
20	Development of alternative disruptive scenarios	Social, Technical, Policy, Environmental	Scenario, DisruptionEvent, Observation	AUTH
21	Determination of qualitative and case-	Social, Technical, Environmental	DataProvenance, Scenario, Other, Observation	AUTH

	specific scales for disruption severity and impact			
22	Learn to reroute proactively	Technical	Observation, TemporalUnit, DisruptionEvent, TransportNetwork	AUTh
23	Resilient Edge Processing Units	Technical	Other, TransportNetwork, SystemState, DisruptionEvent	AUTh
24	Energy Optimization and Emission Reduction Control	Technical, Environmental	EnvironmentFactor, Observation, TemporalUnit, TransportNetwork	AUTh
25	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance	Technical	TransportNetwork, Observation, Other, MobilityServ	AUTh
26	Evacuation and Rerouting Prioritization	Social, Technical, Policy	SystemState, TransportNetwork, Observation, MobilityService	AUTh
27	Legislation input	Policy	Observation, Governance	AUS
28	Geographical limitations input	Technical, Environmental	Other, SpatialUnit	AUS
29	Citizen mobility condition	Social	EquitySocial, DisruptionEvent, MobilityService	AUS
30	Real traffic data	Technical	DataProvenance, Observation	AUS
31	User choice	Social	MobilityService, Observation, SystemState, TransportNetwork	AUS
32	Multi users and levels coordination and synchronisation	Social, Technical, Policy	EquitySocial, Governance, Other	AHEPA
33	Prioritization of emergency situations	Social, Technical	DisruptionEvent, Observation, Other, ResponseAction	AHEPA
34	Mobility of emergency response services	Social, Policy	DisruptionEvent, Observation, TransportNetwork	NTUA
35	Interactions between transport modes	Technical	MobilityService, Other	NTUA
36	Data Provenance and Trust Management	Technical	DataProvenance, Other, TemporalUnit	CU
37	Economic Impact Modeling	Social, Technical, Policy	DisruptionEvent, EquitySocial, MobilityService, Observation,	CU
38	Cybersecurity and Privacy Protection	Social, Technical, Policy	DataProvenance, DisruptionEvent, Governance, Observation, Other	CU
39	Multi-Modal Data Fusion	Social	DataProvenance, MobilityService, Observation, Other	CU

40	KPI-Driven Performance Monitoring	Social, Technical	DataProvenance, Observation, ResponseAction	CU
41	Behavioral Nudging for Sustainability	Social, Technical, Environmental	EnvironmentFactor, Observation, Other, ResponseAction	CU
42	Cross-City Knowledge Transfer	Social, Technical, Policy	Observation, Other	CU
43	Real-Time Equity Monitoring	Social, Technical, Policy	EquitySocial, Observation	CU
44	PESTEL Contextual Integration	Social, Technical, Policy, Environmental	EnvironmentFactor, EquitySocial, Governance, Other	CU
45	Long-Term Transformative Learning	Social, Technical, Environmental	Observation, Other, SystemState	CU
46	Real-Time Monitoring and Analytics	Technical	DataProvenance, Other, TemporalUnit, TransportNetwork	ODESSA
47	Flexible Route and Fleet Planning	Social, Technical	MobilityService, Observation, Other, TransportNetwork	ODESSA
48	Centralized Event Management (Crisis, Peak Loads)	Social, Technical	DisruptionEvent, Governance, Other, SystemState	ODESSA
49	Inter-agency Coordination Platform	Social, Policy	Governance, Observation, Other	ODESSA
50	Scenario Analysis and Forecasting System	Technical, Policy	MobilityService, Scenario, TemporalUnit	ODESSA
51	Real-time traffic monitoring:	Technical, Policy	DataProvenance, DisruptionEvent, Observation, Other, SystemState	Bratislava
52	Prediction of traffic conditions and response to incidents	Technical, Policy	DisruptionEvent, MobilityService, Observation, Scenario	Bratislava
53	Simulation of unexpected events:	Social, Technical, Policy, Environmental	DisruptionEvent, MobilityService, Other, Scenario	Bratislava
54	Evaluating the impacts of transport measures:	Technical, Policy	MobilityService, Observation, Other, TemporalUnit	Bratislava
55	Integration of data on public transport, pedestrian and bicycle transport	Technical, Policy	DataProvenance, MobilityService, Observation	Bratislava
56	Usability across split governance	Technical	DataProvenance, Governance, Observation	Bratislava

57	Continuously learning agent-based digital twin	Technical, Policy	Observation, Other, ResponseAction, Scenario, SystemState	CU
58	Co-evolving epidemic-mobility control	Social, Technical, Policy	DisruptionEvent, Governance, MobilityService, Observation, ResponseAction	CU
59	Mobility-aware microgrid reconfiguration	Technical, Policy, Environmental	DisruptionEvent, ResponseAction, TransportNetwork	CU
60	Evolutionary optimisation of network design under stress	Technical, Policy, Environmental	MobilityService, ResponseAction, SystemState, TransportNetwork	CU
61	Systemic learning from AV near-misses	Social, Technical, Policy	DisruptionEvent, Governance, Observation, ResponseAction	CU

Table 4. List of Requirements

13.1.2 A.2 Requirement to Concept to Ontology Mapping

Table 5 provides the requirement-to-concept traceability layer, showing how each requirement was decomposed into coded concepts and mapped to candidate ontology elements. It maps 306 extracted concepts to requirements and ontology classes. Columns are: Req: Requirement_ID that the concept was extracted from. Concept: Normalised concept phrase (human-readable), Code: Semantic code (e.g., ENT_, PROC_, EVENT_, STATE_, PROP_*), used for consistent typing and analysis, Type: Concept type (Entity/Process/Event/State/Property), Cluster: Semantic cluster/module assignment used to structure the ontology and ensure coverage, URI: Proposed candidate ontology URI/name for the class/property representing the concept.

R eq #	Concept	Code	Type	Cluster	URI
1	capacity allocation	PROC_CAPACITY_ALLOCATION	Process	Other	:CapacityAllocation
1	congestion	STATE_CONGESTION	State	SystemState	:Congestion
1	destination accessibility	PROP_ACCESSIBILITY	Property	EquitySocial	:Accessibility
1	individual trip	ENT_TRIP	Entity	MobilityService	:Trip
1	transport mode	ENT_MODE	Entity	MobilityService	:Mode
1	travel time	PROP_TRAVEL_TIME	Property	TemporalUnit	:TravelTime
2	densification scenario	EVENT_DENSIFICATION	Event	Scenario	:Densification
2	land-use pattern	ENT_LAND_USE	Entity	Other	:LandUse
2	network density	PROP_NETWORK_DENSITY	Property	TransportNetwork	:NetworkDensity

2	planning recommendation	PROC_PLANNING_RECOMMENDATION	Process	ResponseAction	:PlanningRecommendation
2	vulnerable area	ENT_VULNERABLE_AREA	Entity	EquitySocial	:VulnerableArea
3	active mobility corridor	ENT_CORRIDOR	Entity	TransportNetwork	:Corridor
3	demand for active modes	PROP_ACTIVE_DEMAND	Property	Observation	:ActiveDemand
3	reallocation of space	PROC_SPACE_REALLOCATION	Process	Other	:SpaceReallocation
3	safety of active users	PROP_SAFETY	Property	Observation	:Safety
3	walking/cycling mode	ENT_ACTIVE_MODE	Entity	MobilityService	:ActiveMode
4	antifragile control algorithm	PROC_ANTIFRAGILE_CONTROL	Process	SystemState	:AntifragileControl
4	baseline algorithm	ENT_BASELINE_ALGO	Entity	Scenario	:BaselineAlgo
4	demand/supply shock	EVENT_DEMAND_SUPPLY_SHOCK	Event	DisruptionEvent	:DemandSupplyShock
4	disruption event	EVENT_DISRUPTION	Event	DisruptionEvent	:Disruption
4	performance under disruption	PROP_SYSTEM_PERFORMANCE	Property	DisruptionEvent	:SystemPerformance
5	eco-routing	PROC_ECO_ROUTING	Process	Other	:EcoRouting
5	emissions	PROP_EMISSIONS	Property	EnvironmentFactor	:Emissions
5	energy consumption	PROP_ENERGY_USE	Property	EnvironmentFactor	:EnergyUse
5	environmental target	STATE_ENV_TARGET	State	SystemState	:EnvTarget
5	mode shift to low-emission modes	PROC_MODE_SHIFT	Process	MobilityService	:ModeShift
6	access to services	PROP_SERVICE_ACCESS	Property	EquitySocial	:ServiceAccess
6	accessibility index	PROP_ACCESS_INDEX	Property	EquitySocial	:AccessIndex
6	distributional impact	PROP_DISTRIBUTIONAL_IMPACT	Property	EquitySocial	:DistributionalImpact
6	equity group	ENT_EQUITY_GROUP	Entity	EquitySocial	:EquityGroup
6	inclusive mobility intervention	PROC_INCLUSIVE_INTERVENTION	Process	MobilityService	:InclusiveIntervention
7	disruption history	ENT_DISRUPTION_HISTORY	Entity	DisruptionEvent	:DisruptionHistory
7	learning from past disruptions	PROC_LEARNING	Process	DisruptionEvent	:Learning

7	performance improvement	PROP_PERFORMANCE_DELTA	Property	SystemState	:PerformanceDelta
7	response strategy	PROC_RESPONSE_STRATEGY	Process	ResponseAction	:ResponseStrategy
7	uncertainty level	PROP_UNCERTAINTY	Property	Observation	:Uncertainty
8	adaptation plan	PROC_ADAPTATION_PLAN	Process	ResponseAction	:AdaptationPlan
8	climate stressor	ENT_CLIMATE_STRESSOR	Entity	EnvironmentFactor	:ClimateStressor
8	critical threshold	PROP_THRESHOLD	Property	Observation	:Threshold
8	exposure of infrastructure	PROP_INFRA_EXPOSURE	Property	TransportNetwork	:InfraExposure
8	long-term climate projection	ENT_CLIMATE_PROJECTION	Entity	EnvironmentFactor	:ClimateProjection
9	alert generation	PROC_ALERTING	Process	ResponseAction	:Alerting
9	event severity	PROP_SEVERITY	Property	Observation	:Severity
9	real-time incident detection	PROC_INCIDENT_DETECTION	Process	DisruptionEvent	:IncidentDetection
9	resource deployment	PROC_RESOURCE_DEPLOYMENT	Process	Other	:ResourceDeployment
9	response time	PROP_RESPONSE_TIME	Property	TemporalUnit	:ResponseTime
10	function configurability	PROP_CONFIGURABILITY	Property	Observation	:Configurability
10	multi-device access	PROP_MULTI_DEVICE	Property	EquitySocial	:MultiDevice
10	usability	PROP_USABILITY	Property	Observation	:Usability
10	user interface	ENT_UI	Entity	Other	:Ui
10	user profile	ENT_USER_PROFILE	Entity	Other	:UserProfile
11	causal effect estimation	PROC_CAUSAL_EVAL	Process	Other	:CausalEval
11	intervention	EVENT_INTERVENTION	Event	ResponseAction	:Intervention
11	intervention history	ENT_INTERVENTION_HISTORY	Entity	ResponseAction	:InterventionHistory
11	outcome monitoring	PROC_OUTCOME_MONITORING	Process	DataProvenance	:OutcomeMonitoring
11	policy update	PROC_POLICY_UPDATE	Process	Governance	:PolicyUpdate
12	baseline scenario	ENT_BASELINE_SCENARIO	Entity	Scenario	:BaselineScenario

12	multi-criteria evaluation	PROC_MC_EVAL	Process	Other	:McEval
12	ranking of scenarios	PROP_SCENARIO_RANK	Property	Scenario	:ScenarioRank
12	scenario	ENT_SCENARIO	Entity	Scenario	:Scenario
12	scenario outcome	PROP_SCENARIO_OUTCOME	Property	Scenario	:ScenarioOutcome
13	communication channel	ENT_COMM_CHANNEL	Entity	Other	:CommChannel
13	conflict resolution	PROC_CONFLICT_RESOLUTION	Process	Other	:ConflictResolution
13	coordination process	PROC_COORDINATION	Process	Other	:Coordination
13	shared action plan	ENT_ACTION_PLAN	Entity	Other	:ActionPlan
13	stakeholder group	ENT_STAKEHOLDER	Entity	Governance	:Stakeholder
14	antifragility score	PROP_ANTIFRAGILITY_SCORE	Property	SystemState	:AntifragilityScore
14	fragility metric	PROP_FRAGILITY_METRIC	Property	SystemState	:FragilityMetric
14	resilience indicator	PROP_RESILIENCE_INDEX	Property	SystemState	:ResilienceIndex
14	scoring method	PROC_SCORING_METHOD	Process	Other	:ScoringMethod
14	time-series performance	PROP_PERFORMANCE_TS	Property	SystemState	:PerformanceTs
15	impact range	PROP_IMPACT_RANGE	Property	Observation	:ImpactRange
15	risk assessment	PROC_RISK_ASSESSMENT	Process	Other	:RiskAssessment
15	scenario library	ENT_SCENARIO_LIBRARY	Entity	Scenario	:ScenarioLibrary
15	scenario probability	PROP_SCENARIO_PROB	Property	Scenario	:ScenarioProb
15	what-if scenario	ENT_WHATIF_SCENARIO	Entity	Scenario	:WhatifScenario
16	confidence in recommendation	PROP_RECOMMENDATION_CONF	Property	ResponseAction	:RecommendationConf
16	decision criteria	PROP_DECISION_CRITERIA	Property	Observation	:DecisionCriteria
16	multi-scenario evaluation	PROC_MULTI_SCENARIO_EVAL	Process	Scenario	:MultiScenarioEval
16	option set	ENT_ACTION_OPTIONS	Entity	Other	:ActionOptions
16	recommended action	ENT_RECOMMENDED_ACTION	Entity	Other	:RecommendedAction
17	consultation event	EVENT_CONSULTATION	Event	Other	:Consultation

17	participatory input process	PROC_PARTICIPATORY_INPUT	Process	Other	:ParticipatoryInput
17	requirement refinement	PROC_REQUIREMENT_REFINEMENT	Process	Other	:RequirementRefinement
17	stakeholder feedback	ENT_STAKEHOLDER_FEEDBACK	Entity	Governance	:StakeholderFeedback
18	graph query	PROC_GRAPH_QUERY	Process	TransportNetwork	:GraphQuery
18	graph representation of city	ENT_GRAPH	Entity	TransportNetwork	:Graph
18	network edge	ENT_EDGE	Entity	TransportNetwork	:Edge
18	network node	ENT_NODE	Entity	TransportNetwork	:Node
18	path computation	PROC_PATH_COMPUTE	Process	Other	:PathCompute
19	cascade effect	EVENT_CASCADE	Event	DisruptionEvent	:Cascade
19	domain (transport/health/economy)	ENT_DOMAIN	Entity	Other	:Domain
19	interdependency	REL_INTERDEPENDENCY	Relationship	Other	:Interdependency
19	multi-domain disruption propagation	PROC_PROPAGATION	Process	DisruptionEvent	:Propagation
20	disruptive scenario	ENT_DISRUPTIVE_SCENARIO	Entity	Scenario	:DisruptiveScenario
20	hazard type	ENT_HAZARD_TYPE	Entity	DisruptionEvent	:HazardType
20	magnitude	PROP_MAGNITUDE	Property	Observation	:Magnitude
20	scenario generation	PROC_SCENARIO_GENERATION	Process	Scenario	:ScenarioGeneration
20	sensitivity analysis	PROC_SENSITIVITY_ANALYSIS	Process	Scenario	:SensitivityAnalysis
21	calibration to case	PROC_SCALE_CALIBRATION	Process	DataProvenance	:ScaleCalibration
21	comparability across scenarios	PROP_COMPARABILITY	Property	Scenario	:Comparability
21	impact scale	ENT_IMPACT_SCALE	Entity	Other	:ImpactScale
21	qualitative category	PROP_QUAL_CATEGORY	Property	Observation	:QualCategory
21	severity scale	ENT_SEVERITY_SCALE	Entity	Other	:SeverityScale
22	compliance rate	PROP_COMPLIANCE	Property	Observation	:Compliance

22	false alarm rate	PROP_FALSE_ALARM	Property	Observation	:FalseAlarm
22	lead time	PROP_LEAD_TIME	Property	TemporalUnit	:LeadTime
22	predicted disruption	STATE_PREDICTED_DISRUPTION	State	DisruptionEvent	:PredictedDisruption
22	proactive rerouting	PROC_PROACTIVE_REROUTE	Process	TransportNetwork	:ProactiveReroute
23	central server	ENT_CENTRAL_SERVER	Entity	Other	:CentralServer
23	edge computing node	ENT_EDGE_NODE	Entity	TransportNetwork	:EdgeNode
23	local control logic	PROC_LOCAL_CONTROL	Process	Other	:LocalControl
23	operational continuity	STATE_OPERATIONAL_CONTINUITY	State	SystemState	:OperationalContinuity
23	outage event	EVENT_OUTAGE	Event	DisruptionEvent	:Outage
24	emission reduction control	PROC_EMISSION_CONTROL	Process	EnvironmentFactor	:EmissionControl
24	fuel/energy use	PROP_FUEL_USE	Property	EnvironmentFactor	:FuelUse
24	idling time	PROP_IDLING	Property	Observation	:Idling
24	peak period	PROP_PEAK_PERIOD	Property	TemporalUnit	:PeakPeriod
24	signal timing plan	ENT_SIGNAL_PLAN	Entity	TransportNetwork	:SignalPlan
25	asset	ENT_ASSET	Entity	TransportNetwork	:Asset
25	failure risk	PROP_FAILURE_RISK	Property	Observation	:FailureRisk
25	maintenance schedule	PROC_MAINT_SCHED	Process	Other	:MaintSched
25	predictive maintenance model	ENT_PRED_MAINT_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:PredMaintModel
25	remaining useful life	PROP_RUL	Property	Observation	:Rul
26	congestion during evacuation	STATE_EVAC_CONGESTION	State	SystemState	:EvacCongestion
26	evacuation route	ENT_EVAC_ROUTE	Entity	TransportNetwork	:EvacRoute
26	prioritization rule	PROP_PRIORITY_RULE	Property	Observation	:PriorityRule
26	priority vehicle	ENT_PRIORITY_VEHICLE	Entity	MobilityService	:PriorityVehicle

26	rerouting strategy	PROC_REROUTE	Process	TransportNetwork	:Reroute
27	compliance status	PROP_COMPLIANCE	Property	Observation	:Compliance
27	legal constraint	ENT_LEGAL_CONSTRAINT	Entity	Governance	:LegalConstraint
27	legal scenario	ENT_LEGAL_SCENARIO	Entity	Governance	:LegalScenario
27	policy change event	EVENT_POLICY_CHANGE	Event	Governance	:PolicyChange
27	regulation	ENT_REGULATION	Entity	Governance	:Regulation
28	cross-border movement	PROC_CROSS_BORDER_FLOW	Process	Other	:CrossBorderFlow
28	geographic layer	ENT_GEO_LAYER	Entity	SpatialUnit	:GeoLayer
28	jurisdiction boundary	ENT_BOUNDARY	Entity	SpatialUnit	:Boundary
28	no-go area	ENT_NO_GO_AREA	Entity	SpatialUnit	:NoGoArea
28	spatial constraint	PROP_SPATIAL_CONSTRAINT	Property	SpatialUnit	:SpatialConstraint
29	access to critical services	PROP_SERVICE_ACCESS	Property	EquitySocial	:ServiceAccess
29	citizen segment	ENT_CITIZEN_SEGMENT	Entity	EquitySocial	:CitizenSegment
29	disruption exposure	PROP_EXPOSURE	Property	DisruptionEvent	:Exposure
29	mobility condition	PROP_MOBILITY_CONDITION	Property	MobilityService	:MobilityCondition
29	trip necessity	PROP_TRIP_NECESSITY	Property	MobilityService	:TripNecessity
30	calibration process	PROC_CALIBRATION	Process	DataProvenance	:Calibration
30	data quality	PROP_DATA_QUALITY	Property	DataProvenance	:DataQuality
30	historical traffic dataset	ENT_TRAFFIC_DATASET	Entity	DataProvenance	:TrafficDataset
30	real-time speed/flow	PROP_SPEED_FLOW	Property	Observation	:SpeedFlow
30	traffic sensor	ENT_TRAFFIC_SENSOR	Entity	DataProvenance	:TrafficSensor
31	choice model	ENT_CHOICE_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:ChoiceModel
31	mode choice	PROC_MODE_CHOICE	Process	MobilityService	:ModeChoice
31	route choice	PROC_ROUTE_CHOICE	Process	TransportNetwork	:RouteChoice
31	stated vs revealed preference	PROP_PREF_TYPE	Property	SystemState	:PrefType

31	user preference	PROP_USER_PREFERENCE	Property	Observation	:UserPreference
32	access rights	PROP_ACCESS_RIGHTS	Property	EquitySocial	:AccessRights
32	governance level	ENT_GOV_LEVEL	Entity	Governance	:GovLevel
32	multi-level user group	ENT_USER_GROUP	Entity	EquitySocial	:UserGroup
32	shared protocol	ENT_PROTOCOL	Entity	Governance	:Protocol
32	synchronization process	PROC_SYNCHRONISATION	Process	Other	:Synchronisation
33	emergency type	ENT_EMERGENCY_TYPE	Entity	DisruptionEvent	:EmergencyType
33	limited resource allocation	PROC_RESOURCE_ALLOCATION	Process	Other	:ResourceAlloc
33	priority rule	PROP_PRIORITY_RULE	Property	Observation	:PriorityRule
33	response level	PROP_RESPONSE_LEVEL	Property	ResponseAction	:ResponseLevel
33	triage for incidents	PROC_TRIAGE	Process	DisruptionEvent	:Triage
34	alternative route	ENT_ALTERNATIVE_ROUTE	Entity	TransportNetwork	:AlternativeRoute
34	blocked route	STATE_BLOCKED_ROUTE	State	TransportNetwork	:BlockedRoute
34	emergency response service	ENT_EMERGENCY_SERVICE	Entity	DisruptionEvent	:EmergencyService
34	response time to incident	PROP_RESPONSE_TIME	Property	DisruptionEvent	:ResponseTime
34	service coverage	PROP_COVERAGE	Property	Observation	:Coverage
35	demand shift between modes	PROC_DEMAND_SHIFT	Process	Other	:DemandShift
35	intermodal transfer	PROC_INTERMODAL_TRANSFER	Process	MobilityService	:IntermodalTransfer
35	mode interaction effect	PROP_MODE_INTERACTION	Property	MobilityService	:ModeInteraction
35	substitution/complementarity	REL_SUBSTITUTION_COMPLEMENT	Relationship	Other	:SubstitutionComplement
35	transport mode	ENT_MODE	Entity	MobilityService	:Mode
36	audit trail	PROC_AUDIT	Process	Other	:Audit
36	confidence level	PROP_CONFIDENCE	Property	DataProvenance	:Confidence
36	data source	ENT_DATA_SOURCE	Entity	DataProvenance	:DataSource

36	provenance record	ENT_PROVENANCE	Entity	DataProvenance	:Provenance
36	timestamp	PROP_TIMESTAMP	Property	TemporalUnit	:Timestamp
36	trust score	PROP_TRUST_SCORE	Property	DataProvenance	:TrustScore
37	compensation scenario	ENT_COMP_SCENARIO	Entity	Scenario	:CompScenario
37	cost per group	PROP_COST_PER_GROUP	Property	EquitySocial	:CostPerGroup
37	economic cost of disruption	PROP_ECON_COST	Property	DisruptionEvent	:EconCost
37	economic model	ENT_ECON_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:EconModel
37	productivity loss	PROP_PRODUCTIVITY_LOSS	Property	Observation	:ProductivityLoss
38	anonymisation method	PROC_ANONYMISATION	Process	Other	:Anonymisation
38	cyber-attack event	EVENT_CYBER_ATTACK	Event	DisruptionEvent	:CyberAttack
38	legal basis	PROP_LEGAL_BASIS	Property	Governance	:LegalBasis
38	personal data	ENT_PERSONAL_DATA	Entity	DataProvenance	:PersonalData
38	privacy risk	PROP_PRIVACY_RISK	Property	Observation	:PrivacyRisk
38	security protocol	ENT_SECURITY_PROTOCOL	Entity	Governance	:SecurityProtocol
39	consistency indicator	PROP_CONSISTENCY	Property	Observation	:Consistency
39	data stream per mode	ENT_MODE_STREAM	Entity	MobilityService	:ModeStream
39	fused mobility dataset	ENT_FUSED_DATA	Entity	MobilityService	:FusedData
39	fusion algorithm	PROC_FUSION	Process	DataProvenance	:Fusion
39	temporal alignment	PROC_TEMP_ALIGNMENT	Process	Other	:TempAlignment
40	KPI	ENT_KPI	Entity	Observation	:Kpi
40	alert when KPI breached	PROC_KPI_ALERT	Process	ResponseAction	:KpiAlert
40	current performance	PROP_CURRENT_VALUE	Property	Observation	:CurrentValue
40	dashboard	ENT_DASHBOARD	Entity	DataProvenance	:Dashboard

40	target value	PROP_TARGET	Property	Observation	:Target
41	behaviour change metric	PROP_BEHAVIOUR_CHANGE	Property	Observation	:BehaviourChange
41	behavioural nudge	PROC_NUDGE	Process	ResponseAction	:Nudge
41	feedback to user	PROC_FEEDBACK	Process	Other	:Feedback
41	reward/incentive	ENT_INCENTIVE	Entity	Other	:Incentive
41	sustainable choice	PROP_SUSTAINABLE_CHOICE	Property	EnvironmentFactor	:SustainableChoice
42	benchmarking metric	PROP_BENCHMARK_METRIC	Property	Observation	:BenchmarkMetric
42	source city	ENT_CITY_SOURCE	Entity	Other	:CitySource
42	target city	ENT_CITY_TARGET	Entity	Observation	:CityTarget
42	transferability assessment	PROC_TRANSFER_ASSESS	Process	Other	:TransferAssess
42	transferable strategy	ENT_STRATEGY	Entity	Other	:Strategy
43	alert for inequity	PROC_EQUITY_ALERT	Process	EquitySocial	:EquityAlert
43	benefit distribution	PROP_BENEFIT_DIST	Property	Observation	:BenefitDist
43	equity KPI	PROP_EQUITY_KPI	Property	EquitySocial	:EquityKpi
43	real-time monitoring process	PROC_EQUITY_MONITOR	Process	EquitySocial	:EquityMonitor
43	risk exposure by group	PROP_RISK_EXPOSURE	Property	EquitySocial	:RiskExposure
44	PESTEL factor	ENT_PESTEL_FACTOR	Entity	EnvironmentFactor	:PestelFactor
44	economic indicator	ENT_ECON_INDICATOR	Entity	Other	:EconIndicator
44	legal constraint	ENT_LEGAL_CONSTRAINT	Entity	Governance	:LegalConstraint
44	political context	ENT_POLITICAL_CONTEXT	Entity	Other	:PoliticalContext
44	social vulnerability	PROP_SOCIAL_VULNERABILITY	Property	EquitySocial	:SocialVulnerability
45	adaptive vs transformative response	STATE_ADAPTIVE_TRANSFORMATIVE	State	SystemState	:AdaptiveTransformative
45	long-term learning process	PROC_LONGTERM_LEARNING	Process	Other	:LongtermLearning
45	path dependency	PROP_PATH_DEPENDENCY	Property	Observation	:PathDependency
45	structural change	EVENT_STRUCTURAL_CHANGE	Event	Other	:StructuralChange

45	transformative measure	ENT_TRANSFORM_MEASURE	Entity	Other	:TransformMeasure
46	anomaly detection	PROC_ANOMALY_DETECTION	Process	Other	:AnomalyDetect
46	data latency	PROP_LATENCY	Property	DataProvenance	:Latency
46	integrated sensor network	ENT_SENSOR_NETWORK	Entity	TransportNetwork	:SensorNetwork
46	lag time	PROP_LAG_TIME	Property	TemporalUnit	:LagTime
46	real-time analytics engine	ENT_ANALYTICS_ENGINE	Entity	DataProvenance	:AnalyticsEngine
47	capacity utilisation	PROP_CAPACITY_UTIL	Property	Observation	:CapacityUtil
47	contingency plan	ENT_CONTINGENCY_PLAN	Entity	Other	:ContingencyPlan
47	dynamic adjustment	PROC_DYNAMIC_ADJUST	Process	Other	:DynamicAdjust
47	fleet allocation	PROC_FLEET_ALLOC	Process	MobilityService	:FleetAlloc
47	route plan	ENT_ROUTE_PLAN	Entity	TransportNetwork	:RoutePlan
48	crisis event	EVENT_CRISIS	Event	DisruptionEvent	:Crisis
48	event lifecycle	PROC_EVENT_LIFECYCLE	Process	Other	:EventLifecycle
48	event management centre	ENT_EVENT_CENTRE	Entity	Other	:EventCentre
48	multi-agency coordination	PROC_MULTIAGENCY_COORD	Process	Governance	:MultiagencyCoord
48	overload state	STATE_OVERLOAD	State	SystemState	:Overload
49	coordination platform	ENT_PLATFORM	Entity	Other	:Platform
49	information sharing	PROC_INFO_SHARING	Process	Other	:InfoSharing
49	participating agency	ENT_AGENCY	Entity	Governance	:Agency
49	role/responsibility	PROP_ROLE	Property	Observation	:Role
49	shared situation picture	ENT_SITREP	Entity	Other	:Sitrep
50	forecast uncertainty	PROP_FORECAST_UNCERTAINTY	Property	Scenario	:ForecastUncertainty
50	forecasting model	ENT_FORECAST_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:ForecastModel

50	scenario analysis system	ENT_SCENARIO_SYSTEM	Entity	Scenario	:ScenarioSystem
50	scenario comparison	PROC_SCENARIO_COMPARE	Process	Scenario	:ScenarioCompare
50	time horizon	PROP_TIME_HORIZON	Property	TemporalUnit	:TimeHorizon
51	alarm threshold	PROP_THRESHOLD	Property	Observation	:Threshold
51	congestion state	STATE_CONGESTION	State	SystemState	:Congestion
51	incident detection	PROC_INCIDENT_DETECTION	Process	DisruptionEvent	:IncidentDetect
51	traffic monitoring module	ENT_MONITOR_MODULE	Entity	DataProvenance	:MonitorModule
51	visualisation on map	PROC_MAP_VIS	Process	Other	:MapVis
52	incident response recommendation	PROC_INCIDENT_RESPONSE_REC	Process	DisruptionEvent	:IncidentResponseRec
52	prediction error	PROP_PRED_ERROR	Property	Observation	:PredError
52	prediction model	ENT_PRED_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:PredModel
52	short-term traffic forecast	PROP_SHORT_TERM_FORECAST	Property	Scenario	:ShortTermForecast
52	update frequency	PROP_UPDATE_FREQ	Property	Observation	:UpdateFreq
53	experiment run	PROC_EXPERIMENT_RUN	Process	Other	:ExperimentRun
53	scenario input	ENT_SCENARIO_INPUT	Entity	Scenario	:ScenarioInput
53	simulated impact	PROP_SIM_IMPACT	Property	Scenario	:SimImpact
53	simulation model	ENT_SIM_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:SimModel
53	unexpected event	EVENT_UNEXPECTED	Event	DisruptionEvent	:Unexpected
54	Before-after comparison	PROC_BEFORE_AFTER	Process	Other	:BeforeAfter
54	evaluation period	PROP_EVAL_PERIOD	Property	TemporalUnit	:EvalPeriod
54	impact on flows	PROP_FLOW_CHANGE	Property	Observation	:FlowChange
54	modal split change	PROP_MODE_SPLIT_CHANGE	Property	MobilityService	:ModeSplitChange
54	transport measure	ENT_MEASURE	Entity	Other	:Measure
55	PT vehicle movement	ENT_PT_MOVEMENT	Entity	MobilityService	:PtMovement

55	cyclist flow	PROP_CYCLE_FLOW	Property	Observation	:CycleFlow
55	integrated multi-modal dataset	ENT_MULTIMODAL_DATA	Entity	DataProvenance	:MultimodalData
55	passenger volume	PROP_PASSENGER_VOLUME	Property	Observation	:PassengerVolume
55	pedestrian flow	PROP_PEDE_FLOW	Property	Observation	:PedeFlow
56	data sharing agreement	ENT_DATA_SHARING_AGREEMENT	Entity	DataProvenance	:DataSharingAgreement
56	governance level	ENT_GOV_LEVEL	Entity	Governance	:GovLevel
56	interoperability requirement	PROP_INTEROPERABILITY	Property	Observation	:Interoperability
56	openness level	PROP_OPENNESS	Property	Observation	:Openness
56	organisation	ENT_ORG	Entity	Governance	:Org
57	agent-based digital twin	ENT_DIGITAL_TWIN	Entity	Other	:DigitalTwin
57	continuous calibration	PROC_CALIBRATION	Process	SystemState	:Calibration
57	multimodal mobility simulation	PROC_SIMULATION	Process	Scenario	:Simulation
57	behaviour observation	ENT_BEHAVIOUR_DATA	Entity	Observation	:BehaviourData
57	routing rule update	PROC_RULE_UPDATE	Process	ResponseAction	:RuleUpdate
58	epidemic spread model	ENT_EPIDEMIC_MODEL	Entity	DisruptionEvent	:EpidemicModel
58	contact-risk score	PROP_CONTACT_RISK	Property	Observation	:ContactRisk
58	dynamic mobility model	ENT_MOBILITY_MODEL	Entity	MobilityService	:MobilityModel
58	epidemic control policy	ENT_EPIDEMIC_POLICY	Entity	Governance	:EpidemicPolicy
58	outbreak recalibration	PROC_OUTBREAK_RECALIB	Process	ResponseAction	:OutbreakRecalibration
59	microgrid	ENT_MICROGRID	Entity	TransportNetwork	:Microgrid
59	power island reconfiguration	PROC_POWER_RECONFIG	Process	ResponseAction	:PowerReconfiguration
59	grid disruption	EVENT_GRID_DISRUPTION	Event	DisruptionEvent	:GridDisruption
59	node criticality ranking	PROP_CRITICALITY	Property	TransportNetwork	:Criticality
59	critical mobility asset	ENT_CRITICAL_ASSET	Entity	TransportNetwork	:CriticalAsset

60	evolutionary optimisation	PROC_EVOLUTIONARY_OPT	Process	ResponseAction	:EvolutionaryOptimisation
60	network configuration	ENT_NETWORK_CONFIG	Entity	TransportNetwork	:NetworkConfiguration
60	lane allocation	PROC_LANE_ALLOCATION	Process	TransportNetwork	:LaneAllocation
60	fleet distribution	ENT_FLEET_DISTRIBUTION	Entity	MobilityService	:FleetDistribution
60	stress performance	PROP_STRESS_PERF	Property	SystemState	:StressPerformance
61	near-miss data	ENT_NEAR_MISS	Entity	Observation	:NearMissData
61	autonomous vehicle incident	EVENT_AV_INCIDENT	Event	DisruptionEvent	:AVIncident
61	systemic failure pattern	ENT_FAILURE_PATTERN	Entity	DisruptionEvent	:FailurePattern
61	operational design domain	ENT_ODD	Entity	Governance	:OperationalDesignDomain
61	signalling rule update	PROC_SIGNAL_UPDATE	Process	ResponseAction	:SignalUpdate

Table 5. Extracted concepts to requirements and ontology classes

13.1.3 A.3 Competency Questions

The competency questions below (**Table 6**) consolidate and harmonise information needs gathered throughout WP2, including questions first articulated in the urban event mapping (D2.1) and equilibrium analysis (D2.3), so that a single CQ list drives ontology design and validation. This table lists 131 competency questions extracted from requirements. Columns are: CQ ID: Unique identifier for each competency question (e.g., CQ-001), Competency Question: The natural-language question the ontology should be able to answer (typically via SPARQL once populated), Req: Requirement_ID(s) the CQ traces back to, Title: Requirement title for quick contextual interpretation of the CQ.

CQ ID	Competency Question	Req #	Title
CQ-001	1. What is the average travel time per mode for all trips in the CBD?	1	Maximize individual mobility
CQ-002	2. Which modes or streets experience the largest delays, and how can these be mitigated?	1	Maximize individual mobility
CQ-003	3. How does lane reallocation affect total person-hours travelled and distribution of travel time across socio-economic groups?	1	Maximize individual mobility
CQ-004	4. Which interventions most effectively reduce peak congestion compared to a baseline scenario with fixed infrastructure allocation?	1	Maximize individual mobility
CQ-005	5. How does the expected redistribution of travel demand affect peripheral communities?	1	Maximize individual mobility

CQ-006	1. Which areas would benefit most from densification or peripheral development to reduce long trips (>10 km)?	2	Urban planning suggestions
CQ-007	2. How do different land-use interventions affect congestion hotspots, travel times, and modal choices across the city?	2	Urban planning suggestions
CQ-008	3. How can interventions be prioritized to maximize overall mobility efficiency and equity?	2	Urban planning suggestions
CQ-009	4. Which densification or decentralization measures yield the largest reduction in long trips?	2	Urban planning suggestions
CQ-010	1. Which street segments have the highest demand for active mobility and are candidates for lane reallocation?	3	Active mobility
CQ-011	2. What is the expected increase in active mode uptake and resulting impact on congestion for motorized traffic?	3	Active mobility
CQ-012	3. How much reduction in CO ₂ and pollutant emissions can be achieved under peak and off-peak conditions?	3	Active mobility
CQ-013	4. Are there any groups disadvantaged by lane reallocation, and what mitigation measures can be implemented?	3	Active mobility
CQ-014	1. How to translate a given disruption from the previous WPs as a disruption in the simulation?	4	Antifragile against disruptions
CQ-015	2. Which regions are to be protected from incoming traffic and which are associated traffic lights?	4	Antifragile against disruptions
CQ-016	3. What is the system performance under no control / state-of-the-art optimal control algorithm	4	Antifragile against disruptions
CQ-017	4. What is the system performance under antifragile control algorithm	4	Antifragile against disruptions
CQ-019	1. Which pollutants can be examined within the given framework and simulation software	5	Environment-friendly
CQ-020	2. What is the pollutant emission under no control / state-of-the-art optimal control algorithm	5	Environment-friendly
CQ-021	3. What is the pollutant emission under antifragile control algorithm	5	Environment-friendly
CQ-022	1. How does the system measure and monitor travel-time equity across different neighbourhoods?	6	Equitable access and inclusive mobility
CQ-023	2. What data sources are used to identify underserved or mobility-poor areas?	6	Equitable access and inclusive mobility
CQ-024	3. Do mobility interventions incorporate community feedback from marginalized or peripheral populations?	6	Equitable access and inclusive mobility
CQ-025	1. How does the system capture and store data from past disruptions?	7	Antifragile disruption response

CQ-026	2. What metrics indicate improved performance in response to recurring or similar disruptions?	7	Antifragile disruption response
CQ-027	1. What data and partnerships (e.g., meteorological services, urban planners) support the climate adaptation models?	8	Climate stress anticipation
CQ-028	2. Are vulnerable populations (e.g., elderly, low-income, carless households) considered in climate stress adaptation planning?	8	Climate stress anticipation
CQ-029	3. Which climate scenarios and time horizons are integrated into the system's models?	8	Climate stress anticipation
CQ-030	1. What are the hardware requirements for the system?	9	Quick response to events
CQ-031	2. How to efficiently integrate and manage the data flow from different sources?	9	Quick response to events
CQ-032	3. How to turn simulation results into actionable strategies?	9	Quick response to events
CQ-033	1. What functions should be integrated into the interface?	10	User-friendly and versatile functions
CQ-034	2. How to clearly deliver the functions by graphs or other manners?	10	User-friendly and versatile functions
CQ-035	3. How to design the modules of interface to align with the needs from users?	10	User-friendly and versatile functions
CQ-036	1. For a given intervention, how did key KPIs (e.g. travel time, reliability, equity index, emissions) change compared to the baseline scenario?	11	Learning from interventions
CQ-037	2. Which past interventions are most similar to the current context (disruption type, location, time of day), and what outcomes did they produce?	11	Learning from interventions
CQ-038	3. Which parameter changes (e.g. signal timing, pricing, communication measures, PT reinforcement) are statistically associated with improved performance?	11	Learning from interventions
CQ-039	4. Given the current disruption, which previously tested strategy is expected to work best, and with what confidence?	11	Learning from interventions
CQ-040	1. For disruption type X (e.g. flood, strike), how do key KPIs (recovery time, person-hours of delay, equity index, emissions) compare across cities A, B, and C under similar conditions?	12	Comparative scenario evaluation
CQ-041	2. Which response strategies (e.g. detours, communication measures) consistently achieve the best performance across comparable cities or network typologies?	12	Comparative scenario evaluation
CQ-042	3. How can we cluster or group cities/scenarios so that comparisons are made only between truly	12	Comparative scenario evaluation

	comparable cases (similar scale, network structure, demand patterns, hazard intensity)?		
CQ-043	4. What lessons or parameter settings from city A's successful strategy can be transferred and adapted to city B, and what changes are needed for local context?	12	Comparative scenario evaluation
CQ-044	5. Over time, which cities show the largest improvement in antifragility KPIs for a given disruption type, and which strategies contributed most to that improvement?	12	Comparative scenario evaluation
CQ-045	1. Which stakeholders (e.g. municipality, police, emergency services) are currently involved in managing a given disruption, and what actions have each one taken and when?	13	Stakeholder coordination
CQ-046	2. Are there any conflicting plans or commands between stakeholders (e.g. different detour routes, different priorities), and how can the system highlight and help resolve them?	13	Stakeholder coordination
CQ-047	3. How long does it take from incident detection to a coordinated response agreed by all relevant stakeholders?	13	Stakeholder coordination
CQ-048	4. What information must be visible to each stakeholder on the shared dashboard to support fast and consistent decisions?	13	Stakeholder coordination
CQ-049	5. After a disruption, how can the system summarise who did what, when, and with what impact, so stakeholders can learn and improve future coordination?	13	Stakeholder coordination
CQ-050	1. What is the antifragility score of city X for disruption type Y (e.g. flood, strike, heatwave), and how has it changed over time?	14	Antifragility Score Calculation
CQ-051	2. Which indicators (e.g. recovery time, variability of performance, equity of access, emissions) contribute most to the antifragility score, and how are they weighted?	14	Antifragility Score Calculation
CQ-052	3. How does the antifragility score of city X compare to similar cities (size, network type, hazard profile), and which factors explain the differences?	14	Antifragility Score Calculation
CQ-053	1. For event X and proposed action A (e.g. road closure, detour), what are the predicted impacts on key KPIs (travel time, reliability, equity, emissions) compared to a "do nothing" baseline and alternative actions?	15	Possible Scenario Evaluation
CQ-054	2. How do the results change under different assumptions about disruption severity, demand levels, or user compliance (i.e. how robust is action A across multiple scenarios)?	15	Possible Scenario Evaluation

CQ-055	3. Which areas, modes, and population groups benefit or are negatively affected in each scenario, and how large are these effects?	15	Possible Scenario Evaluation
CQ-056	1. How does the recommended option compare to the second-best and to the “do nothing” baseline? What are the main assumptions, uncertainties, and data sources behind the recommendation, and how confident is the system in this choice?	16	Recommended action suggestion
CQ-057	2. What are the main assumptions, uncertainties, and data sources behind the recommendation, and how confident is the system in this choice?	16	Recommended action suggestion
CQ-058	1. When stakeholders add new information (e.g. a local constraint, a corrected value, a new priority), how does this change the system’s parameters or scenarios, and can we still see what the values were before?	17	Stakeholder input
CQ-059	2. What is the timestamp, source and confidence level of each stakeholder contribution, and how does this influence the weight of that information in future analyses or recommendations?	17	Stakeholder input
CQ-060	1. How are events, places, infrastructure, stakeholders and indicators linked to each other in the graph for a given city?	18	Graph Database
CQ-061	2. When new data arrives (e.g. a new disruption), how is it added to the graph and connected to existing nodes and relationships?	18	Graph Database
CQ-062	1. How are the different component aspects of the urban system affected during the evolution of a disruptive event?	19	Interdisciplinary propagation of disruptive events
CQ-063	2. What is the common assessment for the observed impacts across the different component aspects?	19	Interdisciplinary propagation of disruptive events
CQ-064	3. How can these diverse impacts be comparably assessed and ranked based on the vulnerability or sensitivity of the examined components?	19	Interdisciplinary propagation of disruptive events
CQ-065	4. Which is the prioritization of mitigation and adaptation strategies, considering the intricate interdependencies within urban systems?	19	Interdisciplinary propagation of di
CQ-066	1. How sensitive are the examined systems to disruptive events of increasing magnitude? For example, how significantly would a 5cm increase in floodwater affect the mobility system's functionality?	20	Development of alternative disruptive scenarios
CQ-067	2. What are the limit states of urban mobility systems, and what fail-safe adaptation measures should be developed or revised to address them?	20	Development of alternative disruptive scenarios

CQ-068	1. How do the proposed adaptation measures compare against each other and with the existing conditions?	21	Determination of qualitative and ca
CQ-069	2. How can these proposed measures be ranked based on their effectiveness in restoring or improving the urban mobility system's functionality?	21	Determination of qualitative and case-specific scales for disruption severity and impact
CQ-070	3. Which outputs of the API are transferable to existing urban management and planning frameworks, comprehensible and explicit to end-users, and readily applicable in real-time decision-making?	21	Determination of qualitative and case-specific scales for disruption severity and impact
CQ-071	1. How many minutes before predicted flooding does the system issue proactive rerouting commands?	22	Learn to reroute proactively
CQ-072	2. How accurately does the system predict the timing and severity of the flooding?	22	Learn to reroute proactively
CQ-073	3. Which bus lines receive reroutes, and what is the expected vs. actual delay reduction?	22	Learn to reroute proactively
CQ-074	4. Does proactive rerouting actually improve bus reliability and travel time?	22	Learn to reroute proactively
CQ-075	5. Are the alternative routes safe and functionally suitable for buses?	22	Learn to reroute proactively
CQ-076	1. Which intersections continued autonomous operation during the outage, and what control logic was used?	23	Resilient Edge Processing Units
CQ-077	2. How long did each node remain functional, and what performance deviations occurred?	23	Resilient Edge Processing Units
CQ-078	1. Which is the critical parameter of the traffic flow that determines the operation of the smart traffic lights?	24	Energy Optimization and Emission Reduction Control
CQ-079	2. Which are the consequences of the total urban network system?	24	Energy Optimization and Emission Reduction Control
CQ-080	3. How does the dynamic traffic light affect total person-hours travelled groups?	24	Energy Optimization and Emission Reduction Control
CQ-081	4. How many smart equipment are needed to implement	24	Energy Optimization and Emission Reduction Control
CQ-082	5. How does the system prioritize between delay minimization and emission reduction?	24	Energy Optimization and Emission Reduction Control
CQ-083	1. Which are the critical indicators will be measured, and which are the upper limit before the failure?	25	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance
CQ-084	2. Which are the consequences of this failure in the transport system operation?	25	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance
CQ-085	3. Are there any adaptation measures from the protection of the failure?	25	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance
CQ-086	4. Which infrastructure nodes have predicted failure probabilities \geq threshold in the next 7 days?	25	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance

CQ-087	5. How accurate were the last 30 predictive alerts compared to real outcomes?	25	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance
CQ-088	1. Which populations and districts must be prioritized given hazard severity + vulnerability + network capacity constraints?	26	Evacuation and Rerouting Prioritization
CQ-089	2. What percentage of the population can be evacuated within 15, 30, 60, and 120 minutes under real-time conditions?	26	Evacuation and Rerouting Prioritization
CQ-090	3. How are optimal evacuation routes under evolving road damage and congestion conditions being planned?	26	Evacuation and Rerouting Prioritization
CQ-091	1. The creation of a rapid passage route for emergency vehicles will be necessary. With which parameters and priorities will the fastest and safest route be determined?	32	Multi users and levels coordination and synchronization
CQ-092	2. This is not a general event but a specific - local event. Is it possible for administrators to add such sub-models in order to build the general algorithm of «Antifragility»?	32	Multi users and levels coordination and synchronization
CQ-093	3. Will the system administrator be able to create black swans for simulation?	32	Multi users and levels coordination
CQ-094	4. If we use secondary roads and not central arteries in the simulation, what will be the final results, in terms of the disruption caused to the system?	32	Multi users and levels coordination and synchronization
CQ-095	1. What will be the overall results in the city? Which streets should be excluded as dangerous, and by what criteria?	33	Prioritization of emergency situations
CQ-096	2. How do weather conditions affect traffic in combination with such an event? How does the system in a simulation perceive weather conditions as a parameter?	33	Prioritization of emergency situations
CQ-097	3. Is the circulation of Public Transport affected, should it be stopped or should it take on another role?	33	Prioritization of emergency situations
CQ-098	1. How much has the effectiveness of the emergency response services been affected (e.g. how much time will an ambulance need to reach its destination given the disruption)?	34	Mobility of emergency response services
CQ-099	2. How much time is it expected to take in order for the disruption to be addressed (e.g. clearing the road and restoring traffic flow)?	34	Mobility of emergency response services
CQ-100	3. What is the best alternative route for different emergency response services to achieve, for example, 90% of the original effectiveness (considering that a resilient service does not need to regain 100% of its functionality given a disruption)?	34	Mobility of emergency response services

CQ-101	1. How much is it expected that traffic will be increased in different urban transport modes given the disruption?	35	Interactions between transport modes
CQ-102	2. What is the probability/likelihood that the given disruption can lead to disruptions in the other transport modes (e.g. gridlocks in road networks)?	35	Interactions between transport modes
CQ-103	3. How much time would it take to reach a destination with different alternative transport modes?	35	Interactions between transport modes
CQ-104	1. For the disruption at time T, list every data source we used to make recommendations for elderly and low-income people in the chosen area (e.g., Cardiff city centre).	36	Data Provenance and Trust Management
CQ-105	2. For each source, say how it was produced (method), what the legal terms for using the data are (licence), and how trustworthy it is (confidence).	36	Data Provenance and Trust Management
CQ-106	1. After the last flood, how much money did people lose per person, comparing hourly-paid workers in the Periphery AOI with salaried workers in the city-centre AOI, and where did the pay data come from?	37	Economic Impact Modelling
CQ-107	1. Which data used for real-time mobility includes personal info, what legal basis is used (e.g., consent), and what anonymisation is applied?	38	Cybersecurity and Privacy Protection
CQ-108	2. Which groups show the highest privacy risk score, and what controls (access limits, aggregation) were applied? Did any group lose service access because of these controls?	38	Cybersecurity and Privacy Protection
CQ-109	3. Was mobility data processed on the device or in the cloud? What security certification covers it, and when?	38	Cybersecurity and Privacy Protection
CQ-110	1. For the disruption, which travel data streams did we combine (e.g., live buses/trains, road sensors, bike-share), and are they lined up to the same time and map area?	39	Multi-Modal Data Fusion
CQ-111	2. In the last public-transport strike, how did results change when we used step-free station availability data compared with general station data (what was used, how well matched)?	39	Multi-Modal Data Fusion
CQ-112	1. After recent heatwaves, how long did it take to get back to near-normal service (about 90%) in the AOI, for elderly, low-income, and the general population? Which sensors/data were used?	40	KPI-Driven Performance Monitoring
CQ-113	2. We see a e.g. 20% improvement in access for marginalised groups. Which equity score method (name/version/date) was used, and where did the demographic data come from?	40	KPI-Driven Performance Monitoring

CQ-114	1. During the last disruption, which saved traveller settings did we use to send eco-friendly travel tips to low-income commuters, and how many followed the tips (e.g., % who tapped or switched route)?	41	Behavioural Nudging for Sustainability
CQ-115	2. Which past nudge results did we use to design today's advice, by area (e.g., city centre vs outer wards)? Which survey are they from, when did it run, and what share of people answered? Show the split by group (e.g., low-income, elderly, children).	41	Behavioural Nudging for Sustainability
CQ-116	1. Which actions from City A were used in City B to help older people during heatwaves, and what result did City B get?	42	Cross-City Knowledge Transfer
CQ-117	2. When we compare cities, which numbers do we use (e.g., time to recover, change in access) for low-income areas, and are the same rules and units used in both places?	42	Cross-City Knowledge Transfer
CQ-118	1. In the last public-transport strike, which groups (e.g., low-income) had wait times above the limit, where, and did this trigger extra shuttles?	43	Real-Time Equity Monitoring
CQ-119	2. When making live routing changes, how does the system combine slow-changing data (e.g., census) with live traces (e.g., phones/vehicles) and what changed on the routes?	43	Real-Time Equity Monitoring
CQ-120	1. Which policy or law change did we use (name and date), and how did it change? who we prioritised (e.g., low-income commuters) during the energy crisis?	44	PESTEL Contextual Integration
CQ-121	2. Which cost figures did we use to judge the effect on bus-dependent areas (name of dataset, last update), and what did they show?	44	PESTEL Contextual Integration
CQ-122	1. Looking at several years of past disruptions, what evidence supports installing heated pavements for mobility-impaired older people, and what improvement do we expect (e.g., faster return to normal)?	45	Long-Term Transformative Learning
CQ-123	2. What proof (from sensors, reports, dates) supports creating green travel corridors in low-income areas with poor air, and what benefit do we expect (e.g., better access, safer air)?	45	Long-Term Transformative Learning
CQ-124	1. How to ensure uninterrupted collection and synchronization of data from different sources in real time?	46	Real-Time Monitoring and Analytics
CQ-125	2. How is fast coordination between the Department of Transport and response services carried out?	46	Real-Time Monitoring and Analytics
CQ-126	3. How does the system guarantee data integrity and reliability?	46	Real-Time Monitoring and Analytics

CQ-127	1. How does the system identify overloaded directions and calculate the need for additional vehicles?	47	Flexible Route and Fleet Planning
CQ-128	2. Who makes decisions on timetable and route changes in crisis conditions?	47	Flexible Route and Fleet Planning
CQ-129	3. How are the needs of IDPs, people with reduced mobility, and women with children considered?	47	Flexible Route and Fleet Planning
CQ-130	1. How will the system operate without power or connectivity (offline mode)?	48	Centralized Event Management (Crisis, Peak Loads)
CQ-131	2. Which entities are responsible for emergency traffic management?	48	Centralized Event Management (Crisis, Peak Loads)
CQ-132	3. How is priority movement for emergency vehicles ensured?	48	Centralized Event Management (Crisis, Peak Loads)
CQ-133	1. How to ensure rapid data exchange across agencies without duplication?	49	Inter-agency Coordination Platform
CQ-134	2. Who administers the shared platform and defines user access levels?	49	Inter-agency Coordination Platform
CQ-135	3. How are interaction results logged after each incident?	49	Inter-agency Coordination Platform
CQ-136	1. How does the system estimate the impact of planned works on traffic flows?	50	Scenario Analysis and Forecasting System
CQ-137	2. How are alternative detour / temporary route scenarios generated?	50	Scenario Analysis and Forecasting System
CQ-138	3. Who approves the choice of the optimal option?	50	Scenario Analysis and Forecasting System
CQ-139	1. Which data sources must be integrated (loops, cameras, counters, Waze/Google/GPS, dispatch)?	51	Real-time traffic monitoring
CQ-140	2. How frequently must the traffic data update (real-time, seconds, minutes)?	51	Real-time traffic monitoring
CQ-141	3. How should the system visualize traffic conditions and incidents on the map?	51	Real-time traffic monitoring
CQ-142	4. Should the platform detect and alert operators to incidents automatically?	51	Real-time traffic monitoring
CQ-143	1. What traffic modelling tools must be used (e.g., VISUM, real-time simulation engine)?	52	Prediction of traffic conditions and response to incidents
CQ-144	2. How quickly must the system predict and update traffic conditions after an incident occurs?	52	Prediction of traffic conditions and response to incidents
CQ-145	3. Should the system automatically suggest detours and alternative routes, or only display predicted impacts?	52	Prediction of traffic conditions and response to incidents

CQ-146	4. What level of accuracy and detail is required in the traffic predictions (e.g., by segment, intersection, corridor)?	52	Prediction of traffic conditions and response to incidents
CQ-147	1. Which types of crisis events must the system be able to simulate (e.g., floods, outages, closures, cyberattacks)?	53	Simulation of unexpected events:
CQ-148	2. What traffic and infrastructure data must be included to model these scenarios accurately?	53	Simulation of unexpected events
CQ-149	3. Should the system provide impact assessments only, or also recommend mitigation measures?	53	Simulation of unexpected events
CQ-150	4. How quickly must simulations be created, run, and visualized for decision-making?	53	Simulation of unexpected events
CQ-151	1. Which transport measures must the system be able to evaluate (lane changes, bus lanes, signal plans, crossings, intersection redesigns)?	54	Evaluating the impacts of transport measures
CQ-152	2. How should the system compare current vs. proposed conditions (KPIs, maps, charts, before/after scenarios)?	54	Evaluating the impacts of transport measures
CQ-153	3. What performance indicators are required (travel time, capacity, safety, delays, emissions, PT reliability)?	54	Evaluating the impacts of transport measures
CQ-154	4. How detailed must the model environment be (corridor level, intersection microsimulation, network-wide)?	54	Evaluating the impacts of transport measures
CQ-155	1. Which data sources must be integrated (PT vehicle positions, passenger counts, pedestrian and cyclist counters)?	55	Integration of data on public transport, pedestrian and bicycle transport
CQ-156	2. What granularity and frequency of data updates are required (real-time, minute-by-minute, hourly)?	55	Integration of data on public transport, pedestrian and bicycle transport
CQ-157	3. How should the system visualize multimodal flows and compare modes (maps, graphs, heatmaps, dashboards)?	55	Integration of data on public transport, pedestrian and bicycle transport
CQ-158	4. What KPIs are needed to support multimodal planning (PT reliability, passenger load, pedestrian volumes, cycling flows)?	55	Integration of data on public transport, pedestrian and bicycle transport
CQ-159	1. Which organizations and user groups must access the system (city, region, PT operator, police, contractors)?	56	Usability across split governance
CQ-160	2. What data access levels or permissions are required (full access, read-only, anonymized, aggregated)?	56	Usability across split governance
CQ-161	3. How should the system manage data sharing across agencies with different openness and privacy policies?	56	Usability across split governance

CQ-162	4. What are the requirements for coordination tools (shared dashboards, notifications, comment layers, export options)?	56	Usability across split governance
CQ-163	1. What action should happen here, and how will we know it worked (e.g., faster recovery time or better access)?	57	Continuously learning agent-based digital twin
CQ-164	2. Who is affected (by group and area), and how do their results change before vs after the action?	57	Continuously learning agent-based digital twin
CQ-165	3. Which data did we use (name), when was it taken, and how sure are we (Low/Med/High or a score)?	57	Continuously learning agent-based digital twin
CQ-166	1. What change is expected in this scenario, and what simple KPI shows success (e.g., wait time, access, reliability)?	58	Co-evolving epidemic-mobility control
CQ-167	2. Which groups and areas are impacted most, and how do results differ before vs after?	58	Co-evolving epidemic-mobility control
CQ-168	3. What data powered the result (name), when was it collected, and what is the confidence?	58	Co-evolving epidemic-mobility control
CQ-169	1. What decision or action do we take, and what outcome measure proves it helped (e.g., time to 90% normal)?	59	Mobility-aware microgrid reconfiguration
CQ-170	2. For each group and area, did outcomes improve or worsen?	59	Mobility-aware microgrid reconfiguration
CQ-171	3. Which sources fed this (names), what dates, and how certain are we?	59	Mobility-aware microgrid reconfiguration
CQ-172	1. Which signals or inputs trigger the action, and what KPI shows success?	60	Evolutionary optimisation of network design under stress
CQ-173	2. Do results differ for target groups (by area)?	60	Evolutionary optimisation of network design under stress
CQ-174	3. Which datasets were used, when collected, and what is the confidence?	60	Evolutionary optimisation of network design under stress
CQ-175	1. What long-term change is proposed, and which metric shows a lasting benefit?	61	Systemic learning from AV near-miss
CQ-176	2. Which groups benefit most/least, and where?	61	Systemic learning from AV near-misses
CQ-177	3. What evidence supports the change (source, date), and how certain is it?	61	Systemic learning from AV near-misses

Table 6. Competency Questions

13.2 Appendix B: Ontology Specification (OWL / Rules / Patterns)

This appendix provides representative specification fragments (OWL / constraints / rule and query patterns); the main body provides a summary overview in Section 7.

Here we introduce the formal OWL artefacts, rule patterns, and validation constraints used to specify the ontology. It introduces:

- the **OWL representation** of key classes and properties,
- selected **constraints and design patterns**, and
- **rule patterns (SWRL)** and example queries supporting antifragility reasoning.

The specification is presented in a **modular, illustrative way**. It is not an exhaustive TBox listing, but a set of core fragments that can be directly implemented and extended.

A complete machine-readable OWL file with all classes, properties, annotations and rules will be finalised and versioned in the project repository as part of the ontology implementation workflow.

13.2.1 B.1 Namespaces and general conventions

For readability, we assume the following namespaces:

Prefix: : <http://antifragicity.eu/ontology#>
 Prefix: rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
 Prefix: rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
 Prefix: owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
 Prefix: xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
 Prefix: time: <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#> # optional
 Prefix: geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#> # optional
 Prefix: prov: <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#> # optional
 Prefix: sosa: <http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/> # optional

We use **Manchester OWL syntax** in code blocks for classes and properties.

- **UpperCamelCase** for classes (e.g. TransportElement, DisruptionEvent).
- **lowerCamelCase** for properties (e.g. affects, hasAntifragilityScore).
- URIs follow the **Candidate_URI** suggestions from the enhanced extraction, simplified into this naming convention.

13.2.2 B.2 Core class hierarchy fragments

13.2.2.1 B.2.1 Transport and network concepts

Class: TransportElement

Annotations:

rdfs:label "Transport element"

Class: Node

SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: Edge

SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: Corridor
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: EvacRoute
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: RoutePlan
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: Asset
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: SignalPlan
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: SensorNetwork
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Class: MonitorModule
SubClassOf: TransportElement

Examples of individuals in later pilot instantiation:

Individual: bratislava_edge_123
Types: Edge

Individual: larissa_main_sensor_network
Types: SensorNetwork

13.2.2.2 B.2.2 Mobility, trips and services

Class: MobilityService

Class: Mode
SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: ActiveMode
SubClassOf: Mode

Class: PublicTransportMovement
SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: ChoiceModel
SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: PredMaintModel
SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: PredModel

SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: SimModel

SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: ForecastModel

SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: ScenarioSystem

SubClassOf: MobilityService

Class: Trip

SubClassOf:

Observation

and (usesMode some Mode)

and (performedBy some Actor)

Note: in this design, a Trip is an **observation / event of service usage**, linked to Mode and Actor. This refines the original suggestion that ENT_TRIP falls under MobilityService.

13.2.2.3 B.2.3 Disruptions and hazards

Class: DisruptionEvent

Class: Disruption

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: DemandSupplyShock

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: Cascade

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: Outage

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: CyberAttack

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: Crisis

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: UnexpectedEvent

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: HazardType

SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

Class: EmergencyType
SubClassOf: DisruptionEvent

The alignment with the D2.1 event taxonomy is reflected in the following pattern:

Class: :DisruptionEvent
SubClassOf:
:Event,
:hasDomain some :DisruptionDomain,
:hasScale some :EventScale,
:hasSeverityLevel some :SeverityLevel,
:hasImpactType some :ImpactType

Class: :DisruptionDomain
Class: :EventScale
Class: :SeverityLevel
Class: :ImpactType

ObjectProperty: :hasDomain
Domain: :DisruptionEvent
Range: :DisruptionDomain

ObjectProperty: :hasScale
Domain: :DisruptionEvent
Range: :EventScale

ObjectProperty: :hasSeverityLevel
Domain: :DisruptionEvent
Range: :SeverityLevel

ObjectProperty: :hasImpactType
Domain: :DisruptionEvent
Range: :ImpactType

The individuals of :DisruptionDomain, :EventScale, :SeverityLevel and :ImpactType correspond to the categories defined in the D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue.

13.2.2.4 B.2.4 System states, KPIs and antifragility indicators

Class: SystemState

Class: OperationalState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: CongestionState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: EvacCongestionState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: OverloadState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: PredictedDisruptionState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: EquilibriumState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: DesiredEquilibriumState
SubClassOf: EquilibriumState

Class: UndesiredEquilibriumState
SubClassOf: EquilibriumState

Class: ResilienceState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: AntifragileState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: EnvTargetState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: AdaptiveTransformativeState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: CalibrationState
SubClassOf: SystemState

KPI observation pattern

Indicators/KPIs can be represented as **KpiObservation instances (with CoreKPI subclass for the 13 stakeholder-prioritised indicators)** to capture value, unit, time and provenance. Each KpiObservation is linked to a Scenario (via forScenario) and to the relevant SystemState through the scenario's hasSystemState relation; additionally, SystemState instances reference their KPI observations via hasKpiObservation property. Where needed, summary indicators may additionally be stored as datatype properties on SystemState (e.g., hasAntifragilityScore, hasResilienceIndex, hasFragilityMetric).

KPI catalogue consolidation and prioritisation

The KPI catalogue has been consolidated using the updated stakeholder survey results (KPIs Survey_RESULTS.xlsx). It contains 209 candidate KPIs, organised into 7 groups and 20 subgroups (Table 7). These KPIs cover all aspects of urban mobility antifragility including network performance, ecological impacts, transport characteristics, safety, accessibility, land use, and urban development. To support cross-city comparability while preserving extensibility, we distinguish: (i) a core KPI subset prioritised by stakeholders (Table 8). This core subset comprises 13 KPIs that were prioritised by at least 4 out of 6 stakeholders (ETH, Cardiff, DEMO, AUTH, Bratislava, and Odessa) in the Task 2.7

survey. These KPIs represent the essential measurements for cross-city comparability and antifragility assessment across all pilot cities, and are represented in the ontology using the CoreKPI subclass. (ii) an extended KPI set retained for city-specific analysis and future refinements, represented using the general KpiObservation class. Importantly, the ontology structure remains stable: KPIs are referenced consistently via the SystemState/KPI observation pattern, while the KPI catalogue can evolve through iterative validation.

Table 7 provides the KPI catalogue structure (group/subgroup and size).

Table 8 lists the **core KPI subset**, defined here as KPIs selected by **≥4 stakeholders** (out of 5 respondents contributing selections in the spreadsheet).

The complete KPI catalogue is maintained in the companion spreadsheet (**KPIs Survey_RESULTS.xlsx**) and mirrored in the KG as KPI individuals with metadata (name, definition, group/subgroup, and prioritisation attributes), including: **hasKPINumber**: Catalogue position (1-209), **hasKPIGroup**: One of 7 top-level groups (e.g., "Ecological Impacts", "Transport Modes"), **hasKPISubgroup**: One of 20 subgroups (e.g., "Emissions", "Travel Times and Delays"), **hasStakeholderSelectionCount**: Number of stakeholders who prioritised this KPI (0-6), **hasName**: KPI name (e.g., "CO₂ emissions from transport"), **hasDefinition**: Detailed KPI description and measurement approach, **hasUnit**: Measurement unit (e.g., "tonnes CO₂/day", "minutes", "percentage"), **hasTarget**: Target value for performance assessment (where applicable), while measured or predicted KPI values are stored as KPI observations (instances of KpiObservation or CoreKPI) linked to scenario and system state, with properties including **hasCurrentValue**: The measured or predicted KPI value, **hasBaselineValue**: Reference value for comparison, **hasTimestamp**: Temporal validity of the observation, **hasDataQuality**: Quality score for the observation (0-1), **hasTrustScore**: Trust level in the data source (0-1), **hasConfidence**: Confidence in the value (0-1), **hasForecastUncertainty**: Uncertainty for predicted values, **generatedBy**: Link to DataSource, Sensor, or ForecastModel that produced the observation, **forScenario**: Link to the Scenario this observation evaluates, **observedOn**: Link to the TransportElement, SpatialUnit, or Actor being measured.

This structure enables systematic KPI tracking across scenarios, quantitative antifragility assessment through KPI change patterns, cross-city comparison via standardised core indicators, and provenance-aware decision support with uncertainty quantification.

Group	Subgroup	Number of KPIs	what it captures
Network/System performance		19	
	Centrality	5	Graph/network centrality measures capturing critical nodes/flows and structural importance.
	Capacity	14	Network capacity, redundancy and resilience/recovery indices (throughput, reserve capacity, recovery rates).
Ecological impacts		18	
	Emissions	11	Transport-related emissions (CO ₂ , NO _x /PM and related air-pollutant indicators).

	Noise pollution	2	Noise exposure/levels associated with transport activity.
	Ecological degradation	5	Indicators of transport-induced ecological stress (e.g., land/ecosystem impacts, degradation proxies).
Transport Modes, Travel Times and Characteristics		49	
	Modal split	4	Shares of passenger/freight movement by mode (incl. active vs motorised).
	Travel times and delays	24	Travel time, delay, reliability and congestion-related performance measures.
	Travel demand	8	Magnitude of travel demand (volumes, passenger-km/ton-km, motorised demand).
	Transport characteristics	13	Traffic/transport operating characteristics (speed/flow/density, vehicle/ICT-related indicators).
Transport safety		27	
	Traffic accidents	10	Accident occurrence and severity (collisions, fatalities/injuries, crash types).
	Security	3	Security-related incidents and perceived security of the transport system.
	Safety control	14	Enforcement/controls and safety compliance indicators (violations, checks, control measures).
Accessibility, costs, and satisfaction			
	Accessibility	6	Access to destinations/services and equity-oriented accessibility measures.
	Public perception and satisfaction	19	User perception, satisfaction and quality-of-life indicators related to mobility.
	Transport costs and affordability	24	User/operator cost indicators (travel/parking/operating costs, affordability proxies).
Land use and Infrastructure		28	
	Transport infrastructure	15	Physical infrastructure supply indicators (road length, operational roads, network features).

	Land use and space consumption	13	Land/space consumed by transport and parking (paved share, land consumption).
Urban development and growth		19	
	Energy consumption	9	Energy use, efficiency and fuel mix indicators in transport (incl. EV-related resilience).
	Urban and spatial planning	7	Urban form/planning indicators affecting mobility (density, green space, planning capacity).
	Economic growth	3	Macro-economic context indicators relevant to mobility (e.g., GDP/employment proxies).

Table 7. KPI Catalogue Overview (from KPIs Survey_RESULTS.xlsx)

Group	Subgroup	KPI	Stakeholders selecting (n)	Short definition / intent
Ecological impacts	Emissions	CO ₂	5	Undesirable output variable, consumption calculation of non-renewable energy sources; CO ₂ emissions.
Ecological impacts	Emissions	Pollutant emissions from transport	4	Transport emissions of nitrogen oxides, volatile organic compounds, and particulate matter.
Ecological impacts	Noise pollution	Noise pollution	4	Sound levels, often related to traffic (incl. population exposed).
Transport Modes, Travel Times and Characteristics	Modal split	Modal split	4	Personal travel mode split / proportion of trips by each mode.
Transport Modes, Travel Times and Characteristics	Modal split	Personal travel mode split	4	Share of non-motorized, automobile, public transport and other modes in total trips.
Transport Modes, Travel Times and Characteristics	Modal split	Freight mode split	4	Percentage share of each inland freight transport mode (road/rail/waterway).

Transport Modes, Travel Times and Characteristics	Travel times and delays	Travel time	4	Total duration a vehicle spends on a journey, including moving time and delays.
Transport Modes, Travel Times and Characteristics	Travel demand	Motorized transport demand	4	Overall need for motorized movement of people and goods (demand magnitude).
Land use and Infrastructure	Transport infrastructure	Infrastructure spatial features	4	Physical characteristics of transportation infrastructure within a given area.
Land use and Infrastructure	Transport infrastructure	Length of total operational roads	4	Total physical extent of all roads within a city or region (operational network size).
Urban development and growth	Urban and spatial planning	Urban density	4	Concentration of population/buildings in urban areas (density indicator).
Urban development and growth	Urban and spatial planning	Green space area	4	Total land cover of green space within the urban boundary.
Urban development and growth	Urban and spatial planning	Green space area per capita	4	Total amount of green space within a city divided by population.

Table 8. Core KPI subset (stakeholder-prioritised, selected by ≥ 4 stakeholders)

To support the equilibrium analysis in D2.3, the following additional classes and properties are introduced:

Class: SystemState

Class: EquilibriumState
SubClassOf: SystemState

Class: DesiredEquilibriumState
SubClassOf: EquilibriumState

Class: UndesiredEquilibriumState
SubClassOf: EquilibriumState

DataProperty: hasEquilibriumGap
Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:double

DataProperty: hasRecoveryTime

Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:duration

DataProperty: hasAntifragilityScore

Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:double

13.2.2.5 B.2.5 Scenarios and evaluation concepts

Class: Scenario

Class: BaselineScenario

SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: DisruptiveScenario

SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: WhatIfScenario

SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: PolicyScenario

SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: Simulation

SubClassOf: Scenario

Class: ScenarioLibrary

Class: ScenarioInput

Class: ForecastModel

13.2.2.6 B.2.6 Environment and context

Class: EnvironmentFactor

Class: ClimateFactor

SubClassOf: EnvironmentFactor

Class: ClimateStressor

SubClassOf: ClimateFactor

Class: ClimateProjection

SubClassOf: ClimateFactor

Class: WeatherCondition
SubClassOf: ClimateFactor

Class: PestelFactor
SubClassOf: EnvironmentFactor

Class: PoliticalFactor
SubClassOf: PestelFactor

Class: EconomicFactor
SubClassOf: PestelFactor

Class: SocialFactor
SubClassOf: PestelFactor

Class: TechnologicalFactor
SubClassOf: PestelFactor

Class: EnvironmentalFactor
SubClassOf: PestelFactor

Class: LegalFactor
SubClassOf: PestelFactor

13.2.2.7 B.2.7 Actors, equity groups and institutions

Class: Actor

Class: InstitutionalActor
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: EquityGroup
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: VulnerableGroup
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: CitizenSegment
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: UserGroup
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: UserProfile
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: Stakeholder

SubClassOf: Actor

Class: StakeholderGroup
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: Incentive
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: CitySource
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: CityTarget
SubClassOf: Actor

Class: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Regulation
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: LegalConstraint
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: LegalScenario
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Legislation
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Organisation
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Agency
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Protocol
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: SecurityProtocol
SubClassOf: Protocol

Class: DataSharingAgreement
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Platform
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: CoordinationSystem

SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: EventManagementSystem
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: CrisisManagementCentre
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

Class: Sitrep
SubClassOf: GovernanceInstrument

13.2.2.8 B.2.8 Spatial and temporal units

Class: SpatialUnit

Class: Boundary
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: SpatialConstraint
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: NoGoArea
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: VulnerableArea
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: GeoLayer
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: GeoLimitation
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: ProtectedArea
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: EvacuationZone
SubClassOf: SpatialUnit

Class: TemporalUnit

Class: TimeInstant
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: TimeInterval
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: TimePeriod
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: Duration
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: TimeHorizon
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: EvaluationPeriod
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: PeakPeriod
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

Class: Timestamp
SubClassOf: TemporalUnit

13.2.2.9 B.2.9 Observations, data provenance and uncertainty

Class: Observation

Class: SensorObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: TrafficObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: EmissionObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: EquityObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: EconomicObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: KpiObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: CoreKPI
SubClassOf: KpiObservation

Class: DataQualityObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: FusionObservation

SubClassOf: Observation

Class: ClimateObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: SafetyObservation
SubClassOf: Observation

Class: DataSource

Class: TrafficSensor
SubClassOf: DataSource

Class: SensorNetwork
SubClassOf: DataSource

Class: IoTDevice
SubClassOf: DataSource

Class: AnalyticsEngine
SubClassOf: DataSource

Class: ForecastModel
SubClassOf: DataSource

Class: DigitalTwin
SubClassOf: DataSource

Class: Provenance

Class: MultimodalData

Class: TrafficDataset
SubClassOf: MultimodalData

Class: PTData
SubClassOf: MultimodalData

Class: ActiveMobilityData
SubClassOf: MultimodalData

Class: EconomicData

Class: PersonalData

Class: Graph

Class: LearningRepository

Class: BestPractice

Class: Dashboard

Class: UserInterface

13.2.2.10 B.2.10 Response actions and learning processes

Class: ResponseAction

Class: ControlAction

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Class: EmergencyAction

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Class: PolicyAction

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Class: CoordinationAction

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Class: BehaviouralNudge

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Class: MonitoringAction

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Class: LearningAction

SubClassOf: ResponseAction

Control action examples:

Class: AntifragileControl

SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: AdaptiveControl

SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: ModeShift

SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: EmissionControl

SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: EnergyOptimization

SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: ProactiveReroute
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: Reroute
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: PriorityRouting
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: FleetAlloc
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: ResourceAlloc
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: SignalControl
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: NetworkOptimization
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Class: DynamicAdjust
SubClassOf: ControlAction

Emergency action examples:

Class: EvacuationManagement
SubClassOf: EmergencyAction

Class: EmergencyResponse
SubClassOf: EmergencyAction

Class: Triage
SubClassOf: EmergencyAction

Class: EmergencyPrioritisation
SubClassOf: EmergencyAction

Class: Alerting
SubClassOf: EmergencyAction

Policy action examples:

Class: PolicyUpdate
SubClassOf: PolicyAction

Class: RegulationChange

SubClassOf: PolicyAction

Class: LegalScenarioActivation
SubClassOf: PolicyAction

Class: AdaptationPlanning
SubClassOf: PolicyAction

Class: ClimateAdaptation
SubClassOf: PolicyAction

Coordination action examples:

Class: MultiagencyCoord
SubClassOf: CoordinationAction

Class: CrisisCoordination
SubClassOf: CoordinationAction

Class: CrossAuthorityCoord
SubClassOf: CoordinationAction

Class: StakeholderEngagement
SubClassOf: CoordinationAction

Class: InfoSharing
SubClassOf: CoordinationAction

Behavioural nudge examples:

Class: Nudge
SubClassOf: BehaviouralNudge

Class: Feedback
SubClassOf: BehaviouralNudge

Class: IncentiveDesign
SubClassOf: BehaviouralNudge

Class: InclusiveIntervention
SubClassOf: BehaviouralNudge

Monitoring action examples:

Class: PerformanceMonitoring
SubClassOf: MonitoringAction

Class: EquityMonitor
SubClassOf: MonitoringAction

Class: EquityAlert
SubClassOf: MonitoringAction

Class: ImpactEval
SubClassOf: MonitoringAction

Class: OutcomeMonitoring
SubClassOf: MonitoringAction

Learning action examples:

Class: InterventionLearning
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: SystemicLearning
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: KnowledgeTransfer
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: RiskAssessment
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: MultiScenarioEval
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: CausalEval
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: ScenarioCompare
SubClassOf: LearningAction

Class: LongtermLearning
SubClassOf: LearningAction

13.2.3 B.3 Object properties (structural relations)

Below are key object properties, with domains and ranges at the level of the 12 top-level classes. Subproperties can later refine semantics (e.g. affectsEquity, affectsAccessibility).

ObjectProperty: affects
Domain: DisruptionEvent
Range: TransportElement or Actor or SystemState

ObjectProperty: affectedBy
InverseOf: affects

ObjectProperty: hasSystemState

Domain: Scenario
Range: SystemState

ObjectProperty: hasObservation
Domain: TransportElement or MobilityService or Actor or Scenario
Range: Observation

ObjectProperty: observedOn
Domain: Observation
Range: TransportElement or Actor or Scenario

ObjectProperty: governedBy
Domain: TransportElement or MobilityService or Actor
Range: GovernanceInstrument

ObjectProperty: locatedIn
Domain: TransportElement or Actor or DisruptionEvent
Range: SpatialUnit

ObjectProperty: validDuring
Domain: Scenario or SystemState or ResponseAction
Range: TemporalUnit

ObjectProperty: triggersResponse
Domain: DisruptionEvent
Range: ResponseAction

ObjectProperty: respondsTo
Domain: ResponseAction
Range: DisruptionEvent or Scenario

ObjectProperty: updatesState
Domain: ResponseAction
Range: SystemState

ObjectProperty: previousState
Domain: SystemState
Range: SystemState

ObjectProperty: nextState
Domain: SystemState
Range: SystemState

ObjectProperty: inLayer
Domain: TransportElement
Range: InfrastructureLayer

ObjectProperty: dependsOn
Domain: TransportElement
Range: TransportElement

ObjectProperty: memberOf
Domain: Actor
Range: Organisation or Agency

ObjectProperty: participatesIn
Domain: Actor
Range: ResponseAction (e.g. Consultation, Coordination)

ObjectProperty: generatedBy
Domain: Observation
Range: DataSource or AnalyticsEngine

ObjectProperty: hasProvenance
Domain: Observation or MultimodalData
Range: Provenance

ObjectProperty: hasKpiObservation
Domain: SystemState
Range: KpiObservation

ObjectProperty: forScenario
Domain: Observation or KpiObservation
Range: Scenario

ObjectProperty: affectsEquity
Domain: ResponseAction or GovernanceInstrument
Range: EquityGroup

ObjectProperty: constrainedBy
Domain: ResponseAction
Range: GovernanceInstrument or LegalConstraint

ObjectProperty: appliesTo
Domain: GovernanceInstrument or Regulation or ResponseAction
Range: SpatialUnit or TransportElement or Actor

ObjectProperty: subjectTo
Domain: Actor or SpatialUnit
Range: LegalConstraint

ObjectProperty: hasRole
Domain: Actor
Range: xsd:string

ObjectProperty: calibrates
Domain: DigitalTwin or CalibrationState
Range: SystemState or DigitalTwin

ObjectProperty: monitors
Domain: SensorNetwork or TrafficSensor
Range: TransportElement

ObjectProperty: comparedWith
Domain: Scenario
Range: Scenario

ObjectProperty: includesResponseAction
Domain: Scenario
Range: ResponseAction

ObjectProperty: includesEvent
Domain: DisruptiveScenario
Range: DisruptionEvent

ObjectProperty: implementsPolicy
Domain: PolicyScenario
Range: GovernanceInstrument

ObjectProperty: involvesStakeholder
Domain: PolicyScenario or CoordinationAction
Range: StakeholderGroup or Stakeholder

ObjectProperty: runsOn
Domain: Simulation
Range: DigitalTwin

ObjectProperty: usesForecasting
Domain: Scenario
Range: ForecastModel

ObjectProperty: affectsSpatialUnit
Domain: DisruptionEvent
Range: SpatialUnit

ObjectProperty: within
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: SpatialUnit

ObjectProperty: overlaps
Domain: SpatialUnit

Range: SpatialUnit

ObjectProperty: occursAt
Domain: DisruptionEvent or ResponseAction
Range: TimeInstant

ObjectProperty: hasTemporalExtent
Domain: Scenario or DisruptionEvent
Range: TimeInterval

ObjectProperty: precedes
Domain: Event or ResponseAction
Range: Event or ResponseAction

ObjectProperty: follows
Domain: Event or ResponseAction
Range: Event or ResponseAction

ObjectProperty: derivedFrom
Domain: Observation
Range: DataSource or Observation

ObjectProperty: targetsActor
Domain: ResponseAction
Range: Actor or EquityGroup

ObjectProperty: evaluatedBy
Domain: Scenario or ResponseAction
Range: LearningAction or KpiObservation

13.2.4 B.4 Data properties and indicators

13.2.4.1 B.4.1 Performance and antifragility indicators

DatatypeProperty: hasAntifragilityScore
Domain: SystemState
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasResilienceIndex
Domain: SystemState
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasFragilityMetric
Domain: SystemState
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPerformanceDelta
Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPerformanceTimeSeriesRef

Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:anyURI (pointer to external TS data)

DatatypeProperty: hasEquilibriumGap

Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasRecoveryTime

Domain: SystemState

Range: xsd:duration

13.2.4.2 B.4.2 Mobility and network properties

DatatypeProperty: hasTravelTime

Domain: Trip or Edge or Corridor

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasCapacityUtilisation

Domain: TransportElement

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasNetworkDensity

Domain: SpatialUnit

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasSpeedFlow

Domain: TrafficObservation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasModalSplit

Domain: SystemState or Observation

Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasRidership

Domain: MobilityService or Observation

Range: xsd:integer

DatatypeProperty: hasSatisfactionScore

Domain: MobilityService or Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasTravelCost

Domain: MobilityService or Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasDelayTime
Domain: Trip or Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasWaitingTime
Domain: Facility or Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasServiceFrequency
Domain: MobilityService
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasAccessibilityIndex
Domain: SpatialUnit or EquityGroup
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPassengerKilometers
Domain: MobilityService or Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasCriticality
Domain: TransportElement
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasOperationalStatus
Domain: TransportElement
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasSpeedLimit
Domain: Edge or Corridor
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasLanes
Domain: Edge
Range: xsd:integer

DatatypeProperty: hasInfrastructureSpatialFeatures
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasTotalOperationalRoadLength
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasRoadLength
Domain: SpatialUnit or Edge
Range: xsd:double

13.2.4.3 B.4.3 Equity, vulnerability and socio-economic properties

DatatypeProperty: hasServiceAccess
Domain: EquityGroup or CitizenSegment or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasRiskExposure
Domain: EquityGroup or CitizenSegment
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasSocialVulnerability
Domain: EquityGroup or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasBenefitDistribution
Domain: EquityGroup
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasCostPerGroup
Domain: EquityGroup
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasExposureLevel
Domain: VulnerableGroup or VulnerableArea
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasUserPreference
Domain: UserProfile or CitizenSegment
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasMobilityCondition
Domain: UserProfile or CitizenSegment
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasEconomicImpact
Domain: EconomicObservation or Scenario
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasGDPEffect
Domain: EconomicObservation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasQualityOfLife
Domain: CitizenSegment or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPopulationSatisfaction
Domain: SpatialUnit

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasSocialEquity
Domain: SystemState or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

13.2.4.4 B.4.4 Environmental and economic properties

DatatypeProperty: hasEmissions
Domain: EmissionObservation or SystemState
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEnergyUse
Domain: EmissionObservation or SystemState
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEconCost
Domain: EconomicObservation or Scenario
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasProductivityLoss
Domain: EconomicObservation or Scenario
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEmissionLevel
Domain: EmissionObservation or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasCO2Emissions
Domain: EmissionObservation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPollutantEmissions
Domain: EmissionObservation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasNoiseLevel
Domain: Observation or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasNoisePollution
Domain: Observation or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEnergyConsumption
Domain: TransportElement or Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEcologicalImpact
Domain: EnvironmentFactor or Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEcologicalFootprint
Domain: SystemState or SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPopulationExposure
Domain: SpatialUnit or EnvironmentFactor
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasUrbanDensity
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasGreenSpaceArea
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasGreenSpaceAreaPerCapita
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPopulation
Domain: SpatialUnit
Range: xsd:integer

DatatypeProperty: hasRenewableEnergyUtilization
Domain: SystemState or TransportElement
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasFuelUse
Domain: Vehicle or MobilityService
Range: xsd:double

13.2.4.5 B.4.5 Uncertainty and data quality

DatatypeProperty: hasDataQuality
Domain: DataQualityObservation or Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasTrustScore
Domain: Observation
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasConfidence
Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasLatency

Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasUpdateFrequency

Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasPredictionError

Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasForecastUncertainty

Domain: Observation or Scenario

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasCompleteness

Domain: Observation or DataQualityObservation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasAccuracy

Domain: Observation or DataQualityObservation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasUncertainty

Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasConfidenceInterval

Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasDataLineage

Domain: Provenance

Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasPrivacyRisk

Domain: DataSharingAgreement or PersonalData

Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasEncryptionStatus

Domain: SecurityProtocol or DataSharingAgreement

Range: xsd:string

13.2.4.6 B.4.6 Time-related properties

DatatypeProperty: hasStartTime

Domain: TemporalUnit

Range: xsd:dateTime

DatatypeProperty: hasEndTime

Domain: TemporalUnit

Range: xsd:dateTime

DatatypeProperty: hasValue

Domain: TemporalUnit

Range: xsd:double (e.g. duration in minutes)

DatatypeProperty: hasTimestamp

Domain: Observation or SystemState

Range: xsd:dateTime

DatatypeProperty: hasSourceTimestamp

Domain: Observation

Range: xsd:dateTime

DatatypeProperty: hasResponseTime

Domain: ResponseAction or EmergencyAction or SystemState

Range: xsd:duration

DatatypeProperty: hasLeadTime

Domain: PredictedDisruptionState or Observation

Range: xsd:duration

DatatypeProperty: hasLagTime

Domain: SystemState or ResponseAction

Range: xsd:duration

DatatypeProperty: hasValidFrom

Domain: GovernanceInstrument or SystemState

Range: xsd:dateTime

DatatypeProperty: hasValidUntil

Domain: GovernanceInstrument or SystemState

Range: xsd:dateTime

DatatypeProperty: hasDuration

Domain: DisruptionEvent or Scenario

Range: xsd:duration

DatatypeProperty: hasTimeHorizon

Domain: Scenario or ForecastModel

Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasEvalPeriod
Domain: Scenario or Observation
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasPeakPeriod
Domain: SystemState or Observation
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasTemporalExtent
Domain: Scenario or DisruptionEvent
Range: xsd:duration

13.2.5 B.5 Constraints, axioms and design patterns

13.2.5.1 B.5.1 Disjointness axioms

To prevent unintended inferences, we define key disjointness relationships:

DisjointClasses: TransportElement, Actor, GovernanceInstrument, Observation, Scenario, ResponseAction, EnvironmentFactor, DisruptionEvent, SpatialUnit, TemporalUnit, SystemState, MobilityService.

DisjointClasses: EquityGroup, Organisation, Agency.

DisjointClasses: Disruption, EmergencyType, Cascade.

DisjointClasses: BaselineScenario, DisruptiveScenario, WhatIfScenario, PolicyScenario, Simulation.

13.2.5.2 B.5.2 Domain/range and inverse properties

Example: governance and location.

ObjectProperty: governedBy
Domain: TransportElement or MobilityService or Actor
Range: GovernanceInstrument

ObjectProperty: governs
InverseOf: governedBy

ObjectProperty: locatedIn
Domain: TransportElement or Actor or DisruptionEvent
Range: SpatialUnit

ObjectProperty: contains
InverseOf: locatedIn

ObjectProperty: observedOn
Domain: Observation
Range: TransportElement or Actor or Scenario

ObjectProperty: observedBy

InverseOf: observedOn

ObjectProperty: affects

Domain: DisruptionEvent

Range: TransportElement or Actor or SystemState

ObjectProperty: affectedBy

InverseOf: affects

13.2.5.3 B.5.3 Cardinality constraints (illustrative)

Class: DisruptiveScenario

SubClassOf:

Scenario

and (hasSystemState min 1 SystemState)

and (hasSystemState max 1 SystemState)

and (respondsTo some DisruptionEvent)

Class: ProactiveReroute

SubClassOf:

ControlAction

and (appliesTo some TransportElement)

and (targetsActor some Actor)

Class: EquityObservation

SubClassOf:

Observation

and (observedOn some EquityGroup)

Class: CoreKPI

SubClassOf:

KpiObservation

and (hasKPINumber exactly 1 xsd:integer)

and (hasKPIGroup exactly 1 xsd:string)

and (hasKPISubgroup exactly 1 xsd:string)

and (hasStakeholderSelectionCount exactly 1 xsd:integer)

13.2.5.4 B.5.4 N-ary patterns for KPIs and scenario evaluation

To evaluate a KPI for a group in a scenario and time period, we use an **n-ary design pattern** with an intermediate class KpiObservation:

Class: KpiObservation

SubClassOf: Observation

Class: CoreKPI

SubClassOf: KpiObservation

ObjectProperty: forScenario

Domain: KpiObservation
Range: Scenario

ObjectProperty: forActorGroup
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: EquityGroup or CitizenSegment

ObjectProperty: forTemporalUnit
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: TemporalUnit

DatatypeProperty: kpiValue
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: xsd:double

Class: KPI
ObjectProperty: observes
Domain: KpiObservation
Range: KPI

DatatypeProperty: hasKPINumber
Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
Range: xsd:integer

DatatypeProperty: hasKPIGroup
Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasKPISubgroup
Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
Range: xsd:string

DatatypeProperty: hasStakeholderSelectionCount
Domain: CoreKPI
Range: xsd:integer

DatatypeProperty: hasTarget
Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasCurrentValue
Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasBaselineValue
Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
Range: xsd:double

DatatypeProperty: hasUnit
 Domain: KpiObservation or CoreKPI
 Range: xsd:string

This pattern allows us to answer CQs such as:
 "What is the equity KPI for vulnerable groups in district X under scenario S over period P?".

Example instantiation:

```
:BA_KPI_CO2_Flood2030 a :CoreKPI ;
  :hasKPINumber 21 ;
  :hasKPIGroup "Ecological Impacts" ;
  :hasKPISubgroup "Emissions" ;
  :hasStakeholderSelectionCount 5 ;
  :hasCurrentValue 185.5 ;
  :hasBaselineValue 145.2 ;
  :hasTarget 120.0 ;
  :hasUnit "tonnes CO2/day" ;
  :hasTimestamp "2030-06-15T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  :forScenario :BA_Scenario_Flood2030_Baseline ;
  :generatedBy :BA_EmissionModel_1 .
```

13.2.6 B.6 Rule patterns (SWRL) for antifragility and equity reasoning

The ontology is complemented by **rule patterns**, implemented e.g. in SWRL or a similar rule language. Below are illustrative rules in SWRL-like syntax.

Note: these are **patterns**; actual thresholds and constants are project-specific and will be calibrated with data.

13.2.6.1 B.6.1 Basic antifragility classification rule

If performance improves after a disruption and the system remains within acceptable bounds, classify the state as antifragile.

```
SystemState(?s_before) ^ SystemState(?s_after) ^
previousState(?s_after, ?s_before) ^
hasPerformanceDelta(?s_after, ?delta) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?delta, 0.0) ^
hasAntifragilityScore(?s_after, ?score) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?score, 0.0)
  -> AntifragileState(?s_after)
```

We may introduce a **class**:

```
Class: AntifragileState
  SubClassOf: SystemState
```

13.2.6.2 B.6.2 Vulnerable area determination

If an area hosts high-risk groups and low service access, classify it as a vulnerable area.

```

EquityGroup(?g) ^
SpatialUnit(?a) ^
locatedIn(?g, ?a) ^
hasServiceAccess(?g, ?access) ^
hasRiskExposure(?g, ?risk) ^
swrlb:lessThan(?access, 0.4) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?risk, 0.6)
  -> VulnerableArea(?a)

```

13.2.6.3 B.6.3 Equity alert rule

If, for a given scenario and period, the equity KPI for a group falls below a threshold, trigger an equity alert action.

```

KpiObservation(?k) ^
forScenario(?k, ?sc) ^
forActorGroup(?k, ?g) ^
forTemporalUnit(?k, ?t) ^
kpiValue(?k, ?v) ^
swrlb:lessThan(?v, 0.5)
  -> EquityAlertAction(?a),
    respondsTo(?a, ?sc),
    targetsActor(?a, ?g)

```

With:

```

Class: EquityAlertAction
SubClassOf: ResponseAction

```

13.2.6.4 B.6.4 Cascading disruption detection

If a disruption affects an element that depends on another element, and that dependency is critical, infer a potential cascade.

```

DisruptionEvent(?d1) ^
TransportElement(?e1) ^
TransportElement(?e2) ^
affects(?d1, ?e1) ^
dependsOn(?e1, ?e2) ^
hasCriticality(?e2, ?crit) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?crit, 0.7)
  -> CascadeRiskEvent(?d2),
    Cascade(?d2),
    propagatesTo(?d1, ?d2),
    affects(?d2, ?e2)

```

Here CascadeRiskEvent is a subclass of DisruptionEvent used for forecasted cascades.

13.2.6.5 B.6.5 Legal compliance check

If an action is applied to an element or area with a legal constraint that forbids such action, infer a non-compliant situation.

```

ResponseAction(?a) ^
appliesTo(?a, ?x) ^      (x may be TransportElement or SpatialUnit)
governedBy(?x, ?lc) ^

```

```

LegalConstraint(?lc) ^
forbidsAction(?lc, ?atype) ^
hasActionType(?a, ?atype)
  -> NonCompliantAction(?a)
forbidsAction and hasActionType are domain-specific properties.
We then define:
Class: NonCompliantAction
  SubClassOf: ResponseAction

```

13.2.6.6 B.6.6 Learning and improvement recognition

If a series of interventions on a measure leads to improved performance in repeated scenarios, increase the antifragility score.

```

LearningAction(?la) ^
OutcomeMonitoring(?la) ^
appliesTo(?la, ?measure) ^
Scenario(?sc) ^
hasSystemState(?sc, ?s1) ^
nextState(?s2, ?s1) ^
hasPerformanceDelta(?s2, ?delta) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?delta, 0.0) ^
hasAntifragilityScore(?s1, ?score1) ^
swrlb:add(?score2, ?score1, 0.1)
  -> hasAntifragilityScore(?s2, ?score2)

```

This illustrates how **learning processes** can update antifragility scores over time.

13.2.7 B.7 Example SPARQL queries aligned with competency questions

The SPARQL query templates in this appendix are illustrative examples showing how the ontology can be used to address typical competency-question themes such as disruption impacts, equity and vulnerability patterns, and antifragility indicators. They are not intended to provide a one-to-one mapping to individual CQs in Appendix A, but rather to demonstrate how groups of related competency questions can be operationalised over the AntifragiCity knowledge graph.

To demonstrate how the ontology supports competency questions, we include a few **SPARQL query patterns**.

13.2.7.1 B.7.1 CQ: Affected equity groups in a disruption scenario

“Which equity groups in district D are most affected by a flood scenario S?”

```

SELECT ?group ?riskExposure ?serviceAccess
WHERE {
  :Scenario_S rdf:type :DisruptiveScenario .
  :Scenario_S :hasSystemState ?state .

  ?state :locatedIn :District_D .

  ?group rdf:type :EquityGroup ;
    :locatedIn :District_D ;
    :hasRiskExposure ?riskExposure ;

```

```

    :hasServiceAccess ?serviceAccess .
  }
ORDER BY DESC(?riskExposure)

```

13.2.7.2 B.7.2 CQ: Antifragility score comparison across scenarios

“Compare antifragility scores of the network under scenarios S1 and S2.”

```

SELECT ?scenario ?score
WHERE {
  VALUES ?scenario { :Scenario_S1 :Scenario_S2 }

```

```

  ?scenario :hasSystemState ?state .
  ?state :hasAntifragilityScore ?score .
}
ORDER BY ?scenario

```

13.2.7.3 B.7.3 CQ: Legal feasibility of a proposed evacuation route

“Is evacuation route R compliant with current legal constraints?”

```

SELECT ?constraint
WHERE {
  :EvacRoute_R rdf:type :EvacRoute ;
    :governedBy ?constraint .

  ?constraint rdf:type :LegalConstraint .
}

```

If the result set is non-empty and any ?constraint forbids the planned action (checked via rules or an additional triple pattern), the route is flagged as non-compliant.

13.2.8 B.8 Implementation status and next steps

Appendix B provides representative specification fragments of the AntifragiCity Ontology (core class and property patterns, selected constraints, and illustrative rule/query patterns) to make the modelling choices transparent and to support review. The authoritative, complete ontology is maintained as a machine-readable OWL artefact in the project’s version-controlled repository, where it is iteratively updated as requirements and pilot instantiations evolve. This approach ensures (i) a stable, citable specification snapshot in the deliverable, while (ii) preserving a reproducible implementation history (versioning, change tracking, and release tagging) for integration with the platform knowledge graph and pilot deployments.

At this stage, the ontology specification provides:

- a **stable meta-model** with 12 top-level classes
- a set of **core subclasses** covering transport, disruptions, states, actors, governance, environment, observations and response actions
- key **object and data properties** supporting reasoning about antifragility, equity and multi-layer networks
- illustrative **constraints** and **rule patterns** in SWRL; and
- example **SPARQL queries** aligned with key competency questions.

Next steps, beyond the scope of this deliverable, include:

- finalising the complete OWL implementation (TBox) and publishing it in the project repository
- implementing and testing SWRL/SHACL rules in the chosen triple store / rule engine
- refining thresholds and parameters (e.g. antifragility score calculations, vulnerability thresholds) based on pilot data.

13.3 Appendix C: Object and Data Property Tables

13.3.1 C.1 Object Properties

13.3.1.1 C.1.1 Disruption & System Dynamics

Object properties that represent disruption events, their impacts, causal links, propagation/cascades, and state transitions, where columns are Property: The object property name (relation), Domain: Class(es) permitted on the subject side of the relation, Range: Class(es) permitted on the object side of the relation, Inverse: Declared inverse property (if defined), Description: Intended semantics/usage guidance (applies to **Table 9-Table 13**).

Property	Domain	Range	Inverse	Description
affects	DisruptionEvent	TransportElement SystemState	affectedBy	Links a disruption event to the elements it impacts
respondsTo	ResponseAction	DisruptionEvent	hasResponse	Links a response action to the disruption it addresses
triggersResponse	DisruptionEvent	ResponseAction	triggeredBy	Links a disruption to its triggered responses
updatesState	ResponseAction	SystemState	-	Links an action to the resulting system state
previousState	SystemState	SystemState	nextState	Links to the prior system state for trajectory analysis
propagatesTo	DisruptionEvent	DisruptionEvent	-	Models cascading failures between disruptions
hasCause	DisruptionEvent	DisruptionEvent ⊔ EnvironmentFactor ⊔ GovernanceInstrument ⊔ Actor	-	Links a disruption event to its immediate cause (another disruption event) or to a contextual cause

				factor (environmental, governance, or actor-related). <i>Inverse property (optional): causes.</i>
hasDomain	DisruptionEvent	DisruptionDomain	-	Links a disruption to its domain (transport, energy, social, health) as defined in D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue
hasScale	DisruptionEvent	EventScale	-	Links a disruption to its spatial/administrative scale (local, city-wide, regional, national) from D2.1
hasSeverityLevel	DisruptionEvent	SeverityLevel	-	Links a disruption to its severity/urgency level, aligned with D2.1 severity categories
hasImpactType	DisruptionEvent	ImpactType	-	Identifies primary impact type (mobility, economic, environmental, social) following D2.1 impact coding

Table 9. Disruption & System Dynamics

13.3.1.2 C.1.2 Network & Spatial

Object properties for spatial containment, network connectivity, and dependency relations among transport elements and spatial units.

Property	Domain	Range	Inverse	Description
locatedIn	TransportElement Actor	SpatialUnit	contains	Locates an element within a spatial unit
contains	SpatialUnit	TransportElement Actor	locatedIn	Lists elements contained in a spatial unit

dependsOn	TransportElement	TransportElement	-	Models infrastructure dependencies
connectsTo	TransportElement	TransportElement	connectsTo	Symmetric connection between network elements
usesMode	MobilityService	TransportElement	-	Links a service to transport modes used

Table 10. Network & Spatial

13.3.1.3 C.1.3 Actors & Governance

Object properties capturing who governs what, membership/roles, and who implements actions (governance and institutional relations).

Property	Domain	Range	Inverse	Description
governedBy	TransportElement MobilityService	GovernanceInstrument	governs	Links elements to governing policies/regulations
governs	GovernanceInstrument	TransportElement MobilityService	governedBy	Links policies to what they regulate
memberOf	Actor	Actor	hasMember	Group membership for actors
implementedBy	ResponseAction	Actor	implements	Links actions to implementing actors

Table 11. Actors & Governance

13.3.1.4 C.1.4 Observation & Data

Object properties describing observations, what they observe, provenance links, and how observations relate to scenarios, actor groups, and time.

Property	Domain	Range	Inverse	Description
hasObservation	TransportElement SystemState	Observation	observes	Links elements to their observations/measurements

observes	Observation	TransportElement SystemState	hasObservation	What an observation measures
generatedBy	Observation	Actor	-	Data provenance - source of observation
forScenario	Observation	Scenario	-	Links observation to evaluation scenario
forActorGroup	Observation	Actor	-	Links KPI to the actor group it evaluates
forTemporalUnit	Observation	TemporalUnit	-	Links observation to time period

Table 12. Observation & Data

13.3.1.5 C.1.5 Scenario

Object properties linking scenarios to applicable areas and to the system states that are evaluated/produced under those scenarios.

Property	Domain	Range	Inverse	Description
evaluatedIn	SystemState	Scenario	-	Links state to evaluation scenario
hasSystemState	Scenario	SystemState	-	Links scenario to resulting states
appliesTo	Scenario	SpatialUnit	-	Links scenario to applicable area

Table 13. Scenario

13.3.2 C.2 Data Properties

13.3.2.1 C.2.1 Mobility & Performance

KPI-style attributes describing mobility performance, capacity use, emissions/energy, and costs. Columns are: Property: The datatype property name (attribute/indicator), Domain: Class(es) the attribute applies to, Range: Datatype (typically xsd:double, xsd:dateTime, etc.), Unit: Measurement unit or unit convention (or “varies” where not fixed), Description: Meaning and intended interpretation of the value (applies to **Table 14-Table 18**)

Property	Domain	Range	Unit	Description
hasTravelTime	Trip Edge	xsd:double	minutes	Travel time for a trip or edge
hasCapacityUtilisation	TransportElement	xsd:double	ratio 0-1	Current capacity usage ratio
hasSpeedFlow	Edge	xsd:double	km/h	Current speed on network edge
hasEmissions	TransportElement Trip	xsd:double	kg CO ₂ eq	Emissions generated
hasEnergyUse	MobilityService	xsd:double	kWh	Energy consumption
hasEconCost	ResponseAction DisruptionEvent	xsd:double	EUR	Economic cost

Table 14. Mobility & Performance data properties

13.3.2.2 C.2.2 Antifragility & Resilience

Core antifragility/resilience indicators and performance deltas used for reasoning over improvement vs degradation after disruptions.

Property	Domain	Range	Unit	Description
hasAntifragilityScore	SystemState	xsd:double	index -1 to +1	Antifragility metric (positive = improves under stress)
hasResilienceIndex	SystemState	xsd:double	index 0-1	System resilience measure
hasFragilityMetric	TransportElement	xsd:double	index 0-1	Fragility/vulnerability measure
hasPerformanceDelta	SystemState	xsd:double	percentage	Performance change from baseline
hasRecoveryTime	SystemState	xsd:double	minutes	Time to recover to baseline

Table 15. Antifragility & Resilience data properties

13.3.2.3 C.2.3 Equity & Socio-economic

Attributes for access, exposure, vulnerability, and equity-relevant KPI values across groups/areas.

Property	Domain	Range	Unit	Description
hasServiceAccess	Actor	xsd:double	index 0-1	Access to mobility services
hasRiskExposure	Actor SpatialUnit	xsd:double	index 0-1	Exposure to disruption risks
hasSocialVulnerability	Actor	xsd:double	index 0-1	Social vulnerability score
hasBenefitDistribution	ResponseAction	xsd:double	ratio	How benefits are distributed across groups
hasEquityKpi	Observation	xsd:double	varies	Generic equity KPI value

Table 16. Equity & Socio-economic data properties

13.3.2.4 C.2.4 Uncertainty & Data Quality

Attributes that qualify observation quality, trust, confidence, and timeliness/latency.

Property	Domain	Range	Unit	Description
hasTrustScore	Observation	xsd:double	index 0-1	Data trustworthiness
hasDataQuality	Observation	xsd:double	index 0-1	Data quality measure
hasConfidence	Observation	xsd:double	index 0-1	Confidence level of observation
hasLatency	Observation	xsd:double	seconds	Data latency/freshness
hasPredictionError	Observation	xsd:double	percentage	Prediction error margin

Table 17. Uncertainty & Data Quality properties

13.3.2.5 C.2.5 Temporal

Time attributes used to anchor events/units in time and compute durations for analysis and validation.

Property	Domain	Range	Unit	Description
hasStartTime	DisruptionEvent TemporalUnit	xsd:dateTime	ISO datetime	Start time

hasEndTime	DisruptionEvent TemporalUnit	xsd:dateTime	ISO datetime	End time
hasDuration	DisruptionEvent Trip	xsd:double	minutes	Duration

Table 18. Temporal data properties

13.4 Appendix D: Mapping to External Standards and Ontologies

This appendix documents alignments between AntifragiCity ontology concepts and existing standards (22) to ensure interoperability and reuse.

14 Standards Referenced

- **GeoSPARQL (OGC):** Spatial data representation and querying
- **INSPIRE:** EU spatial data infrastructure themes
- **SOSA/SSN (W3C/OGC):** Sensor and observation ontology
- **PROV-O (W3C):** Data provenance ontology
- **OWL-Time (W3C):** Temporal concepts and relations
- **Transmodel (CEN):** European public transport reference model
- **GTFS:** General Transit Feed Specification
- **CityGML 3.0 (OGC):** 3D city models including transportation

13.4.1 D.1 Class-Level Mappings

Alignments from AntifragiCity classes to external standards/ontologies to support interoperability and reuse, where columns are: AFC Class: AntifragiCity class being mapped, Standard: Target standard/ontology (e.g., GeoSPARQL, INSPIRE, SOSA/SSN, PROV-O, OWL-Time, etc.), External URI: External class URI/prefix for the aligned concept, Mapping: Relationship type (e.g., SubClassOf, equivalentClass, closeMatch/relatedMatch-style mapping choices as used), Rationale: Why the mapping is appropriate (semantic justification), Notes: Implementation notes, modelling cautions, or usage guidance.

AFC Class	Standard	External URI	Mapping	Rationale	Notes
SpatialUnit	GeoSPARQL	geo:Feature	SubClassOf	SpatialUnit represents geographic features with geometry	Use geo:hasGeometry for spatial representation
AdministrativeUnit	INSPIRE	au:AdministrativeUnit	equivalentClass	Direct alignment with INSPIRE	Hierarchy via au:administeredBy

				administrative units	
TransportElement	GeoSPARQL	geo:Feature	SubClassOf	Transport elements are spatial features	Add transport-specific properties
Observation	SOSA/SSN	sosa:Observation	equivalentClass	Direct alignment with W3C/OGC sensor observation model	Use sosa:hasResult, sosa:observedProperty
SensorNetwork	SOSA/SSN	sosa:Platform	SubClassOf	Sensor networks are platforms hosting sensors	Link sensors via sosa:hosts
TrafficSensor	SOSA/SSN	sosa:Sensor	SubClassOf	Traffic sensors are observation devices	Define sosa:observes for traffic properties
DataSource	PROV-O	prov:Entity	SubClassOf	Data sources are provenance entities	Use prov:wasGeneratedBy, prov:wasAttributedTo
Provenance	PROV-O	prov:Activity	SubClassOf	Provenance records are activities	Link via prov:generated, prov:used
Actor	PROV-O	prov:Agent	SubClassOf	Actors can be provenance agents	Use prov:wasAssociatedWith
TemporalUnit	OWL-Time	time:TemporalEntity	SubClassOf	Temporal units are time entities	Use time:hasBeginning, time:hasEnd

TimePeriod	OWL-Time	time:Interval	equivalentClass	Time periods are intervals	Use time:hasDuration
MobilityService	Transmodel	tm:Service	closeMatch	Mobility services align with Transmodel service concept	Extend with antifragicity properties
Trip	GTFS	gtfs:Trip	closeMatch	Trip concept similar to GTFS trip	Add equity and antifragicity dimensions
Route	Transmodel	tm:Route	equivalentClass	Direct alignment with route concept	Link to network elements
TransportElement	CityGML 3.0	tran:TransportationSpace	closeMatch	Transport elements map to CityGML transportation	Use for 3D city model integration
Facility	CityGML 3.0	bldg:Building	relatedMatch	Facilities may be buildings in city model	For intermodal hubs, stations

Table 19. Class-Level Mappings

13.4.2 D.2 Property-Level Mappings

Alignments from AntifragiCity properties to external properties to enable consistent querying and data integration across standards where columns are: AFC Property: AntifragiCity property being mapped, Standard: Target standard/ontology, External URI: External property URI/prefix, Mapping Type: Nature of alignment (e.g., equivalentProperty, subPropertyOf, closeMatch), Notes: Comments/constraints for correct use.

AFC Property	Standard	External URI	Mapping Type	Notes
locatedIn	GeoSPARQL	geo:sfWithin	subPropertyOf	Spatial containment relationship
contains	GeoSPARQL	geo:sfContains	subPropertyOf	Inverse of locatedIn
hasObservation	SOSA/SSN	sosa:isFeatureOfInterestOf	equivalentProperty	Links feature to its observations
observes	SOSA/SSN	sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest	equivalentProperty	What the observation is about
generatedBy	PROV-O	prov:wasGeneratedBy	subPropertyOf	Data provenance
hasStartTime	OWL-Time	time:hasBeginning	equivalentProperty	Start of temporal entity
hasEndTime	OWL-Time	time:hasEnd	equivalentProperty	End of temporal entity
hasDuration	OWL-Time	time:hasDurationDescription	closeMatch	Duration representation

Table 20. Property-Level Mappings

Mapping Types: equivalentClass/Property (exact match), SubClassOf/PropertyOf (specialisation), closeMatch (similar semantics), relatedMatch (related concept).

13.4.3 D.3 Gaps and Novel Contributions

This subsection summarises the concepts/patterns for which no suitable existing ontology was identified; these are therefore modelled as novel AntifragiCity classes and patterns, complementing the reused standards listed in Sections 5.5 and Appendix D.1-D.2. The following concepts are novel contributions of the AntifragiCity ontology with no direct mapping to existing standards. Columns are: AFC Property: The AntifragiCity concept (class/property/pattern) considered novel, Standard: Explanation of the gap (i.e., why no standard mapping exists), rather than a standard name, External URI: The modelling decision/implementation approach in AntifragiCity, rather than an external URI.

AFC Property	Standard	External URI
AntifragileState	Novel concept - no existing ontology models antifragility	Define as new class with specific properties
SystemState (equilibrium)	Equilibrium states specific to project framework	Create subclasses for equilibrium types
EquityGroup	No standard ontology for transport equity groups	Define with social vulnerability properties
AntifragilityScore	Novel metric - no existing ontology property	Define as data property with range [-1, 1]
CascadeEvent	Cascading failures not modelled in transport ontologies	Define with propagatesTo relationship
ResponseAction (behavioural)	Behavioural nudges not in existing ontologies	Create subclass for behavioural interventions

Table 21. Novel contributions of the AntifragiCity ontology with no direct mapping to existing standards

Note: These novel concepts represent the core scientific contribution of the AntifragiCity ontology, addressing gaps in existing urban mobility ontologies regarding antifragility, equity, and cascading failure modelling.

13.4.4 D.4 Internal Mapping to AntifragiCity Urban Event Catalogue (D2.1)

Although D2.1 is an internal project deliverable rather than an external standard, the D2.1 Urban Event Catalogue is treated as a reference taxonomy for disruptions and hazards. The Disruption & Risk module therefore includes the following internal mappings:

- **:DisruptionEvent** ↔ D2.1 "Event type" (Urban Event Catalogue)
- **:DisruptionDomain** ↔ D2.1 "Domain" (transport, energy, health, social, etc.)
- **:EventScale** ↔ D2.1 "Scale" (local, city-wide, regional, national)
- **:SeverityLevel** ↔ D2.1 severity / urgency levels
- **:ImpactType** ↔ D2.1 "Main impact" / "Secondary impact" fields

These internal mappings ensure that datasets and analyses produced under D2.1 can be semantically integrated into the AntifragiCity knowledge graph without loss of information.

13.5 Appendix E: SWRL Rules, SHACL Shapes, and SPARQL Queries

13.5.1 E.1 SWRL Rule Examples

SWRL rules enable automated inference of new facts from existing ontology assertions.

Rule metadata summarising how a system state is classified as antifragile based on post-disruption performance change and antifragility indicators.

Rule ID: Field/descriptor name. Right column (e.g., "SWRL-01"): The corresponding field content for that rule (applies to **Table 22-Table 24**).

Rule ID	SWRL-01
Name	Antifragility Classification (Performance Improvement)
Intent	Classify a system state as Antifragile if performance improved after disruption
Inputs	SystemState, previousState, hasPerformanceDelta, hasAntifragilityScore
Outputs	Infers AntifragileState classification

Table 22. Antifragility Classification

Rule Body:

```
SystemState(?s_after) ^
previousState(?s_after, ?s_before) ^
hasPerformanceDelta(?s_after, ?delta) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?delta, 0.0) ^
hasAntifragilityScore(?s_after, ?score) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?score, 0.0)
-> AntifragileState(?s_after)
```

SWRL-02: Vulnerable Area Detection

Rule metadata describing how spatial units are classified as vulnerable when exposure is high and service access is low.

Rule ID	SWRL-02
Name	Vulnerable Area Detection
Intent	Identify spatial units with high risk and low service access
Inputs	SpatialUnit, hasRiskExposure, hasServiceAccess
Outputs	Infers VulnerableArea classification

Table 23. Vulnerable Area Detection

Rule Body:

```
SpatialUnit(?area) ^
hasRiskExposure(?area, ?risk) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?risk, 0.7) ^
hasServiceAccess(?area, ?access) ^
swrlb:lessThan(?access, 0.3)
-> VulnerableArea(?area)
```

SWRL-03: Equity Alert Trigger

Rule metadata specifying how an alert is inferred when an equity group's access drops below a threshold during a disruption.

Rule ID	SWRL-03
Name	Equity Alert Trigger

Intent	Trigger alert when equity group loses service access during disruption
Inputs	EquityGroup, DisruptionEvent, affects, hasServiceAccess
Outputs	Infers EquityAlert

Table 24. Equity Alert Trigger**Rule Body:**

```
EquityGroup(?group) ^
DisruptionEvent(?event) ^
affects(?event, ?group) ^
hasServiceAccess(?group, ?access) ^
swrlb:lessThan(?access, 0.5)
-> EquityAlert(?group)
```

SWRL-04: Cascade Risk Detection**Rule Body:**

```
DisruptionEvent(?e1) ^
DisruptionEvent(?e2) ^
propagatesTo(?e1, ?e2) ^
affects(?e2, ?element) ^
hasFragilityMetric(?element, ?fragility) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?fragility, 0.8)
-> CriticalCascadeRisk(?e1)
```

13.5.2 E.2 SHACL Shape Examples

SHACL shapes (55) validate that ontology instances conform to structural constraints.

SHACL-01: KPI Observation Validation

Target: :KpiObservation

Constraints: Must have forScenario, forActorGroup, forTemporalUnit, observes (KPI identity), kpiValue

```
:KpiObservationShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass :KpiObservation ;
  sh:property [
    sh:path :forScenario ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:class :Scenario ;
  ] ;
  sh:property [
    sh:path :forActorGroup ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:or (
      [ sh:class :EquityGroup ]
      [ sh:class :CitizenSegment ]
    ) ;
  ] ;
```

```

];
sh:property [
  sh:path :forTemporalUnit ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class :TemporalUnit ;
];
sh:property [
  sh:path :observes ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class :KPI ;
];
sh:property [
  sh:path :kpiValue ;
  sh:datatype xsd:double ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
].

```

SHACL-02: Disruption Event Validation:

DisruptionEventShape

```

a sh:NodeShape ;
sh:targetClass :DisruptionEvent ;
sh:property [
  sh:path :hasStartTime ;
  sh:datatype xsd:dateTime ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
];
sh:property [
  sh:path :affects ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:or ( [sh:class :TransportElement] [sh:class :Actor] [sh:class :SystemState] ) ;
];
sh:property [
  sh:path :locatedIn ;
  sh:class :SpatialUnit ;
].

```

13.5.3 E.3 SPARQL Query Templates

SPARQL queries enable competency question answering against the ontology.

SPARQL-01: Disruption Impact on Corridors and Equity Groups

Query template metadata for listing affected areas/groups and related risk/service-access indicators for a given disruption/time window.

Query ID: Field/descriptor name, SPARQL-01: The corresponding field content for that query.

Query ID	SPARQL-01
CQ Reference	CQ-001, CQ-015, CQ-037

Purpose	List vulnerable areas and equity groups affected by a disruption
Parameters	?disruptionType, ?city, ?timeStart, ?timeEnd
Output	Table: area, group, riskExposure, serviceAccess

Table 25. Disruption Impact on Corridors and Equity Groups

```
PREFIX afc: <http://antifragility.eu/ontology#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
```

```
SELECT ?area ?group ?riskExposure ?serviceAccess
```

```
WHERE {
```

```
  ?event a afc:DisruptionEvent ;
    afc:hasStartTime ?time ;
    afc:locatedIn ?city ;
    afc:affects ?area .
```

```
  ?group a afc:EquityGroup ;
    afc:locatedIn ?area ;
    afc:hasRiskExposure ?riskExposure ;
    afc:hasServiceAccess ?serviceAccess .
```

```
  FILTER (?time >= ?timeStart && ?time <= ?timeEnd)
```

```
}
```

```
ORDER BY DESC(?riskExposure)
```

SPARQL-02: Antifragility Score Comparison Across Scenarios

Query template metadata for comparing antifragility scores (and performance deltas) across scenarios, typically aggregated by scenario/city.

Query ID: Field/descriptor name, SPARQL-02: The corresponding field content for that query.

Query ID	SPARQL-02
CQ Reference	SPARQL-02
Purpose	Compare antifragility scores across different scenarios
Parameters	?city
Output	Table: scenario, avgAntifragilityScore, performanceDelta

Table 26. Antifragility Score Comparison Across Scenarios

```
SELECT ?scenario (AVG(?score) AS ?avgScore) (AVG(?delta) AS ?avgDelta)
```

```
WHERE {
```

```
  ?scenario a afc:Scenario ;
    afc:appliesTo ?city ;
    afc:hasSystemState ?state .
```

```
?state afc:hasAntifragilityScore ?score ;
    afc:hasPerformanceDelta ?delta .
}
GROUP BY ?scenario
ORDER BY DESC(?avgScore)
```

SPARQL-03: Equity KPI Monitoring

```
SELECT ?group ?kpiType ?kpiValue ?scenario ?period
WHERE {
  ?obs a afc:KpiObservation ;
    afc:forActorGroup ?group ;
    afc:forScenario ?scenario ;
    afc:forTemporalUnit ?period ;
    afc:kpiValue ?kpiValue ;
    afc:observes ?kpiType .

  ?group a afc:EquityGroup .

  FILTER (?kpiValue < 0.5) (Alert threshold)
}
ORDER BY ?group ?period
```

SPARQL-04: Cascade Failure Chain Analysis

```
SELECT ?event1 ?event2 ?element ?fragility
WHERE {
  ?event1 a afc:DisruptionEvent ;
    afc:propagatesTo ?event2 .

  ?event2 afc:affects ?element .

  ?element afc:hasFragilityMetric ?fragility .

  FILTER (?fragility > 0.7)
}
ORDER BY DESC(?fragility)
```

SPARQL-05: Response Action Effectiveness

```
SELECT ?action ?actionType ?stateBefore ?stateAfter ?improvement
WHERE {
  ?action a afc:ResponseAction ;
    a ?actionType ;
    afc:respondsTo ?event ;
    afc:updatesState ?stateAfter .
```

```
?stateAfter afc:previousState ?stateBefore ;  
    afc:hasPerformanceDelta ?improvement .  
  
FILTER (?improvement > 0)  
FILTER (?actionType != afc:ResponseAction)  
}  
ORDER BY DESC(?improvement)
```